

Can You Hear The Shape Of A Drug? Applying Riemannian Geometry For Shape-Based Virtual Screening

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Abstract

The use of virtual screening in drug discovery to minimise human effort and required resources has gained popularity in recent years. In the absence of structural information, methods based on the similar property principle, which states that two molecules that are similar are also likely to have similar biological activity, can be used to rank large libraries using known binders as templates. An emerging approach to quantify similarity is the use of molecular shape described by using mathematical approximations to the volume, distribution of interatomic distances, or the surface of the molecule. The use of surface-based methods offers a promising intermediate between the accuracy of volume-based methods and the speed of atomic distance-based methods, but it is yet to be widely adopted in the context of drug discovery.

This thesis aims to address this with the application of Riemannian geometry to produce two novel descriptors of molecular surface shape. Both use the *Riemannian metric* associated with the surface, which is a matrix of functions that captures the geometric properties of the molecule. However, two metrics cannot be easily compared. Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation (RGMolSA) gives a 9-element vector by using the metric to approximate the spectrum of the Laplacian. Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation (KQMolSA) applies the theory of Kähler geometry to transform the metric into a Hermitian matrix descriptor of shape. Both descriptors are alignment-free and are fast to compute. An initial investigation using a series of PDE5 inhibitors of known shape is reported. Both methods outperform existing open-source descriptors, with RGMolSA slightly outperforming KQMolSA. A full retrospective benchmarking study, focusing primarily on the Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced (DUD-E) data set, was also completed. The performance of both methods across the full data set compared favourably with the existing work in the field. Improvements could be made in the ability to place true actives early in the ranked list in both cases, but both methods gave overall promising performance after the first round of development.

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation represents my own work, with any collaborations specified in the text and Acknowledgements. This dissertation contains fewer than 80,000 words including appendices, bibliography, footnotes, tables and equations.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms / Abbreviations

3D – BRS Three-Dimensional Biologically Relevant Spectrum

3DZD 3D Zernike Descriptors

ACPC AutoCorrelation of Partial Charges

ASV Analytical Calculation of van der Waals Surfaces and Volumes

AUC Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve

BEDROC Boltzmann-Enhanced Discrimination of ROC

CADD Computer-Aided Drug Discovery

CNS MPO Central Nervous System Multi-Parameter Optimization

CoMFA Comparative Molecular-Field Analysis

CoMMA Comparative Molecular Moment Analysis

CREST Conformer–Rotamer Ensemble Sampling Tool

D – COID Data Set of Congruent Inhibitors and Decoys

DEKOIS Demanding Evaluation Kits for Objective in Silico Screening

DUD Directory of Useful Decoys

DUD – E Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced

ECFP Extended-Connectivity Fingerprint

EF Enrichment Factor

ETKDG Experimental Torsion Knowledge Distance Geometry

FCFP Functional-Class Fingerprint

FN False Negative

FP False Positive

Nomenclature

HBA Hydrogen Bond Acceptors

HBD Hydrogen Bond Donor

HPCC Harmonic Pharma Chemistry Coefficient

HTS High Throughput Screening

IC₅₀ Half Maximal Inhibitory Concentration

IDSS Inner Distance Shape Signatures

KQMolSA Kähler Quantisation for Molecular Surface Approximation

LBDD Ligand-Based Drug Design

LBVS Ligand-Based Virtual Screening

MACCS Molecular Access System

MD Molecular Dynamics

MDDR MDL Drug Data Report

MLR Multivariable Linear Regression Analysis

MolSG Alignment-Free Molecular Shape Comparison Using Spectral Geometry

MUBD – HDACs Maximum Unbiased Benchmarking Data sets for Histone Deacetylases Inhibitors

MUV Maximum Unbiased Validation

PAINS Pan Assay Interference Compounds

PAINS Pan Assay Interference Compounds

PCA Principal Component Analysis

PDB Protein Data Bank

PDE5 Phosphodiesterase 5

PLS Partial Least Square Analysis

PM Power Metric

PoPSS ROCS in Pose Prediction

QED Quantitative Estimate of Drug-likeness

QSAR Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship

QSD Quadratic Shape Descriptors

RBO Rank-Bias Overlap

REOS Rapid Elimination of Swill

RGMolSA Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation

RIE Robust Initial Enhancement

RMD Random Matrix Discriminant

RMSE Root Mean Square Deviation

Ro5 Rule of Five

ROC Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve

ROCS Rapid Overlay of Chemical Structures

SAS Solvent-Accessible Surface

SBDD Structure-Based Drug Design

SBVS Structure-Based Virtual Screening

SDF Structural Data File

SH Spherical Harmonics

ShaEP Shape and Electrostatic Potential

SHeMS Spherical Harmonics Expansion-Based Molecular Similarity Method

SVM Support Vector Machine

TN True Negative

TP True Positive

TPR True Positive Rate

UFSRAT Ultrafast Shape Recognition with Atom Types

USR Ultrafast Shape Recognition

USRCAT Ultrafast Shape Recognition with CREDO Atom Types

VAMS Volumetric Aligned Molecular Shapes

WHIM Weighted Holistic Invariant Molecular

Chapter 1. Introduction

As the development of novel drugs is lengthy and expensive, chemists have long sought to supplement experiment with computational studies. Computer-aided drug design methods can be split into two classes: those based on the protein structure and those that make use of ligands known to bind. The latter is used on the premise that similar molecules are likely to share similar biological activity, which has been widely exploited in drug discovery. This permits the use of a small handful of known actives to be used as templates in virtual screening, omitting the need for protein structure information [1]. While there are many ways in which molecular similarity can be quantified, the use of shape has gained popularity in recent years [2]. The need for protein-ligand shape complementarity allows the shape of a known binder to act as a proxy for the shape of the binding site. As no chemical information is considered, these approaches often identify more diverse scaffolds compared to other similarity methods.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the field of computer-aided drug design, focusing particularly on similarity searching. A complete review of the existing approaches to molecular shape-based similarity screening is presented. Here the gap for a method that is both open-source and based on the approximation of the molecular surface, which offers a desirable balance between speed and accuracy, is identified. This thesis aims to address this gap with the development of two novel descriptors that approximate surface shape using the mathematical theory of Riemannian geometry.

Central to the theory of Riemannian geometry is an object known as the *Riemannian metric*, which efficiently captures the geometric features of the surface of an object. Due to the dependence of the Riemannian metric on the initial orientation of the molecule in 3D space, comparing two metrics to establish similarity is not an easy task. This work therefore presents two routes to convert the underlying metric into an alignment-free, easy to compare descriptor of shape. The theory of Riemannian geometry and the initial parameterisation steps common to both shape descriptors are presented in **Chapter 3**.

Chapter 4 outlines the first of the two molecular shape descriptors developed, known as Riemannian geometry for molecular surface approximation or RGMolSA. This method approximates the *Riemannian metric* presented in **Chapter 3** using the *spectrum* of the Laplacian. This yields a 9-element vector of eigenvalues capturing molecular shape that can be easily compared using the Bray-Curtis distance. The use of the Laplacian is not new in itself [3, 4], but the use of Riemannian geometry removes the need for computationally expensive mesh generation. An initial case study exploring the initial capability of the method using a series of molecules of known shape is reported.

An alternative approach is presented in **Chapter 5**, where the theory of Kähler quantization is applied to convert the Riemannian metric into a Hermitian matrix descriptor of molecular shape. Known as Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation, or KQMolSA, this represents an entirely novel approach to molecular shape representation. An overview of the theory is provided here, as the full detail is beyond the scope of this work. As for RGMolSA, an early case study considering the potential of the method is reported.

To establish the full performance of RGMolSA and KQMolSA, a benchmarking study is reported in **Chapter 6**. A full retrospective benchmarking study to compare this work to Shape-It, USRCAT and MolSG, existing open-source shape similarity software, was completed using the Directory of Useful Decoys – Enhanced community benchmarking set. Subsets of this data were used to probe consideration of multiple conformers for RGMolSA and USRCAT. Further investigation of the conformer-relations provided by RGMolSA and KQMolSA was achieved using a high number of conformers of eicosane, a very flexible molecule. Capability compared to the current gold standard was established indirectly by replicating a drug repurposing approach reported in [5]. A series of molecules with quantified shape-similarity scores were also investigated. Finally, the usefulness of RGMolSA as a feature representation was considered.

Chapter 7 provides conclusions to the overall findings of this thesis, and proposes potential future work to further improve the methods presented.

The full theory underpinning the methods outlined is beyond the scope of this thesis. The interested reader is directed to the preprints [6] and [7] for further mathematical detail for RGMolSA and KQMolSA respectively. The code to run each method can be found at [8] and [9].

Chapter 2. Similarity Searching in Drug Discovery

2.1. Introduction

This chapter introduces the general concept of molecular similarity for ligand-based virtual screening. An overview of the wider field of computer-aided drug design is provided for context, and an introduction given to the main ways that similarity can be represented. An in-depth review of previous shape-based similarity searching methods is then given. Data and metrics for performance evaluation and other pertinent considerations such as conformer generation methods, screening databases, and general rules of thumb in drug discovery are also reviewed.

2.2. Computer Aided Drug Design

Development of novel drugs is a lengthy and expensive process, with an average time frame of 10–15 years and estimated costs of \$2.6 billion for each new drug that reaches the consumer [10]. While improvements have been made to experimental discovery through the automation of high throughput screening (HTS), and the development of novel techniques such as DNA Encoded Libraries [11] and Fragment Based Drug Discovery [12], the process is still expensive and requires resources that are often inaccessible to academic groups. Computer-aided, or *in silico*, drug discovery (CADD) can be considered a “virtual shortcut” in the identification of new compounds at each stage of the drug discovery pipeline (**Figure 2.1**) to reduce the cost and time required to reach the market [13]. Many drugs originating from CADD studies are now available on the market, with drugs targeting the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) developed in the 1990s as the most prominent examples (**Table 2.1**).

Figure 2.1 Summary of the stages typically involved in the development of a new drug. Computational approaches have been developed to assist across the pipeline, and have been found to be particularly beneficial at the hit identification, hit to lead and lead optimisation stages, where experimental costs are high.

Screening first with CADD methods drastically reduces the number of molecules to test experimentally and helps to ensure that the best lead molecule enters *in vivo* studies. In general, CADD methods can be split into two classes: structure-based drug design (SBDD), which can be used where 3D structural information is available for the target of interest, and ligand-based

Drug	Biological Activity	Year of Approval
Captopril	Antihypertensive	1981
Dorzolamide	Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitor	1995
Ritonavir	HIV Protease Inhibitor	1996
Triofiban	Fibrinogen Antagonist	1998
Raltegravir	HIV Integrase Inhibitor	2007

Table 2.1 Some examples of drugs discovered using CADD approaches. Table adapted from [14].

drug design (LBDD), deployed in cases where the protein structure is unknown [14]. Virtual screening, the *in silico* equivalent to HTS, is the most commonly deployed method, and can be carried out on either a structure-based (SBVS) or ligand-based (LBVS) basis [15]. A summary of the most commonly used SBDD and LBDD approaches is given in **Section 2.2.1** and **Section 2.2.2** respectively. The interested reader is referred to [16], [14], [10] and [13] for a full review of the topic.

2.2.1. Structure-Based Drug Discovery (SBDD)

When structural information for the target is available, usually obtained from X-ray crystallography or NMR spectroscopy, structure-based approaches can be employed. Common strategies include docking [17], molecular dynamics [18] and *de novo* design [19].

By far, the most widely used SBDD approach is molecular docking, which provides a computational means to estimate the binding affinity between a ligand and its intended target. The possible conformations and orientations of the ligand within the binding pocket are sampled and then ranked using a scoring function [17]. Treatment of the system can be carried out in three ways: the ligand and the target are considered rigid, the ligand is treated flexibly while the target is rigid, or both the ligand and the target are treated flexibly [20]. The complexity of the calculation increases with increasing degree of flexibility. This method requires selection of an appropriate screening library (see **Section 2.7** for examples of publicly available libraries that can be used), the size of which is dictated by the available computational resources. The state of the art can consider ultra-large libraries containing tens of billions of molecules [21]. While there are many possible applications of molecular docking, its most prominent use is in structure-based virtual screening [22]. Widely used docking software include AutoDock [23], Glide [24], and GNINA [25].

Molecular dynamics (or MD) provide a method for studying the behaviour of drug-target systems over a defined simulation time frame [18]. MD uses a force field to calculate the energy of the system and to probe interatomic interactions, and Newtonian mechanics to construct different configurations of the system as it evolves. This allows construction of a trajectory detailing the position and velocity of each atom over time, and provides information on system properties including free energy and kinetics. MD can be used within drug discovery in combination with docking to account for target flexibility [26], to refine initial binding poses from docking output [27], and to investigate drug binding [28]. Popular MD packages include Amber [29], CHARMM [30], GROMACS [31] and OpenMM [32].

De novo drug design constructs a ligand within the context of the binding pocket by growing an initial scaffold or fragment, or by linking several initial fragments [19]. Compared to virtual screening of existing libraries, *de novo* design permits development of ligands specific to the target of interest, generates new intellectual property and permits exploration of a wider area of chemical space. However, as generated molecules will require synthesis, compared to purchase when an existing library is used, synthetic accessibility must be considered when scoring *de novo* molecules [33]. Several open source solutions are available, including AutoGrow [34], Ligbuilder [35] and FEGrow¹ [36].

2.2.2. Ligand-Based Drug Discovery (LBDD)

When structural information is unavailable, an alternative approach lies in the use of ligand-based drug discovery. Techniques include quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) modelling [37], pharmacophore modelling [38] and molecular similarity searching [1], which will be discussed in **Section 2.3**. Machine learning approaches have also been proposed for virtual screening and generation of new structures [39]. Ligand-based strategies rely on the availability of previously identified active molecules, for example those occurring naturally within the body or from experiment or another discovery campaign that requires improvement.

Quantitative structure-activity relationship, or QSAR, modelling provides a mathematical means of linking measured activity and chemical structure [37]. QSAR modelling relies on the premise that similar molecules are likely to display similar biological activity, so can be used to predict the activity of a new molecule [40]. Construction of a QSAR model typically relies on three steps:

1. Identification of active molecules using HTS or from literature, with activities measured using either the half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) or the inhibition constant (K_i).
2. Selection of an appropriate descriptor of the features that relate structure and activity, e.g. molecular fingerprint, shape, pharmacophore model, functional group counts.
3. Application of a statistical model to correlate structure and activity. Commonly used approaches include principal component analysis (PCA), multivariable linear regression analysis (MLR) and partial least square analysis (PLS) [41].

The success of QSAR modelling is dependent on the quality of the activity data available, as well as selection of an appropriate statistical model for the problem. Several commercial applications are available, including PHARMQSAR from Pharmacelera [42], within the Flare package from Cresset [43] and AutoQSAR from Schrödinger [44].

A pharmacophore is defined by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry as “the ensemble of steric and electronic features that is necessary to ensure the optimal supramolecular interactions with a specific biological target structure and to trigger (or to block) its biological

¹The author of this thesis contributed the molecular property analysis component of this publication.

response” [45]. Pharmacophores are an abstract concept covering the physical properties (1D), substructures (2D) and groups (e.g. hydrogen bond donors/acceptors, hydrophobic groups, charged groups, 3D) that form interactions. Each atom within the molecule is labelled with its corresponding pharmacophore features. Overlay of the models for a set of actives can then be performed to identify features responsible for activity [38]. This does mean that the quality of the model depends on the available known actives. Pharmacophore modelling software is available from MOE [46], Schrödinger’s Phase [47], and inte:ligand’s LigandScout [48].

Examples of supervised, unsupervised and deep learning have been reported in LBDD [39]. Supervised learning builds models trained on data for which the labels are known, either with positive (active) examples only or for both positive (active) and negative (inactive) data. The labels of unseen data are then predicted based on the features of the training set. Unsupervised learning models are trained on unlabelled data, and instead infer underlying patterns directly. Both supervised and unsupervised approaches have been frequently deployed as a quicker alternative to traditional similarity score-based virtual screening with molecular features represented using physicochemical features [49], 2D fingerprints [50, 51], or shape [52, 53]. Deep learning takes a slightly different approach and is designed to mimic the way the brain works. Models consist of layers that have each learned from the previous level. While deep learning has been applied for virtual screening [54], the expense and amount of data required for accurate predictions compared to simpler methods mean that this approach has been applied more commonly in a generative context for ligand-based *de novo* design. Methods using common deep learning techniques have been reported, including the use of variational autoencoders [55], generative adversarial networks [56], reinforcement learning [57, 58] and convolutional neural networks [59]. While features like consideration of pharmacophore constraints have been introduced [59], generative models often produce non-drug like or invalid molecules, preventing their widespread use without further improvement.

2.3. Molecular Similarity Searching

First introduced by Johnson and Maggiora, the similar property principle has been widely exploited in drug discovery [40]. It states that two molecules that are similar in some way are likely to share biological activity. This principle can be used to rank a database relative to a query molecule of known activity, with the highest scoring hits prioritised for further investigation. Similarity searching requires minimal starting information and is typically faster than both HTS and SBVS. While the premise here is simple, similarity, much like beauty, lies in the eye of the beholder and as such there are many equally sensible ways to quantify how similar two molecules are [1]. Most commonly, molecular similarity is investigated using descriptors derived from either the 2D structure (**Section 2.3.1**) or 3D shape (**Section 2.3.2**) of the molecules under consideration. 1D physicochemical property-based descriptors such as the molecular weight, LogP and functional group counts could also be used in theory, but often are not discriminating enough alone [60]. A similarity metric is then deployed to compare descriptors, usually giving a score between 0, where no common features exist, and 1 where they are identical. It is worth

noting that different methods often provide different estimations of similarity [61]. It may be necessary to trial different descriptors or make use of multiple methods, dependent on the project [62]. The success of the screen will also depend on careful choice of query molecules [63].

To assess the statistical significance of the similarity scores produced, Baldi and Nasr proposed the use of several probabilistic models of fingerprints used to probe the distribution of the scores [64]. The Z-score, E-values and p -values associated with the distribution were proposed as measures of significance. Investigation using the ChemDB database found a strong agreement between the theory and observed results. While developed for binary fingerprints and Tanimoto scores, the authors report that the method could be easily applied to other descriptors. Quantifying the significance of the scores in this way could be applied for more robust selection of the descriptors used.

2.3.1. 2D Descriptors

Currently, the most widely adopted means to compare similarity makes use of 2D information derived from molecular graphs. As direct comparison of graphs is computationally expensive, fingerprint descriptors that capture this information as a bit vector can be defined to permit quick searches [65]. The means by which molecular fingerprints are defined typically fall into two classes: structural keys and hashed fingerprints, which can either be path-based or circular in nature (**Figure 2.2**). 2D descriptors tend to be favoured as chemists are trained to interpret molecular graphs, so are more familiar with these than, for example, 3D representations. Despite their simplicity, 2D methods have been found to give better results than other similarity approaches, although care needs to be taken to avoid the inherent bias towards 2D similarity within chemical data due to the design choices of chemists [1, 66].

Structural keys represent information from a molecular graph using a defined library of fragments. The molecule is searched for the presence of the fragments, with a vector, of length corresponding to the number of features, constructed with values 1 where a feature is present and 0 where it is absent. Such descriptors are limited to the consideration of molecular features defined within the library. The most popular of this type of fingerprint are Molecular Access System (MACCS) structural keys, that contain 166 chemist-defined structural fragments (represented as SMARTS) representing features of interest in a drug discovery context (**Figure 2.2a**) [67].

Hashed fingerprints are constructed by enumerating all possible fragments of a specified size within the molecule and using a hashing function to assign a numerical value to each fragment. These values can then be used to assign bit positions. Unlike structural keys, hashed fingerprints can consider all possible fragments, however the use of fixed values to describe the fragment can result in bit collisions if a large enough number of bits is not used. Hashed fingerprints can be split into two further types: path-based and circular fingerprints. Path-based fingerprints use linear enumeration of fragments up to a defined number of bonds (**Figure 2.2b**). The most common implementation is the Daylight fingerprint, that can consist of up

Figure 2.2 Examples of the construction of 2D fingerprint descriptors using Paracetamol as an example (a) structural keys constructed from a set of predefined features (b) path-based fingerprints, where all possible fragments are enumerated and mapped to a fixed size vector (c) circular fingerprints, where the environment within a “radius” of each atom is considered

to 2048 bits [68]. Circular fingerprints are produced by probing the circular environment of a defined radius or diameter around each atom (**Figure 2.2c**). The two most prominent types are Extended-Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFPs) and Functional-Class Fingerprints (FCFPs) [69]. ECFP (or Morgan) fingerprints most commonly use a diameter of four or six (ECFP4 and ECFP6 respectively), and iteratively update the hash value for each atom based on consideration of its neighbours. FCFP extends on this by considering the role of each atom rather than the atom itself to account for pharmacophoric features. Atoms are classed as positive or negatively ionizable, hydrogen bond donor or acceptor, aromatic or halogen then hashed to a fingerprint in the same way as ECFP.

Similarity between two molecular fingerprints is typically evaluated using either the Tanimoto coefficient,

$$T_{AB} = \frac{c}{a + b - c}, \quad (2.1)$$

or the Dice coefficient,

$$D_{AB} = \frac{c}{\frac{1}{2}(a + b)}, \quad (2.2)$$

where a and b are the number of features present in molecules A and B respectively, and c is the number of shared features. In both cases, a score of 0 is assigned to pairs of no similarity, and 1 when all features are identical.

Implementations of popular molecular fingerprints and their similarity metrics are available via the RDKit [70].

2.3.2. 3D Descriptors

As shape is an important factor in molecular recognition for protein-ligand binding, there has also been significant interest in similarity searching methods based on molecular shape [71, 2]. Shape is defined generally as the space an object occupies, defined by its outer boundary. In the context of molecules, shape captures structural features including size, surface, and depth [72]. Typically, 3D shape-based similarity methods condense the molecule down to a set of numbers that capture the shape, and also often include consideration of the pharmacophoric features involved in binding. The use of 3D shape allows for consideration of the different conformers a molecule can adopt and allows identification of non-intuitive candidates through scaffold hopping [73]. The latter is beneficial in addressing any unwanted properties in the initial query molecules, such as toxicity or poor solubility, and increases the strength of an intellectual property application compared to close structural analogues. However, the challenge in developing a molecular shape representation is that it must be rotationally and translationally invariant, and requires sufficient sampling of the conformational space of each molecule to capture the bioactive conformer, which can be a time-consuming process.

Methods for representing and comparing molecular shape are broadly classed as alignment-free or alignment-based [2]. Alignment-based methods require pre-calculation of the optimal superposition of two molecules prior to their comparison, and are highly effective at representing similarity at the cost of computational efficiency. Poor alignment can also introduce errors into the similarity calculation. In contrast, alignment-free methods produce descriptors of molecular shape independently, and are invariant to position and orientation of the molecules in real space. These comparisons are more efficient, but result in greater loss of information than alignment-based methods.

Mezey [74] proposed that an ideal shape descriptor S :

1. Is derived from the physical properties of the molecule.
2. Encompasses the full, 3D shape of the molecule.
3. Easy to compute.
4. Reproducible, and not affected by subjective elements of human perception.

A summary of the current approaches to molecular shape similarity is presented in **Figure 2.3** and **Table 2.2**. A full review of the field is reported in **Section 2.4**.

2.4. An In-Depth Review of 3D Shape Descriptors

2.4.1. Atomic-Centred Based Shape Similarity

The most widely adopted class of molecular shape descriptors makes use of the volume of the molecule to describe shape, based on either a hard sphere [75] or Gaussian sphere [76, 77]

Figure 2.3 Timeline of the major developments in shape similarity searching.

	Atomic-Centred	Atomic Distance	Molecular Surface
Shape Representation	Volume overlap of Gaussian Spheres	Distribution of distances between atoms	Approximation of molecular surface
Metric	Tanimoto Coefficient	Manhattan Distance	Euclidean Distance
Advantages	Simple visualisation, sufficient efficiency for VS	Computationally efficient, no pre-alignment required	Captures global shape of molecule well
Disadvantages	Success depends heavily on query choice	Visualisation of shape challenging	In infancy for small molecule comparison
Classification	Alignment-Based	Alignment-Free	Alignment-Free

Table 2.2 An overview of the main shape-based similarity approaches and their advantages and disadvantages.

model. Two molecules with similar common volumes are classed as having similar shape. Atomic-centre based methods are considered the most accurate approximation to molecular shape, but are typically slower to compute than atomic-distance or surface based methods due to the requirement for alignment of molecules before their comparison.

2.4.1.1. *Hard Spheres*

The hard sphere model for molecular volume was first presented by Connolly for the comparison of macromolecules from crystallographic data [75]. The use of the hard spheres approach permits highly accurate computation of the solvent-excluded volume, the volume inaccessible to the solvent modelled as a hard sphere of given radius, and the van der Waals volume, obtained using a probe sphere radius of zero. Analytical calculation of the volume is achieved by constructing a polyhedron inside the solvent-accessible surface using triangles joining each triplet of atoms. The volume of the polyhedron is obtained by taking the volume of each constituent prism. The remaining volume within the solvent-accessible surface but outwith the polyhedron is then obtained by breaking it down into pieces corresponding to the known surface face shapes –

concave, convex and saddle. The molecular volume is finally calculated by taking the sum of the components.

An extension to this was proposed by Masek *et al.* for comparison of small molecules [78]. Beginning with the van der Waals surface to define the volume boundary, similarity between two optimally aligned molecules can be obtained using the inclusion-exclusion principle, where similarity is given by the intersection volume, $V(A \cap B)$,

$$V(A \cap B) = V(A) + V(B) - V(A \cup B), \quad (2.3)$$

where $V(A \cup B)$ is the union between A and B, and $V(A)$ and $V(B)$ are the volume of molecules A and B respectively obtained explicitly as outlined by Connolly [75]. The intersection and the union of volume are shown in **Figure 2.4**. Additionally, chemical property consideration can be added by classifying atoms based on their electrostatic potential, hydrogen bonding ability and hydrophobicity, then computing the intersection volume as given by **Equation 2.3** for each class of atoms separately. Validation for a series of 4-(biphenyl-4-ylmethoxy) quinoline derivatives and N-(biphenyl-4-ylmethyl)imidazole derivatives, both antagonists of the angiotensin II receptor, highlighted the capability of the method in identifying pairs of high shape similarity, and in identifying novel pharmacophore models for a given target. While the hard spheres approach provides an analytical solution to computing molecular volume, the formulae become increasingly complex for greater numbers of atomic intersections, and therefore more difficult to implement.

Figure 2.4 Example of shape similarity based on molecular volume based on the intersection (\cap) and union (\cup) of the volume (Image reproduced with permission from [79]).

2.4.1.2. Gaussian Spheres

The Gaussian sphere model to compute molecular volume makes use of a set of overlapping Gaussian spheres in place of hard spheres [76, 77]. The use of Gaussians permits easy integration and derivation with respect to nuclear position, and as the Gaussians have rapid, smooth falloff

over distance they can be used to capture the observed electron densities of atoms. For each atomic centre i , a weighted Gaussian is defined as

$$g_i = p_i \exp(-\alpha_i r_i^2), \quad (2.4)$$

where r_i is a local radial coordinate, the constant p_i gives the value of the Gaussian at the centre of the atom and α_i controls the rate of decay. The Gaussian spheres can be used as a “soft” replacement for hard spheres. As for the hard spheres approach, the volume over the molecule can be obtained by considering the inclusion-exclusion principle where optimal alignment has first been found. An initial application in predicting the relative orientations of ligands within a shared binding pocket for the targets thrombin, HIV protease, and thermolysin found Gaussian-based volume to agree well with the results obtained using the hard spheres approach [77].

The current gold standard in shape-based similarity searching is OpenEye’s Rapid Overlay of Chemical Structures (ROCS) [80]. The method was first outlined by Rush *et al.*, and is based on the earlier hard spheres and Gaussian spheres volume calculations. Here the volume overlap between molecules A and B is defined as

$$O_{A,B}(\vec{q}_A, \vec{q}_B) = \int \int \int \chi^A(\vec{r}, \vec{q}_A) \chi^B(\vec{r}, \vec{q}_B) d\vec{r}, \quad (2.5)$$

where r is the position in real space, q is a set of variables defining the orientation and position of each molecule. For Gaussian shape, the volume function χ is given by

$$\chi(\vec{r}) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^{i=N} (1 - g_i(\vec{r})) \quad (2.6)$$

where

$$g_i(\vec{r}) = p_i e^{-\gamma r_i^2}. \quad (2.7)$$

The weight p_i takes a value of 2.7 to replicate the hard spheres volume, and the width, γ , of the Gaussian used to model an atom of radius R given by

$$\gamma = \pi \left(\frac{3p}{4\pi R^3} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}. \quad (2.8)$$

The similarity between two molecules can then be computed using the Tanimoto coefficient,

$$T_{A,B} = \frac{O_{A,B}}{(O_{A,A} + O_{B,B} - O_{A,B})}, \quad (2.9)$$

with a score of one indicating two molecules to be identical, and zero no overlap between them. The method was initially applied to identify molecules with activity against the ZipA-FtsZ protein-protein interaction, a target of interest for novel antibiotic therapies. The scaffold hopping capability of ROCS was exploited to screen Wyeth’s internal database for molecules of similar shape but different structure to a known binder to improve its undesirable toxicity. Three molecules with micromolar activity were discovered with improved cytotoxic properties

compared to the initial binder. Overlay of the new structures in the binding pocket also showed the shape overlays to give reasonable prediction of the binding mode. Subsequent development of the method has added pharmacophore matching, termed ROCS colour, visualisation of overlays and multiprocessor support [80]. Open source implementations of the method are also available. Shape-it, originally by Silicos-it, is available through the RDKit as a Python wrapper [81, 82]. PAPER provides an open source GPU implementation of the ROCS algorithm [83].

As ROCS is currently the gold standard in molecular shape comparison, many uses of the method have been reported. ROCS has been used in virtual screens for a wide range of disease applications. Most commonly, this has involved screening of large databases for molecules with anticancer properties for a wide range of targets [84–91]. Further virtual screening for molecules with antibacterial properties has been reported, targeting biotin carboxylase [92], *Francisella tularensis* (FabI) [93] and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [94]. Targets involved in HIV treatment have also been investigated: C-C chemokine receptor type 5 [95]; ribonuclease H [96] and C-X-C chemokine receptor type 4 [97]. The method has also been deployed in screens for treatments with antifungal properties [98], for type 2 diabetes [99], metabolic syndrome [100], modulation of cholesterol metabolism [101], Chagas disease [102], IP₃ receptor modulators (involved in a range of diseases) [103], and Hepatitis C virus [104]. Several uses of ROCS for its scaffold-hopping capabilities have also been reported. Böstrom *et al.* used ROCS to produce shape overlays for a series of 5,6-diaryl-pyrazine-2-amide derivatives to the existing drug Rimonabant to validate their shape similarity in a program to discover CB1 receptor antagonists with different scaffolds, and improved properties, to treat obesity [105]. Freitas, Oprea and Montanari deployed ROCS to identify inhibitors with increased selectivity for cruzain over cathepsin L [106]. Patel and co-workers used the scaffold hopping capabilities of ROCS to improve the physicochemical properties through a core swap from pyrimidine to pyrazole for a known inhibitor of dual leucine zipper kinase, a target thought to be involved in a number of neurological conditions [107]. A proof of concept study has also been reported where ROCS was used to predict whether any existing approved drugs would be likely to show activity against the H₁ histamine receptor based on their similarity to drugs to permit repurposing as antihistamines [5].

Several uses of ROCS as part of a wider method have also been reported. Swann and colleagues derived a probabilistic framework to combine activity predictions from structure- and ligand-based virtual screening [108]. The framework makes use of BeliefTheory to provide a quantifiable measure of probability through construction of probability assignment curves (PACs), functions to translate a score into a probability of activity. The PACs are constructed from a set of active and inactive molecules for 2D similarity (from ECFP6 fingerprints), 3D similarity (using ROCS) and docking (converted to Z values), with the cumulative belief computed as

$$cb = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^N (1 - P_i), \quad (2.10)$$

where N is the number of independent beliefs and P_i is the belief that the i^{th} measure (on a scale from 0 to 1) is true. The framework permits consideration of all chemical and structural

information available when screening for new candidates, and was found to give better retrieval rates in terms of AUC and enrichment factor for the top 1% ($EF_1\%$) compared to any of the constituent methods alone.

The use of ROCS in combination with machine learning has also been proposed [52]. As ROCS does not provide a direct explanatory variable in the same way that a 2D fingerprint does, a 3D similarity profile of ROCS scores to a set of actives, derived using an empirical kernel map, was proposed as a feature representation for use with a support vector machine (SVM) to predict compound classes. The model was trained using 5-fold cross validation for 15 target proteins derived from ChEMBL. The actives for each target were clustered to avoid overestimation of similarity, and a set of 4950 decoys per target selected from ZINC. A single conformer was generated for each molecule with OMEGA [109], and the data split 50:50 for train and test. Based on evaluation using the AUC and $EF_1\%$ metrics, the SVM model was found to outperform predictions made using maximum ROCS similarity alone. Performance was found to scale with increasing number of queries available, and when a combination of shape and colour scores was used.

A further application makes use of ROCS in pose prediction (PoPSS) [110]. Usually docking algorithms find the optimal binding pose through extensive sampling and scoring of the conformations and orientations a molecule can adopt. Kumar and Zhang proposed that errors related to insufficient sampling could be addressed by identifying the ligand conformation of highest similarity to the known crystal ligand from a pool of conformers generated using OMEGA [109], then refining this through energy minimization and side chain repacking. Initial tests using 8 proteins with known co-crystal structures from the 2012 and 2014 CSARdock benchmarking sets showed PoPSS to outperform both traditional docking and other similar 3D-shape based pose prediction, especially for cases where a set of congeneric crystal ligands was available. The method has subsequently been deployed for the CSARdock exercise, an annual event to allow blind testing of docking and scoring methods, where PoPSS was found to give one of the top performances for the dataset [111]. The method was also found to rank among the top performers when used to predict binding poses for the D3R Grand Challenge 2015 [112].

While the original commercial ROCS implementation has remained the most widely used, several related methods and improvements have been proposed.

Shapelets computes shape by building patches from the surface, constructed using Gaussian functions, to produce a 3D graph approximating shape [113]. Either full or partial shape matching is achieved by scoring the least squares alignment of the matching points.

Shape and Electrostatic Potential (ShaEP) presents a hybrid approach to molecular similarity that takes advantage of the benefits of field-based similarity in identifying partial matches, and volume-based shape similarity in matching molecules of similar size [114]. An initial superimposition of the molecules is constructed using graphs to represent the coarse electrostatic potential and local shape, which are overlaid using a matching algorithm. This is then refined using

Gaussian-derived volume overlays. The method has been used to identify Ubc9 sumoylation inhibitors [115].

Shape-feature similarity (SHAFTS) combines molecular shape and pharmacophore features to establish similarity [116]. Six pharmacophore features (hydrophobic centre, positive charge centre, negative charge centre, hydrogen bond acceptor, hydrogen bond donor, and aromatic rings) are captured using feature triplet hashing, with a hybrid similarity score obtained from weighting this with shape similarity using the Gaussian volume. The method was found to give competitive performance when compared to ROCS and ShaEP using the DUD data set.

Similar to SHAFTS, Phase Shape makes use of atom distributions to produce initial molecular alignments, which can be refined using volume overlap [79]. The method permits use of either shape only or inclusion of pharmacophore features. Benchmarking using a set of 11 diverse targets revealed the hybrid scoring to give improved performance compared to shape only, and favourable performance compared to ROCS. The use of Phase Shape has been reported in the discovery of non-steroidal FXR ligands [117, 118], and SIRT3 inhibitors [119].

Hamza and co-workers proposed two additions to the original ROCS method [120, 121]. Reduced structures were used to produce an initial alignment, where any functional groups in the test molecule not contained in the query are removed before refining using volume overlap. A new scoring function was also proposed,

$$HWZ = \sum_{k=1}^{N=3} \left[a_k \left(\frac{V_{AB}}{V_A} \right)^k + b_k \left(\frac{V_{AB}}{V_B} \right)^k + c_k \left(\frac{V_{AB}}{V_A + V_B} \right)^k \right], \quad (2.11)$$

where V_A and V_B are the volumes of molecules A and B respectively, V_{AB} is the volume of their intersection, and the coefficients a_k , b_k and c_k , and N have been derived by calibration. The function aims to account for the bias in the Tanimoto coefficient towards bigger molecules. The performance of their novel method and scoring function, SABRE, was validated using the DUD database, and was found to outperform ROCS and Phase Shape in terms of early enrichment [122].

SimG provides a means of comparing shape between two ligands, and between a ligand and a binding pocket [123]. Chemical features are included as for SHAFTS, and a downhill simplex searching algorithm can be deployed to rapidly find the alignment between the objects under consideration.

In MolShaCS an empirical objective function is used to model the distribution of charge within the molecular overlay optimization [124]. Chemical features are modelled using the same Gaussian distributions as shape, and similarity quantified using a Hodgkin's index,

$$Similarity = \frac{2V_{AB}}{V_{AA} + V_{BB}}. \quad (2.12)$$

Weighted Gaussian Algorithm (WEGA) aims to improve on the shape approximation given by the Gaussian volume by adding a weight to account for how crowded each atom is [125]. The

proposed method retained the efficiency of the original implementation while improving virtual screening performance based on a screen of the DUD dataset. A GPU implementation has also been made available to increase the speed of WEGA [126]. WEGA has been deployed to search for novel scaffolds with anti-tumour properties [127]. HybridSim-VS provides a web server implementation of WEGA alongside 2D similarity using MACCS keys [128]. OptiPharm offers a further iteration of the WEGA method, where global optimization techniques are deployed to rapidly identify the relevant areas of the search space [129].

2.4.2. Atomic-Distance Based Shape Similarity

Molecular shape can be captured by the relative positions of atoms, permitting comparison using the distribution of interatomic distances. Typically, such approaches are faster than atomic-centred or surface-based methods, and generally alignment of molecules prior to their comparison is not required. Shape descriptors based on interatomic distance calculations fall into two classes: those based on atom triplet distances, and those which use the distribution of atomic distances from a set of fixed reference points.

2.4.2.1. Atom Triplet Distances

First presented by Bemis and Kuntz, atom triplet distances capture molecular shape by dividing the molecule into 3-atom sub-molecules [130]. The 3D coordinates of the molecule are first condensed into a symmetric distance matrix, recording all through-space intra-atomic distances. The distance matrix is then transformed into a series of 3-atom sub-matrices for each triplet of atoms, where n heavy atoms yield $n(n-1)(n-2)/3!$ sub-matrices. The shape of the molecule is then represented by constructing a histogram from the sum of the squares of the sub-diagonal elements of each sub-matrix. Each histogram contains 64 bins, with numerical ranges chosen for individual bins to give reasonable spread of data. Two histograms can then be compared by taking the Euclidean distance,

$$D_{Euc} = \sqrt{(A_1 - B_1)^2 + (A_2 - B_2)^2 + \dots + (A_i - B_i)^2}, \quad (2.13)$$

where A_i is the i^{th} histogram bin for molecule A , and B_i is the i^{th} histogram bin for molecule B . The method was found to handle an average of 21.9 molecules per second, with the run time dependent on the number of heavy atoms present. While this approach showed initial promise, it had drawbacks in the form of selecting an appropriate bin size generalizable to all molecules, and typically requires a large amount of storage space.

To address this, Nilakantan *et al.* proposed the use of a condensed triplet signature [131]. Similar to the work proposed by Bemis and Kuntz, triplet descriptors are first constructed by calculating the sides of the triangle formed by each set of 3 atoms in the molecule, with distances between atoms greater than 100 Å excluded. The integer component of each length is retained and the set of three lengths for each triplet sorted into ascending order before packing into a

single 32-bit integer,

$$nt = n_1 + 1000n_2 + 1000000n_3. \quad (2.14)$$

The molecules are then compared to determine the number of shared triplets, then a score between 0 (different) and 1 (identical) computed as

$$s = 2c / (nt + nc), \quad (2.15)$$

where c is the number of triplets in common, nt is the number of triplets in the template molecule and nc is the number of triplets in the candidate molecule. The method was further streamlined using a pre-computed database of triplet signatures to address the high number of 300–500 triplets typically generated per molecule, leading to large storage requirements. Each triplet in a molecule is hashed to two numbers between 1 and 2048, with each corresponding pair of bits set in a 2048-bit string. This compressed representation can be used to estimate rough similarity quickly between a candidate and the pre-computed database, using the score reported above. If the similarity falls above a defined threshold, the full set of triplets are generated for the probe molecule and the database entry to permit more detailed comparison. This does run the risk of missing some potentially useful candidates, and, as with the previous atom triplet distance based method, does not consider pharmacophore information.

A further approach was proposed by Good *et al.* who made use of atom triplet distance based descriptors derived from the Connolly surface of the molecule, rather than the 3D coordinates [132]. Four different descriptors were reported in the work. Histogram descriptors were constructed from the surface, with the triplets derived from surface point centroids to reduce the overall number of triangle calculations required. A second descriptor based on the centroid triangles was derived, with the perimeter and area weighted to account for the relative frequency each triangle occurs within the histogram without consuming excessive storage. A multi-surface descriptor bit string constructed from a 5-dimensional array encompassing all the methods described was also presented. The final approach permits use of the full non-centroid triangles to describe high density surfaces by clustering surface points. These searches were found to perform quickly, but there was little additional discrimination from the more detailed descriptors, and these still required a large amount of storage space.

2.4.2.2. Ultrafast Shape Recognition

Ultrafast Shape Recognition (USR) captures molecular shape using the mean, standard deviation and skew of the Euclidean distance of each atom from four reference points: the centre of the molecule, the closest atom to the centre, the furthest atom from the centre and the furthest atom from the furthest from the centre (**Figure 2.5**) [133, 134]. This yields a concise 12-element vector that is alignment free, rotation-translation invariant and quick to calculate. The position and number of the centroids is arbitrary, but the selected four were found to give a balance between accuracy and efficiency. The accuracy can be improved by adding more reference points at additional computational cost. Similarity is quantified by considering the inverse Manhattan

distance (**Equation 2.16**), where M_l^q is the vector value for the query molecule at position l and M_l^i is the vector value for the test molecule at the same position. As with the Tanimoto Similarity used for ROCS this takes a value of 0 when two molecules are completely different and 1 when they are identical.

$$S_{qi} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{12} \sum_{l=1}^{12} |M_l^q - M_l^i|} \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.5 Example of the four reference points used to construct the USR descriptor (centre of the molecule (ctd), the closest atom to the centre (cst), the furthest atom from the centre (fct) and the furthest atom from fct (fft)) using Zidovudine as an example (Image adapted from [53] with permission).

The efficiency of USR as a shape descriptor was evaluated by visually inspecting the similarity of the top scoring molecules retrieved from a set of 2,433,493 commercially available molecules compared to five queries. In each case, the molecules retrieved were found to be visually similar to the query, and also displayed the scaffold hopping potential of USR. More similar shaped molecules were found to be retrieved compared to MOE's ESshape3D, an atomic-distance based fingerprint derived from the eigenvalues of the matrix of distances between heavy atoms. Through indirect comparison, USR was found to perform ~14,000 times faster than ROCS when the difference in computational resource is taken into account. A later paper presented a retrospective benchmarking study comparing USR to ESshape3D [135]. The study made use of the DrugBank database of ~3500 molecules, taking known actives for 8 diverse targets as queries. In each case, the remainder of the data are treated as inactive. Molecules outwith the molecular weight range 100-800 Da and with more than 10 heavy atoms were excluded. For each molecule, a maximum of 1000 conformers were generated using MOE's stochastic search, then filtered to remove any with energy greater than 0.7 kcal/mol/rotor. Each active, represented by its lowest energy conformer, was used in turn to rank the remaining molecules. The performance was then evaluated by taking the average $EF_{1\%}$ for each target. Overall, USR was found to outperform ESshape3D both in terms of average early enrichment and speed, with an overall average of $EF_{1\%} = 10.4$ vs $EF_{1\%} = 6.6$ for ESshape3D. While quick, these descriptors are challenging to visualise and are invariant under reflection, producing identical vectors for enantiomers.

Since their initial publication, use of the USR descriptors has been widely reported. USR has been deployed in virtual screening, either alone or in combination with other methods, to identify novel arylamine N-acetyltransferase inhibitors [136], potential antibiotics against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Streptomyces coelicolor* [137], inhibitors of Protein Arginine Deiminase type 4 (a target for rheumatoid arthritis) [138], for phosphatases of regenerating liver 3 (PRL-3, involved in cancer metastasis) inhibitors using thienopyridone as a query [139], and to screen the DrugBank database for novel p53–MDM2 inhibitors [140].

More recently, the USR descriptors have also been used to construct shape maps to relate the shape of molecules to one another. Molecules with similar shapes lie closer together within the map, with the distribution of molecules easy to visualise, allowing molecules of preferred shape for activity to be identified [141]. An array of USR descriptors for the actives and inactives is converted using the self-organizing map software SOMbrero. Validation using the DUD-E showed the method could be used to determine the difference in binding modes between relatively rigid protein and ligands vs more flexible ones.

A fast workflow has also been reported for conformer generation and USR shape matching that does not rely on pre-computed conformers, with the option to store the generated descriptors for later use [142]. The approach was validated to screen 70 million compounds to identify novel structures with activity against TLR4.

USR has also been investigated as a feature representation for machine learning. Bonnano and Ebejer made use of USR with a series of models trained using the DUD-E database (split 80:20 train:test) to determine if any performance improvement could be gained compared to using the Manhattan distance [53]. Gaussian Mixture Models, Isolation Forests and Artificial Neural Networks were used, each trained using 5-fold cross validation with both the lowest energy conformer and multiple conformers. Performance was evaluated using the AUC and EF metrics. All three models were found to give improvements in performance compared to traditional virtual screening. The performance was also maintained when smaller amounts of data were used for training, especially when multiple conformers were considered, and the use of machine learning was 10 times quicker on average. USR has also been combined with spiking neural networks (SNNs), a technique used to parallelize time-consuming tasks to perform quick similarity searches [143]. The method was found to perform two orders of magnitude faster than traditional screening of the ZINC database with USR for consideration of multiple conformers.

Since the development of the original USR descriptor, several improvements have been proposed. To add functional group information, a hybrid USR/MACCS key descriptor was presented, which was found to improve recall compared to either descriptor alone [144]. Consideration of chiral molecules has also been added using the cross product to assign centroids which permit variance under reflection [145], or by constructing vectors to connect the origin of the molecular coordinates to each of the four reference points used in USR, then constructing an optical isomerism descriptor by taking the cubic root of the vectors [146]. Armstrong and co-workers reported ElectroShape, the extension of the original USR descriptors to include electrostatic information by including partial charge data as a fourth dimension and atomic

lipophilicity (alogP) as a fifth dimension to their previously reported chiral shape representation [147, 148]. The descriptors are available online as part of the SwissSimilarity platform [149]. AutoCorrelation of Partial Charges (ACPC) adds consideration of partial charges to the USR descriptor [150]. The method uses the autocorrelation function to encode the atoms into two vectors considering atomic distances and partial charges that are invariant to rotation and translation.

The two most notable improvements, UFSRAT [151] and USRCAT. [152], add atom type information to the original descriptor.

Ultrafast Shape Recognition with Atom Types (UFSRAT) considers the distance distributions of all, hydrophobic, hydrogen bond donor and hydrogen bond acceptor atom subsets. The four reference points used in USR are determined for each subset, giving a 48-value descriptor [151]. As for USR, the inverse Manhattan distance (**Equation 2.16**) is used to quantify similarity. A comparison to USR using the DUD-E dataset with performance evaluated using the enrichment factor for the top 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5% of ranked molecules showed significant improvement when UFSRAT was used. The method was then deployed to search for inhibitors of FKBP12 and 11 β -HSD1, with four new candidates with experimentally validated activity identified for each target. One potential disadvantage of UFSRAT is the treatment of each atom subset independently. If a subset does not contain enough atoms to generate a distribution, it is excluded from the description. As some pharmacophores are less common than others, this can impact the quality of the representation. UFSRAT has been deployed to search for inhibitors of the Oncoprotein MDM2 [153] and to search for Kynurenine 3-Monooxygenase inhibitors, where Diclofenac was identified from DrugBank as a potential hit [154].

Ultrafast Shape Recognition with CREDO Atom Types (USRCAT) offers an alternative approach to including atom type information [152]. The method makes use of the CREDO atom types database, which includes all interatomic interactions between all small- and macromolecules in the Protein Data Bank. The method includes the same atom types as UFSRAT, but additionally includes aromatic atom types. The atom subsets are identified using SMARTS pattern matching to yield a 60-element vector to represent shape. Benchmarking of USRCAT against USR using the DUD-E dataset showed considerable improvement in the average enrichment factor for the top 1%, 0.5% and 0.25% of ranked hits, and was found to display significant scaffold hopping potential. USRCAT has subsequently been deployed to screen for human hexokinase II (HKII) inhibitors, a target of interest for the treatment of dengue fever [155].

USR and USRCAT are available via RDKit [70] and via a web server [156], while a web based version of UFSRAT is available.

2.4.3. *Surface Based Shape Similarity*

Unlike the way an apple has a skin, molecules do not have a true surface in the classical sense. However, consideration of their surface is useful in the interpretation of molecular shape and size. While a precise definition of molecular surfaces can be given by wave-function based

methods, these are generally too computationally expensive when screening large databases. For this purpose, approximate surface definitions have been developed based on the van der Waals or solvent-accessible surface [157]. **Figure 2.6 (a)** depicts the van der Waals surface, [158] or the fused sphere model, which considers the surface as a series of intersecting spheres of van der Waals radii and the distance between the atoms as the experimentally determined bond length. **Figure 2.6 (b)** shows the solvent-accessible surface (SAS) [159, 160], that considers the areas of the van der Waals surface accessible to solvent molecules (modelled using a probe sphere) for a fixed conformation of the molecule. The majority of the molecular surface-based shape similarity methods discussed below take one of these two models as a starting point for descriptor construction.

Figure 2.6 Common approaches to modelling the surface of a molecule that are simpler to calculate than precise wave function-based approaches (a) the van der Waals surface, for example, for penicillin, and (b) the Solvent-Accessible Surface (Image produced using code from [161]).

2.4.3.1. Spherical Harmonics

The shape of molecular surfaces can be approximated using a coefficient vector obtained by expanding the spherical harmonics (SH) functions on a unit sphere [162]. The approximation becomes closer to the true surface when a greater number of terms are included in the expansion. Starting with the solvent-accessible surface centred at the origin $(0, 0, 0)$, the coefficients C_{nk} for the spherical harmonic function Y_{nk} are given by

$$C_{nk} = \int_F \frac{Y_{nk}(\theta, \varphi)}{r(\theta, \varphi)} U(\theta, \varphi) \cdot N(\theta, \varphi) dA, \quad (2.17)$$

where F is the surface, $U(\theta, \varphi)$ is a unit vector that describes the spherical coordinates of the point, $N(\theta, \varphi)$ is the unit surface normal and A is the area. (θ, φ) represents a point on the surface projected onto a unit sphere, whose Cartesian coordinates can be defined as: $x = \sin \theta \cos \varphi$; $y = \sin \theta \sin \varphi$; $z = \cos \theta$. Descriptors based on spherical harmonics are easy to visualise and provide a good description of global shape. The initial implementation is limited to the description of starlike sets to prevent multiple-valued radii from the centre to a surface point that result from the presence of cavities, tunnels, or overhangs in the surface. SH descriptors also

Figure 2.7 Construction of the spherical harmonics descriptor is achieved by mapping the surface onto a series of SH functions, the coefficients of which are used to construct a shape descriptor. Figure reproduced from [163] with permission.

require alignment of the molecules prior to comparison, as they are not invariant to rotation or translation. An overview of the construction of spherical harmonic descriptors is given in **Figure 2.7**.

Several attempts have been made to introduce rotation-translation invariance into the SH approach. Kazhdan *et al.* produced a tool for generally converting shape descriptors to a rotationally invariant form derived by describing spherical functions in terms of their energy at different frequencies [164]. As these values do not change upon rotation, the resulting descriptor is invariant to rotation. Mak *et al.* made use of the radial Zernike function to extend the spherical harmonic to a 3D polynomial invariant to rotation and translation, with scope beyond star-like objects [165]. However, the approach only offered minor improvement in shape matching performance, and had a greater computational cost per coefficient.

Further development of the method was proposed by Pérez-Nueno and co-workers, who suggested the use of spherical harmonics to construct consensus shapes from known actives as queries for LBVS [166]. Using the ParaSurf implementation of spherical harmonics, the consensus shape is constructed by taking the average of N individual spherical harmonic shape descriptors, a_{lm}^k for $k = 1, \dots, N$ as

$$\bar{r}(\theta, \varphi) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=0}^l \sum_{m=-1}^l a_{lm}^k y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi), \quad (2.18)$$

where a_{lm} are the expansion coefficients and $y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)$ are real spherical harmonics. To compute the average, each molecule must first be rotated to minimize the distance between it and the remaining $N - 1$ molecules. This is an iterative process, with the two molecules of highest shape similarity taken as an initial seed shape, then the remaining molecules superpositioned to the seed. Three to four cycles are typically required for convergence. The performance of this approach was validated by retrospective virtual screening for HIV entry inhibitors of CXCR4 and CCR5, where the consensus shape gave higher AUC performance than ROCS, spherical harmonics alone and docking. The performance of the consensus shape was compared with ROCS and conventional docking (MSSH/SHEF and GOLD) using the Directory of Useful Decoys [167].

The study found that the consensus shape gives the best AUC performance across the 40 targets. In cases where poorer performance is often observed (targets COMT, TRYPSIN, PDGFRB, P38, ALR2), the consensus shape, which captures important features of known actives, provided a better query than the crystallographic ligand. Furthermore, the consensus shape was found to be useful in identifying targets with multiple binding sites based on the clustering of shapes. A further study introduced the consideration of key surface properties (molecular electrostatic potential, the local ionization energy, local electron affinity, and local polarizability) to the above approach, validated using the Directory of Useful Decoys [168]. A clear improvement to the performance, based on the AUC metric, was observed for the addition of surface properties compared to consensus shape alone and ROCS.

SH-expansion-based molecular similarity method (SHeMS) aims to improve on the original implementation through the use of weighted coefficients, with the weights selected by a genetic algorithm to best separate actives and inactives [163]. The use of the genetic algorithm permits a fully customisable choice of weights based on a user-supplied reference set. The use of weighted coefficients gives each a distinct contribution to the final similarity score. In a benchmarking study with the Directory of Useful Decoys, SHeMS was found to give a better overall performance, based on the AUC metric and enrichment factor, than the original implementation and USR.

Harmonic pharma chemistry coefficient (HPCC) adds consideration of pharmacophoric features by treating the harmonic surface as a triangulated mesh and assigning chemotype properties to these triangles [169]. Initially, the shape and pharmacophore features are given separate scores based on their Tanimoto similarity, before they are combined to give an overall score. The performance of HPCC was compared to that of OpenEye's ROCS using the Directory of Useful Decoys, taking the crystallographic ligand conformation as the query. Based on the AUC and the normalized sum of logarithms of ranks, a measure of early enrichment, HPCC was found to give a performance similar to ROCS, although the success in both cases was dependent on the kind of target considered.

The first application of spherical harmonics to the comparison of surface shape was reported by Ritchie and Kemp, who demonstrated this by comparison of the variable heavy domains of the HyHel-5 and KOL antibodies [170]. The method was further extended by Gramada and Bourne to permit protein structure comparison by bridging the gap between atomic-level structure and overall protein-level functionality, tested on a protein kinase-like superfamily benchmarking set [171]. Spherical harmonics have also been applied to binding pocket similarity, using the L_2 distance as a similarity metric [172]. Several uses in protein-ligand docking have also been reported, where spherical harmonics are used to accelerate low-energy conformer searches [173], for finding the best candidate conformation [174], probing intermolecular binding properties [175] and as a pre-docking surface-complementarity filter [176]. Spherical harmonics have also been applied in ligand-based virtual screening. The first application in this context was made by Mavridis and colleagues, who took 73 drug molecules covering several of the main pharmacological drug classes and 1108 random molecules from the NCI database, and ranked them using spherical harmonics with Lorazepam as a query [177]. The method was found to

give meaningful clusters of molecules, suggesting that spherical harmonics provide an effective approach for database screening. Spherical harmonics have also been deployed to screen for cyclooxygenase-1 and cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors in the ChemBridge database [178].

2.4.3.2. 3D Zernike Descriptors

Closely related to the spherical harmonics approach is the use of 3D Zernike descriptors (3DZD), which improve SH by allowing orientation-independent comparison of molecules, extending beyond the constraint of star-shaped surfaces [179]. These were initially developed for computer vision as a general shape-based object descriptor. The shape of the object is captured by the 3D Zernike function,

$$Z_{nl}^m(r, \theta, \phi) = R_{nl}(r)Y_l^m(\theta, \phi), \quad (2.19)$$

where $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ is the spherical harmonic basis function, and $R_{nl}(r)$ is the radial function, and n is the number of moments. $Z_{nl}^m(r, \theta, \phi)$ is translationally invariant and is expressed as the norm F_{nl}^m to invoke rotational invariance,

$$F_{nl}^m = \frac{3}{4\pi} \int f(x) \overline{Z_{nl}^m(x)} dx, \quad (2.20)$$

where $f(x)$ is a 3D shape function projected onto a linear combination of these geometric moments that have been scaled to fit a unit sphere, and $\overline{Z_{nl}^m(x)}$ is the conjugate of the complex-valued Zernike function.

3DZD was first extended into the chemical space for the consideration of protein surface similarity. Sael and co-workers deployed the descriptors for comparison of protein surfaces [180]. The surface is first represented as a triangulated mesh placed in a grid, with the surface containing voxels assigned a value of 1, and 0 otherwise. The 3D Zernike descriptor is then computed as above. The similarity between two descriptors is then given using the Euclidean distance,

$$d_E = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{i=nl} (z_{Ai} - z_{Bi})^2}. \quad (2.21)$$

The simplified representation of shape was found to permit searches against a few thousand structures in under a minute. The proposed approach was found to be easily extended to include pharmacophoric surface properties, taking electrostatic potential and hydrophobicity into account by assigning their values to surface voxels [181].

Several subsequent applications of the 3DZD descriptor have been proposed. Venkatraman *et al.* studied the use of the descriptors to compare molecular shape for ligand-based virtual screening [182]. Compared to USR and SIMCOMP (a graph matching approach) using the Directory of Useful Decoys, where on average 3DZD and USR outperform SIMCOMP, but the relative performance of USR and 3DZD varies depending on the performance metric. The use of 3DZD descriptors in LBVS was extended to include pharmacophoric properties, including hydrophobicity and electrostatic potential associated with the surface [183]. These descriptors

have also been deployed for both protein-protein docking [184] and protein-ligand docking [185] based on shape complementarity. Esquivel-Rodríguez and Kihara deployed the 3DZD method to fit high resolution structures for multiple proteins into a cryoelectron microscopy map by comparison of a candidate set of proteins from docking conformations to an electron microscopy (EM) density map to determine which will fit the EM map best [186]. 3D Zernike descriptors have also been used to characterise the binding pockets of biological systems to identify differences in similar regions of the proteins from molecular dynamics trajectories [187]. More recently, 3DZD has been proposed as a feature representation for machine learning. Daberdaku and Ferrari used the 3DZD descriptors to as a rotation-translation invariant representation of the surface shape and physicochemical properties in combination with a support vector machine classifier to predict which surface patches are involved in antibody-antigen binding [188]. Aderinwale *et al.* extended the use of 3DZD for protein comparison, applying the approach as a descriptor for AlphaFold2 output and using it to train a neural network to identify other proteins of the same fold as a query protein [189].

2.4.3.3. *Alpha Shapes*

Alpha shapes [190–192] are an alignment-free coarse method for the representation of molecular surfaces [193]. The Alpha shapes for a set of points “S” are a generalisation of the convex hull, where the parameter α controls the level of detail reported. At $\alpha = \infty$ the Alpha shape is equivalent to the convex hull, where the detail of the shape features increases with decreasing α . In a chemical context, when α corresponds to the radii of a set of spheres, the space filling model of the molecule can be described exactly by the Alpha shapes. The distance between the Alpha shapes of two molecules is computed using the Earth-Mover distance [194]. The method was found to discriminate between octane conformers with high accuracy; however, these descriptors are almost size-independent, so they would classify two molecules of different sizes but similar shapes as similar, leading to a potential increase in false positives.

2.4.3.4. *Shape Signatures*

Shape Signatures offer another alternative [195, 196]. Here, ray-tracing, a technique borrowed from computer animation, is used to explore the volume contained within the solvent-accessible surface of the molecule. The SAS is first constructed using a series of smaller triangular surface elements. The reflection of light rays at right angles from random points is then measured for a fixed number of light sources originating at the midpoint of the triangular surface elements. The shape is then represented by a histogram that captures the probability distribution of the ray trace. Two such representations are compared using either the L_1 norm,

$$L_1(H^1, H^2) = \sum_i |H_i^1 - H_i^2|, \quad (2.22)$$

for histograms H^1 and H^2 representing the molecules under comparison (with i ranging over the length of the bins) when only shape is considered, or the L_2 norm when

$$L_2(H^1, H^2) = \sum_i \sum_j |H_{ij}^1 - H_{ij}^2|. \quad (2.23)$$

where i is the index over the length of the bins and j varies over the electrostatic potential scale, used as the second dimension. These measures assume that the bins for any two histograms have 1-1 correspondence, and that the histograms are normalised to have height of 1 across all bins. This gives a score of 2 where there is no similarity, and 0 where two histograms are identical.

The Shape Signatures approach has been shown to offer several advantages. The use of histograms to represent shape makes these descriptors easy to visualise compared to other shape descriptors. They are also alignment-free and do not depend on the initial orientation of the molecule. The descriptors are also relatively fast to calculate, taking ~10s per molecule on a single processor. Shape Signature descriptors do not change much with small changes in conformation; however, the method is sensitive to stereoisomerism, especially the presence of multiple chiral centres or molecules with the possibility of cis/trans isomerism. Chemical diversity is also needed in the screening library for inclusion of electrostatic information to have an impact.

Several uses of Shape Signatures in drug discovery projects have been reported. Nagarajan *et al.* used the method to rank 825 agonists and 400 antagonists of Serotonin receptors, using 10,000 random molecules from the NCI database as decoys [197]. The method was found to be efficient at identifying agonists, as well as separating the agonists and antagonists from a wider pool of molecules active against the receptor. In the work presented by Wang and co-workers, Shape Signatures were used as part of a computational workflow to identify molecules with antiestrogenic properties [198]. 4-hydroxytamoxifen and diethylstilbestrol were used as queries to screen a database of ~200,000 commercially available organic molecules. The approach identified 8 potential hits, with 2 having experimentally verified antiestrogenic activity. A further two Estrogen receptor α antagonists were identified using a similar approach to screen the ZINC database of commercially available compounds [199]. Ai *et al.* used Shape Signatures to screen a set of 200,000 commercially available compounds for tyrosinase inhibitory activity, using Kojic acid and Glabridin as queries [200]. The screen yielded two lead compounds that represented a novel class of depigmentation agents with promise in the development of new skin lightening products. The method was also used by Werner *et al.* to screen for new DNA gyrase inhibitors for the treatment of MRSA [201]. Novobiocin was used as a query in an initial screen for molecules of similar shape, which were then carried forward to docking experiments to predict their binding affinity and study receptor-ligand binding interactions. Shape Signatures have also been proposed as a molecular feature representation in Machine Learning. Chekmarev *et al.* proposed the combination of Shape Signatures and the 2D MOE descriptors in a Support Vector Machine model to predict new inhibitors of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) [202].

While the original method showed promise in the screening of large databases, high rates of false positives were observed. Inner Distance Shape Signatures (IDSS) were proposed to address this [203]. Starting from the boundary of a set of intersecting spheres, a set of boundary points were sampled, and a graph constructed from the inside visibility between each pair of points. A histogram of these distances is used to represent each molecule, with the similarity between two molecules established using the Manhattan distance. The method was found to handle small changes in the conformation well, but to be sensitive to changes in the surface topology. A web-based implementation of IDSS is available [204].

Another problem occurs when the chemical structures under consideration are large and contain heterogeneous ring systems. In such cases, the discriminative power of the method diminishes, as the descriptors tend to only capture the size of the molecule. Fragment-based Shape Signatures (FBSS) were introduced to remedy this, the ray-trace is partitioned in accordance with the fragment assignments to produce descriptors [205]. The query fragments are mapped onto the test fragments to facilitate comparison.

2.4.3.5. *Local Surface Shape*

Descriptors of local surface regions can be used to align and estimate the similarity between molecules. Cosgrove *et al.* proposed a method that describes the molecular shape by considering the curvature of the molecular surface [206]. The molecule is split into equal patches, with a clique detection algorithm used to align molecules by identifying patches of the same class and curvature. A correspondence graph is constructed to permit multi-molecule overlays. The method was found to perform well in replicating the orientations of a set of molecules from the Brookbank database, quantified using the RMSD. Quadratic shape descriptors (QSD) capture shape using least-squares fitting of a quadratic function to patches of the surface [207]. Geometrically invariant properties of each patch are extracted to produce a descriptor of the shape. QSD was found to be successful in replicating the experimental orientation of a set of inhibitors of HIV-1 protease, thrombin, and serine protease when assessed using the RMSD. SURFCOMP uses a similar approach to that of Cosgrove and co-workers, applying an additional set of shape and property filters to reduce the number of critical points and including chemical property information by considering the electrostatic potential and lipophilic potential associated with the surface [208]. The overlays of the thermolysin inhibitors found by Cosgrove *et al.* were replicated by the approach and reasonably replicated the experimental orientation of a set of additional dihydrofolate reductase ligands. The method was later extended to detect differences in binding domains of related proteins, considering the SH2 domain of Sap and Eat-2 as an example [209].

2.4.3.6. *More Recent Surface Descriptors*

Surfaces can also be approximated by considering the eigenvalues that form the *spectrum* of the Laplacian. This was first proposed as a shape descriptor by Reuter and co-workers [3], and extended to the description of molecular shape by Seddon *et al.* known as MolSG [4]. Here

the geodesic distance is considered rather than the Euclidean distance, giving the descriptor the advantage of being invariant to isometric deformation. The molecular shape representation is generated in four main steps:

1. The solvent-accessible surface of the molecule is represented by a triangulated mesh of N vertices and M faces, produced using TSMesh [210].
2. The Finite Element Method is then used to compute the Laplace-Beltrami spectrum (**Equation 2.24**) at each vertex of the mesh, truncated to the 20th eigenvalue,

$$\Delta\phi = -\lambda\phi, \quad (2.24)$$

where Δ is the Laplace-Beltrami operator, and ϕ and λ are the corresponding eigenfunctions and eigenvalues respectively.

3. Feature vectors capturing the local geometry about the vertex are generated by applying the Wave Kernel Signature to the spectrum. This applies Gaussian functions to the spectrum over 100 intervals to amplify the signal at each point.
4. The local descriptors are then aggregated to produce a global descriptor of surface shape using a bag of features approach. A *codebook* of 500 representative local descriptors is constructed. For an input molecule, the local descriptors for each vertex are assigned as the closest codeword in the codebook. These vertex encodings are combined as a normalised frequency histogram to give a descriptor of global shape. Two descriptors can be compared using the cosine distance.

Compared to established open source shape similarity methods, significant improvement was seen when the DUD-E data set was screened using MolSG, with 20 actives per target selected at random as queries. While this approach compares well with these methods, which are more established for small molecule comparison, its widespread adoption may prove challenging, as the mesh generation step is too slow for consideration of the large databases used in virtual screening.

Electrostatic-field and surface-shape similarity (eSim), presented by Cleves, Johnson, and Jain, captures the similarity between two aligned molecules by considering both molecular surface shape and directional hydrogen bonding preferences [211]. The method uses 6 feature values at a series of n observer points 4.0 Å from the surface of the molecule: the distance between the observer and the atom surface (*steric_{dist}*); the Coulombic energy to move a point charge of +0.2e from an infinite distance to the observer point; the minimum distance (*coul_{en}*); the minimum distance from the observer point to any donor proton's surface (*don_{dist}*); the angle formed between the observer point, the donor proton and the atom attached to the donor proton (*don_{theta}*); the minimum distance from the observer point to any acceptor atom's surface (*acc_{dist}*) and the angle formed by the observer point, the acceptor atom and the atom attached to the acceptor atom (*acc_{theta}*) (**Figure 2.8**). The method requires alignment of molecules prior to their comparison, which is achieved using the ForceGen method [212]. The similarity between two molecules is then given by using the sum of a set of Gaussian functions of the difference between

Figure 2.8 2D depiction of the feature calculation in eSim for 2-pyrrolidone (Image reproduced from [211] with permission).

the feature values at each point

$$S(L_p^s) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i (S_i^{stc} + S_i^{coul} + S_i^{don} + S_i^{acc})}{C^t} + e(L_p^s). \quad (2.25)$$

Comparison of a set of identical molecules yields a score of 10.0, where C^t is a normalising constant and $e(L_p^s)$ is a negative value based on an estimate of the ligand strain. ESim was compared with OptiPharm, ROCS, USR, VAMS and WEGA using AUC scores for the DUD-E benchmarking set. The similarity measure was found to be responsive to shape differences independent of atomic centre correspondence, as well as being able to detect differences in local electrostatic fields of near-isosteric molecules. The inclusion of electrostatic information improved performance compared to the consideration of shape alone, and eSim was found to perform significantly better than the best-performing alternative based on the average AUC. The use of the AUC as a performance metric does not provide any information on the method's capability to rank true actives early in the list, which is considered a better indication of high performance for drug discovery applications.

Sensitive surface as a shape (SENSAAS) carries out alignment of molecules using molecular surface shape and pharmacophoric features represented by a 3D point cloud. These descriptors can capture both local and global similarity. Alignment involved four steps:

- A 3D point cloud is generated for the van der Waals surface for each molecule under comparison. Each atom is coloured by type.
- Geometric-based global alignment of the point clouds is carried out using Fast Point Features Histograms to match corresponding points.
- The alignment is then refined locally by considering both the shape and pharmacophore features.
- Scores based on fitness that indicate how many points are paired and the superimposition of the molecules displayed.

Dense point clouds offer the advantage that the property does not correspond to a single point in space, and that the variation in pharmacophoric properties can be mapped onto the surface. The ability of the method to reproduce experimentally verified superpositions of dissimilar molecules from the AstraZeneca data set was investigated. SENSAAS was found to identify the correct alignment of similar structures and rank them first. It also gave an accurate performance, in line with ShaEP and SHAFTS, and gives greater accuracy in the first precision interval ($\text{RMSD} \leq 0.5 \text{ \AA}$).

2.4.4. Other Approaches to Shape Similarity

There are also several examples of molecular shape descriptors that fall outwith the classes described above. Instead, these make use of implicit shape descriptions using size, symmetry, and atom distributions.

The most widely used of these is Comparative Molecular-Field Analysis (CoMFA), a technique for analysing structure-activity relationships for a series of molecules [213]. The pre-aligned molecules are placed in a lattice, and their similarity established by considering the steric and electrostatic interactions at lattice intersections. SAR information is then extracted using partial least-squares analysis. The requirement for alignment permits extraction of shape information from the potential energy fields. As steric and electrostatic interactions are most common in binding, sufficient sampling should answer most questions about the possible receptor interactions a molecule may display. Coefficient contour maps can be easily produced, making CoMFA easy to visualise. However, in addition to the need for alignment, the method fails when a few molecules have considerably different shape and properties to the others under consideration. Related to CoMFA is Comparative Molecular Moment Analysis (CoMMA) [214]. Again these descriptors were designed for use in 3D QSAR studies, but unlike CoMFA, no superpositioning of the molecules is required before comparison. Molecular shape and charge properties are captured by considering the three principal moments of inertia, the dipole moment and the quadrupole moment.

Several descriptors have also been reported that make use of the volume of the molecule to describe shape. Mansfield *et al.* presented an approach that uses the integrals over the Cartesian coordinates of the molecule $V(n_1, n_2, n_3) = \int dx^n, y^n, z^n$ [215]. The set of integers $0 \leq n_1 + n_2 + n_3 \leq 6$ constitute moments of the volume distribution of the molecule to give a set of 84 numbers that describe shape. The descriptors capture information about the absolute orientation and position and can additionally be used to rapidly align molecules. Screen3D from ChemAxon provides a platform for shape-based similarity searching without the need for prior conformer generation [216]. An initial pre-processing step is carried out using the Standardizer and Generate3D modules. The shape of the two molecules under consideration, represented as the van der Waals volume, is then overlaid by considering the intersection between the two volumes. The method was found to give similar performance to 2D fingerprints in a test screen for β -secretase (BACE1) inhibitors, and showed promise at returning genuine hits. Volumetric Aligned Molecular Shapes (VAMS) provides an efficient representation of molecular shape using

voxelized volume [217]. The volume is stored in an oct-tree, a hierarchical data structure that permits comparison of the relevant subsets of voxels only. Comparison is made using Tanimoto similarity. VAMS was found to provide a good balance between run time and performance, although the method does require pre-alignment of molecules before comparison. Fragment oriented molecular shape (FOMS) is an extension of VAMS, where the alignment of molecules is achieved using fragments [218].

Weighted Holistic Invariant Molecular (WHIM) descriptors capture molecular size, shape, symmetry, and atom distribution derived from the x , y , z coordinates of the molecule [219]. The descriptors are constructed by performing principal component analysis on the coordinates considering different weighting schemes for the atoms to construct a covariance matrix.

Hu *et al.* presented the three-dimensional biologically relevant spectrum (3D-BRS), which takes advantage of the fact that ligands taken from bound crystal structures can be treated as a proxy for the shape of the active site [220]. A diverse set of 300 ligands were selected and a matrix of their self-similarity based on surface shape computed. The molecule under scrutiny was then superimposed on each of the ligands, and the resulting 300-dimensional array descriptor fed into a support vector machine model to predict activity.

2.5. Evaluation of 3D Shape-Similarity Methods

As there is no absolute definition of 3D molecular shape, the quality of the approximation given by different descriptors cannot be explicitly validated. Instead, we mimic a real virtual screening experiment using a set of molecules whose activity is known *a priori*, composed of N_A actives and N_D decoys (those which are known or presumed inactive). The new method under consideration is compared to existing work in the field to evaluate their relative predictive power, known as retrospective benchmarking. A series of query molecules are selected to produce a ranking of the data. The quality of the approximation given by each method is then extrapolated from the ability to correctly place active molecules at the beginning of a ranked list [221]. Several public data sets have been designed for retrospective benchmarking. These will be discussed further in **Section 2.5.1**.

For a given data set, the goal is to maximise the number of true positives (TP) at the top of the ranked list, and the number of true negatives (TN) at the bottom of the ranked list. Similarly, we wish to minimise incorrect classifications that give false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN). A user defined cut-off threshold is picked, within which all molecules would be expected to be active. The performance of a method is then quantified by how many correct predictions are made within this threshold (**Figure 2.9**). Several metrics exist that quantify how well true active molecules are retrieved for a given method. These will be discussed in **Section 2.5.2**.

As 3D shape similarity has not been widely adopted for virtual screening, there is currently no “gold standard” combination of data and performance metric used in benchmarking. Several previous studies have made use of the Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced (DUD-E) data set [223], however, each study took a slightly different approach in terms of how many of the

Figure 2.9 Illustration of the expected vs observed outcomes of a ranking produced by virtual screening for a chosen cut-off threshold. All molecules to the left of the cut-off are those classified as active by the method, while those on the right are inactive. Figure reproduced with permission from [222].

active molecules were used as queries and what, if any, consideration was given to the possible conformers accessible to the molecules.

A good comparative study will carefully select the molecules used as queries [63], make use of a data set appropriate for the methods used, and a performance metric that does not rely too heavily on human decision. It should also be easily reproduced by making use of publicly available software and data where possible, and providing copies of the prepared data and original code with any publications.

2.5.1. Data Sets for Retrospective Benchmarking

As the results of validation have been shown to depend on the data used, the choice of a robust data set is an important consideration for a successful retrospective benchmark [224]. Over the years, numerous publicly available benchmarking sets have been developed, which are summarised in **Table 2.3**. Ideally, these would be derived from experimentally validated data. However, as publications tend to favour positive results only, such sources are limited. Several alternative data sets have been curated using decoys in place of true inactives. These are molecules that have been property matched to an active set such that their inactivity can be presumed. The set used must be chosen carefully to avoid confirmation bias [225] and to account for the different requirements of SBVS and LBVS [226].

The first was reported by Bissantz *et al.* in order to evaluate docking software, and consisted of just two targets (Estrogen Receptor Alpha and Thymidine Kinase). Each set contained the Protein Data Bank (PDB) structure of the target, along with 10 known active molecules and 990 decoy molecules from the Advanced Chemical Directory [227]. This was followed by a set curated by McGovern *et al.* to investigate the effect of conformation of the binding site on docking performance. They consider 2200 active compounds and 95579 decoys, both selected from the MDL Drug Data Report (MDDR), across 10 enzymatic targets. Three conformations of the protein are also provided per target [229]. In both of the above cases, the decoys are selected at random. While this aids in avoiding human bias, it gives a decoy set for which the risk of false

Data Set	No. Data Sets	No. Actives	No. Decoys	Class	Source	Year
Bissantz <i>et al.</i> [227]	2	20	1980	SBVS	Curated	2000
Diller <i>et al.</i> [228]	6	958	32000	SBVS	Curated	2003
McGovern <i>et al.</i> [229]	10	2200	95579	SBVS	Curated	2003
DUD [230]	40	2950	95316	SBVS	Curated	2006
MUV [231]	17	510	25500	LBVS	Bioassay	2009
DUD-E [223]	102	66695	1420433	SBVS	Curated	2012
DEKOIS 2.0 [232]	81	3240	97200	SBVS	Curated	2013
MUBD-HDACs [233]	14	631	24609	Both	Curated	2015
Lindh <i>et al.</i> [234]	7	592	1467748	Both	Bioassay	2015
Leśniak <i>et al.</i> [235]	100	17084	19670	LBVS	Bioassay	2019
D-COID [236]	–	1383	69150	SBVS	Curated	2020
LIT-PCBA [237]	15	9780	407839	Both	Bioassay	2020

Table 2.3 Overview of the main data sets for benchmarking virtual screening methods.

negatives has not been minimised. In addition, this does not present a particularly challenging data set, as the decoys may be easily separated from the actives based on simple properties alone (known as artificial enrichment).

An initial attempt to obtain better decoys was proposed by Diller *et al.*, who composed a set of 958 inhibitors and 32000 decoys across 6 kinase targets. The decoys were property matched to the inhibitors based on their molecular weight, number of rotatable bonds and number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors in a bid to construct a more challenging data set [228]. The utility of this was limited by its use of the MDDR, which was not publicly accessible.

The Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD) posed the first true approach to rational decoy design, and quickly became standard for performance evaluation amongst the SBVS community [230]. Covering 40 targets from 6 different classes (Nuclear Hormone Receptors, Kinases, Serine Proteases, Metalloenzymes, Folate Enzymes and Other Enzymes) the set was the most diverse available at the time, offering a reliable view of how a given method may perform on targets of therapeutic interest. The DUD consists of 2950 active ligands, for which 36 decoys have been selected per active. These were chosen to have similar physicochemical properties (molecular weight, calculated LogP, number of rotatable bonds, and hydrogen bond donors and acceptors) to reduce artificial enrichment while minimising topological similarity (through the use of 2D fingerprints) to curb the likelihood of false negatives. The actives and protein structures were taken from the PDB, while the decoys came from the drug-like subset of ZINC. This was later extended to include more diverse protein targets [223]. The Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced (DUD-E) spans 102 protein targets, including those from the original DUD set (**Figure 2.10**). 22886 actives from the ChEMBL database remained after clustering by their Bemis-Murcko frameworks to increase the scaffold diversity amongst the actives. This was carried out to reduce the analogue bias of the DUD. 50 decoy molecules per active were selected from ZINC on the same basis as the DUD, but with the addition of net charge to reduce the ability of the decoys to bind.

Figure 2.10 Broad protein categories for the 102 targets included in DUD-E [223].

An alternative improvement to DUD was proposed by Vogel *et al.*, in which a physicochemical similarity score is constructed from the difference in molecular weight, LogP, number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors and number of rotatable bonds between each active and potential decoy to select challenging decoys from the ZINC database [238]. As with DUD, these are also matched to the actives by 2D dissimilarity to reduce the presence of false negatives. Demanding evaluation kits for objective in silico screening (DEKOIS) initially considered the same set of targets and actives as DUD, with a set of 30 decoys per active. It was later expanded to consider 81 benchmarking sets for targets of therapeutic interest [232]. In DEKOIS 2.0 the active molecules were selected from the BindingDB using filters to remove PAINS, exclude weak binders and removal of ligands with non-specified stereocentres or reactive groups. The decoys were selected in the same way as for DEKOIS, but with the additional consideration of charge and aromatic rings.

The major limitation of DUD, DUD-E and DEKOIS is that they are, by design, too easy for comparison of 2D methods. The dissimilarity between the actives and decoys makes them simple for 2D methods to distinguish [239]. This is aggravated further by the inherent similarity amongst the actives [66].

More recently, Adeshina *et al.* proposed a data set constructed from a few challenging decoys [236]. The Data set of Congruent Inhibitors and Decoys (D-COID) was designed to train machine learning models to optimise scoring functions for docking. Instead of 2D similarity, the decoys were picked from an initial pool of 50 per active (following the DUD-E protocol) using their ROCS similarity to the actives. Interestingly, 8 different scoring functions showed little discriminatory power over the set, suggesting it may be too challenging. As the decoys have been selected based on their shape-similarity to the actives, D-COID would be inappropriate for benchmarking shape-based methods.

In response to the shortcomings of the DUD data set, Rohrer and Baumann proposed Maximum Unbiased Validation (MUV) Data Sets specifically for use in benchmarking LBVS methods [231]. The 17 MUV sets each contain 30 actives and 1500 decoys extracted from the PubChem Bioassay database. As a result, the decoys in this case are true inactive compounds. The set was constructed by first removing potentially problematic actives such as frequent hitters and promiscuous aggregators. A filter is then applied to reduce the differences in physicochemical properties between the active and decoy sets, reducing artificial enrichment. Refined nearest neighbour analysis is then used to reduce both self-similarity amongst the actives and the separation from the decoys to prevent analogue bias. The set has subsequently been proven to have significantly lower bias than DUD [240].

The need for appropriate data to benchmark ligand-based machine learning methodologies was also noted by Leśniak *et al.* who constructed a set of benchmarking sets from the ChEMBL database [235]. The authors note that a major problem with the data for this purpose is that they only cover a small fraction of the total possible drug-like chemical space, and typically cluster around similar scaffolds. This results in the common assumption within machine learning of an independent and identical distribution not being met. This in turn can lead to incorrect training of the model and incorrect evaluation of the incorrectly trained model. To address this, a protocol for data set creation was proposed using 10 receptors as an initial test case. The activity data were standardised to LogK in nM, with a threshold for activity set as 100 nM. Potential duplicates were removed before grouping by SMILES, so that only one compound was associated with a given SMILES representation. Studies using various ligand-based and machine learning models revealed a low level of bias in the set. Using this protocol, the authors published a set of 100 Class A GPCR target data sets for use in machine learning studies.

There are also several publicly available data sets which have been designed to be appropriate for comparison of both SBVS and LBVS methods. The first of these, Maximal Unbiased Benchmarking Data sets for Histone Deacetylases Inhibitors (MUBD-HDACs) consists of 14 sets, 5 of which are dedicated to LBVS due to lack of protein structure availability [233]. 3036 initial actives from the ChEMBL database were reduced to 631 after excluding close structural analogues to reduce bias. A set of 24609 decoys were selected, initially following the same protocol as per the DUD data set, then further filtered down based on high similarity in terms of physicochemical properties and their random spatial distribution to each active compound.

Another approach was proposed by Lindh *et al.* to produce a collection of 7 data sets of varying sizes based on PubChem Bioassay activity data [234]. The MOL2PRINT2D fingerprints between each decoy and the actives were used to promote chemotype diversity, and the count of unique Bemis-Murcko scaffolds used to determine scaffold diversity amongst the actives in a bid to reduce analogue bias. The authors argue that a diverse collection of experimentally validated sets give a more realistic measure of virtual screening performance, as benchmarking data based on actives taken from the literature looks at the final optimised molecules with higher target affinity than typical “hits” from a high throughput screen. They also suggest comparison of any

new method with a basic physicochemical screen as a baseline – if the method outperforms this, then its performance is not based on artificial enrichment.

More recently, LIT-PCBA was proposed by Tran-Nguyen and co-workers as a set suitable for LBVS, SBVS and machine learning [237]. The set of 15 diverse targets taken from the PubChem Bioassay database consists of 9780 actives and 407839 unique inactives which had been filtered to remove false positives and assay artefacts and to keep active and inactive compounds within similar molecular property ranges. The set was tested using ROCS, ECFP4 fingerprints and Surflex-Dock, where docking was found to perform best overall. Each of 15 included sets can have the top 1% enriched by a factor of 2 with true actives retrieved by at least 1 of the above methods.

One further class of benchmarking data centres around the validation of pharmacophore overlay programs. These aim to overlay ligands based on their pharmacophoric features to rationalise their binding affinity, and require known ligand overlays to validate their performance. Giangreco and co-workers identified that most published methods used a different selection of proteins for validation, so set about constructing a consistent data set, known as the AstraZeneca Data Set [241]. The set contains 121 complexes for a range of enzymes (**Figure 2.11**), with ligands filtered to include only organic atoms (C, N, O, P, S, Br, Cl, and F), remove solvents and co-factors and to ensure compliance with Lipinski's Rule of 5. The approach works on the basis that accurate superpositioning of the proteins leads to meaningful overlay of the ligands. The construction of the data set makes use of PROSITE motifs (10-20 amino acids in length important for biological function) to superimpose the proteins without bias from the protein flexibility, with the overlays performed using the OERMSD function from OEChem. The ligand overlays were then analysed using a combination of shape similarity and colour score (using OEShape), and 2D fingerprint similarity. A consensus ranking was constructed to distinguish good and poor overlays, where higher shape and colour similarity and lower 2D fingerprint similarity were given higher priority. As the structures are derived from crystallography, they also make a good test case for shape similarity methods, as they negate the need to consider multiple conformers. The data are available via the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre.

There are also several methods available for creating bespoke decoy sets. DUD-E and DEKOIS both have online servers for data set creation, while the scripts to produce MUV and the Class A GPCR set by Leśniak *et al.* are available on GitHub. The software DecoyFinder is available online to create a set of 36 decoys per active for a given uploaded set [242]. It works similarly to DUD, selecting decoys based on similarity between molecular weight, number of rotational bonds, hydrogen bond donors and acceptors and LogP, while ensuring chemical dissimilarity to the actives based on MACCS keys. In this case, the decoys are retrieved from ZINC.

Figure 2.11 Broad protein categories for the 121 targets included in the AstraZeneca Data Set [241].

2.5.2. Performance Evaluation Metrics

Several metrics then exist to evaluate how well a shape-descriptor has retrieved active compounds from the selected benchmarking data. A good performance metric should have independence to extensive variables, have no free parameters, be statistically robust, give a straightforward assessment of error bounds, be easily understandable [243] and have well-defined lower and upper bounds to facilitate easy comparison between different methods [222].

The simplest of these considers the true and false positives identified. The ability of a method to recall true positives is given by the true positive rate (TPR),

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{N_A}, \quad (2.26)$$

where TP is the number of true positives retrieved, and N_A is the total number of actives in the data set. This is also known as the sensitivity, where a high TPR indicates the method successfully assigns high similarity to molecules with the same activity. The false positive rate,

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{N_D}, \quad (2.27)$$

where FP is the number of false positives retrieved and N_D is the total number of decoys or inactives, can be used to derive the specificity of a method,

$$specificity = 1 - FPR. \quad (2.28)$$

This gives an indication of the ability to give low scores to molecules with different activity. One measure of performance widely used in other fields, and that has been adopted in chemoinformatics, is the area under a receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) [244]. A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve is a plot of the TPR vs FPR as a threshold defining activity is varied,

and depicts the cost-benefit pay-off for a method (**Figure 2.12**). The area under the ROC curve indicates the performance of the method, where an AUC score of 1 means perfect classification, a score of 0 is an entirely imperfect classification and a score of 0.5 is equivalent to a ranking produced by random selection [245]. This offers the advantage of being easy to interpret the relative overall performance of different methods. However, for drug discovery applications, we are most interested in the prevalence of true actives early in the ranked list. As such, a metric which gives higher weighting to the quality of early enrichment is more appropriate.

Figure 2.12 Example of a ROC curve for the ranking of the CXCR4 subset of the DUD-E benchmarking set using USRCAT with the active molecule CHEMBL1089844 as a query. The red dashed line indicates the performance of random selection.

Another widely used evaluation metric is the Enrichment Factor (EF), which gives a measure of the number of actives in a specified top percentage of the ranked list. Several definitions of the EF exist, but it can commonly be considered as the TPR for this fraction of the list [246],

$$EF_{x\%} = \frac{TP_{x\%}}{N_A \times x\%}, \quad (2.29)$$

or by considering the number of both actives and decoys for this fraction [247],

$$EF_{x\%} = \frac{TP_{x\%}/FP_{x\%}}{N_A/N_D}. \quad (2.30)$$

An EF of 1 is considered equivalent to random selection, with higher EF scores indicating higher enrichment, and a negative value showing the method to favour selection of inactive. While this does give an indication of early enrichment, use of EFs has been found to have several flaws. The metric is suitable for comparison of various methods for a single set of ligands, but due to its dependence on the ratio of actives present does not average well across multiple protein targets with different active:inactive ratios [231]. There is also a lack of discrimination within the cut-off point: a method which finds actives as the first 5 of a list of top 10 scoring molecules would be

given the same EF as one which finds actives as the latter 5, where the first case is clearly a better result. What percentage of the ranked list to consider is also arbitrary, and requires a choice from the user that is avoided in other metrics [248]. Consideration of the top 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5% has previously been reported to quantify early enrichment while reducing the dependence on the ratio of actives present [249].

Robust Initial Enhancement (RIE) was introduced by Sheridan and coworkers to address the variation of EF with small numbers of actives [250]. RIE was originally defined as the ratio of the count of actives at the beginning of the ranked list compared to an average derived from a Monte Carlo simulation, in which the actives are randomly assigned a rank from 1 to N, using 1000 trials,

$$RIE = \frac{\sum_i e^{x_i/N}}{\langle \sum_i e^{x_i/N} \rangle_{1000}}, \quad (2.31)$$

where x_i is the relative rank of active i . It has subsequently been recognised that for larger numbers of actives, 1000 trials may not be sufficient to obtain an accurate value. The RIE has therefore been redefined,

$$RIE = \frac{\int_0^1 f_a(x) e^{-\alpha x} dx}{1/\alpha(1 - e^{-\alpha})}, \quad (2.32)$$

to remove the requirement for sampling by taking the averaged exponential of the active position (numerator) and the averaged exponential over a uniform distribution (denominator) [248]. Compared to the EF, RIE has the advantage of including the contribution of all actives in the final score and can discriminate between whether the actives are at the beginning (better ranking) or close to the cut-off threshold (not as good). However, as RIE is a weighted metric, the minimum (all actives at the end) and maximum (all actives at the beginning) values depend on the number of actives (n), the total number of molecules (N) and the early recognition parameter (α) and as such, the metric must be used with care.

An alternative to RIE was proposed by Truchon and Bayly in order to address the dependencies on the active to inactive ratios. The Boltzmann-Enhanced Discrimination of ROC (BEDROC) gives the probability that an active ranked by the evaluated method will be found before a compound from a hypothetical distribution for a specified early recognition parameter α . The metric is defined for a range of possible RIE values:

$$BEDROC = \frac{RIE - RIE_{min}}{RIE_{max} - RIE_{min}}. \quad (2.33)$$

The metric is bound by 0 (poor recall) and 1 (perfect recall), giving easy to interpret results. Scores given by different α values cannot be compared. Instead, α is the equivalent of asking what the required baseline enrichment is for the method to be useful, where a higher value gives higher weighting to early retrieval. The authors suggest setting $\alpha = 20$, which corresponds to 80% of the BEDROC score originating from the top 8% of ranked molecules. It has been

subsequently reported that the BEDROC metric overemphasises a very small proportion of actives, making it poorer than other metrics for early recognition [251]. This can be improved by considering a smaller value of α , but this requires careful balancing to ensure early recognition is also accounted for.

More recently, Lopes *et al.* presented a new performance metric based on the underlying principles of the power of hypothesis test [222]. The Power Metric (PM) for a given cut-off threshold (x) is defined as:

$$PM_{x\%} = \frac{TPR_{x\%}}{TPR_{x\%} + FPR_{x\%}}, \quad (2.34)$$

where $PM_{x\%}$ takes a value between 0 (poor) and 1 (perfect recall). The method was reported to depend less on the selected cut-off threshold and the ratio of actives compared to the total number of molecules than previous performance metrics, but is yet to be widely adopted in virtual screening experiments.

In conclusion, there is currently no explicit way of validating the quality of a 3D shape approximation. Instead, the ability of a method to accurately approximate molecular shape is extrapolated from the ability of the method to correctly predict the activity of a set of known molecules. Retrospective benchmarking currently has no “gold standard” set of data or performance metric for use across all virtual screening attempts. A survey of the literature reveals that most previous shape-similarity methods make use of the DUD-E data set, with the AUC, EF and BEDROC metrics most commonly used to evaluate performance. DUD-E has the advantage of covering a wide range of protein targets, and is well curated, but does not permit comparison of 3D methods to 2D fingerprints due to the analogue bias and deliberate 2D dissimilarity between actives and decoys giving artificially higher enrichment with fingerprint methods. The AUC offers an easy to interpret metric due to the clear bounding between 0 and 1, but does not carry any weighting for early enrichment, while the EF gives a measure of early enrichment but is not easily interpreted and depends on the number of actives and the user-selected cut-off thresholds. The BEDROC metric gives the best account of early enrichment, but also is not easily interpreted due to the choice of α . To best gain insight into overall performance, it is recommended to make use of more than one metric [249].

2.6. Current Limitations of 3D Virtual Screening

As chemists are generally more familiar with 2D representations, 3D shape descriptors have yet to overtake fingerprint representations as the method of choice for LBVS [1]. The advantage of using 3D descriptors is also one of their drawbacks, as generation and comparison of multiple conformers adds significantly to the computational cost compared to 2D screening.

Studies comparing 2D and 3D descriptor performance, as well as their use for virtual screening compared to docking, have been reported [252, 253]. In both cases, the DUD data set (described in **Section 2.5.1**) was used for comparison. Venkatraman *et al.* compared the

fingerprint representations from OpenBabel, BCI, MACCS, Daylight and MOLPRINT2D to five 3D shape representations spanning the different possible approximations: EShape3D, ROCS, Parafit, ShaEP and USR [252]. Their study found the 2D fingerprints to give better overall performance, which was proposed to be due to the consideration of only a single conformer with the 3D methods. Hu *et al.* studied the ECFP2 and FCFP4 fingerprints, Phase Shape (atomic-centred) and Glide docking [253]. Both 2D and 3D methods outperformed docking in terms of early enrichment, with the 2D methods again outperforming the 3D approach. In both cases, the inherent bias towards 2D similarity within the DUD family of data sets was not accounted for [239]. As most chemical data is the result of Chemists' design choices, where close structural analogues are generally favoured, establishing the true relative performance of similarity methods is not a trivial problem. As discussed previously, as different methods generally identify different actives, a hybrid approach may be the best way forward to take advantage of the benefits of both fingerprint and shape-based similarity searching [62].

2.7. Publicly Available Databases for Virtual Screening Experiments

In addition to benchmarking, the choice of database for virtual screening is also important. There are many publicly available databases of compounds that are purchasable, easily synthesised, naturally occurring or theoretical. The databases can be split more broadly into two classes: those containing target information and those that do not.

2.7.1. Databases Containing Target Information

2.7.1.1. ChEMBL

The ChEMBL database, created by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (Funding: European Molecular Biology Laboratory, Wellcome Trust), contains 1879206 compounds corresponding to 12482 target structures [254]. The core database is constructed from structures drawn by hand from peer-reviewed journals, but also contains FDA approved drug molecules. For each structure ADMET properties, binding and functional information, alternative forms, molecular weight and whether Lipinski's Rule of 5 is obeyed is reported [255]. Each structure is listed in its standard InChI format to enable identification of identical molecules. The database can be searched by keyword, protein family, organism, and compound structure (both drawn and in InChI and SMILES format). The full database can also be downloaded free of charge in a number of formats including MySQL, Oracle, SDF and XML. Individual structures can be downloaded as SMILES, InChI, or molfiles.

2.7.1.2. DrugBank

Drugbank is a database collated by the Wishart group at the University of Alberta (Funding: Genome Prairie) consisting of 13450 drug entries linked to 5160 non-redundant protein structures [256]. To be included, molecules must contain more than 1 atom, be non-redundant, have a

known structure and be identified as a drug or be drug-like. The database was designed to allow for more targeted research with molecules drawn from four categories:

- (i) FDA approved small molecule drugs
- (ii) FDA approved biotech (protein or peptide) drugs
- (iii) nutraceuticals or micronutrients
- (iv) experimental drugs

Records include information on the molecular weight, chemical and structural formulae as well as the commercial and IUPAC names. Drugbank can be searched by chemical structure, molecular weight range, drug and food interactions, target sequences or by mass-spec, GC/MS or NMR. The structures can be downloaded individually as SMILES, InChI, SDF or in MOL format, and the entire database is available to download in XML or SDF format (subject to creation of a free account).

2.7.1.3. *PubChem*

PubChem is an open database created by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (Funding: Intramural Research Program of the National Library of Medicine). This database is constructed from substances submitted by individual contributors including university laboratories, government agencies, pharmaceutical companies, chemical vendors, publishers, and chemical biology resources [257]. The structures submitted are then processed, and unique structures are separated into the compound database, which currently consists of 97 million structures. Sub-sets of this data are available to download in SDF, SMILES, InChI and XML formats, with the full database available in XML or SDF format. 97 million compounds (structures extracted from substances), 17847 protein targets, 237 million substances (information deposited by individual contributors) and 268 million bioactivities are represented in the database.

2.7.1.4. *NPACT*

The Naturally Occurring Plant-based Anti-cancer Compound-Activity-Target database (NPACT) is a collection of naturally occurring molecules with experimentally determined anti-cancer activity produced by the Agarwal group at the Institute of Cytology and Preventive Oncology (now known as the National Institute of Cancer Prevention and Research, funding: National Innovation Foundation) [258]. The database currently contains 1574 molecules selected from 762 articles which correspond to 353 different cancer cell lines. Each record contains information on the structure, properties, inhibitory values (IC_{50} , ED_{50} , EC_{50} , GI_{50}), molecular target, supplier and drug-likeness of the molecule. The compounds are categorised by the cancer-type they act on, the corresponding cell line, the target name, compound class and by supplier. **Figure 2.13** shows the distribution of the molecules amongst the different cancer types. The database can be searched online, and individual structures can be downloaded in MOL format.

Figure 2.13 Distribution of molecules against cancer type in NPACT database [258].

2.7.2. Databases Without Target Information

2.7.2.1. ZINC

One of the most highly cited resources is the ZINC database, produced by the University of California (Funding: National Institute of General Medical Sciences) [259]. The database currently contains 230 million 3D structures, designed to be ready for use in docking studies. These can be downloaded in several formats, including as SMILES, MOL2, 3D SDF and DOCK flexibase files. The structures available in the database have been retrieved from a number of commercial catalogues, with all the included structures available to purchase. Molecules with molecular weight > 700 Da, $\text{LogP} > 6$ and < -4 , number of hydrogen bond donors > 6 , number of hydrogen bond acceptors > 11 , number of rotatable bonds > 15 and elements other than H, C, N, O, F, S, P, Cl, Br or I are not included in the database. These conditions lead to a significant proportion of the molecules included obeying either Lipinski's "Rule of Five" (i.e. are "drug-like") [255] or Congreve's "Rule of Three" (i.e. are "lead-like") [260].

2.7.2.2. Asinex Collections

Asinex is a screening library and drug discovery services company who have several electronically available libraries [261]. The newest of these is their BioDesign library, which currently contains 202988 compounds. To generate this set, the structural features of natural products with known pharmacological relevance were analysed. Saturated fused ring, spiro, and bridged systems where multiple chiral centres are common were found to be highly privileged in natural products, but poorly represented in commercial libraries. To remedy this, new synthetic molecules were developed to better represent these structures, with an aim of creating a library of "natural product-like" compounds. Another of the Asinex libraries (Synergy or EliteTM Library) contains 94945 "lead-like" compounds. This library was constructed by screening for ADMET issues. This included DMSO and water solubility, PAMPA, PGP and CYP inhibition, and allowed for creation of a library suitable for hit-to-lead optimisation. Finally, the Gold and Platinum

Collections consisting of 292926 compounds are also available. These libraries contain historical compounds and provide a diverse and cost-effective coverage of drug-like chemical space, with the majority of the compounds obeying Lipinski's Rule of 5 [255]. Each of the three libraries is available to download in SDF format.

2.7.2.3. *GDB Databases*

An interesting approach to the creation of data to screen is that used by the Reymond research group at the University of Bern (Funding: University of Bern, Swiss National Science Foundation). Their GDB databases [262] hold a set of theoretical molecules from mathematical graphs of simple hydrocarbons generated by an in-house Java program. The molecules consider all possible molecules containing hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, and fluorine in accordance with Lipinski's Rule of 5 [255]. This dataset is reduced to a set of synthetically relevant compounds by filtering for stability and functional group synthetic feasibility, followed by the generation of all possible stereoisomers. This was carried out for cases where there are up to 11 atoms (GDB-11 [262], 26.4 million molecules), up to 13 atoms (GDB-13 [263], 970 million molecules) and up to 17 atoms (GDB-17 [264], 166 billion molecules). GDB-11 and GDB-13 are available to download in SMILES format in full and as sub-sets, while GDB-17 is currently only available as sub-sets due to the size of the set.

2.7.2.4. *NCI Database*

The NCI database is a collection of small molecules tested by the National Cancer Institute for anticancer activity [265]. The molecules cover all naturally occurring elements in the periodic table, largely thanks to the activity of platinum complexes against tumours, in addition to the abundance of copper and tin containing compounds and were obtained by scanning of the literature for novel molecules of interest. The database was generated by conversion of 2D structural information into 3D coordinates. For the original release (1994) several challenges are encountered with this, including assignment of stereochemistry, calculation of structures containing elements other than H, C, O, N, F, P, S, F, Cl, Br, I and Si (many early programs did not contain the necessary parameters) and accounting for conformational flexibility and potential energy within 3D structures. For the most recent release this was done using CORINA and includes 265242 structures in SDF format. An online database browser is available, allowing the user to search by similarity (using Tanimoto Index), molecular weight range, a range of number of hydrogen bond donors or acceptors, CAS number and LogP range.

2.7.2.5. *Informative Library Design*

An alternative to searching large libraries is to create a targeted library based on informative library design [266]. In their paper, Bradley *et al.* highlight how improved enrichment for activity can be obtained in this way compared to standard library design by retrospective analysis of a previously published set of data, experimentally assayed for activity as cyclin-dependent

kinase-2 agonists. The goal in this approach is to determine which features are required for activity towards a particular target, then a library is created which maximises these features. The entire library is available in the supplementary information as an Excel spreadsheet along with an explanatory PDF. The file contains SMILES and measured data (including activities towards CDK2) for 17550 compounds. An approach to processing these data was published on the RDKit blog [267], and contains a Jupyter Notebook with all required outputs for use.

2.8. Conformer Generation Methods

In solution, most drug-like molecules are flexible and tend to exist as an ensemble of low energy conformers in equilibrium. Binding to a protein may induce formation of a new conformer, which may be similar to those found in solution, or entirely different [268]. For an effective shape-similarity screen, it is therefore important to efficiently sample the range of possible conformers a molecule can adopt in order to ensure the bioactive conformer is represented in the screening data. An example of the conformational changes that can occur are shown for the antihistaminic drug Temelastine in **Figure 2.14**. Conformational analysis algorithms follow the same general workflow [269]:

1. Rotatable bonds and ring systems are identified. More rigid rings typically require separate treatment using pre-calculated, allowed conformations.
2. Generation of conformers. This typically begins with the connection table, with bond lengths fixed and only dihedral angles of the rotatable bonds varied. Unfavourable conformations may be pruned at this stage, and initial conformers may be subjected to energy minimization and geometry optimization.
3. Identical and very similar conformations are removed by considering the root-mean-square deviation (RMSD, $RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^N ((\Delta d_i)^2)}{N}}$ where N is the number of heavy atoms and Δd_i is the distance between the i^{th} corresponding atom pair).
4. Selection of a set of representative conformers. This step can be completed at the end, or embedded in one of the above steps.

The algorithms used in conformational analysis fall into two broad categories – Stochastic and Systematic. Stochastic algorithms make use of techniques such as Monte-Carlo simulated annealing and distance geometry to randomly sample the available conformational space. In the systematic approach, the torsion angles of all rotatable bonds are incremented by a set amount to regularly sample each of the search space dimensions. Several popular algorithms have been developed that are available on both a commercial and open-source basis. These are discussed in **Section 2.8.1** and **Section 2.8.2**, and are summarised in **Table 2.4**. The final set of conformers generated require scoring, which can be completed using electronic structure methods (quantum mechanical (QM) or density functional theory (DFT)), force fields, rules based on knowledge or probability or through the use of machine learning potentials such as the ANI potential [270]. While more accurate, electronic structure methods are typically too expensive for use with large data sets and as such are typically avoided for LBVS.

Figure 2.14 Example conformational ensemble for 100 conformers of Temelastine. The rotatable bonds are shown in green.

Tool	Type	Algorithm	Availability	Reference
OMEGA	systematic	knowledge-based; full enumeration	commercial	[109]
MOE	both	partial enumeration	commercial	[46]
CORINA	both	rule- and data-based	commercial	[271]
Balloon	stochastic	distance geometry; genetic algorithm	open-source	[272]
Confab	systematic	torsion driven; knowledge-based	open-source	[273]
Frog2	stochastic	Monte-Carlo	open-source	[274]
Conformator	systematic	knowledge-based	open-source	[275]
RDKit	stochastic	distance geometry	open-source	[70]
Auto3D	stochastic	distance geometry ML potential	open-source	[276]
CREST	stochastic	semiempirical QC sampling	open-source	[277]

Table 2.4 An overview of the main conformer generation methods available on a commercial and open-source basis.

2.8.1. Commercial Solutions

OMEGA from OpenEye Scientific Software is a knowledge-based, stochastic approach that computes a conformational ensemble in five key steps [109]. The first two steps involve the construction of the knowledge base, and only have to be completed if and when this changes. A large selection of commercially available compounds is first fragmented into ring systems and small linkers, and at least one conformation is generated for each using an approach similar to

distance geometry, where a rough 3D conformation is generated in line with a set of distance constraints and then optimised using the MMFF94 force field. A set of torsion angle patterns is then populated with a set of values derived from experimental and calculated structures. To generate the conformers, the molecule is matched to the fragment library and assembled using chemical and geometric rules. The torsion angle rules are then applied to the generated conformations to expand to a larger ensemble, with atomic clashes and duplicates removed. The resulting set of conformers are then iteratively ranked until a defined number of conformers is reached based on assessment of atom clashes using a force field. OMEGA is known to perform quick calculations due to its use of pre-defined libraries and effectively captures the space about bioactive conformations.

Molecular Operating Environment (MOE) is a commercial drug discovery package from the Chemical Computing Group that contains both systematic and stochastic search modules [46]. The systematic approach generates the ensemble by rotation of the dihedral angles using fixed increments of 15° for cyclic and 60° or 120° for acyclic bonds. Structures with close van der Waals contacts and atom clashes are removed, then the remaining conformations can be energy minimized. The final set is then filtered to retain only conformations within a fixed energy of the lowest energy conformation, and duplicates based on RMSD dropped. Systematic searching is typically slow, and only suitable for molecules with low numbers of rotatable bonds. The stochastic approach randomly rotates all rotatable bonds in the molecule and inverts stereochemistry. The algorithm used is similar to the Random Incremental Pulse Search [278]. An energy minimization is then completed, and conformers outwith energy and RMSD constraints discarded. The algorithm terminates if a defined number of cycles is reached or a defined number of conformers generated, and is therefore typically fast, but has to be adjusted to sample drug-like space [279].

The CORINA [271] and ROTATE [280] packages are rule- and data-based approaches respectively developed by Molecular Networks. In CORINA, the cyclic fragments of the molecule are treated using a library of ring geometries, which are then relaxed using a force field. The acyclic portions of the molecule are treated by setting the torsion angles to anti or trans configurations, aside from specified cis double bonds, to minimise non-bonding interactions. ROTATE uses a set of rules derived from the conformational preferences of small molecules taken from the Cambridge Structural Database to vary the torsion angles of the acyclic fragments. Similar conformations are grouped, with each group represented by a single conformation to reduce the final number of conformations. CORINA and ROTATE both reproduce bioactive conformers well, but need to be used in combination to cover the cyclic and acyclic fragments of the molecule.

2.8.2. *Open Source Solutions*

The freely available software Balloon makes use of a genetic algorithm to refine the produced conformers [272]. The need for the generated conformers to have energy within a certain range of the minimum, show the greatest geometric variance within the given energy window and not

contain any duplicates makes conformer generation a multimodal optimization problem. Genetic algorithms offer an easy-to-implement solution to such problems, although they do require choice of parameters to balance run time and quality. An initial 3D structure is first generated using distance geometry. The rest of the population is then filled with N random conformers, and their energies calculated using the MMFF94 force field. The initial conformations are then subjected to the genetic algorithm, which adjusts the initial ring conformations, stereochemistry, torsion angles and chiral centres to produce a diverse set of conformers near the energy minimum. A further filter is then applied to remove duplicates, those within a RMSD threshold of the lowest energy conformer and those of high energy to ensure the final set are all unique and biologically relevant.

Confab is a knowledge-based command-line tool that aims to provide systematic coverage of the possible conformational space [273]. This is achieved by sampling all the allowed torsion angles, based on a set of allowed angles defined in a supplied file using SMARTS strings. No conformers are therefore generated for molecules with no rotatable bonds. If a maximum number of conformers to generate is specified, the conformational space is sampled randomly to make sure sufficient coverage is achieved. The energies are then computed using the MMFF94 force field, and any conformer outwith a threshold energy of the minimum or with an RMSD within a user selected value of the conformers already produced are discarded. Confab is also available as part of the Open Babel toolbox [281].

Frog2 is a web-based tool that can produce conformers from 1D, 2D and 3D initial inputs [274]. An initial conformation is produced by graph decomposition of the molecule into cyclic and acyclic components, and identification of stereo centres with unspecified chirality. The rings are treated by selecting a conformation from a library, and the acyclic components are constructed using bond lengths and angles derived from literature. An ensemble is then generated using a two stage Monte-Carlo method. Conformational flexibility is first explored based on a defined number of atom-type dependent dihedral angles, with a filter applied to remove redundant conformations. The first stage conformations are then refined by uniform consideration of small rotations. The final set of conformations are then energy minimised using the AMMOS force field.

Conformator is a command line conformer generation tool that uses an enhanced torsion-driven approach with clustering to efficiently compile the final ensemble while minimising the number of comparisons between pairs [275]. Methods are defined for both fast and best that focus on computational efficiency and accuracy respectively. Each single acyclic bond is assigned a torsion angle based on fragment matching to the supplied library and the bond lengths calculated by summing the covalent radii and adjusting for atom type. Torsion angle values are then iteratively removed so that the maximum number of possible conformations is less than or equal to the maximum number of generated conformations for clustering, with priority for a higher number of torsion angles placed on non-terminal rotatable bonds. After selection of all torsion angles, conformer generation is completed by construction of the fragments, beginning with the central fragment. Ring conformations are then accounted for using a template library,

with the rings added to the constructed conformer starting with the highest connected ring. The clustering algorithm groups the generated conformers based on adjustment of the minimum RMSD between them, and determines an appropriate threshold for each molecule such that the ensemble produced does not exceed a defined maximum size. The procedure can handle a variety of input formats (SMILES, SDF, MOL2 and InChI), and has additional capacity to produce conformations for macrocyclic molecules.

The widely used Chemoinformatics toolkit RDKit also contains inbuilt capability to produce conformer ensembles. Originally, this made use of a distance geometry outlined by Blaney and co-workers [282]. A matrix of pairwise distances within the molecule is created to describe the structural space for a molecule. The matrix is then refined using the triangle inequality rule, then multiple conformers produced by generating random distance matrices that ensure the conditions imposed by the initial bounds matrix are met. An improvement to yield more chemically meaningful conformers was later proposed by Riniker and Landrum using experimental torsion knowledge distance geometry (ETKDG) [283]. Distance geometry is quick, but is known to cause issues with distorted aromatic rings and sp^2 centres. The approach uses experimental torsion angles derived from the Cambridge Structural Database described using SMARTS patterns to correct conformers generated using the distance geometry. The conformers generated can be optionally energy optimised using the UFF or MMFF94 force fields. A threshold RMSD can also be specified to produce a diverse set of conformations. Further improvements have been made to the ETKDG approach using improved torsion angles and to produce better ring and macrocycle conformations [284, 285]. To address the limitation within RDKit of the requirement to specify a number of conformers to produce, which poses a particular issue with inflexible molecules, Ebejer *et al.* proposed a set of further conditions to build a diverse and representative set of conformers. They proposed that the maximum number of conformers generated should be dictated by the number of rotatable bonds (n_{rot}) with thresholds as outlined below:

$$n = \begin{cases} 50 & \text{if } n_{rot} \leq 7 \\ 200 & \text{if } 8 \leq n_{rot} \leq 12 \\ 300 & \text{if } n_{rot} \geq 12 \end{cases}$$

The set of generated conformers are then energy minimized and sorted, and the lowest energy conformer kept. For each remaining conformer, a comparison is made to each in the list to keep, and if any RMSD is below a threshold of 0.35\AA the conformer is discarded as already being represented within the ensemble.

The Conformer–Rotamer Ensemble Sampling Tool (or CREST) outlined by Pracht and colleagues provides an alternative quantum chemical approach, where semi-empirical quantum chemical sampling is used to generate conformational ensembles [277]. Unlike the chemoinformatics-type algorithms such as RDKit, CREST can produce sensible conformations of any molecule without the need for special heuristics, but cannot compete in terms of speed.

Li *et al.* recently proposed a Python pipeline to combine several of the above tools for automated generation of low energy conformations for a set of input SMILES [276]. For the molecule under consideration, tautomers, and stereoisomers are first enumerated using OpenEye's toolkit [286] before building a set of low energy 3D conformations with using the ETKDG algorithm from RDKit [283]. Use of OpenEye's software does require a licence, but these components equally could be replaced with equivalents from RDKit. The initial conformers are then optimised using neural network potentials such as ANI [270], and any duplicates removed by a RMSD filter. The pipeline also includes modules for parallelization of larger jobs.

2.8.3. Conformer Generation using Machine Learned Approaches

More recently, several approaches have been proposed that make use of machine learning models to produce conformer ensembles, although these have yet to be widely adopted. Simm and Hernández-Lobato proposed the use of a conditional variational autoencoder with Euclidean distance geometry to give a probabilistic model for generating samples of molecular conformations from an initial graph representation [287]. The model was trained using the CONF17 benchmarking set, and was found to produce conformations closer to the ground truth than those given by RDKit. To add consideration of torsion angles, Ganea and co-workers developed GEOMOL, which uses a message passing neural network to capture both global and local graph information to predict torsion angles and atomic structures [288]. The model uses only one angle per non-terminal bond, reducing the need to over-parameterize the degrees of freedom of the molecule. GEOMOL was found to generate ensembles quicker and as effectively as other machine learning models. Further use of conditional variational autoencoders was proposed by Xu and colleagues, where instead of the typical two-stage approach of atomic distance prediction then distance geometry optimisation, an end-to-end single step framework is implemented [289]. The initial molecular graph representation is first embedded in the latent space, then a principled bi-level optimization program is solved to generate 3D structures. Conformer-RL is an open-source Python package presented by Jiang *et al.* to generate diverse, low energy conformers using reinforcement learning [290]. Conformer-RL uses a simple interface to permit training of the model without the need for an in-depth understanding of machine learning or programming. The module also includes tools to save and visualise the generated conformers.

2.9. “Rules of Thumb” in Drug Discovery

Given the scale of enumerated chemical space, statistically, many of the molecules contained within databases are unlikely to yield promising drugs. As such, the construction of a set of robust filters to remove such cases without time-consuming analysis (termed rapid elimination of swill or REOS by Walters *et al.* [15]) is crucial for efficient *in silico* efforts. Several sets of general “Rules of Thumb” have been proposed to predict whether a molecule will display drug-like behaviour. These are designed to exclude molecules that do not meet the following criteria:

- Molecules containing functional groups that are known to yield undesirable properties.
- Molecules with properties unlikely to give drug-like behaviour, including but not limited to large molecular weight and flexibility.
- Drug-likeness of the chemical composition, usually limited to consider atom types commonly found in molecules (H, C, N, O, F, P, S, Cl) and common scaffolds found in drugs.

While such rules usually do not provide a “catch-all” solution, they are generally successful in biasing the search towards promising candidates.

Perhaps the most widely used set of rules for drug discovery is Lipinski’s Rule of Five (Ro5), which provides a set of criteria to estimate oral bioavailability [255]. If a compound violates more than one of the following conditions, poor absorption or permeation is more likely:

- Molecular Weight \leq 500 Da
- Number of Hydrogen Bond Acceptors \leq 10
- Number of Hydrogen Bond Donors \leq 5
- Calculated LogP (octanol-water coefficient) \leq 5.

The rules were later extended to consider additional important bioavailability predictors, including the number of rotatable bonds present (\leq 10) and polar surface area (\leq 140 Å²) [291]. Although these rules have proven useful, they must be used with care. As these were developed for consideration of oral bioavailability, they do not apply in the search for medicines to be delivered via other routes. While there are many approved drugs that pass the Ro5 test, often this is by design, and there are equally many notable examples of approved oral drugs that disobey Lipinski’s rules [292].

Analogous to the Rule of Five is Congreve’s Rule of Three, proposed for identification of ideal fragments for fragment-based lead discovery [293]. These proposed fragments should have:

- Molecular Weight $<$ 300 Da
- Number of Hydrogen Bond Acceptors $<$ 3
- Number of Hydrogen Bond Donors $<$ 3
- Calculated LogP (octanol-water coefficient) $<$ 3
- Number of Rotatable Bonds $<$ 3

in order to probe key binding interactions in the protein while minimizing unfavourable interactions.

Several sets of filters for unwanted functional groups have also been proposed. Pan assay interference compounds (PAINS) are compounds that show activity for multiple targets, and as a result often appear as false positives in a high throughput screen [294]. This promiscuity can often lead to unwanted side effects and increased risk of toxicity. The structures of some common PAINS are given in **Figure 2.15**. While in many cases such compounds are worth

Figure 2.15 Structures of the common pan-assay interference compounds (PAINS) known to frequently give false positive results.

avoiding, there are many examples of approved drugs containing PAINS, and as such their use should be considered with caution [295].

A further list of undesirable substructures was compiled by Brenk and co-workers during their work screening for neglected tropical disease treatments [296]. These substructures (**Figure 2.16**) were found to be reactive (thiols and 2-halopyridines), mutagenic (nitro groups) or had poor pharmacokinetic properties (sulfates).

Figure 2.16 Examples of unwanted substructures found to give undesirable pharmacokinetics or toxicity by Brenk *et al.* [296]: Thiols (reactive); 2-Halopyridines (reactive, where X = F, Cl, Br, I); Nitro groups (mutagenic); Sulfates (unfavourable pharmacokinetic properties).

The NIH filter set based on the work of Jadhav *et al.* [297] and Doveston *et al.* [298] defines a list of unwanted functional groups, categorised as either reactive functionalities or those considered unsuitable for medicinal chemistry optimisation. Michael acceptors, epoxides, metals, aldehydes, α -chloroketones and β -lactams are amongst those considered reactive functionalities, while hydrazines, flavanoids, oximes, crown ethers, polyphenols, and primary halide sulfates are classed as medicinal chemistry exclusions.

Various attempts have also been made to define value-based metrics of drug-likeness. Quantitative Estimate of Drug-likeness (QED) was introduced as an easy to interpret measure of desirability [299]. QED assigns a value between zero (all unfavourable properties) to one (all favourable properties) based on the construction of empirically derived functions d of property distributions by fitting to a set of 771 approved oral drugs. Akin to Lipinski’s rules, included in the functions are the molecular weight, octanol–water partition coefficient, number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, with additional consideration of number of rotatable bonds, polar surface area, number of aromatic rings and number of structural alerts. The QED score is then calculated by taking the geometric mean of all functions,

$$\text{QED} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln d_i \quad (2.35)$$

A similar metric was proposed by Wager *et al.* for drugs targeting the central nervous system [300]. The central nervous system multi-parameter optimization (CNS MPO) algorithm assigns a score between 0 and 6 by summation of the desirability of six properties, each given equal weighting: calculated partition coefficient, distribution coefficient, molecular weight, topological polar surface area, number of hydrogen bond donors and most basic centre. The score was

constructed by considering 119 central nervous system marketed drugs, and 108 CNS candidates from Pfizer, with 74% of the marketed drugs displaying a high CNS MPO score > 4 , compared to just 60% of the Pfizer candidates.

All the checks and filters above are available via the RDKit and provide a rapid means to check for drug-likeness of user-designed molecules [70]. As a side project to the work presented in this thesis, these “Rule of Thumb” checks were implemented in FEGrow, our in-house software for building congeneric series of ligands in protein binding pockets [36].

2.10. Summary

In summary, the premise that similar molecules share similar biological activity has been used widely in ligand based virtual screening. Similarity searching generally has been shown to successfully identify hits from minimal initial activity data. While there are many ways to quantify how similar two molecules are, the use of molecular shape has gained traction in recent years, as the need for complementarity allows the shape of a known binder to act as a proxy for the shape of the binding pocket. Compared to other similarity methods, the use of 3D shape permits consideration of the different conformers that can be adopted and can identify novel scaffolds, a useful trait when addressing unwanted properties with the initial query. Currently, compared to 2D fingerprint applications, there are no widely adopted open-source shape similarity methods. Additionally, the use of molecular surface-based shape descriptors have been under adopted compared to atomic-centred and atomic-distance descriptors, despite offering a desirable balance between speed and accuracy. This thesis aims to address this through the introduction and benchmarking of two molecular-surface based descriptors based on the application of the mathematical theory of Riemannian geometry.

Chapter 3. Hearing the Shape of a Drug

3.1. Introduction

Riemannian geometry, a branch of differential geometry, involves the study of spaces, in particular curved surfaces. A full introduction to the theory of Riemannian geometry is beyond the scope of this work. The interested reader can find further technical detail in [301]. Central to the theory is a mathematical object associated with the surface, known as the *Riemannian metric*, g . The metric is a positive definite symmetric matrix, that is one of positive eigenvalues, that captures shape by describing the distribution of the area across the surface. However, due to the dependence of the metric on the initial orientation and parameterisation of the surface, direct comparison of two metrics is not a simple task. Riemannian geometry has found a wide range of applications, including in physics [302], medical signal processing [303, 304] and machine learning [305, 306]. The ability to represent a surface as a series of intersecting spheres permits the explicit calculation of g . This makes the description of molecules a natural novel application of Riemannian geometry, as each atom can be represented as a sphere of its van der Waals radius.

Two approaches to transform the metric into an easily comparable object for use in virtual screening have been proposed: Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation (RGMolSA, **Chapter 4**) and Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation (KQMolSA, **Chapter 5**). This work was completed in collaboration with Dr Stuart Hall, who produced the underpinning mathematics. The resulting code, hosted at [8] and [9] respectively, was produced jointly, with all benchmarking results produced by the author of this thesis. The full theory is outlined in [6] and [7]. The remainder of this chapter details the construction of g common to both approaches. **Section 3.2** provides an outline of the practical implementation of the parameterisation of molecules, and **Section 3.3** discusses the development work behind these steps.

3.2. Parameterising Molecules for Riemannian Geometry

Molecules are initially viewed as a series of N intersecting spheres of van der Waals radii, known as the space filling or CPK model (**Figure 3.1**), first introduced by Corey and Pauling [158]. The problem is simplified without much loss in quality of the approximation by treating all hydrogen atoms as implicit, which is possible due to their comparatively small size and well-defined positions based on the valence of the parent atom. The CPK model can be constructed by obtaining the number of atoms, Van der Waals radii (re-scaled by a factor of 0.6 to prevent clashing), 3D coordinates of the atomic centres and the $N \times N$ adjacency matrix, T , describing

the bonds between atoms where

$$T_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if spheres } i \text{ and } j \text{ intersect} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise (or } i = j \text{)}. \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

These are obtained from a Structural Data File (SDF) using the RDKit toolkit [70].

Figure 3.1 Space filling (CPK) model of Sildenafil.

The first assumption made is that the molecular surface, S , to be approximated contains no “holes”. Mathematically, this is described as the surface having a genus of 0. Small rings with fewer than 12 atoms (such as benzene and pyridine) are replaced with a single sphere of radius 2.25 Å, with the new centre taken as the centre of mass of the constituent atoms. The choice of radius is discussed further in **Section 3.3.1**. As the eventual shape descriptors provide only an approximation, and as most rings contained in molecules are of a relatively similar size, there would be no significant advantage to differentiating between rings. The adjacency matrix is also updated to include the intersection of each ring with its neighbours. An example of the input data before and after replacement of rings is given in **Figure 3.2**. The assumption that molecular surfaces have a genus of zero introduces the limitation that molecules containing genuine rings cannot be described. This rules out the consideration of macrocyclic molecules, large rings containing more than twelve atoms that have a genuine hole in their surface [307] (**Figure 3.3**). While the ability to include macrocycles would be useful, such molecules do not feature heavily in small-molecule drug design. Molecules containing these motifs can be removed as defined in **Chapter A, Algorithm 2**.

To simplify the subsequent mathematics, the surface of the molecule is mapped into the complex plane using *piecewise stereographic projection*. This mapping requires the definition of a starting sphere within the molecule, termed the “level-0” or base sphere. The base sphere is chosen by finding the centre of mass of the molecule,

$$[C_x, C_y, C_z] = [\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}], \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.3 Cyclosporin A, an example of a macrocyclic drug used in immunosuppression.

Figure 3.4 Each sphere has a level determined by how many spheres connect it to the base (level-0) sphere. (a) Levels within Sildenafil with each level shown as a different colour, starting from the base sphere in grey. (b) Corresponding level matrix describing the path through the molecule.

In the theory of Riemannian geometry, two metrics that differ only in size are treated as having essentially equivalent shape. This equivalence is accounted for in the final shape descriptors by re-scaling molecules to have a total surface area equal to 4π , chosen as it is the surface area of a unit sphere. While the fixed values of the atomic radii prevent this phenomenon in the context of molecular surface approximation, the re-scaling is still included as it significantly simplifies the subsequent mathematics. The initial surface area of the molecule is computed as the area of each sphere minus the “missing parts” where two spheres intersect:

$$\text{Area} = 2\pi \sum_i \left(2r_i^2 - \left(r_i \sum_j T_{ij} |r_i - \lambda_{ij}| \right) \right), \quad (3.4)$$

where r_i are the atomic radii, T_{ij} is the adjacency matrix, and λ_{ij} is a matrix encoding distance information between the atoms,

$$\lambda_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{r_i^2 - r_j^2 + \|c_i - c_j\|_{\text{Euc}}^2}{2\|c_i - c_j\|_{\text{Euc}}} & \text{if } i \neq j, \\ 0 & \text{if } i = j, \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\|c_i - c_j\|_{\text{Euc}}$ is the Euclidean distance between the i^{th} and j^{th} atomic centres in real space. This value is used to re-scale the initial radii r_i , atomic centres and λ_{ij} that represent the space filling model of the molecule to give a surface area of 4π .

One further consideration arising from the choice of base sphere is the positions of the atoms surrounding it. If there is an atom directly over the ‘‘North Pole’’ of the base sphere, this can affect the mapping into the complex plane. To adjust for this, if such an atom exists, the atomic centres of the molecule are rotated in increments of 10° until a gap between the base sphere and the ‘‘North Pole’’ atom is found.

The final preparation step prior to computing the shape descriptor of the surface S is to ‘‘unwrap’’ the molecule from 3D space (\mathbb{R}^3) onto the complex plane, \mathbb{C} , one sphere at a time, using a *map* known as *piecewise stereographic projection*. The resulting embedding of a single sphere of radius r centred at the origin can be visualised by imagining shining a torch from the North Pole (N). The points on the plane where the light lands, shown on the left of **Figure 3.5** in red, give the coordinates of the disc (shown in red on the right) that represents the ‘‘cap’’ of the sphere – the portion above the grey dotted line. The remainder of the sphere from the base to the cap, of height h , lies outside the disc as shown in grey. The North Pole is omitted from the image produced.

Figure 3.5 Stereographic projection sends the cap (above the grey dotted line) of a sphere of radius r in 3D space to a disc (red) in the complex plane \mathbb{C} .

Mathematically, the inverse map $\varphi_r : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ is given by the function from the complex plane onto a sphere of radius r centred at the origin,

$$\varphi_r(z) = \frac{r}{1 + |z|^2} (2\text{Re}(z), 2\text{Im}(z), |z|^2 - 1), \quad (3.6)$$

where Re is the real part and Im is the imaginary part for a complex number $z = x + yi$. This results in the sphere representing an atom in real space being mapped to a disc,

$$\mathbb{D}(\mathcal{R}) = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| \leq \mathcal{R}\} \subset \mathbb{C}, \quad (3.7)$$

in the complex plane with radius

$$\mathcal{R} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{r+h}{r-h}\right)}. \quad (3.8)$$

Beginning with the base sphere, which we treat as the North Pole, the molecule is iteratively rotated so that each atom is unwrapped in turn into \mathbb{C} . This gives the “discs within discs” picture shown in **Figure 3.6**, where the holes within a disc represent where the corresponding atom connects to a higher level sphere, and the space outside the discs represents connection to lower level spheres. The base sphere lies outside the discs, as shown in grey.

Figure 3.6 The “discs within discs” picture associated to the domains of piecewise stereographic projection for Sildenafil, with the base sphere shown in grey, and the discs representing higher level spheres.

Both descriptors derived from the metric are computed in \mathbb{C} rather than \mathbb{R}^3 as the formulae involved are more naturally manipulated using complex coordinates. RGMolSA and KQMolSA both consider the molecule as constructed from a family of shapes, rather than as a single shape. The use of complex coordinates simplifies the tracking of how these shapes relate to each other.

One shortcoming with the method is that it provides a good representation of the surface geometry near to the base sphere. However, atoms at a high number of levels from the base sphere are mapped onto artificially small regions in the complex plane, and as such would need many eigenvalues to describe them accurately. This is less problematic for small molecules, but can introduce numerical instability, in particular for long chain molecules with few rings.

The *Riemannian metric* then takes the general form

$$g = \mathcal{F}(dx^2 + dy^2) \quad (3.9)$$

where \mathcal{F} is a differentiable function over the disc $\mathbb{D}(a_i, R_i)$ corresponding to the i^{th} atom of the form

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{C_i}{(|z - A_i|^2 + B_i)^2}, \quad (3.10)$$

where A_i , B_i and C_i are derived from the initial input data. This allows the metric, g , to be described as a single function capturing the shape by describing the distribution of the area across the surface. As discussed previously, the dependence of the metric on the initial parameterisation of the surface prohibits direct comparison. The methods RGMolSA and KQMolSA outlined in the subsequent chapters address this using slightly different forms of the metric (given in **Equations 4.3** and **5.3** respectively).

3.3. Development of Parameterisation Steps

3.3.1. Accounting for Rings

To permit the treatment of a molecule as having a genus of zero, the small rings must be accounted for. This includes rings such as benzene, fused bicyclic rings, rings joined by a single bond and bridged bicyclic compounds (**Figure 3.7**). Two strategies to achieve this were considered.

Figure 3.7 The four main categories of rings to account for (from left to right): single rings, fused bicyclic rings, single bonded rings and bridged bicyclic rings.

The first makes use of the fact that a surface with a metric induced in the complex plane can be allowed to intersect in \mathbb{R}^3 . The molecule can then be imagined as being constructed from a material that can pass through itself. This allows the ring to be treated as a self-intersecting cylinder, which can then be treated with the existing mathematics. The cost of this is to render the meaning of the surface area as a little cloudy, as some of the area of the ring is hidden inside the interior. To achieve this, one of the ring bonds is “cut”. This is a trick commonly used in Riemannian geometry to handle donut-shaped surfaces: we make a slice transverse to the ring and then cap off the slice to remove the hole and allow our ring to be described with our existing method.

In practise, this involves changing the 1 to 0 in the adjacency matrix for the indices at which we are making the cut. Ideally, this should be made at a position within the ring next to a non-ring atom, and not at the base sphere. This works well for simple examples such as Paracetamol (**Figure 3.8**), however, extending to more complex examples such as bridged bicyclic molecules proved challenging. Additionally, there is some redundancy in the position selected for the break, as in many cases there will be multiple possibilities for where the break can be made. In the case of Paracetamol, we could make the cut between ring atoms 1 and 2 (red) or between atoms 1 and

6 (blue). A different choice of position would result in differences in the descriptor produced (Tables 3.1-3.2).

Figure 3.8 Structure of Paracetamol, highlighting the possible positions for a bond cut.

Cut Position	Descriptor
Cut At 1-2 (red)	[101.581, 0.75, 7.72, 12.019, 12.491, 22.441, 26.579, 36.386, 39.197]
Cut At 1-6 (blue)	[101.532, 0.754, 8.416, 10.397, 12.369, 24.613, 26.802, 37.19, 40.092]

Table 3.1 Example of the differences that arise for the different bond cuts shown in Figure 3.8 for the RGMolSA descriptors.

Cut Position	Descriptor
Cut At 1-2 (red)	$\begin{bmatrix} 3.305 + 0.j & -2.112 - 4.412j & -4.611 + 6.918j \\ -2.112 + 4.412j & 8.537 + 0.j & -6.182 - 12.176j \\ -4.611 - 6.918j & -6.182 + 12.176j & 22.959 + 0.j \end{bmatrix}$
Cut At 1-6 (blue)	$\begin{bmatrix} 4.042 + 0.j & -3.045 + 0.836j & 2.276 - 1.251j \\ -3.045 - 0.836j & 2.625 + 0.j & -1.965 + 0.543j \\ 2.276 + 1.251j & -1.965 - 0.543j & 1.709 + 0.j \end{bmatrix}$

Table 3.2 Example of the differences that arise for the different bond cuts shown in Figure 3.8 for the KQMolSA descriptors with $k = 1$.

The second approach considered, and ultimately used, was that of replacing each ring with a single sphere in order to remove the holes from the surface. This required the choice of a radius to represent the approximate size of rings. To do this, the surface area, volume (using RDKit [70]) and radius derived from the volume as

$$r = 0.75(V/\pi)^{1/3}, \quad (3.11)$$

where 0.75 is a scale factor similar to that applied to the radii of the other atoms in order to prevent clashing of the discs in \mathbb{C} , for a series of saturated and unsaturated ring structures commonly found in drug molecules were computed [308, 309]. These are reported in Tables 3.3-3.4. Generally, across rings of 3–7 atoms in size, the surface area, volume, and radii are all relatively similar, allowing the approximation of rings with a single radius. While this will overestimate smaller rings and underestimate larger rings, the nature of the shape as approximate anyway means this has little effect on the overall quality of shape descriptor while significantly simplifying the replacement of rings. Based on the average radius (with a small adjustment to

Name (No. Atoms)	Area (Å ²)	Volume (Å ³)	Radius (Å)
Cyclopropane (3)	33.56	42.88	2.17
Oxirane (3)	31.90	39.54	2.11
Aziridine (3)	32.50	40.62	2.13
Cyclobutane (4)	45.41	53.68	2.34
Cyclopentane (5)	56.35	64.69	2.49
Pyrrolidine (5)	55.34	62.74	2.46
Oxolane (5)	54.33	61.30	2.45
Thiolane (5)	62.12	70.93	2.57
Cyclohexane (6)	67.32	76.16	2.63
Piperazine (6)	62.62	70.43	2.56
Piperidine (6)	65.87	73.88	2.60
Cycloheptane (7)	78.64	88.54	2.76

Table 3.3 Saturated Rings

Name (No. Atoms)	Area (Å ²)	Volume (Å ³)	Radius (Å)
Cyclopentene (5)	53.98	62.54	2.46
Cyclopentadiene (5)	52.32	61.45	2.45
Furan (5)	49.66	57.58	2.40
Imidazole (5)	48.99	56.24	2.38
Thiazole (5)	55.43	63.97	2.48
Triazole (5)	48.15	54.37	2.35
Benzene (6)	61.73	71.34	2.57
Pyridine (6)	60.70	69.34	2.55
Oxazine (6)	60.57	68.22	2.53
Cyclohexene (6)	65.98	75.17	2.62

Table 3.4 Unsaturated Rings

ensure all spheres still intersect), a value of 2.25 Å was selected for use in the final descriptor calculation.

Replacing rings with a single sphere does introduce a couple of limitations to the method. Primarily, for bridged bicyclic structures composed of multiple rings (e.g. Memantine, **Figure 3.9**) replacement of each constituent ring leads to too many “intersecting bits” in the calculation of the surface area (see **Equation 3.4**) giving a negative value. As such, any molecule with a negative surface area is excluded from comparisons. In total this gives an estimated 23 known drugs RGMolSA cannot approximate (based on the Drugbank Database consisting of 2451 unique entries) [256].

One further error is introduced in the replacement of rings for a handful of test cases. Tadalafil is one such example (**Figure 3.10**). Depending on the order in which RDKit numbers the atoms, upon replacement of rings, one of the bonds making up ring 4 is counted as a direct single bond between rings 1 and 5. This leads to an extra intersection being added to the adjacency matrix, and a slight over-estimation of the area of the molecule when this bond is not used to account for the intersection between rings 1 and 4 (as each bond is only considered once).

Figure 3.9 Structure of Memantine, a bridged bicyclic drug constructed of 4 rings.

Figure 3.10 The bonds between rings 1 and 2 and rings 1 and 5 are treated as chemically equivalent, as the method cannot “see” ring 4 as in between rings 1 and 5.

3.3.2. Choosing the Base Sphere

Several possibilities were considered for the best approach to choosing a starting point for descriptor construction. Theoretically the atom selected as the base sphere is arbitrary, but, as discussed previously, this choice aims to minimise the subsequent number of steps through the rest of the molecule. To achieve this, the selected atom should give the lowest number of “levels” in the matrix of levels.

Initially, the atom with the most immediate neighbours was used as the starting point. This was calculated by taking the sum of each row in the adjacency matrix, and taking base to be the atom with the highest value as the base. If more than one atom had the same value, the first occurrence was used. From a mathematical perspective, this seemed a sensible approach. However, in a chemical context, valency constraints give a maximum of 4 neighbouring atoms (e.g. for tetrahedral carbon) in most cases, with many equally connected atoms within the molecule. The use of the first instance also led to the base sphere often ending up as a chain end, giving numerous levels for larger molecules.

One alternative to this was to compute the number of levels obtained when each atom is considered in turn as the base sphere. While this does result in the optimal choice, it is computationally inefficient to do this.

Instead, the use of the molecular centroid offers a good compromise between efficiency and appropriate selection. The theory here is that the atom in the middle of the molecule should be roughly equidistant from each end point in the molecule, resulting in a reduced number of levels. This does introduce some variance in the choice of base sphere for conformers of the same molecule, which also helps to discern cases where shape is genuinely different.

For example, for Paracetamol (**Figure 3.8**), the most connected and minimised-levels approaches both pick the carboxyl oxygen as the base sphere, while the molecular centroid approach uses the benzene ring as the base sphere. This choice will give a better descriptor of the global shape, as the number of subsequent steps through the molecule are reduced. For a small molecule like paracetamol this is less of an issue, but for larger molecules the choice of an “end” atom as the base sphere makes the “discs within discs” smaller than Python can handle at the other end, introducing numerical errors into the method.

One further possibility for the selection of the base sphere could make use of the natural representation of a molecule as a graph, and using the shortest path problem to identify the optimal base sphere. This will be investigated in future development of the method.

3.4. Conclusion

The theory of Riemannian geometry can be applied to approximate the shape of molecular surfaces. The underlying object that captures the shape, known as the *Riemannian metric*, can be computed explicitly by representing the molecule as a space filling model. The initial parameterisation steps to construct the metric are summarised in **Figure 3.11**.

Figure 3.11 Summary of the initial parameterisation steps to construct the *Riemannian metric*, g .

The use of Riemannian geometry takes the assumption that the surface, S , under consideration contains no holes. This is achieved for molecular surfaces by replacing small rings with a single sphere, but introduces the constraint that both subsequent descriptors cannot be used to approximate the shape of macrocycles. Computation of the metric also requires the selection of a “base sphere” – an atom within the molecule to use as a starting point to map the molecule into the complex plane. This is taken as the atom with the closest Euclidean distance to the geometric centre of the molecule. The robustness of this choice could be further improved in future development by using graph theory, treating base sphere selection as a shortest path problem.

While the metric does capture the geometric properties of the surface, comparison of two metrics is non-trivial. In the subsequent Chapters, two methods to convert the metric into a molecular descriptor suitable for comparison in virtual screening are presented. **Chapter 4** outlines Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation, which makes use of the *spectrum* of the Laplacian to approximate the metric with a 9-element vector descriptor. **Chapter 5** describes Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation, where the subfield of Kähler geometry is applied to produce a *Hermitian matrix* descriptor of molecular shape from g .

Chapter 4. Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the first of two approaches to transform the *Riemannian metric*, introduced in **Chapter 3**, into an easily comparable object for use in virtual screening. Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation (RGMolSA) achieves this using the *spectrum* of an operator called the Laplacian. An overview of the method is given here, with the full theory outlined in [6].

The *spectrum* is the ordered set of *eigenvalues* (v_S) obtained by examining the behaviour of the *Laplace-Beltrami operator* (Δ) associated with a surface, given by

$$\Delta f = \lambda f, \quad (4.1)$$

where λ is an *eigenvalue* and f is the associated *eigenfunction*.

The use of *spectrum* of the Laplacian as a shape descriptor was first proposed by Reuter and co-workers [3]. The approach was later applied by Seddon *et al.* to describe molecular surfaces, representing the molecule using a mesh, and then clustering the local spectral descriptors computed for each vertex of the mesh to produce a global shape descriptor [4]. While this proved an effective shape descriptor compared to existing approaches, the need to first approximate the molecular surface using a mesh is time-consuming.

RGMolSA approximates the metric g using the *spectrum* of the Laplacian, which can be truncated to the 9^{th} eigenvalue producing a vector, v_S . In theory, if two metrics are close in the space of all metrics, then the spectra must also be close. The vector describes the geometry of the surface in a way that permits comparison. In this approach, the convention that the eigenvalues will be non-negative is adopted. The form of the final descriptor v_S is

$$v_S = (10^4/A, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_8), \quad (4.2)$$

where A is the surface area of the molecule, which replaces the smallest eigenvalue (which always has a value of 0) to account for the re-scaling of the molecule to have a surface area equivalent to that of a unit sphere (4π). The choice of scale factor will be discussed further in **Section 4.3.2**. The ability to compute the metric g explicitly as a result of treating the molecule as a set of intersecting spheres permits the exact integrals involved in computing the *spectrum* to be calculated, and avoids the need for computationally expensive mesh generation. The

descriptors are also invariant to rotation and translation, and do not require alignment prior to their comparison.

The method for computing v_s is described further in **Section 4.2**, using Sildenafil (a PDE5 inhibitor used in the treatment of Erectile Dysfunction) as an example to illustrate the concepts described. **Section 4.3** discusses the development work completed, and **Section 4.4** presents a case study investigating the initial potential of the method.

4.2. Constructing the RGMolSA Descriptor from the Riemannian Metric

To construct the RGMolSA descriptor, the molecule is first parameterised as outlined in **Chapter 3**. A summary of the steps to construct the descriptor are given in **Figure 4.1**.

Figure 4.1 Key steps involved in the computation of the RGMolSA surface descriptor for Sildenafil (a PDE5 inhibitor).

The *Riemannian metric* is computed explicitly in its symmetric form:

$$g = \begin{cases} \frac{4r_B^2}{(1+|z|^2)^2} (dx^2 + dy^2) & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{C} \\ \frac{C_1}{(|z-A_1|^2+B_1)^2} (dx^2 + dy^2) & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{D}(a_1, R_1), \\ \frac{C_2}{(|z-A_2|^2+B_2)^2} (dx^2 + dy^2) & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{D}(a_2, R_2), \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{C_{N-1}}{(|z-A_{N-1}|^2+B_{N-1})^2} (dx^2 + dy^2) & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{D}(a_{N-1}, R_{N-1}), \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

where r_B is the radius of the base sphere and

$$\mathcal{C} = \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{D}(a_1, R_1) \cup \mathbb{D}(a_2, R_2) \cup \dots \cup \mathbb{D}(a_{N-1}, R_{N-1}), \quad (4.4)$$

is the complement of the discs associated with the base sphere. This allows the metric, g , to be described as a single function.

As discussed in **Section 4.1**, the geometry of the molecular surface can be approximated using the *Laplacian*, by solving the equation

$$\Delta f = \lambda f \quad (4.5)$$

to obtain a set of eigenvalues λ , that can be ordered to give the *spectrum* of the Laplacian. There are several definitions of the *Laplacian*, Δ , one of which makes explicit the reliance on g :

$$\Delta f := -\frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{|g|} g^{ij} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_j} \right), \quad (4.6)$$

where $|g|$ is the determinant of the metric g and g^{ij} is the matrix inverse of g in these coordinates. It is not possible to compute the *spectrum* exactly. Instead, the *Rayleigh–Ritz approximation* is used to define two symmetric matrices \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , such that

$$\mathcal{A}^{-1} \mathcal{B} \varepsilon = \lambda \varepsilon, \quad (4.7)$$

giving λ is an eigenvalue of the symmetric matrix $\mathcal{A}^{-1} \mathcal{B}$.

The calculation of the \mathcal{B} matrix is straightforward, with the integrals computed in terms of the metric, defined as:

$$\mathcal{B} = \text{Diag} \left(0, \frac{8\pi}{3}, \frac{8\pi}{3}, \frac{8\pi}{3}, \frac{32\pi}{5}, \frac{8\pi}{5}, \frac{8\pi}{5}, \frac{8\pi}{5}, \frac{96\pi}{5} \right). \quad (4.8)$$

Obtaining the \mathcal{A} matrix on the other hand is a little more complicated, but can be achieved using the *Rayleigh–Ritz approximation* with a set of test functions. The choice of functions used is arbitrary, but they are required to be in some sense independent of each other. Here these are taken as

$$X(z) = \frac{2\text{Re}(z)}{1+|z|^2}, \quad Y(z) = \frac{2\text{Im}(z)}{1+|z|^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad Z(z) = \frac{1-|z|^2}{1+|z|^2}. \quad (4.9)$$

These functions are not entirely independent of one another, as $X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 = 1$. This property allows some of the possible combinations to be excluded when constructing the first 9 spherical harmonics as test functions, f_i :

$$\begin{aligned} f_0 &= 1, \\ f_1 &= X, \quad f_2 = Y, \quad f_3 = Z, \\ f_4 &= X^2 - Y^2, \quad f_5 = XY, \quad f_6 = XZ, \quad f_7 = YZ, \quad f_8 = 3Z^2 - 1. \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

Spherical harmonics were chosen here as the test functions as these already appear as a solution to the eigenfunction problem (and therefore work for a round surface) [162]. The functions required were obtained using Mathematica [310], and can be called as needed by the user. The entries of the \mathcal{A} matrix are then given by

$$A_{ij} = \int \int_{\mathcal{C}} f_i f_j \mathcal{F} dx dy, \quad (4.11)$$

where,

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{2\mathcal{C}}{(|x + iy - A|^2 + B)^2}, \quad (4.12)$$

and the area over which to integrate is defined by g . For a sensible choice of f_i , the eigenvalues given by **Equation 4.7** are approximately equivalent to those of the Laplacian.

The resulting set of eigenvalues can then be ordered as a sequence

$$0 = \lambda_0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_3 \leq \lambda_4 \leq \lambda_5 \leq \lambda_6 \leq \lambda_7 \leq \lambda_8 \quad (4.13)$$

known as the truncated *spectrum* of the Laplacian. The convention that eigenvalues are non-negative is used, and λ_0 always has a value of zero. To account for the re-scaling of all molecules to have surface area equal to 4π , and to prevent two very different sizes from being classed as similar, λ_0 is replaced with the surface area of the molecule, scaled so that the size contribution does not dominate over the shape contributions in the distance calculation. The selection of this scale factor is discussed further in **Section 4.3.2**. The final shape descriptor then takes the form:

$$v_S = (10^4/A, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_8). \quad (4.14)$$

The use of the truncated spectrum of the Laplacian as a descriptor for molecular shape offers the advantage of being rotation and translation invariant, negating the need for alignment of molecules prior to similarity calculation as is needed in several other existing shape similarity methods. The descriptors are also invariant under isometric deformation, meaning distance preserving deformations to the surface yield the same set of eigenvalues. Compared to the previous use of the Laplacian reported by Seddon and co-workers [4], the use of the *Riemannian metric* avoids the need to first approximate the surface with a mesh, making RGMolSA more computationally efficient.

The method does depend on the choice of base sphere, especially in the case of very large long-chain molecules, where higher level spheres are projected onto smaller and smaller discs, leading to numerical errors in the calculation of the spectrum. As the spectrum is constrained to have non-negative eigenvalues, and only one eigenvalue equal to 0, any descriptor where this is not met indicates a numerical error has occurred. The contribution to the \mathcal{A} matrix of any sphere with integrals below a certain threshold are set to 0 to stabilise the calculation, the choice of which is discussed in **Section 4.3.1**.

There are many sensible ways to compute the similarity between two simple 1D vectors. In chemical similarity searching, it is convention for easy interpretation to select a measure such that a score of 1 is given for self-comparison, and 0 when two molecules share no common features. RGMolSA makes use of the Bray-Curtis distance, a metric originating from ecology used to compare the presence of a species in two sites [311]. The measure is naturally bounded by 0 (identical) and 1 (no similarity) and is available via the distance module of the SciPy package [312]. Here similarity between two vectors u and v is defined as the inverse Bray-Curtis distance to fit with the previous convention of a similarity score of 1 when two molecules are identical:

$$d(u, v) = 1 - \frac{\sum |u_i - v_i|}{\sum |u_i + v_i|}. \quad (4.15)$$

4.3. Development of the RGMolSA Descriptor

4.3.1. Selecting Thresholds for \mathcal{A} Matrix Contributions

As discussed in **Section 4.2**, numerical instability exists within the method, indicted by the presence of negative or 0 values of λ_2 in the descriptor. This arises in particular for the case of long chains of atoms. To address this, constraints can be applied so that the contributions of integrals that fall below a certain value are set to 0. To investigate the values that these constraints (b and c) should take, the descriptors for the Drugbank database were computed. This is a database of 13450 approved and investigational small molecule drugs associated with 5160 protein structures [256]. These were filtered according to the protocol outlined in **Appendix A** (ignoring the Rule of 5 and PAINS filters) to give 9988 test cases. Initially the thresholds for b and c were arbitrarily selected as 10^{-9} , however, this still resulted in a significant number of errors. To select the optimal threshold pair to minimise errors while maintaining descriptor quality, b and c were varied together and independently when computing the descriptors for the Drugbank set (**Tables 4.1-4.3**).

c	b	no. $\lambda_2 < 0$	no. $\lambda_2 = 0$
10^{-9}	10^{-9}	538	484
10^{-8}	10^{-8}	395	347
10^{-7}	10^{-7}	335	290
10^{-6}	10^{-6}	256	214
10^{-5}	10^{-5}	215	317
10^{-4}	10^{-4}	684	816

Table 4.1 Count of negative λ_2 values when the contributions to the \mathcal{A} matrix of both b and c are varied.

The number of instances of negative and zero values for λ_2 were counted for each value of b and c . From this, a stronger dependence on the contribution of the c terms was identified, allowing the selection of $c = 10^{-5}$ and $b = 10^{-7}$ to minimize the presence of negative and zero eigenvalues. This still resulted in 215 cases of $\lambda_2 < 0$. These remaining instances were accounted for by setting $\lambda_2 = 0$ at the end of the algorithm before returning the final descriptor.

b	no. $\lambda_2 < 0$	no. $\lambda_2 = 0$
10^{-9}	538	484
10^{-8}	512	461
10^{-7}	379	330
10^{-6}	329	283
10^{-5}	279	267
10^{-4}	379	544

Table 4.2 Count of negative λ_2 values when the contributions to the \mathcal{A} matrix when b is varied and $c = 10^{-9}$.

c	no. $\lambda_2 < 0$	no. $\lambda_2 = 0$
10^{-9}	538	484
10^{-8}	397	360
10^{-7}	345	289
10^{-6}	256	214
10^{-5}	215	216
10^{-4}	680	815

Table 4.3 Count of negative λ_2 values when the contributions to the \mathcal{A} matrix when c is varied and $b = 10^{-9}$.

4.3.2. *Weighting the Surface Area in the Final Descriptor*

Selection of the appropriate weight for inclusion of the original surface area (A , measured in \AA^2) of the molecule in the final descriptor was completed by considering the similarity of Sildenafil and the follow-up drugs Vardenafil and Tadalafil, that both share similar shape to Sildenafil and as such should have similarity scores close to 1 (**Section 4.4**). The scores given by the original descriptor do reflect this, but could also result in molecules with significantly different sizes being classed as similar. **Table 4.4** presents the results of varying the scale of the surface area included in the descriptor.

For these drugs (and indeed most others) the surface area takes a value of magnitude 10^2 , a factor of 10-100 bigger than the typical values observed in the descriptor and therefore at risk of dominating over the other values in the similarity calculation. In other words, the shape description would become near-redundant, with only molecules of similar size being classified as similar. The first element of the vector, λ_1 is therefore replaced by the inverse area weighted by a scaling factor (a):

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{a}{A} \quad (4.16)$$

When $a = 1$, the surface area term contributes negligibly to the similarity measure. As a increases, the similarity score increases, and the relative ordering (Sildenafil and Vardenafil as the most similar) remains the same. In the final descriptor $a = 10^4$ is selected as a compromise, giving a/A of order 1, comparable to the larger eigenvalues in the surface descriptor.

	no A term	A	$a = 10^0$	$a = 10^1$	$a = 10^2$	$a = 10^3$	$a = 10^4$
Sildenafil-Vardenafil	0.882	0.955	0.882	0.882	0.882	0.885	0.903
Sildenafil-Tadalafil	0.769	0.875	0.768	0.768	0.769	0.774	0.809
Vardenafil-Tadalafil	0.667	0.833	0.667	0.667	0.668	0.675	0.725

Table 4.4 The inverse Bray-Curtis distance between a series of PDE5 inhibitors. The first element of the vector descriptor is replaced by either the unscaled surface area (A), or the inverse area (scaled by a).

4.3.3. Investigating Enantiomers

Another important consideration in drug discovery is the ability for molecules to adopt different enantiomers. These are non-superimposable mirror images that can have different properties as drugs. For example, the small molecule drug Propoxyphene has two uses - one enantiomer Dextropropoxyphene is an analgesic, while the other Levopropoxyphene relieves the symptoms of the common cold. While it would therefore be useful to be able to distinguish between different enantiomers in virtual screening, as mirror images these should be classed as identical when considering shape alone. To investigate how RGMolSA handles this, the molecules in **Figure 4.2** were used. Enantiomer pairs were generated from the SMILES representation of the molecule using the RDKit EnumerateStereoisomers module, then embedded in 3D. The similarity score, surface area and base sphere for each pair are reported in **Table 4.5**.

Figure 4.2 Known enantiomeric drugs: Thalidomide (sedative), Fluoxetine (antidepressant), Methadone (opioid addiction relief) and Pentobarbital (sedative)

Name	Base Sphere 1	Base Sphere 2	Area 1	Area 2	Score
Thalidomide	1	1	172.009	173.649	0.991
Fluoxetine	1	7	211.899	211.710	0.573
Methadone	7	6	227.960	227.021	0.887
Pentobarbital	4	4	149.082	149.578	0.308

Table 4.5 Similarity scores between enantiomers of the same molecule for RGMolSA.

In each case, the surface areas are very similar for each enantiomer, however some variance is observed in the selected base sphere for Fluoxetine and Methadone. How different the two enantiomers are varies across the molecules considered. However, none give a score of exactly 1, meaning that at a minimum the different enantiomers would not be assigned as exactly the

Figure 4.3 3D structures of the known enantiomeric drugs.

same by the method. A significantly lower score is observed for Pentobarbital than the other enantiomers. Inspection of the 3D conformations (**Figure 4.3**) shows a difference, especially for Pentobarbital, suggesting this is the reason for the lower scores.

The variation in conformation means that these examples are not true mirror images. True enantiomers in 3D space can instead be produced by embedding a single conformer then inverting the z coordinates, $(X, Y, Z) \rightarrow (X, Y, -Z)$. As above, the similarity score, surface area and base sphere for each pair are reported in **Table 4.6**.

Name	Base Sphere 1	Base Sphere 2	Area 1	Area 2	Score
Thalidomide	1	1	170.258	170.25	0.999
Fluoxetine	7	7	208.660	208.660	0.996
Methadone	4	4	147.724	147.724	0.990
Pentobarbital	7	7	225.087	225.087	0.973

Table 4.6 Similarity scores between enantiomers of the same molecule using $(X, Y, Z) \rightarrow (X, Y, -Z)$.

This time both the surface area and base sphere values are the same for each enantiomer, and the scores obtained are much closer to the expected value of 1 (identical). Any remaining difference can be attributed to numerical instability and rounding within the method.

4.4. Case Study: Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) Inhibitors

The first in class Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) inhibitor Sildenafil used to treat erectile dysfunction [66], and the follow-up drugs Vardenafil and Tadalafil provide a good initial test case for molecular shape descriptors (**Figure 4.4**). Structurally Tadalafil is quite different from Sildenafil and Vardenafil (which is a close structural analogue of Sildenafil with only minor improvement in potency). However, all three occupy similar volumes in the binding pocket of PDE5, implying they also have similar shapes. Sildenafil to Tadalafil is an example of scaffold hopping, where the difference in chemical structure gives a marked improvement in therapeutic profile compared

to the other two drugs [313]. In theory, as these molecules are known to have similar shape, they should give high shape-similarity scores. This section reports the findings from an initial case study using the above PDE5 inhibitors to probe the effectiveness of RGMolSA as a molecular shape descriptor.

Figure 4.4 PDE5 inhibitor Sildenafil and the follow-up drugs Vardenafil (a “me-too” drug) and Tadalafil (example of a scaffold hop).

4.4.1. Investigating Molecular Conformations

As one of the main benefits of using 3D descriptors is the ability to consider different molecular conformations, it is important for the descriptor to differentiate between conformers of the same molecule. To test the tolerance of RGMolSA toward different conformers, two small sets of 10 conformers for each of the PDE5 inhibitors were generated. The first considered conformers chosen at random (**Figure 4.5a**), while the second set selected a subset of the lowest energy conformers from a larger pool (**Figure 4.5b**), as this is a common approach in large scale screening. Due to the relatively rigid nature of these molecules, we’d expect relatively high similarity (scores above 0.7), but less than 1 to permit differentiation. If all descriptors were the same, the shape descriptor effectively becomes an expensive 2D similarity approach, as the benefit to 3D is lost. Slightly higher similarity scores may be expected for the low energy conformers than the random set, where smaller changes have occurred. While this is by no means an exhaustive sample, initial insight can be gained in a short time frame from the general trend. The conformers of each molecule were computed following the procedure outlined in **Appendix B**.

To establish how the shape similarity scores relate to the conformational changes, the root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) for each pair was computed. This is the standard measure used

Figure 4.5 Overlay of (a) 10 random conformers of Sildenafil, (b) 10 low energy conformers of Sildenafil.

widely as a measure of the similarity between two conformers based on their atomic positions,

$$RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^N d_i^2}{N}}, \quad (4.17)$$

where d is the distance between two atoms, and N is the total number of atoms in the molecule.

Figure 4.6a shows the minimum, maximum, and average shape similarity and the average RMSD for each of the small sets of conformers. Comparison of the RMSD and shape similarity values for each pair of conformers, excluding self comparisons, is given in **Figure 4.6b** and **4.6c** respectively. The full results are given in **Appendix C**. As anticipated, for each set the shape similarity remains relatively high despite variance in the RMSD. None of the sets have all scores equal to 1. This highlights the classification of conformers as having similar shape despite differences in their atomic positions, while retaining the capability to distinguish between them. While verification on a larger set is still required, this small initial sample indicates that RGMolSA shows promising potential in handling conformers. This capability may in part be due to the insensitivity of the spectrum of the Laplacian to isometric deformation of the surface. The ability to relate molecular conformations permits the identification of potential hits that can deform to fit into the binding pocket, and confirms the lack of requirement of a pre-alignment of the two molecules before calculating their similarity in this approach. The insensitivity of the method to small surface deformations may also give the additional advantage that small conformational changes can be ignored. For large screens, this would massively improve efficiency, while still capturing the range of shapes a molecule can adopt and offers a potential further application of the method as a conformer-pruning tool.

4.4.2. Comparison to Other 3D Shape Similarity Methods

The known shape similarity of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil also makes these a good initial test case to compare RGMolSA to other existing open source shape descriptors. **Table**

4.4 Case Study: Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) Inhibitors

Figure 4.6 Shape similarity vs RMSD across the test sets of conformers of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil. (a) Overlay of the most and least shape-similar conformers of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average shape similarity and RMSD for each set. On average, the conformers display a high degree of self-similarity despite the variance in atom-position similarity. (b) and (c) show swarm plots of the RMSD (in Å) and shape similarity respectively for our set of conformers. These highlight the general trend that different conformers are classed as having similar shape, despite significant variance in their atomic positions. Conformers with RMSD less than 1 Å are considered similar, while those over 3 Å have significant differences.

4.7 outlines the performance of our method compared to the atomic-distance based USRCAT descriptors implemented in RDKit [152, 70], Shape-It (an open-source version of ROCS) [81], and MolSG, the molecular surface descriptor presented by Seddon *et al.* [4]. The 1024-bit Morgan fingerprint with radius 3 is also included, which is a 2D representation of molecules in binary format, implemented in RDKit [70]. Similarity close to 1 (identical) would be expected for comparison of Sildenafil and Vardenafil across all methods, due to their similarity in terms of both shape and structure. Conversely, while high shape similarity is expected for comparison of Sildenafil and Vardenafil to Tadalafil (although lower than Sildenafil-Vardenafil), lower scores would be anticipated for the fingerprint-based method. Here one conformer is considered for each molecule for simplicity.

Of the descriptors tested, RGMolSA gives the highest scores for Sildenafil–Vardenafil, and produces the similarity ranking expected (Sildenafil-Tadalafil and Vardenafil-Tadalafil as less similar than Sildenafil–Vardenafil). Surprisingly, the method outperforms the more established USRCAT and Shape-It approaches, which each give similarity scores between the PDE5 in-

	RGMolSA	USRCAT	Shape-It	MolSG	Morgan Fingerprint
Sildenafil-Vardenafil	0.903	0.384	0.388	0.704	0.667
Sildenafil-Tadalafil	0.809	0.269	0.278	0.746	0.201
Vardenafil-Tadalafil	0.725	0.291	0.353	0.887	0.209

Table 4.7 Comparison of our method to existing atomic-distance [152], atomic-centred [81] and molecular surface based [4] descriptors. In all cases, the similarity scores given are bound by 0 (no similarity) and 1 (identical).

hibitors less than 0.4. They do however still produce the expected ranking of Sildenafil-Tadalafil and Vardenafil-Tadalafil as less similar than Sildenafil-Vardenafil, so some information can be gleaned from the relative scores in these cases. Using MolSG, Tadalafil is actually identified as more similar to the two closely related analogues, Sildenafil and Vardenafil, than they are to each other. The Morgan fingerprint performs as expected, assigning significantly higher similarity between Sildenafil-Vardenafil and classifying Tadalafil as entirely different. However, the similarity between Sildenafil-Vardenafil is still lower than the typical threshold of 0.7 used in virtual screening. The high ranking produced by RGMolSA suggests it to be a promising approach for full-scale similarity searching in drug discovery.

4.4.3. Control: Comparison to Potential Decoys

Given the comparatively high similarity scores reported for RGMolSA in Section 4.4.2, we wanted to demonstrate that the method does not simply classify all molecules as similar. Comparison to four other potential decoy molecules, with activity against different targets, was completed to achieve this (Figure 4.7): Arginine is smaller but has the same general shape (a long chain of spheres); Lyme cycline has a higher molecular weight but a similar scaffold (4 ring motif) to Sildenafil; Diflorasone has a similar molecular weight and a similar scaffold (4 ring motif); S-octylglutathione again has similar molecular weight, but no rings and the potential for similarity due to the branching in the centre of the molecule.

Figure 4.8 presents the results of this comparison. With scores generally ranging between 0.3-0.7, none of these molecules would likely be identified as potential hits for PDE5 inhibition in a virtual screen. With scores greater than 0.7, only Vardenafil with Arginine, Sildenafil with Diflorasone and Tadalafil with Diflorasone would potentially be classified as having some similarity by RGMolSA. By eye, Diflorasone has a similar shape to Sildenafil and Tadalafil: all contain 4 rings and have similar surface area. High similarity between Tadalafil and Diflorasone especially would be expected due to the presence of 4 fused rings in their structure. Despite one containing rings while the other does not, the overall shape of Vardenafil and Arginine could be considered similar, as both are constructed from a chain of spheres (be they rings or atoms). This suggests the potential capability for scaffold hopping within our method, although also indicates the potential need to include pharmacophoric information, as these molecules would be expected to display significantly different activity.

Figure 4.7 Chemical structures of potential decoy molecules.

Figure 4.8 Inverse Bray-Curtis similarity of four “different” molecules (blue) to the PDE5 inhibitor test series (red). The overlay of the structures was computed using Open3DAlign [314].

4.4.4. Screening a Small Set of Other PDE5 Inhibitors

To gain initial insight into how well RGMolSA may do in identifying true actives in a real virtual screen, a set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors (PubChem AID 446781) with known nanomolar activity were scored using Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil as queries. As these are known actives, they should in theory yield high similarity scores to each of the queries. This study compares the rank order by shape similarity to the true activity (based on pIC_{50}), and probes the effect of conformer choice of both the query and test molecules on the resulting similarity score.

To do this, three cases were considered:

- A single random conformer of both the query and test molecules.
- A single query conformer using the binding pose taken from the crystal structure (PDB IDs 1UDT, 1UHO, 1XOZ). If available, these represent the best query conformation for shape similarity searching, as they give the best approximation to the shape of the binding pocket.
- Multiple conformers of both the query and test molecules, generated using the procedure outlined in **Appendix B**. The number of conformers produced is determined by the number of rotatable bonds present, a measure of the flexibility of the molecule [315].

Additionally, the effect of alignment of the atomic-centres of the test molecules, using Open3DAlign [314], to those of a single query conformer was also investigated. A summary of the computed surface area and number of conformers generated is given in **Tables 4.8 and 4.9** for the query and test molecules, respectively.

Tables **Tables 4.10–4.16** present the similarity scores for the top 5 most potent test cases (**Figure 4.9**), which in theory we would expect reasonably high similarity scores, greater than 0.7 in line with the typical threshold used to indicate potential activity. In each case the average score across the three queries is reported, as this would be used in a real screen to produce the final ranking, as well as the computed surface area to highlight any size differences between the molecules. The full results of this study are presented in **Appendix D**.

Figure 4.9 Structures of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors from the assay AID 446781 by pIC₅₀.

Consideration of a single conformer for the queries (either chosen at random or from the bound crystal structure) and test molecules gave overall lower similarity than expected (**Tables 4.10 and 4.11**). A small improvement is seen for the conformer of the query taken from the bound crystal structure compared to the randomly generated one, suggesting these should be used where available. This result emphasises the need for conformational sampling in a real virtual screen when using shape-based methods to ensure that all potential hits are identified.

4.4 Case Study: Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) Inhibitors

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil
Surface Area (Random)	314.57	326.45	260.86
Surface Area (Crystal)	317.70	333.96	263.83
No. Conformers	199	200	195
Surface Area (average)	318.84	329.11	263.93

Table 4.8 Surface area, and number of conformers considered for the queries Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil.

	ID	Surface Area (Average)	No. Conformers
1	11993170	316.58	278
2	11992634	311.69	296
3	11993171	314.05	300
4	45486504	316.39	275
5	11993561	341.04	298

Table 4.9 Surface area, and number of conformers considered for the top 5 most potent test molecules.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.450	0.509	0.339	0.433	9	313.48
2	0.964	0.874	0.843	0.894	0	308.73
3	0.073	0.085	0.052	0.070	9	311.38
4	0.034	0.039	0.024	0.032	9	313.93
5	0.958	0.901	0.806	0.888	0	336.86

Table 4.10 Similarity scores for a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.504	0.521	0.523	0.516	9	313.48
2	0.887	0.855	0.848	0.863	0	308.73
3	0.084	0.087	0.089	0.087	9	311.38
4	0.039	0.041	0.041	0.040	9	313.93
5	0.907	0.886	0.861	0.885	0	336.86

Table 4.11 Similarity scores for a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to the conformation of Sildenafil (1UDT), Vardenafil (1UHO) and Tadalafil (1XOZ) taken from the molecule bound to PDE5.

As the descriptors produced by RGMolSA are in theory invariant under uniform rotations and translations of the initial molecular data, they should not require any alignment of molecules prior to comparison. Any alignment of two molecules should therefore yield the same similarity score as without alignment. To test this, pre-alignment of the molecules was carried out (**Tables 4.12** and **4.13**). This triples the run time, as the descriptors have to be re-calculated after each alignment. In most cases the scores obtained are reasonably close but not exactly the same as without alignment, with several exceptions where significant difference is observed. This is more prominent for Tadalafil over Sildenafil or Vardenafil, and in the case where random query conformers are used over the binding pose. As this change in score on alignment is not persistent

across all molecules, and as the base sphere and surface area remain consistent, this difference may be due to numerical error within the integration steps in computing the descriptor.

	Sildenafil	ΔS	Vardenafil	ΔV	Tadalafil	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.006	0.444	0.522	-0.013	0.339	-0.011	0.433	9	313.48
2	0.962	0.002	0.882	-0.008	0.843	0.001	0.894	0	308.73
3	0.077	-0.004	0.520	-0.435	0.052	-0.296	0.070	9	311.38
4	0.469	-0.435	0.516	-0.477	0.024	-0.118	0.032	9	313.93
5	0.953	0.005	0.906	-0.005	0.806	-0.004	0.888	0	336.86

Table 4.12 Similarity scores for a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil. The test molecules were aligned to each query prior to scoring using OpenAlign3D. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between scores with and without alignment.

	Sildenafil	ΔS	Vardenafil	ΔV	Tadalafil	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.516	-0.012	0.541	-0.020	0.523	0.305	0.516	9	313.48
2	0.320	0.567	0.854	0.001	0.848	0.002	0.863	0	308.73
3	0.526	-0.442	0.542	-0.455	0.089	-0.447	0.087	9	311.38
4	0.237	-0.198	0.238	-0.197	0.041	-0.494	0.040	9	313.93
5	0.918	-0.011	0.893	-0.007	0.861	0.199	0.885	0	336.86

Table 4.13 Similarity scores for a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to the conformation of Sildenafil (1UdT), Vardenafil (1UHO) and Tadalafil (1XOZ) taken from the molecule bound to PDE5. The test molecules were aligned to each query prior to scoring using OpenAlign3D. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between scores with and without alignment.

Significant improvement is seen in the average similarity scores obtained when multiple conformers of both the test set (**Tables 4.14** and **4.15**) and queries (**Table 4.16**) are used. The maximum score using multiple query conformers is close to that for the bound conformer in each case, suggesting sufficient sampling carried out to capture this. While the average similarity to each query remains low when multiple conformers are considered, the maximum similarity is > 0.8 in all cases, so all 43 inhibitors would be identified as potentially active in a real screen. This differential again highlights the necessity for conformational sampling. Due to the dependence of RGMolSA on the base sphere selected, some of the variance in scores across different conformers of the same molecule may be the result of variation in the selected base sphere (**Figure 4.10a**) in addition to genuine changes in shape. Some variance is also observed in the surface area of the test molecules for different conformers (**Figure 4.10b**), however this is likely less significant.

It is also interesting to note that the most active molecules by pIC_{50} were not the top scoring by shape similarity. These were found to vary depending on the query, as would be expected. **Figure 4.11** shows the space filling models of the top 5 scoring molecules compared to each query. The highest scoring test conformer and binding pose query are used in each case. By-eye inspection of the structures suggests their consideration as similar (scores of > 0.9 in all cases) is reasonable. It's worth noting that Sildenafil and Vardenafil yield the same set of highest scoring

4.4 Case Study: Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) Inhibitors

	Average Sildenafil	Average Vardenafil	Average Tadalafil	Average	Max. Sildenafil	Max. Vardenafil	Max. Tadalafil
1	0.551	0.562	0.450	0.521	0.970	0.939	0.841
2	0.550	0.563	0.448	0.520	0.969	0.942	0.872
3	0.600	0.615	0.489	0.568	0.969	0.937	0.898
4	0.553	0.570	0.446	0.523	0.970	0.939	0.837
5	0.773	0.775	0.650	0.733	0.963	0.964	0.884

Table 4.14 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil.

	Average Sildenafil	Average Vardenafil	Average Tadalafil	Average	Max. Sildenafil	Max. Vardenafil	Max. Tadalafil
0	0.565	0.561	0.557	0.561	0.951	0.920	0.899
1	0.564	0.562	0.561	0.562	0.954	0.925	0.926
2	0.616	0.613	0.609	0.613	0.948	0.918	0.899
3	0.570	0.568	0.564	0.568	0.951	0.919	0.899
4	0.776	0.770	0.754	0.766	0.964	0.951	0.908

Table 4.15 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to the conformation of Sildenafil (1UDT), Vardenafil (1UHO) and Tadalafil (1XOZ) taken from the molecule bound to PDE5.

	Average Sildenafil	Average Vardenafil	Average Tadalafil	Average	Max Sildenafil	Max Vardenafil	Max Tadalafil
1	0.545	0.545	0.503	0.531	0.970	0.970	0.949
2	0.551	0.549	0.504	0.535	0.972	0.969	0.952
3	0.592	0.592	0.548	0.578	0.970	0.970	0.951
4	0.555	0.554	0.505	0.538	0.970	0.970	0.950
5	0.721	0.728	0.701	0.717	0.968	0.969	0.942

Table 4.16 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to multiple conformers of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil.

Figure 4.10 Variation in (a) base sphere and (b) surface area across multiple conformers, the top 5 pIC₅₀.

molecules (with slight variation in their order), while those with highest similarity to Tadalafil are quite different. This highlights the importance of structural diversity amongst the queries, where possible, to yield a varied set of hits, providing insurance against failure.

Figure 4.11 Space filling models of the highest scoring conformer for the top 5 scoring molecules compared to Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil taken from the crystal structure of the ligand bound to PDE5.

To gain insight into how the shape similarity compares with actual activity, plots of the pIC_{50} against the shape similarity were completed for each of the above sets of comparisons (**Figure 4.12**), using the maximum score where multiple conformers have been considered. If shape similarity were to increase with increasing biological activity, the hit identification results from a virtual screen with RGMolSA could be considered more reliable than if no correlation exists.

However, no correlation exists between activity and shape similarity in this case, perhaps as these lie within a small activity range (IC_{50} in the range 0.07-4nM with a single outlier at 16.3nM). A similar general pattern is seen whether alignment is considered (**Figures 4.12c** and **4.12d**) or not (**Figures 4.12a** and **4.12b**), confirming this not to be important for RGMolSA. A significant increase is seen in the maximum similarity scores when multiple conformers are used, both compared to the consideration of a single conformer, and the average score across all conformers. The pattern shown for consideration of multiple conformers of both the query and test molecules also closely matches that of the binding pose-multiple test conformer run, suggesting that sufficient sampling of the query conformers has been completed to capture the binding pose.

The correlation and similarity between the rank produced by shape similarity compared to the experimental activity can be quantified using statistical rank similarity measures. Kendall's τ coefficient gives a measure of the agreement between two ranked lists based on the number of pairs which agree and disagree, which gives a score between +1 for identical rankings, -1 for fully different rankings and 0 where no correlation exists between the two lists [316]. A corresponding

p-value is reported alongside each τ that, assuming the null hypothesis, measures the probability that the observed result occurs. The Jaccard Similarity gives a measure of the overlap between two ranked lists, with a score of 0 indicating no overlap and 1 indicating identical rankings [317]. The scores for each metric are reported in **Tables 4.17** and **4.18**.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average
Single	[-0.125, 0.237]	[-0.147, 0.164]	[-0.198, 0.061]	[-0.130, 0.221]
Crystal	[-0.094, 0.374]	[-0.092, 0.385]	[-0.094, 0.374]	[-0.090, 0.397]
Single Aligned	[-0.081, 0.445]	[-0.056, 0.594]	[-0.039, 0.714]	[-0.130, 0.221]
Crystal Aligned	[-0.050, 0.638]	[-0.023, 0.826]	[-0.103, 0.330]	[-0.090, 0.397]
Single-Multi	[0.282, 0.008]	[0.282, 0.008]	[-0.398, 0.000]	[-0.103, 0.330]
Crystal-Multi	[0.203, 0.055]	[0.212, 0.046]	[0.118, 0.263]	[-0.074, 0.483]
Multi-Multi	[0.316, 0.003]	[0.112, 0.291]	[-0.302, 0.004]	[-0.074, 0.483]

Table 4.17 Kendall's τ correlation for the set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors compared to the rank produced by the pIC_{50} . Each pair represents τ and the corresponding p-value.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average
Single	0.047	0.070	0.047	0.055
Crystal	0.047	0.070	0.047	0.055
Single Aligned	0.023	0.023	0.000	0.015
Crystal Aligned	0.023	0.023	0.000	0.015
Single-Multi	0.047	0.023	0.000	0.023
Crystal-Multi	0.023	0.000	0.070	0.031
Multi-Multi	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.008

Table 4.18 Jaccard similarity for the set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors compared to the rank produced by the pIC_{50} .

Both metrics indicate that no correlation exists between the experimental and shape similarity rankings. Based on Kendall's τ , some improvement is seen for consideration of multiple conformers, with the best performance observed when the conformer obtained from the bound crystal structure is used to rank multiple test conformers. This result confirms the observation in **Figure 4.12** of pIC_{50} vs shape similarity that there is no correlation between the two.

4.5. Conclusions

The use of Riemannian geometry to approximate the *spectrum* of the Laplacian can be used to produce descriptors of molecular surface geometry of the form

$$v_s = (10^4/A, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_8). \quad (4.18)$$

The descriptor is derived from the explicit form of the Riemannian metric, g , obtained through a piecewise stereographic projection of the molecule into the complex plane. From this, the Rayleigh-Ritz approximation is used for a series of test functions to obtain an approximation of the Laplacian, yielding the vector descriptor v_s . The similarity score between two vector

descriptors is computed using the inverse Bray-Curtis distance, bound by 0 (different) and 1 (identical).

RGMolSA descriptors are quick to calculate, independent of rotation and translation, and do not require prior alignment or mesh generation to compute. The method treats the surface as having a genus of zero, and therefore requires the replacement of rings with a single sphere. As the method is approximating the shape, this is believed not to lead to significant loss of quality, however does exclude the consideration of macrocycles which do contain a genuine hole in their surface.

The method does depend on the choice of an initial base sphere. A good representation of the geometry is obtained near the base sphere, but more eigenvalues would be required to accurately describe atoms which lie further away. Molecules that are similar but with different base spheres could therefore be classed as different. This is particularly problematic for long chain molecules, where numerical errors can occur. These are currently handled by excluding contributions below a certain value, but a more robust solution to the issue could be found. The method is also not invariant to the choice of base sphere, with a different descriptor produced for the same molecule depending on the selected base sphere. Further work could be completed to address this issue by considering multiple base spheres, producing a combined matrix descriptor (similar to the approach taken by USRCAT [152]), or by making use of graph theory to find the shortest path through the molecule.

An initial study into the capability of RGMolSA as a molecular shape descriptor was conducted using a series of PDE5 inhibitors of known shape. The method was found to handle comparison of conformers of the same molecule well. The conformers were generally assigned as self-similar as expected, with similarity scores of greater than 0.8 in most cases. These simple test cases were also used to compare the performance of RGMolSA to existing open-source shape similarity methods. While all the methods tested achieved the same expected ranking (Sildenafil and Vardenafil more similar than either to Tadalafil), the scores for RGMolSA were much closer to 1 as expected. The other methods assigned lower scores, which would potentially result in the incorrect choices in a real virtual screen. RGMolSA therefore outperformed existing methods for this simple case. Due to the assignment of high scores, a small set of potential decoys was also tested to check that RGMolSA does not simply assign all molecules as similar. These mostly yielded scores between 0.3-0.7, and would be classed as inactive.

Comparison of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil to a small set of 43 active PDE5 inhibitors was completed to investigate the ability of RGMolSA to rank a set of molecules. The scores assigned were found to improve upon consideration of multiple conformers, believed to be due to the dependence of the method on the position of the base sphere. In some cases, the similarity scores computed changed upon alignment of the molecules despite RGMolSA being, in theory, invariant to rotation and translation. Consistent selection of the same atom as the base sphere, and calculation of the surface area, as well as this difference not occurring in all cases suggest this to be the result of numerical error in the descriptor calculation. A significant increase was observed when multiple conformers of both the query and test molecules are considered, showing this to

be important for a real virtual screen. Small improvements were also observed for comparison to the query structure taken from the bound crystal structure. Inspection of the space filling models of the top 5 scoring molecules for each query revealed that their consideration as similar was reasonable. Across the whole set, shape similarity to the queries was found not to correlate with experimental activity, with the most active molecules not always displaying the highest activity. The method did show maximum similarity scores greater than 0.8 in many cases, highlighting that true actives would be retrieved in a real screen.

A small study was also completed to investigate how the method handles the consideration of enantiomers of different molecules. These are non-superimposable mirror images that can yield different properties. While the ability to distinguish between these in a virtual screen would be useful, these should in theory be classed as having the same shape. The drugs Thalidomide, Fluoxetine, Methadone, and Pentobarbital were considered, and displayed scores close to 1 in all cases, with the small difference attributed to numerical instability within the method.

Overall, in this small case study, the use of RGMolSA shows promise as a shape descriptor for Ligand-Based Virtual Screening. However, a full retrospective benchmarking study (which will be reported in **Chapter 6**) is needed to verify the full scale capability of the method.

In the following Chapter, a second approach to make the *Riemannian metric* comparable by making use of the theory of *Kähler Quantization* to transform the metric into a *Hermitian matrix* which approximates the surface at a global level. These descriptors also do not require alignment prior to comparison, and have the same insensitivity to small deformations of the surface. This work aims to address the dependence of RGMolSA on the selection of an initial base sphere.

Figure 4.12 Plot of the activity (pIC_{50}) against the maximum RGMolSA shape similarity across the three queries for consideration of (a) a single random conformer of the test and queries, (b) single random test conformer and the binding pose queries, (c) a single random conformer of the test and query molecules optimally aligned, (d) a single conformer of the test molecules aligned to the binding pose queries, (e) a single random conformer for each query and multiple conformers for each of the test molecules, (f) the binding pose queries and multiple conformers for each of the test conformers and (g) multiple conformers for both the test and query sets.

Chapter 5. Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation

5.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the second of two approaches to transform the *Riemannian metric*, introduced in **Chapter 3**, into an easily comparable object for use in virtual screening. In **Chapter 4** the use of the *spectrum* of the Laplacian to produce a 9-element vector descriptor of molecular surface shape was outlined. Here, Kähler Quantisation for Molecular Surface Approximation (KQMolSA) is discussed, which makes use of the Kähler potential, φ , associated with the metric, g , to produce a *Hermitian matrix* descriptor of molecular shape. An overview of the method is given here, with the full theory outlined in [7].

Kähler quantization, a sub-field of Riemannian geometry, originates from string theory. The full detail of the theory is beyond the scope of this work, but the interested reader can find further detail in [318]. Associated with the metric is a function known as the Kähler potential, φ , for which something akin to its Taylor expansion can be computed to produce a $(2k + 1) \times (2k + 1)$ Hermitian matrix descriptor of molecular surface shape \mathbb{M} , where k dictates the level of expansion,

$$\mathbb{M}_{ij} = \iint_{\mathbb{C}} z^i \bar{z}^j e^{-k\varphi} F(z) \sqrt{-1} dz \wedge d\bar{z}. \quad (5.1)$$

The Kähler potential is not unique, instead any two differ by a constant. This dependence does not affect the metric, but it does result in a scaling of the Hermitian matrix descriptor by a positive real number. This dependence requires re-scaling of the matrix when computing the distance between them. As with RGMolSA, the descriptors do not require alignment of molecules prior to comparison. The resulting matrix descriptor does depend on the initial parameterisation of the molecules in \mathbb{R}^3 , but the dependence is easily accounted for within $GL(N, \mathbb{C})/U(N)$, the space in which the final descriptors lie. The use of Kähler quantization has reduced dependence on the choice of base sphere compared to RGMolSA.

The method for computing \mathbb{M} is described further in **Section 5.2**. **Section 5.3** discusses the development work completed, and **Section 5.4** presents a case study investigating the initial potential of the method compared to RGMolSA.

5.2. Constructing the KQMolSA Descriptor from the Riemannian Metric

To construct the KQMolSA descriptor, the molecule is first parameterised as outlined in **Chapter 3**. A summary of the steps to construct the descriptor are given in **Figure 5.1**.

Figure 5.1 Key steps involved in the computation of the KQMolSA surface descriptor for Sildenafil (a PDE5 inhibitor).

The Kähler form, ω , of the metric is constructed from g and the coordinates of the molecule produced by the *piecewise stereographic projection* (see **Section 3.2**),

$$\omega = F(z) \sqrt{-1} dz \wedge d\bar{z}, \quad (5.2)$$

where $dz = dx + \sqrt{-1}dy$ and $d\bar{z} = dx - \sqrt{-1}dy$ and $F: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is the “metric function” given by

$$F(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{2r_B^2}{(1+|z|^2)^2} & \text{if } z \in \mathcal{C}, \text{ where } \mathcal{C} = \mathbb{C} \setminus \cup_i \mathbb{D}(a_i, R_i) \\ \frac{C_1}{(|z-A_1|^2+B_1)^2} & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{D}(a_1, R_1), \\ \frac{C_2}{(|z-A_2|^2+B_2)^2} & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{D}(a_2, R_2), \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{C_{N-1}}{(|z-A_{N-1}|^2+B_{N-1})^2} & \text{if } z \in \mathbb{D}(a_{N-1}, R_{N-1}). \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

Here $\mathbb{D}(a_N, R_N)$ refers to the disc N centred at complex number a in the plane with radius R , r_B is the radius of the base sphere and

$$\mathcal{C} = \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{D}(a_1, R_1) \cup \mathbb{D}(a_2, R_2) \cup \dots \cup \mathbb{D}(a_{N-1}, R_{N-1}), \quad (5.4)$$

is the complement of the discs associated with the base sphere. The constants A_N (complex), B_N and C_N (real) are used to control what g looks like over the region of the plane where the corresponding disc N sits. Their dependence on the initial data is difficult to define explicitly, so

they are instead derived computationally. Instead of the symmetric form used with RGMolSA, KQMolSA takes the antisymmetric form of the metric, with the real symmetric $dx^2 + dy^2$ terms replaced with the antisymmetric form $(\sqrt{-1}/2)dz \wedge d\bar{z}$.

In the theory of Riemannian geometry, for a generic surface, S , the Riemannian metric, g , is a 2×2 positive-definite symmetric matrix,

$$g = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.5)$$

where each entry is a function. Three independent functions are therefore needed to describe the metric, as the off-diagonals are the same. The motivation behind the use of Kähler quantization is to simplify the problem to a single function, which is mathematically much easier to deal with. This is achieved through the choice of a function for which the metric is the second derivative. The Kähler potential, $\varphi(z)$, is one such function, and can be associated with g by solving the ‘ $\partial\bar{\partial}$ -equation’:

$$\omega = \sqrt{-1}\partial\bar{\partial}\varphi. \quad (5.6)$$

For each sphere i that makes up the molecule, the Kähler potential is defined as

$$\varphi(z) = \frac{C_i}{B_i} \log(|z - A_i|^2 + B_i) + \sum_{j=1}^N \mathcal{K}_{ij} \log(|\alpha_{ij}z + \beta_{ij}|^2) \quad (5.7)$$

where $\mathcal{K} \in M^{N \times N}(\mathbb{R})$, and $\alpha, \beta \in M^{N \times N}(\mathbb{C})$ are matrices calculated from the initial parameterisation of the molecule, allowing φ to be defined explicitly. In this thesis, this is treated as a black box solution. The interested reader is directed to the Appendix in [7] for the full derivation.

The shape descriptor takes the form of a $(2k + 1) \times (2k + 1)$ Hermitian matrix \mathbb{M}

$$\mathbb{M}_{ij} = \iint_{\mathbb{C}} z^i \bar{z}^j e^{-k\varphi} F(z) \sqrt{-1} dz \wedge d\bar{z}. \quad (5.8)$$

The integrals in **Equation 5.8** are computed by mapping each atom onto a unit disc to ensure the coordinates are numerically controlled, in order to prevent numerical error. The contribution of the m^{th} sphere to the matrix is given by an integral of the form

$$\iint_{\mathbb{D}-\hat{D}} (\mathcal{T}_m(w))^i (\overline{\mathcal{T}_m(w)})^j e^{-k\varphi(\mathcal{T}_m(w))} F(\mathcal{T}_m(w)) d\mathcal{T}_m(w) \wedge d\overline{\mathcal{T}_m(w)}, \quad (5.9)$$

where \mathbb{D} is the unit disc corresponding to the sphere, $\mathcal{T}_m \in PSL(2, \mathbb{C})$ is an element that maps the unit disc \mathbb{D} onto the region $\mathbb{D}(a_m, R_m)$, and \hat{D} is the region inside the disc corresponding to higher level spheres. The integral is calculated numerically by splitting into radial (step size $dr = 15$) and angular (step size $d\theta = 10$) directions and successively applying the trapezium rule. The ability to define the Kähler potential explicitly can account for the redundancy that operations such as rotation or the choice of a different base sphere may give us a descriptor that looks like a different molecule. Within the theory, it is known how a Hermitian matrix will

change in line with parameterisation changes, which gives reduced dependence on the choice of base sphere compared to RGMolSA.

The two positive definite matrix descriptors, \mathbb{M}_1 and \mathbb{M}_2 , under consideration can be viewed as lying on the same fixed vector space, $GL(N, \mathbb{C})/U(N)$. There are many ways to define the distance between two such matrices, but the natural choice is to take the shortest path between them in the space of all descriptors. The full theory behind the calculation of this distance is beyond the scope of this thesis, but can be summarised as follows. The interested reader is referred to [7] for further detail.

As KQMolSA treats molecules as being topologically equivalent to the Riemann sphere $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$, the distance between two descriptors can be obtained by considering a function associated with $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$ known as the Möbius transformation, ϖ , which takes the form

$$\varpi(z) = \frac{\alpha z + \beta}{\gamma z + \delta}. \quad (5.10)$$

The function serves two purposes: it accounts for the dependence on rotation and translation by mapping the molecule onto itself, giving a re-parameterisation while maintaining the structure; as ϖ can act on the vector space it permits the application of representation theory to simplify the distance calculation to a minimisation over the six-dimensional Lie group $SL(2, \mathbb{C})$. The minimisation is completed by parameterising an initial matrix ϖ ,

$$\varpi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6) = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 + \sqrt{-1}x_2 & x_3 + \sqrt{-1}x_4 \\ x_5 + \sqrt{-1}x_6 & * \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.11)$$

where $*$ is selected to give $\det(\varpi) = 1$, and x_n are real variables. The initial choice of ϖ is minimised, using off the shelf solutions from SciPy [312] to yield a final matrix $\vartheta(\varpi)$. For $k = 1$ descriptors, the BFGS and COBYLA algorithms are used, while the BFGS and Powell algorithms were chosen for $k = 2$. Due to numerical instability with the $k = 2$ minimisation, $\vartheta(\varpi)$ found for $k = 1$ was used as the initial matrix rather than ϖ . The final distance between descriptors is given as

$$d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2) = k^{-\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{2k+1} (\log(\eta_i))^2}, \quad (5.12)$$

where $\{\eta_i\}$ are the eigenvalues of the matrix $\mathbb{M}_1^{-1} e^p (\vartheta(\varpi))^* \mathbb{M}_2 (\vartheta(\varpi))$, and the factor of $k^{-3/2}$ stabilises the distance as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

The similarity between two molecules is then given by

$$\text{score}(S_1, S_2) = 0.3(A_{\min}/A_{\max}) + 0.7 \frac{1}{1 + d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2)}, \quad (5.13)$$

where A_{\min}/A_{\max} is the ratio of the computed surface areas to account for the re-scaling of all molecules to have area of 4π and $d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2)$ is the distance between the computed shape descriptors. The two terms are weighted to ensure a greater contribution to the score from the

shape. The selection of these weights is discussed further in **Section 5.3.2**. The final similarity score is bound by 0 (different) and 1 (identical), as is conventional in Chemoinformatics.

The method does contain a small numerical instability in some cases, yielding matrices that are not positive-definite. Hermitian matrices differing only by a scale factor can be considered equivalent, allowing this instability to be handled by scaling one of the matrices under comparison to bring the eigenvalues into the range suitable for consideration by Python. Scale factors of 10, 100 and 1000 were used, and seem to catch most cases.

5.3. Development of the KQMolSA Descriptor

5.3.1. Tuning Radial and Theta Contributions to Trapezium Rule Integration

The trapezium rule method for computing the integrals involved in construction of our Hermitian matrix descriptor relies on two parameters: dr , which determines the number of points to consider in the radial direction, and $d\theta$, the number of points in the angular direction. The effect of varying these parameters on the quality of the descriptors produced was initially investigated using Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil, PDE5 inhibitors of known similar shape. The variation in the distance between two descriptors for the same molecule computed with different parameters should be low. The use of the trapezium rule to compute the integrals introduces a nice additional quality check, as the area of the surface can be easily calculated. As the surface area of each molecule is re-scaled to 4π , this area should be approximately 12.5 for an accurate integration scheme. Here the parameters $dr = 200$ and $d\theta = 100$; $dr = 50$ and $d\theta = 25$; $dr = 15$ and $d\theta = 10$ were considered. The results of this study are reported in **Tables 5.1-5.3**.

	(200, 100 (area = 12.59))	(50, 25, (area = 12.62))	(15, 10, (area = 12.62))
(200, 100)	-	0.032	0.032
(50, 25)	0.038	-	0.040
(15, 10)	0.038	0.040	-

Table 5.1 Computed distances between descriptors of Sildenafil generated using different values of dr and $d\theta$ for $k = 1$. The area reported in brackets is that returned by the integration step.

	(200, 100 (area = 12.57))	(50, 25, (area = 12.58))	(15, 10, (area = 12.58))
(200, 100)	-	0.005	0.005
(50, 25)	0.005	-	0.004
(15, 10)	0.005	0.004	-

Table 5.2 Computed distances between descriptors of Vardenafil generated using different values of dr and $d\theta$ for $k = 1$. The area reported in brackets is that returned by the integration step.

With small distances between descriptors in each case, no significant loss of quality is observed in the descriptor when a lower number of points are used. The reported surface area for Sildenafil and Vardenafil were both close to 12.5, indicating high quality. For Tadalafil, a slight overestimation of the area occurs, due to a known issue in the replacement of rings rather

	(200, 100 (area = 14.32))	(50, 25, (area = 14.37))	(15, 10, (area = 14.37))
(200, 100)	-	0.003	0.003
(50, 25)	0.003	-	0.001
(15, 10)	0.003	0.001	-

Table 5.3 Computed distances between descriptors of Tadalafil generated using different values of dr and $d\theta$ for $k = 1$. The area reported in brackets is that returned by the integration step.

than due to the choice of dr and $d\theta$. Similar results were observed for the consideration of $k = 2$. As the quality is unaffected, the minimum parameters of $dr = 15$ and $d\theta = 10$ were used in the final descriptors to increase the speed of calculation.

To verify the lack of variation in scores for different dr and $d\theta$ values, the AstraZeneca data set (provided by Cresset, see **Section 6.5** for further detail) was used. The data consists of 10 targets, each with a single reference molecule and 9 test molecules to compare to the reference. dr and $d\theta$ were each varied between 10 and 200 in increments of 5, and the similarity scores computed between the resulting descriptors for each set. **Figure 5.2** shows an example heat map for the correlation matrix between the scores across the range of parameters for the first molecule and the reference for target P00489. The maps show variation in dr along the x-axis and $d\theta$ in y, with the diagonal giving the scores where $dr = d\theta$. The full set of results are given in **Appendix E**. Minimal to no variation in colour across the heat map shows that, in general, the resulting similarity scores show little change when the descriptors are computed using different parameters. Thus, a low number of points can be used in each direction to increase speed without reducing the quality of the descriptors or the similarity ranking produced.

5.3.2. Constructing a Shape Similarity Score

While the natural distance measure between two Hermitian matrices does quantify their similarity, it is not as easy to interpret as the typical measures of similarity used in Chemoinformatics. To rectify this, a similarity score was constructed that takes a value between 0 (no similarity) and 1 (identical). To achieve this, the inverse of the distance between matrices, $d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2)$ was taken. Additionally, due to the re-scaling of all molecules to have surface area equal to 4π , a term was introduced to account for the true difference in size. The similarity score between two molecular surfaces \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 therefore takes the form

$$score(\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2) = x(A_{min}/A_{max}) + y \frac{1}{1 + d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2)}, \quad (5.14)$$

where A_{min} is the smaller of the two areas, and A_{max} is the larger to retain the constraint of a score between 0 and 1, and x and y are weights that control the contribution from the area and shape terms to the overall similarity, where $x + y = 1$ and $x < 0.5$, so that the shape contribution is the dominant factor in the overall score. The similarity scores between Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil (PDE5 inhibitors of known similar shape) were used to determine the values of x and y (**Table 5.4**).

Figure 5.2 Example heat map for the correlation matrix displaying the variation in similarity scores for dr and $d\theta$ between 10 and 200 for the reference and first test molecule of Target P00489. Consistent colour across the plot shows the scores obtained are similar across the range of parameter values used to obtain the descriptors.

x	y	Sildenafil-Vardenafil	Sildenafil-Tadalafil	Vardenafil-Tadalafil
0	1	0.884	0.286	0.275
0.1	0.9	0.892	0.340	0.328
0.2	0.8	0.900	0.394	0.380
0.3	0.7	0.908	0.449	0.432
0.4	0.6	0.916	0.503	0.485
0.5	0.5	0.924	0.557	0.537

Table 5.4 Similarity scores for the PDE5 inhibitors for surface area weights ranging from 0 to 0.5.

Increasing the contribution from the surface area term increased the similarity score across all three pairs, as expected. For Sildenafil and Vardenafil, which are more structurally similar, only a small difference in the score is observed, whereas for Tadalafil the inclusion of the size term has a greater effect on the score. Final values of $x = 0.3$ and $y = 0.7$ were chosen to ensure enough contribution from the size term without overpowering that of the shape.

To confirm that this choice is reasonable over a larger number of comparisons, the same data as discussed in **Section 5.3.1** was used, varying x from 0 to 0.5, and y from 1 to 0.5, each in increments of 0.1. **Figure 5.3** shows an example heat map of the variation in scores across the 8 test molecules for target P00489 for each x and y value. The full set of results are given in **Appendix E**. The scores computed generally increase with increasing contribution from the

surface area term, so the original choice of $x = 0.3$ and $y = 0.7$ were maintained to balance the shape and size contributions to similarity.

Figure 5.3 Example heat maps of the similarity scores for target P00489 when x is varied between 0 and 0.5, and y is varied between 1 and 0.5 (using $k = 1$).

5.3.3. Investigating Enantiomers

As discussed in **Section 4.3.3**, similarity comparison based on shape alone should not distinguish between enantiomers of the same molecule. Here the examples considered previously are investigated with KQMolSA. The similarity score, surface area and base sphere for each pair, where enantiomers were produced using the EnumerateStereoisomers RDKit module followed by 3D embedding, are reported in **Table 5.5** using $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ descriptors.

Name	Base Sphere 1	Base Sphere 2	Area 1	Area 2	Score ($k = 1$)	Score ($k = 2$)
Thalidomide	1	1	172.01	173.65	0.869	0.835
Fluoxetine	1	7	211.90	211.71	0.797	0.769
Methadone	7	6	227.96	227.02	0.893	0.502
Pentobarbital	4	4	149.08	149.58	0.675	0.687

Table 5.5 Similarity scores between enantiomers of the same molecule for KQMolSA.

The surface area for each pair is observed to be similar, as with RGMolSA. For $k = 1$ each pair of molecules is assigned reasonably high similarity scores, but not identical. Except for Methadone, similar scores to those for $k = 1$ are obtained using the $k = 2$ descriptors. As the change between enantiomers of Methadone is minor, and the $k = 1$ score falls in line with the others, this is most likely the result of the distance calculation getting trapped in a local minimum, yielding a larger distance in the space of descriptors and hence a lower similarity score.

As discussed previously, this approach to generating enantiomeric pairs in 3D space yields a pair of close conformers rather than true mirror images. As for RGMolSA, these comparisons

were repeated by embedding one instance of the molecule in 3D space, then inverting the z-coordinates to give a true mirror image. The similarity score, surface area and base sphere for these comparisons are reported in **Table 5.6**.

Name	Base Sphere 1	Base Sphere 2	Area 1	Area 2	Score ($k = 1$)	Score ($k = 2$)
Thalidomide	1	1	170.258	170.258	0.998	0.957
Fluoxetine	7	7	208.660	208.660	0.996	0.997
Methadone	4	4	147.724	147.724	0.999	0.957
Pentobarbital	7	7	225.087	225.087	0.999	0.826

Table 5.6 Similarity scores between enantiomers of the same molecule using $(X, Y, Z) \rightarrow (X, Y, -Z)$.

The resulting the surface area and base sphere are now the same for each enantiomer, and for both $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ (with the exception of Pentobarbital with $k = 2$) the similarity scores are now much closer to the expected value of 1. For KQMolSA the remaining difference can be attributed to numerical instability and rounding within the method, and to the distance calculation if the true minimum has not been found. The slightly lower scores for $k = 2$ is expected, as these are less robust than $k = 1$.

5.4. Case Study: Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) Inhibitors

To investigate the usefulness of KQMolSA as a descriptor of molecular shape, the same initial case study was completed as for RGMolSA (**Section 4.4**). The PDE5 inhibitors shown in **Figure 4.4** are known to have similar shape; thus making them a good test case for shape similarity approximation. This section reports the results of this study, which investigates how well KQMolSA handles different conformers, comparison to other existing shape similarity methods, comparison of potential decoy molecules and an initial virtual screen based on experimental data.

5.4.1. Investigating Molecular Conformations

As discussed previously (see **Section 4.4.1**), one of the main advantages of using 3D shape as a measure of similarity between molecules is the ability to account for the different conformers they can adopt. High self-similarity amongst conformers would in theory be expected, with a score of at least 0.7 (the typical threshold for similarity in Chemoinformatics), but less than 1 to permit distinction between them. The same sets of 10 conformers as described for RGMolSA are used to investigate how KQMolSA regards different conformers. As before, higher similarity is expected for the low energy conformers than for the randomly selected examples.

Figure 5.4 provides the minimum, maximum, and average shape similarity and the average RMSD, which provides comparison of the molecules based on their atomic positions. The full set of shape similarity comparisons are available in **Appendix F**, and the RMSD results in **Appendix C**. Higher similarity is observed for $k = 1$ than for $k = 2$, where some scores below 0.6 are observed. This reduced similarity for $k = 2$ is expected, as the descriptors provide a more

detailed approximation to the shape of the surface, and as such is more sensitive to geometric differences.

Figure 5.4 Overlay of the most and least shape-similar conformers of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average shape similarity and RMSD for each set for (a) $k = 1$ and (b) $k = 2$. On average, the conformers display a high degree of self-similarity despite the variance in atom-position similarity

The RMSD and shape similarity for each set are compared in the swarm plots shown in **Figure 5.5**. The $k = 1$ descriptors generally gave high similarity, with a few scores for Tadalafil falling slightly below 0.7. The $k = 2$ descriptors displayed greater variance, with some scores lower than 0.6 obtained. This reduction in similarity is expected for $k = 2$, as this gives a more detailed representation of the surface and is therefore more sensitive to variation in geometry. Overall, compared to RGMolSA, the conformer similarity obtained by KQMolSA was lower and more varied, with the clustering seen in RGMolSA not replicated. Although KQMolSA does handle conformers well, RGMolSA appears to do better. For virtual screening, this consideration of conformers as similar negates the need for a pre-alignment step prior to shape similarity calculation, and may allow molecules that can deform to fit in the binding pocket to

be identified as potential hits. As with RGMolSA, as the Kähler potential is invariant to small surface deformations, the method may permit small conformational changes to be ignored while retaining the full range of shape information, offering improved efficiency in virtual screening.

Figure 5.5 Swarm plots of the RMSD (in Å) and shape similarity for our set of conformers highlight the general trend that different conformers are classed as having similar shape, despite significant variance in their atomic positions. Conformers with RMSD less than 1 Å are considered similar, while those over 3 Å have significant differences.

5.4.2. Comparison to Other 3D Shape Similarity Methods

The PDE5 molecules of known shape similarity were also used to consider how KQMolSA may compare to our previous work, as well as existing open-source shape similarity methods (USRCAT [152, 70], Shape-It [81], MolSG [4] and the Morgan fingerprint (2D)). In all cases presented, a score of 0 indicates no common features between molecules, and 1 means they are identical. The results of this comparison are presented in **Table 5.7**.

Unlike RGMolSA, which identifies similarity between all 3 PDE5 inhibitors, KQMolSA only considers Sildenafil and Vardenafil (close structural analogues) as similar, with a score of 0.907 for $k = 1$. In this case, Tadalafil would be classed as dissimilar. The $k = 2$ descriptors yield lower similarity, which would be expected as discussed previously. A small degree of numerical instability is observed in the distance calculations for the $k = 2$ matrices, where there is some dependence on the order of comparison (**Table 5.8**). As such, for this simple comparison KQMolSA is outperformed by RGMolSA but fares better than the widely used methods USRCAT and Shape-It, however verification in a full retrospective benchmarking study is required.

	KQMolSA (k=1)	KQMolSA (k=2)	RGMolSA	USRCAT	Shape-It	MolSG	Morgan FP
Sildenafil- Vardenafil	0.907	0.652	0.903	0.384	0.388	0.704	0.667
Sildenafil- Tadalafil	0.449	0.482	0.809	0.269	0.278	0.746	0.201
Vardenafil- Tadalafil	0.432	0.470	0.725	0.291	0.353	0.887	0.209

Table 5.7 Comparison of the work presented here (KQMolSA) to our previous work (RGMolSA) [6] and existing atomic-distance [152], atomic-centred [81] and molecular surface based [4] descriptors, as well as the 2D Morgan fingerprint (FP). In all cases, the similarity scores given are bound by 0 (no similarity) and 1 (identical).

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil
Sildenafil	-	0.652	0.462
Vardenafil	0.648	-	0.470
Tadalafil	0.482	0.470	-

Table 5.8 Similarity scores for the PDE5 inhibitors for $k = 2$ highlighting the dependence on the order of comparison.

5.4.3. Control: Comparison to Potential Decoys

As a negative control for similarity, the same set of decoys presented in **Section 4.4.3** are compared to the PDE5 inhibitors. **Figure 5.6** presents the results of this comparison. The scores for both $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ largely fall below 0.7, and would be classed as genuinely different, and assumed inactive against PDE5. The exception here is in the score assigned to Tadalafil and Diflorasone, 0.74 for $k = 1$. Due to the similarity in the structures (both contain a motif of 4 fused rings), some similarity between the two is reasonable. RGMolSA also assigns Tadalafil and Diflorasone as similar, with a score of 0.872. Inspection by eye of the space filling models and surface of the molecules suggests they do have genuinely similar shapes (**Figure 5.7**).

5.4.4. Investigating the Accuracy of the Hermitian Matrix Descriptors

One of the beneficial properties of Kähler quantisation is that there is an in-built check for the quality of the descriptor produced. It is possible when computing the integrals which yield the final descriptor to return the surface area, which should in theory be close to 12.5 - the area of the unit sphere, to which the surface has been re-scaled. **Tables 5.9** and **5.10** report the resulting areas for the single conformer and multi-conformer studies, as well as that of the potential decoy molecules discussed above.

The computed areas are generally very close to 12.5, except for Tadalafil which has a higher area of ~ 14.3 in all cases. The higher computed area for Tadalafil is likely a result of the error in replacing the rings discussed in **Section 3.3.1**. This may explain the lower similarity to Tadalafil seen in **Section 5.4.2** compared to that observed with RGMolSA. Interestingly, Diflorasone also has a computed area of ~ 14.3 , which may be why the two show high similarity.

Figure 5.6 Inverse Bray-Curtis similarity of four 'different' molecules (blue) to the PDE5 inhibitor test series (red). The overlay of the structures was computed using Open3DAlign [314]

(a) Tadalafil - Space Filling Model

(b) Diflorasone - Space Filling Model

(c) Tadalafil - Surface

(d) Diflorasone - Surface

Figure 5.7 Comparison by eye of both the space filling model and the surface of Tadalafil and Diflorasone highlights their similarity.

	Area
Sildenafil	12.62
Vardenafil	12.58
Tadalafil	14.37
Arginine	12.61
Lymecycline	12.66
Diflorasone	14.39
S-Octylglutathione	12.59

Table 5.9 Area as calculated by integration for Sildenafil, Vardenafil, Tadalafil and the potential decoy molecules.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SR	12.62	12.60	12.57	12.59	12.59	12.59	12.60	12.60	12.58	12.60	12.58
SLE	12.62	12.59	12.58	12.60	12.58	12.57	12.59	12.57	12.60	12.59	12.60
VR	12.61	12.59	12.58	12.62	12.60	12.57	12.57	12.60	12.58	12.60	12.58
VLE	12.61	12.57	12.56	12.60	12.60	12.59	12.57	12.59	12.58	12.59	12.54
TR	14.35	14.33	14.32	14.32	14.28	14.32	14.26	14.26	14.27	14.26	14.28
TLE	14.35	14.31	14.33	14.32	14.33	14.32	14.32	14.31	14.31	14.32	14.33

Table 5.10 Area as calculated by integration for the Random (R) and Low Energy (LE) conformer sets of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T)

5.4.5. Screening a Small Set of Other PDE5 Inhibitors

To further investigate how KQMolSA might fare in identifying other true actives, the same study as discussed in **Section 4.4.4** using a set of experimentally validated PDE5 inhibitors with nanomolar activity and Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil as queries was completed (PubChem AID 446781). As for RGMolSA, these molecules would be expected to show high similarity to the queries. This study was also used to further probe the consideration of conformers, taking the same cases as for RGMolSA: a single random conformer for the query and test molecules; the query conformer taken from the bound crystal structure (PDB IDs 1UDT, 1UHO, 1XOZ); alignment of the atomic-centres using Open3DAlign [314]; multiple conformers for both the test and query molecules produced following the procedure outlined in **Chapter B**.

The similarity scores for the top 5 most potent molecules (**Figure 4.9**) for consideration of a single random conformer and for the query conformer taken from the crystal structure are presented in **Tables 5.11** and **5.12** and **Tables 5.13** and **5.14** respectively. As for RGMolSA, low scores are obtained for the top 5 most active molecules based on their pIC₅₀ compared to Sildenafil and Vardenafil when a single conformer of both is considered. However, here Tadalafil yields scores greater than 0.7 in most cases for $k = 1$, and as such would identify these as actives. Comparison of a random conformer for $k = 2$ generally yields a lower similarity score than for $k = 1$, where for comparisons using the query conformer obtained from the bound crystal structure, a slight increase in score is observed in some cases. No increase in scores is observed when using the bound query conformation compared to the random ones.

The KQMolSA descriptors are also invariant to uniform rotation and translation, revoking the requirement for alignment prior to similarity calculation. This is again tested using Open3DAlign

5.4 Case Study: Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5) Inhibitors

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.522	0.502	0.760	0.595	9	313.48
2	0.491	0.473	0.881	0.615	0	310.89
3	0.502	0.484	0.887	0.624	9	311.38
4	0.520	0.500	0.776	0.599	9	313.93
5	0.593	0.586	0.541	0.573	0	336.86

Table 5.11 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 1$.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.493	0.488	0.489	0.490	9	313.48
2	0.473	0.487	0.514	0.491	0	310.89
3	0.476	0.487	0.496	0.486	9	311.38
4	0.469	0.487	0.483	0.480	9	313.93
5	0.493	0.505	0.404	0.467	0	336.86

Table 5.12 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 2$.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.511	0.444	0.877	0.611	9	313.48
2	0.482	0.426	0.771	0.560	0	310.89
3	0.493	0.433	0.857	0.594	9	311.38
4	0.509	0.443	0.899	0.617	9	313.93
5	0.581	0.503	0.582	0.555	0	336.86

Table 5.13 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer taken from the bound crystal structure of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 1$.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.512	0.454	0.490	0.485	9	313.48
2	0.502	0.448	0.513	0.488	0	310.89
3	0.508	0.455	0.497	0.487	9	311.38
4	0.508	0.449	0.483	0.480	9	313.93
5	0.504	0.486	0.432	0.474	0	336.86

Table 5.14 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer taken from the bound crystal structure of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 2$.

[314] to align the test data to each of the queries before calculating their similarity (**Tables 5.15-5.18**). As before, this significantly increases the run time, as the descriptors are re-calculated after each alignment. For both the random and bound conformers, no significant difference is observed in the similarity scores after alignment, confirming QMolSA to be an alignment free method for shape comparison.

Unlike for RGMolSA, no significant difference is observed in the average similarity score when multiple conformers are considered for either the query or test molecules, using either

Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation

	Sildenafil	ΔS	Vardenafil	ΔV	Tadalafil	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.522	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.760	0.000	0.595	9	313.48
2	0.491	0.000	0.473	0.000	0.881	0.000	0.615	0	310.89
3	0.502	0.000	0.484	0.000	0.887	0.000	0.624	9	311.38
4	0.520	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.776	0.000	0.599	9	313.93
5	0.593	0.000	0.586	0.000	0.541	0.000	0.573	0	336.86

Table 5.15 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 1$. The test molecules were aligned to each query prior to scoring using OpenAlign3D. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between scores with and without alignment.

	Sildenafil	ΔS	Vardenafil	ΔV	Tadalafil	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.493	0.000	0.488	0.000	0.489	0.000	0.490	9	313.48
2	0.473	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.514	0.000	0.491	0	310.89
3	0.476	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.496	0.000	0.486	9	311.38
4	0.469	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.483	0.000	0.480	9	313.93
5	0.493	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.404	0.000	0.467	0	336.86

Table 5.16 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 2$. The test molecules were aligned to each query prior to scoring using OpenAlign3D. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between scores with and without alignment.

	Sildenafil	ΔS	Vardenafil	ΔV	Tadalafil	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.511	0.000	0.444	0.000	0.877	0.000	0.611	9	313.48
2	0.482	0.000	0.426	0.000	0.771	0.000	0.560	0	310.89
3	0.493	0.000	0.433	0.000	0.857	0.000	0.594	9	311.38
4	0.509	0.000	0.443	0.000	0.899	0.000	0.617	9	313.93
5	0.581	0.000	0.503	0.000	0.582	0.000	0.555	0	336.86

Table 5.17 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 1$. The test molecules were aligned to each query prior to scoring using OpenAlign3D. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between scores with and without alignment.

	Sildenafil	ΔS	Vardenafil	ΔV	Tadalafil	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area
1	0.512	0.000	0.454	0.000	0.490	0.000	0.485	9	313.48
2	0.502	0.000	0.448	0.000	0.513	0.000	0.488	0	310.89
3	0.508	0.000	0.455	0.000	0.497	0.000	0.487	9	311.38
4	0.508	0.000	0.449	0.000	0.483	0.000	0.480	9	313.93
5	0.504	0.000	0.486	0.000	0.432	0.000	0.474	0	336.86

Table 5.18 Similarity of a single conformer of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil and the average across all queries using $k = 2$. The test molecules were aligned to each query prior to scoring using OpenAlign3D. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between scores with and without alignment.

$k = 1$ or $k = 2$ (Tables 5.19-5.23). The maximum score between conformer pairs is also not significantly higher than the average. The lack of variation amongst different conformers may be due to KQMolSA representing the global shape of the surface and having lower dependence on

the choice of base sphere, thus not being as sensitive to local deformation of the surface. The scale of comparison for multiple conformers of both also proved too large for $k = 2$, where the distances were too slow to compute. As such, only the results for $k = 1$ comparisons are reported here.

	Sildenafil Average	Vardenafil Average	Tadalafil Average	Average	Sildenafil Max.	Vardenafil Max.	Tadalafil Max.
1	0.479	0.461	0.872	0.604	0.497	0.478	0.925
2	0.460	0.444	0.791	0.565	0.488	0.474	0.881
3	0.469	0.452	0.870	0.597	0.497	0.482	0.936
4	0.475	0.457	0.862	0.598	0.511	0.492	0.932
5	0.600	0.571	0.566	0.579	0.629	0.602	0.605

Table 5.19 Average and maximum similarity of multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil for $k = 1$.

	Sildenafil Average	Vardenafil Average	Tadalafil Average	Average	Sildenafil Max.	Vardenafil Max.	Tadalafil Max.
1	0.461	0.461	0.484	0.469	0.492	0.509	0.494
2	0.452	0.451	0.504	0.469	0.500	0.481	0.517
3	0.458	0.458	0.495	0.471	0.499	0.487	0.526
4	0.459	0.460	0.483	0.468	0.502	0.483	0.499
5	0.481	0.473	0.436	0.463	0.515	0.508	0.455

Table 5.20 Average and maximum similarity of multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil for $k = 2$.

	Sildenafil Average	Vardenafil Average	Tadalafil Average	Average	Sildenafil Max.	Vardenafil Max.	Tadalafil Max.
1	0.469	0.412	0.850	0.577	0.487	0.423	0.942
2	0.452	0.401	0.710	0.521	0.483	0.428	0.776
3	0.460	0.406	0.766	0.544	0.491	0.434	0.815
4	0.466	0.409	0.833	0.569	0.500	0.431	0.917
5	0.580	0.471	0.605	0.552	0.613	0.498	0.654

Table 5.21 Average and maximum similarity of multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer taken from the bound crystal structure for Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil for $k = 1$.

	Sildenafil Average	Vardenafil Average	Tadalafil Average	Average	Sildenafil Max.	Vardenafil Max.	Tadalafil Max.
1	0.471	0.429	0.489	0.463	0.494	0.441	0.496
2	0.459	0.417	0.501	0.459	0.481	0.444	0.517
3	0.469	0.425	0.497	0.464	0.498	0.455	0.508
4	0.470	0.428	0.489	0.462	0.509	0.455	0.502
5	0.481	0.454	0.605	0.460	0.522	0.583	0.654

Table 5.22 Average and maximum similarity of multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer taken from the bound crystal structure for Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil for $k = 2$.

	Sildenafil Average	Vardenafil Average	Tadalafil Average	Average	Sildenafil Max.	Vardenafil Max.	Tadalafil Max.
1	0.437	0.422	0.787	0.549	0.501	0.471	0.950
2	0.427	0.412	0.700	0.513	0.487	0.468	0.941
3	0.434	0.418	0.758	0.536	0.503	0.478	0.948
4	0.432	0.417	0.769	0.539	0.516	0.485	0.951
5	0.543	0.505	0.637	0.562	0.644	0.591	0.969

Table 5.23 Average and maximum similarity of multiple conformers of the top 5 most potent PDE5 inhibitors to multiple conformers of Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil. Due to speed constraints, only the comparisons with $k = 1$ are reported.

The top scoring molecules for each query were also found to differ from those most active by pIC_{50} . **Figure 5.8** shows the space filling models of the top 5 scoring molecules compared to each query. Here Sildenafil and Vardenafil yield the same top 5 scoring molecules, with a significantly different set observed for Tadalafil. Observation by eye suggests that higher similarity exists between Tadalafil and its top scoring molecules (also reflected in significantly higher similarity scores) than is observed for either Sildenafil or Vardenafil. The top scoring molecules to Sildenafil and Vardenafil are largely the same as those identified by RGMolSA, where KQMolSA picks a different set for Tadalafil.

Figure 5.8 Space filling models of the top 5 scoring molecules from multiple conformers compared to Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil taken from the crystal structure of the ligand bound to PDE5.

To investigate how shape similarity varies with experimental activity, the pIC_{50} was plotted against the average shape similarity score for $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ (**Figure 5.9**) for each of the above

comparisons, using the maximum score where multiple conformers are considered. As discussed previously, a direct relationship between shape similarity and biological activity would yield more reliable predictions. However, as with RGMolSA no correlation is observed between the shape similarity and the activity. This may be due to these molecules falling in a narrow activity range. These plots show the lack of change across multiple conformers occurs across all 43 molecules, not just the top 5 shown above. The scores for Sildenafil and Vardenafil are consistent, but display a significant drop for Tadalafil using $k = 2$ compared to $k = 1$.

Kendall's τ coefficient and the Jaccard similarity are again used to quantify whether there is any correlation between the ranking produced by shape similarity and that of the true experimental activity. The scores for each metric are reported in **Tables 5.24-5.27**.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average
Single	[0.025, 0.810]	[0.028, 0.794]	[-0.203, 0.055]	[-0.150, 0.158]
Crystal	[0.028, 0.794]	[0.059, 0.579]	[-0.192, 0.070]	[-0.099, 0.352]
Single Aligned	[0.025, 0.810]	[0.028, 0.794]	[-0.203, 0.055]	[-0.150, 0.158]
Crystal Aligned	[0.028, 0.794]	[0.059, 0.579]	[-0.192, 0.070]	[-0.099, 0.352]
Single-Multi	[-0.101, 0.341]	[-0.094, 0.374]	[0.063, 0.551]	[0.034, 0.746]
Crystal-Multi	[-0.096, 0.363]	[-0.094, 0.374]	[-0.132, 0.213]	[-0.145, 0.170]
Multi-Multi	[-0.012, 0.908]	[-0.006, 0.958]	[-0.010, 0.925]	[-0.127, 0.229]

Table 5.24 Kendall's τ correlation for the set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors compared to the rank produced by the pIC_{50} . Each pair represents τ and the corresponding p-value for $k = 1$ descriptors.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average
Single	[0.037, 0.730]	[0.010, 0.925]	[-0.017, 0.875]	[-0.059, 0.579]
Crystal	[0.145, 0.170]	[0.112, 0.291]	[-0.218, 0.039]	[0.017, 0.875]
Single Aligned	[0.037, 0.730]	[0.010, 0.925]	[-0.017, 0.875]	[-0.059, 0.579]
Crystal Aligned	[0.145, 0.170]	[0.112, 0.291]	[-0.218, 0.039]	[0.017, 0.875]
Single-Multi	[-0.123, 0.245]	[-0.167, 0.114]	[-0.063, 0.551]	[-0.068, 0.523]
Crystal-Multi	[-0.196, 0.064]	[-0.112, 0.291]	[-0.136, 0.198]	[-0.143, 0.177]

Table 5.25 Kendall's τ correlation for the set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors compared to the rank produced by the pIC_{50} . Each pair represents τ and the corresponding p-value for $k = 2$ descriptors.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average
Single	0.070	0.070	0.047	0.062
Crystal	0.070	0.047	0.116	0.078
Single Aligned	0.070	0.070	0.047	0.062
Crystal Aligned	0.070	0.047	0.116	0.078
Single-Multi	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Crystal-Multi	0.000	0.000	0.047	0.016
Multi-Multi	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table 5.26 Jaccard similarity for the set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors compared to the rank produced by the pIC_{50} for $k = 1$.

Both metrics suggest that no correlation exists between the experimental activity and the shape similarity score. Here, rather than an improvement, a slight decrease is seen for consideration

Figure 5.9 Plot of the activity (pIC₅₀) against the KQMolSA shape similarity for a single random conformer of the test and queries for (a) $k = 1$ and (b) $k = 2$; a single random test and the binding pose query conformers (c) $k = 1$ and (d) $k = 2$; a single random test and query conformer optimally aligned for (e) $k = 1$ and (f) $k = 2$; a single test conformer aligned to the binding pose queries for (g) $k = 1$ and (h) $k = 2$; a single random query conformer and multiple test conformers (i) $k = 1$ and (j) $k = 2$; the binding pose queries and multiple test conformers for (k) $k = 1$ and (l) $k = 2$ and (m) multiple conformers for both the test and query sets with $k = 1$.

	Sildenafil	Vardenafil	Tadalafil	Average
Single	0.023	0.023	0.000	0.015
Crystal	0.023	0.023	0.000	0.015
Single Aligned	0.023	0.023	0.000	0.015
Crystal Aligned	0.023	0.023	0.000	0.015
Single-Multi	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.023
Crystal-Multi	0.000	0.023	0.000	0.008

Table 5.27 Jaccard similarity for the set of 43 PDE5 inhibitors compared to the rank produced by the pIC_{50} for $k = 2$.

of multiple conformers. This result confirms the observation in **Figure 5.9** of pIC_{50} vs shape similarity that there is no correlation between the two.

5.5. Conclusions

The use of Kähler Quantisation to approximate the *Riemannian metric* associated with a surface yields a $(2k + 1) \times (2k + 1)$ Hermitian matrix descriptor of the form

$$\mathbb{M}_{ij} = \iint_{\mathbb{C}} z^i \bar{z}^j e^{-k\varphi} F(z) \sqrt{-1} dz \wedge d\bar{z}. \quad (5.15)$$

The coefficients of the matrix are computed by taking something similar to a Taylor expansion of the Kähler potential φ associated with the Riemannian metric, with the Trapezium rule used to compute the integrals numerically. The distance between two descriptors $(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2)$ is given by first minimising the distance in the space of descriptors, then the distance given by

$$d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2) = k^{-\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{2k+1} (\log(\eta_i))^2}. \quad (5.16)$$

The similarity between two molecules is then given by weighting the contribution from the ratio of the surface areas and the distance between molecules.

Unlike RGMolSA, the descriptors are not rotation or translation invariant, and instead depend on the initial parameterisation of the molecule. However, this dependence is easily accounted for in the distance calculation. The descriptors themselves are quick to calculate, but due to the need for minimisation, the distance between molecules takes a couple of seconds per pair to generate. This is helped by the use of optimised existing minimisation algorithms, but these do depend on the extent of minimisation needed and do not guarantee that the global minimum has been located. One possibility to improve this in the future development of the method would be the use of gradient descent in the minimisation. There is also a slight dependence on the order of comparison (A compared to B vs B compared to A) that yields slightly different scores after the 3rd decimal place, but this does not introduce any practical limitation in the use of the method.

The capabilities of KQMolSA were tested using a series of PDE5 inhibitors of known shape similarity. Similarity between conformers of the same molecule were generally assigned as

similar, with scores mostly above 0.7. These were higher for $k = 1$ than $k = 2$. As the $k = 2$ descriptors capture greater detail, they are therefore more sensitive to geometric changes. For the initial comparison to other methods, KQMolSA performs relatively well compared to existing methods, classifying Sildenafil and Vardenafil as highly similar. However, unlike with RGMolSA and MolSG (another method based on the spectrum of the Laplacian), low similarity was assigned for Tadalafil. For the same set of decoy molecules used with RGMolSA, low similarity scores were obtained for all except comparison of Tadalafil to Diflorasone, which were also classed as similar by RGMolSA. Consideration of the space-filling and surface models of these suggests they may have some genuine similarity, and thus evidences further potential for scaffold hopping by both methods.

The small set of 43 active PDE5 inhibitors studied with RGMolSA were again used to probe KQMolSA's capabilities in a real screen. In theory, high scores should be assigned to all molecules when compared to Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil. As with RGMolSA, alignment of the molecules prior to their comparison was found unnecessary. However, for KQMolSA, the consideration of multiple conformers was found not to make a significant difference to the scores assigned. This may be the result of KQMolSA giving a global description of shape, that is less sensitive to small deformations of the surface. Inspection by-eye of the space filling models for the top 5 scoring molecules compared to each query showed that while the most similar molecules were largely the same for Sildenafil and Vardenafil, an entirely different set were obtained using Tadalafil. Both the scores and observation by eye suggest that the top molecules for Tadalafil have greater similarity. This highlights the importance of diverse queries to yield a wide range of hits from a real virtual screen. As for RGMolSA, no correlation either by Kendall's τ or Jaccard Index was found between the shape similarity and the true experimental activity. A significant drop in scores was seen for similarity using $k = 2$ compared to $k = 1$.

Thalidomide, Pentobarbital, Fluoxetine, and Methadone were used to investigate the ability of KQMolSA to handle enantiomers of the same molecule. Each pair were assigned similarity scores close to 1, with slightly lower scores for $k = 2$ than $k = 1$. The remaining difference can be attributed to numerical instability and rounding, along with the location of a minimum in the distance calculation.

Overall, in this small case study, the use of KQMolSA shows promised as a shape descriptor for Ligand-Based Virtual Screening. Its full capabilities, along with those of RGMolSA will be investigated in a full retrospective benchmarking study (**Chapter 6**).

Chapter 6. Benchmarking RGMolSA and KQMolSA

6.1. Introduction

The initial case studies outlined in **Section 4.4** and **Section 5.4** suggest promise in both methods. To fully validate the performance of RGMolSA and KQMolSA and evaluate their strength as shape descriptors, a retrospective benchmarking study is required. To maximise reproducibility, only open-source software and publicly available data will be considered. All performance metrics reported were calculated using the RDKit Scoring module [70].

Section 6.2 reports a full screen of the Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced (DUD-E) community benchmarking set (see **Section 2.5.1**, [223]) using RGMolSA (**Chapter 4**, [6]) KQMolSA (**Chapter 4**, [7]), USRCAT [152], Shape-It [81, 82] and MolSG [4]. Multiple conformers for the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 targets from the DUD-E set were studied using RGMolSA and USRCAT (**Section 6.3**). The ability of RGMolSA and KQMolSA to consider molecules with a high degree of flexibility is reported in **Section 6.4**. The relative performances of shape descriptors against a set of absolute shape values were studied using the AstraZeneca Test (**Section 6.5**). Performance for a “real” virtual screen, as well as an indirect comparison to OpenEye’s ROCS is provided by replicating the study originally reported in [5] (**Section 6.6**). Finally, the ability to use RGMolSA as a feature representation is probed in **Section 6.7**. Full results for this study are available via Zenodo [319].

6.2. Retrospective Benchmarking with the Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD-E)

The most commonly deployed test in previous shape-based method development is a full retrospective benchmarking study using the Directory of Useful Decoys – Enhanced (DUD-E) data set described in **Section 2.5.1** [223, 2]. Such studies were replicated here to compare RGMolSA and KQMolSA (with $k = 1$) to Shape-It and USRCAT (both re-run in house) and MolSG, where results were taken from the literature as, while available, the method was too slow to replicate¹ [4]. The use of KQMolSA beyond $k = 1$ was not considered, as the speed of the comparisons was deemed too slow for large scale use. Use of the DUD-E data also permits indirect comparison to other methods for which open source software is unavailable. For the full set of 102 targets available, ranking of each set of actives and inactives was completed, using each active in turn as a query. Each target set contains ~200 actives and 50 decoys per active, and here only the supplied single conformer was considered. Performance was measured in each case considering the BEDROC (with $\alpha = 20$), AUC and EF for the top 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5%

¹Note that this study considered only 20 randomly selected actives per target as queries.

of ranked hits (see **Section 2.5.2**). A summary of the results across the full data set is given in **Table 6.1** and **Figure 6.1**. These show that, on average, both RGMolSA and KQMolSA give a comparable overall performance to the existing shape similarity methods, but slightly lower in terms of early enrichment. As the placement of true actives at the top of a ranked list is a key feature for similarity searching, this would need to be improved before either method could be used in virtual screening. The full results are given in **Appendix J**.

	BEDROC	AUC	EF (0.5%)	EF (1%)	EF (2%)	EF (5%)
USRCAT	0.203 (0.110)	0.596 (0.079)	14.75 (9.12)	10.12 (7.03)	6.76 (4.97)	3.89 (2.25)
Shape-It	0.168 (0.076)	0.579 (0.007)	12.54 (8.89)	8.09 (5.50)	5.25 (3.17)	3.12 (1.49)
RGMolSA	0.118 (0.066)	0.540 (0.079)	6.54 (6.19)	4.56 (3.94)	3.26 (2.51)	2.21 (1.39)
KQMolSA	0.103 (0.054)	0.543 (0.083)	3.50 (3.45)	2.82 (2.41)	2.34 (1.73)	1.87 (1.12)
MolSG*	0.153	0.602	-	-	-	-

Table 6.1 Summary of the Average BEDROC, AUC and Enrichment Factors across the DUD-E benchmarking set. The standard deviation is given in brackets after each score. * Results taken from [4].

Figure 6.1 Summary for each method with the DUD-E data by (a) BEDROC, measuring early enrichment and (b) AUC, measuring overall performance.

Figures 6.2 and **6.3** present scatter plots comparing each pair of methods for the full set of DUD-E targets using the average AUC and BEDROC respectively. The dashed black line through the origin in each plot marks equal performance, with skew towards one axis over the other indicating the better method. The histograms shown on the diagonal describe the distribution of performance metric scores across the DUD-E data.

The scatter plots in **Figure 6.2** show that RGMolSA and KQMolSA are roughly equivalent in terms of AUC. RGMolSA is outperformed by, while KQMolSA gives a similar distribution of AUC values to the other approaches considered. Overall, the best performance is seen with USRCAT. The histograms show that for the majority of targets the AUC values fall above 0.5, indicating average overall performance to be above that obtained with random selection for all methods.

Except for a few outliers, most of the BEDROC scores presented in **Figure 6.3** are on the lower end for all methods included, with the majority falling below 0.4. Unlike for the AUC

6.2 Retrospective Benchmarking with the Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD-E)

Figure 6.2 Pairwise comparison of the AUC scores of methods investigated using the full DUD-E database. The black dashed line indicates random selection (AUC=0.5) and the histograms depict distribution of scores across all targets for a single method.

values, RGMolSA is slightly better than KQMolSA in terms of ability to place true actives at the beginning of the ranked list. Here both methods are outperformed by all others, with USRCAT again giving the best result overall. The improved performance of USRCAT may be due to the additional consideration of pharmacophoric features compared to the other methods.

Comparison of RGMolSA and KQMolSA to a wider range of existing shape similarity methods that were not easily replicated can be achieved by considering results from the literature.

Figure 6.3 Pairwise comparison of the BEDROC scores of methods investigated using the full DUD-E database. The black dashed line indicates random selection (BEDROC=0.5) and the histograms depict distribution of scores across all targets for a single method.

Table 6.2 provides the percentage of the DUD-E database which gave AUC values within a set of thresholds, as well as the number of molecules per second each method can describe as a measure of speed. The results for eSim, ROCS, WEGA, VAMS and OptiPharm were taken from [211].

The recent surface based method eSim, which considers surface shape and pharmacophore features using electrostatic potential, gives the best overall performance, with an average AUC

6.3 Considering Multiple Conformers for the Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD-E)

of 0.755 and just 5% of the targets giving values less than random selection and 8% with AUC above 0.95. ROCS and USRCAT also give notable performance across all targets, with a low percentage less than random selection, and a handful with AUC greater than 0.8. In all three cases, pharmacophore features are considered in addition to shape, suggesting this to be important for shape-based screening and thus represents a route for further development of both RGMolSA and KQMolSA. The best performance in terms of speed was given by VAMS, a shape comparison method based on comparison of voxelized volumes. While over 100 times slower, RGMolSA was found to give similar run times to the surface-based method eSim and the ROCS-analogues WEGA and OptiPharm, each around 10 Mols/s, which would be efficient enough for large scale comparisons. KQMolSA on the other hand was significantly more computationally expensive, processing 0.03 Mols/s. The bottleneck was found to be in the calculation of the distance between molecules, for which there are several possible approaches for improvement, including the use of gradient descent in the minimisation step.

Method	Mean AUC	% AUC < 0.50	% AUC \geq 0.60	% AUC \geq 0.70	% AUC \geq 0.80	% AUC \geq 0.90	% AUC \geq 0.95	Time Mols/s
eSim†	0.755	5	81	69	43	17	8	12.3
ROCS†	0.663	18	66	44	21	9	3	50
MolSG	0.61	4	48	15	2	0	0	-
USRCAT†	0.596	5	40	7	3	1	1	174.8
Shape-It	0.579	11	35	7	0	0	0	0.14
WEGA	0.564	31	44	19	6	0	0	26.7
VAMS	0.56	36	40	14	3	0	0	5000
OptiPharm	0.56	32	41	15	5	0	0	12
KQMolSA	0.543	31	25	7	0	0	0	0.03
RGMolSA	0.54	25	12	1	1	0	0	10.7

Table 6.2 Mean AUC and percentage of the whole DUD-E with AUC values above defined thresholds. Results for eSim, ROCS, WEGA, VAMS and OptiPharm taken from [211] and MolSG taken from [4]. † indicates the inclusion of pharmacophore features.

6.3. Considering Multiple Conformers for the Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD-E)

To probe whether consideration of multiple conformers improves recall of true actives, the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 subsets of the DUD-E set were selected, and multiple conformers generated following the procedure outlined in **Appendix B**. Here only RGMolSA and USRCAT were considered, as both KQMolSA and Shape-It were deemed too slow to make large scale multi-conformer comparison tractable. As for the single conformer study outlined in **Section 6.2**, performance was measured using the BEDROC (with $\alpha = 20$), AUC and EF for the top 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5% of ranked hits. A summary of these measures for both methods comparing the single and multi-conformer comparisons is given in **Table 6.3**. Across the three targets selected, RGMolSA largely gives similar recall on average when multiple conformers are considered, where a small improvement is seen in all cases for USRCAT.

Multiple Conformers						
	BEDROC	AUC	EF_0.5%	EF_1%	EF_2%	EF_5%
RGMolSA						
AKT2	0.191	0.512	21.73	13.23	7.34	3.47
CXCR4	0.236	0.651	17.71	12.14	8.37	4.8
FABP4	0.228	0.606	25.17	15.26	8.71	4.16
USRCAT						
AKT2	0.284	0.663	24.75	15.58	9.82	5.39
CXCR4	0.346	0.648	52.39	29.34	15.36	6.48
FABP4	0.291	0.708	30.55	18.18	11.19	5.40
Single Conformer						
	BEDROC	AUC	EF_0.5%	EF_1%	EF_2%	EF_5%
RGMolSA						
AKT2	0.195	0.600	21.58	13.33	7.48	3.44
CXCR4	0.176	0.66	8.78	6.54	4.86	3.72
FABP4	0.190	0.575	26.84	14.44	7.43	3.3
USRCAT						
AKT2	0.237	0.575	18.99	12.98	8.43	4.57
CXCR4	0.181	0.642	18.28	11.10	6.72	3.38
FABP4	0.245	0.627	22.99	14.45	8.93	4.80

Table 6.3 Average performance metric scores for the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 targets from the DUD-E set for RGMolSA and USRCAT where multiple conformers are considered compared to a single conformer.

Figures 6.4 and **6.5** present scatter plots comparing the average BEDROC and AUC scores respectively for a single conformer of each molecule (blue) vs multiple conformers (red). These show that across all queries for AKT2 and FABP4, no major improvement is seen in either the early enrichment (BEDROC) or overall (AUC) performance of either method. For CXCR4, an uptick is seen in the BEDROC scores for both RGMolSA and USRCAT.

In order to explore the variation in molecules retrieved by each method, the top five scoring test case and the query that gave them (top row in each case) are shown in **Figures 6.6-6.11**. Across all three targets, a different top five is seen for both methods, and for multiple conformers compared to just one. In all cases the top scores for RGMolSA were close to 1, although some false positives were retrieved, where although lower scores were given for USRCAT, all molecules in the top five were true actives. Inspection by eye reveals the molecules retrieved to have similar shape, but mostly exhibit similar structures, suggesting a lack of scaffold hopping in the top ranking molecules.

Figure 6.4 BEDROC scores for single (blue) vs multiple (red) conformers across all queries for the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 targets of the DUD-E data set for RGMolSA and USRCAT.

Figure 6.5 AUC scores for single (blue) vs multiple (red) conformers across all queries for the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 targets of the DUD-E data set for RGMolSA and USRCAT.

6.3 Considering Multiple Conformers for the Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD-E)

Figure 6.6 Top five scoring Query-Test pairs for single vs multiple conformers for RGMSA when considering the AKT2 subset. The top row in each case are the query molecules, and the number given in brackets corresponds to the conformer ID.

USRCAT - Single Conformer

USRCAT - Multi Conformer

Figure 6.7 Top five scoring Query-Test pairs for single vs multiple conformers for USRCAT when considering the AKT2 subset. The top row in each case are the query molecules, and the number given in brackets corresponds to the conformer ID.

6.3 Considering Multiple Conformers for the Directory of Useful Decoys (DUD-E)

Figure 6.8 Top five scoring Query-Test pairs for single vs multiple conformers for RGMolSA when considering the CXCR4 subset. The top row in each case are the query molecules, and the number given in brackets corresponds to the conformer ID.

USRCAT - Single Conformer

USRCAT - Multi Conformer

Figure 6.9 Top five scoring Query-Test pairs for single vs multiple conformers for USRCAT when considering the CXCR4 subset. The top row in each case are the query molecules, and the number given in brackets corresponds to the conformer ID.

Figure 6.10 Top five scoring Query-Test pairs for single vs multiple conformers for RGMSA when considering the FABP4 subset. The top row in each case are the query molecules, and the number given in brackets corresponds to the conformer ID.

Figure 6.11 Top five scoring Query-Test pairs for single vs multiple conformers for USRCAT when considering the FABP4 subset. The top row in each case are the query molecules, and the number given in brackets corresponds to the conformer ID.

Overall, the lack of improvement seen here when multiple conformers used is disappointing. For RGMolSA, the dependence on the choice of base sphere leads to a more “local” description of shape, which may explain this. Improving the robustness of this choice may help improve retrieval where multiple conformers are considered.

6.4. Conformers of a Highly Flexible Molecule

The ability of RGMolSA and KQMolSA to handle different conformers was initially probed by considering a series of PDE5 inhibitors (Sections 4.4 and 5.4). These molecules contain multiple rings, making them relatively rigid, and as such adopt a narrow range of shapes upon conformational changes. For both methods, high similarity scores were assigned to all conformer pairs. It was therefore deemed pertinent to establish how the conformers of a molecule that can

adopt a wider range of shapes would be scored. 1000 conformers of Eicosane (a chain of 20 carbons, **Figure 6.12**) were generated using the procedure outlined in **Appendix B**. These were aligned using the Open3DAlign tool implemented in RDKit for ease of visualisation [314]. In theory, the greater degree of flexibility will result in the adoption of a wider range of shapes, and hence a wider range of similarity scores.

Figure 6.12 (a) Structure of Eicosane (b) Overlay of the 1000 generated conformers of Eicosane.

For each of RGMolSA (**Chapter 4**), KQMolSA (**Chapter 5**) and USRCAT (for comparison to a more established method [152]) each conformer was compared to the lowest energy conformer. The root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) was also computed for comparison. In theory, lower shape similarity scores would be expected for higher RMSD differences. **Figure 6.13** presents plots of the RMSD vs RGMolSA, KQMolSA and USRCAT similarity scores. For USRCAT, a clear downward trend in similarity score with increasing RMSD is observed, where for RGMolSA no correlation is observed, and for KQMolSA all conformers were given scores of ~ 0.3 . This is the case not just for comparison to the lowest energy conformer, but for any two random conformers of Eicosane, KQMolSA gives a score of ~ 0.3 (**Figure 6.14**).

To investigate the observed trends further, the overlay of the conformers with minimum, median, and maximum RMSD values were visualised (**Figure 6.15**). By-eye inspection of both the structures and the surfaces of the conformers shows that there is a large overlap for the minimum RMSD pair, and thus the high similarity scores given by RGMolSA and USRCAT are warranted. The median pair show a high overlap of their surfaces, but the conformer shown in blue is more stretched out than that in red. This could explain the higher scoring by RGMolSA than USRCAT, as the blue conformer would have a significantly different distribution of atoms in space while retaining a high surface overlap. Low scores are correctly assigned by all three methods for the maximum RMSD pair.

To probe this further, the top 10 highest and lowest RMSD to the lowest energy conformer were visualised. **Figure 6.16** shows the structure and surface overlays for the conformers where

Figure 6.13 RMSD (in Å) vs Similarity Score for the lowest energy conformer of Eicosane compared to all others for (a) RGMolSA, (b) KQMolSA and (c) USRCAT.

Figure 6.14 Similarity scores obtained with KQMolSA for two random pairs of conformers.

minimal changes in atomic position have occurred. Inspection by eye shows significant overlap of the structures for (a), (c), (d), (f), (h) and (j), where high similarity is assigned by USRCAT and RGMolSA. For the others lower overlap is seen, with relatively high scores still assigned by USRCAT, while RGMolSA assigns these as lower similarity. **Figure 6.17** shows the structure and surface overlays for the conformers where the most change in atomic position has occurred. Here the difference in positions yields low USRCAT similarity scores, while in some cases

Figure 6.15 RMSD (in Å) and shape similarity scores for the minimum, maximum, and median RMSD values from the 1000 conformers of Eicosane compared to the lowest energy conformer (shown in red).

RGMolSA still assigns high similarity. Overall, these results provide an interesting insight into the way different shape-based similarity methods capture conformers depending on how they define shape. The lack of distinction between conformers of a molecule containing no rings by KQMolSA would be problematic in a real virtual screen, and will require further investigation in the future development of the method.

6.5. The AstraZeneca Test

In this section, the relative performance of RGMolSA and KQMolSA compared to other shape descriptors is assessed using a set of molecules for which the “absolute” shape similarity has been assigned. Extracted from the AstraZeneca Test data set [241], originally designed for validation of pharmacophore overlay programs, the shape similarity between a reference and nine test structures were computed using the analytical van der Waals volume (ASV) for ten targets [320]. These data were kindly provided by Dr Mark Mackey and Dr Rosemary Mantell from Cresset Software. An assessment of the level of difficulty of each data set for correct assignment with pharmacophore overlay programs is given. Of the 10 targets, three are classed as easy (P00489, P0A017 and Q9BJF5), five of intermediate difficulty (O15530, P07900, P24182, P25440 and Q92731) and two are considered challenging (P68400 and Q08499). A summary of the structural (based on 2D fingerprints) and ROCS shape and colour similarity reported in the original publication is provided in **Table 6.4**.

Figure 6.16 Overlay of the lowest energy conformer with the 10 others of lowest RMSD.

ID	Target	Avg. 2D	Avg. Shape	Avg. Colour
P00489	protein (glycogen phosphorylase)	0.604	0.792	0.589
P0A017	dihydrofolate reductase	0.657	0.648	0.465
Q9BJF5	calmodulin-domain protein kinase 1	0.650	0.680	0.396
O15530	3-phosphoinositide dependent protein kinase-1	0.559	0.497	0.183
P07900	HSP 90-alpha	0.464	0.461	0.183
P24182	biotin carboxylase	0.403	0.455	0.200
P25440	bromodomain-containing protein 2	0.391	0.518	0.151
Q92731	estrogen receptor beta	0.433	0.720	0.281
P68400	casein kinase II	0.357	0.428	0.087
Q08499	cAMP-specific 3',5'-cyclic phosphodiesterase 4D	0.442	0.435	0.112

Table 6.4 Summary of the targets included within the AstraZeneca data, along with the average 2D and ROCS similarity from the original paper.

As discussed earlier in this work, there is currently no absolute definition of molecular shape. The van der Waals or hard spheres volume gives a highly accurate approximation to the volume, and thus represents the closest possible approximation to the true shape [320]. The ASV is given by summing the volume of each atom modelled as a hard sphere of van der Waals radius,

Figure 6.17 Overlay of the lowest energy conformer with the 10 others of highest RMSD.

accounting for their intersections using the inclusion-exclusion principle,

$$V(1 + 2 + \dots + n) = [V_1 + V_2 + \dots + V_n] - [V_{1,2} + V_{1,3} + \dots + V_{n-1,n}] + [V_{1,2,3} + V_{1,2,4} + \dots + V_{n-2,n-1,n}] + \dots + (-1)^{n+1}V_{1,2,\dots,n-1,n}. \quad (6.1)$$

These volumes were calculated using an open-source implementation from Michel Petitjean [321]. The similarity between two volumes was then quantified using the Tanimoto coefficient,

$$T_{A,B} = \frac{O_{A,B}}{(O_{A,A} + O_{B,B} - O_{A,B})}, \quad (6.2)$$

where O is the volume overlap between molecules A and B . These “absolute” shape similarity scores provide a standard against which to compare other methods, where in theory similar scores or rank order should be obtained for a good description of shape. In addition to RGMolSA and KQMolSA, the surface area as defined in **Equation 3.4** was considered due to its similarity

to the ASV. The similarity between two areas was computed as

$$\text{score} = \frac{A_{\min}}{A_{\max}}, \quad (6.3)$$

to again give a score between 0 and 1. If accurate enough, use of the surface area defined in this way would represent an extremely quick method for filtering molecules of similar size and shape from large databases. Similarity scores from USRCAT were also considered [152]. To quantify any correlation between the rankings given by each method, three metrics were considered.

The Jaccard Score or Jaccard Index gives a measure of similarity between two ranked lists [317]. It is defined as the ratio of intersection over union:

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}. \quad (6.4)$$

By design, the score takes a value in the range [0, 1], where 0 indicates no similarity and 1 represented two identical lists. We report the average Jaccard Similarity generated using the implementation available in Scikit-Learn.

Kendall's Tau measures the correspondence between two ranked lists [316]. Strong agreement is indicated by a score of 1, strong disagreement by a score close to -1, with a score of 0 indicating no correlation. A p-value is reported alongside τ that indicates the probability of obtaining the result. Lower p-values indicate greater statistical significance in the reported τ , with a p-value of 0.05 typically considered to be statistically significant. τ is a measure of the number of concordant pairs (C) vs the number of discordant pairs (D):

$$\tau = \frac{C - D}{C + D} \quad (6.5)$$

The drawback of using Kendall's Tau is that it requires the lists to be conjoint – while this is appropriate for this dataset, the metric would not be useful for analysing the top scoring molecules in a set for different methods, as these are likely to vary. Again, we use the implementation provided in Sci-kit Learn.

Finally, we considered the Rank-Bias Overlap (RBO) between the ranked lists [322]. This is a similarity rather than a correlation measure, given by

$$RBO(A, B, p) = (1 - p) \sum p^{d-1} \cdot A_d, \quad (6.6)$$

where d is the depth of the list to be considered, p is a tunable parameter that takes a value between 0 and 1 that determines the contribution of the top d ranks to the final value and $A_d = |S_{:d} \cap T_{:d}|/d$, which gives the agreement of lists A and B for the depth considered. The RBO takes a value of 0 where two lists are entirely different, and 1 when they are identical. An implementation of the method using $p = 0.9$ was taken from [323].

For each target set, the space filling models are provided to permit “by-eye” assessment of similarity, along with the score given for each test molecule compared to the reference, and the relative ranking given by each model. These are given here for target P00489 (**Figure 6.18**, **Tables 6.5** and **6.6**) as an example, with the full results provided in **Appendix K**.

Generally, both the relative ranking and scores obtained vary for each method studied, with KQMolSA appearing to get the closest to the ASV. Inspection of the space filling models suggests that the targets Q92731, P0A017, Q9BJF5 and P00489 could be expected to show higher similarity based on shape than the other sets. For P00489 this is seen in the surface area comparison, but scores less than 0.7 are seen for all others. For the other three targets, RGMolSA and KQMolSA (with $k = 1$) also give scores on average above 0.7.

Figure 6.18 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P00489.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA ($k = 1$)	KQMolSA ($k = 2$)	USRCAT	Surface Area
5	0.703	0.735	0.603	0.639	0.178	0.907
3	0.682	0.363	0.526	0.529	0.464	0.992
1	0.671	0.730	0.684	0.709	0.187	0.948
6	0.664	0.737	0.565	0.605	0.168	0.859
7	0.655	0.731	0.613	0.635	0.194	0.904
4	0.643	0.341	0.465	0.476	0.226	0.934
0	0.596	0.733	0.570	0.608	0.151	0.837
2	0.591	0.738	0.537	0.575	0.138	0.824
8	0.476	0.765	0.378	0.414	0.098	0.634
Average	0.631	0.653	0.549	0.577	0.200	0.871

Table 6.5 Similarity Scores for P00489, sorted by highest ASV score.

Tables 6.7-6.9 report the Kendall’s Tau, Jaccard Index and RBO metrics for the ranked list of each method compared to that produced by the ASV. On average, the Kendall’s Tau suggests that there is little correlation between the rankings produced, with scores around 0. The associated p-values suggest there is little statistical significance to these scores, which may be a result of a small sample size. This is also mimicked in the Jaccard Scores, which are all less than 0.3 (where 1 indicates high similarity), suggesting low similarity of the rankings. In both cases, comparison of size only (using the surface area) scores the highest. Use of the RBO metric suggests slightly greater overlap between the ranked lists, but still not high similarity, with scores ~ 0.6 in all cases.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	5	3	1	6	7	4	0	2	8
RGMolSA	8	2	6	5	0	7	1	3	4
KQMolSA (k = 1)	1	7	5	0	6	2	3	4	8
KQMolSA (k = 2)	1	5	7	0	6	2	3	4	8
USRCAT	3	4	7	1	5	6	0	2	8
Surface Area	3	1	4	5	7	6	0	2	8

Table 6.6 Ranking by each method for P00489.

Overall, the lack of correlation between methods is not unanticipated, as different descriptors generally give different estimations of similarity [61]. While the ASV is considered the closest approximation to the true shape, and perhaps a closer relation could have been expected. The retrieval of molecules in a different order could be viewed as a positive, as the use of a combination of methods in a real screen may assist in finding the maximum number of hits.

	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	SA
P00489	[0.056, 0.919]	[0.056, 0.919]	[0.0, 1.0]	[0.278, 0.358]	[0.667, 0.013]
P0A017	[0.722, 0.006]	[0.389, 0.18]	[0.111, 0.761]	[0.056, 0.919]	[0.556, 0.045]
Q9BJF5	[0.333, 0.26]	[-0.222, 0.477]	[0.222, 0.477]	[0.0, 1.0]	[-0.167, 0.612]
O15530	[-0.278, 0.358]	[-0.222, 0.477]	[0.111, 0.761]	[0.222, 0.477]	[-0.111, 0.761]
P07900	[0.222, 0.477]	[0.278, 0.358]	[0.389, 0.18]	[0.222, 0.477]	[0.333, 0.26]
P24182	[0.333, 0.26]	[0.278, 0.358]	[0.111, 0.761]	[0.111, 0.761]	[0.111, 0.761]
P25440	[-0.056, 0.919]	[0.056, 0.919]	[0.556, 0.045]	[0.111, 0.761]	[0.389, 0.18]
Q92731	[-0.111, 0.761]	[0.278, 0.358]	[0.333, 0.26]	[-0.444, 0.119]	[0.222, 0.477]
P68400	[-0.056, 0.919]	[-0.111, 0.761]	[-0.389, 0.18]	[-0.056, 0.919]	[0.278, 0.358]
Q08499	[-0.278, 0.358]	[0.444, 0.119]	[0.333, 0.26]	[-0.333, 0.26]	[0.5, 0.075]
Avg. τ	0.089	0.122	0.178	0.017	0.278
Avg. p-val.	0.524	0.493	0.469	0.605	0.354

Table 6.7 Kendall's Tau scores of each method compared to the ASV for the Cresset Data. For each pair, the first value is τ and the second is the corresponding p-value. The difficulty of the data are colour coded as **Easy**, **Moderate** and **Hard**.

	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	SA
P00489	0.000	0.111	0.111	0.333	0.444
P0A017	0.222	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.556
Q9BJF5	0.000	0.222	0.333	0.111	0.222
O15530	0.111	0.333	0.333	0.556	0.000
P07900	0.000	0.222	0.444	0.111	0.111
P24182	0.111	0.111	0.222	0.333	0.333
P25440	0.111	0.111	0.222	0.111	0.333
Q92731	0.000	0.000	0.111	0.222	0.111
P68400	0.111	0.222	0.111	0.111	0.111
Q08499	0.000	0.222	0.444	0.111	0.556
Avg. Jaccard Index	0.067	0.167	0.244	0.211	0.278

Table 6.8 Jaccard Index of each method compared to the ASV for the Cresset Data. The difficulty of the data are colour coded as **Easy**, **Moderate** and **Hard**.

6.6 Shape-Based Reprofitting of FDA-Approved Drugs for the H₁ Histamine Receptor

	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (<i>k</i> = 1)	KQMolSA (<i>k</i> = 2)	USRCAT	SA
P00489	0.443	0.610	0.666	0.681	0.746
P0A017	0.892	0.694	0.781	0.803	0.911
Q9BJF5	0.465	0.528	0.578	0.615	0.677
O15530	0.776	0.691	0.774	0.888	0.698
P07900	0.641	0.730	0.851	0.722	0.697
P24182	0.741	0.571	0.691	0.569	0.804
P25440	0.578	0.555	0.744	0.728	0.774
Q92731	0.503	0.415	0.456	0.607	0.688
P68400	0.587	0.690	0.566	0.515	0.622
Q08499	0.549	0.708	0.810	0.523	0.875
Avg. RBO	0.618	0.619	0.692	0.665	0.749

Table 6.9 Rank-bias Overlap of each method compared to the ASV for the Cresset Data. The difficulty of the data are colour coded as **Easy**, **Moderate** and **Hard**.

6.6. Shape-Based Reprofitting of FDA-Approved Drugs for the H₁ Histamine Receptor

Drug repurposing or repositioning, where existing approved or investigational drugs are matched to new indications, is an appealing strategy as treatments can be identified more quickly, and the known safety of these molecules reduces risk of failure [324]. As molecules of similar shape are likely to display similar biological activity, this represents a potential route for repurposing, first investigated by Vasudevan and co-workers [5]. They made use of OpenEye's ROCS to search a list of 1216 FDA approved drugs for candidates with potential antihistaminic activity at the H₁ Histamine Receptor. The H₁ receptor was chosen for this study due to the wealth of information available surrounding the interaction of various drugs with this target. Thirteen known antihistamines were selected from the literature for use as queries. Their structures are given in **Figure 6.19**.

In the original study, the ability of ROCS to rank true actives, of which there were 32, near the top of the list was assessed using the percentage of true antihistamines present in the top 1% (12 drugs) and 3% (40 drugs) of the ranked list. From the drugs with no known antihistaminic or antidepressant properties, all with Tanimoto similarity greater than 0.8 to at least three of the queries were purchased for further testing. As many antidepressants are derived from histamine, they were also excluded, removing a further 36 molecules from consideration.

The study found ROCS to show selective recall of existing antihistamines in most cases, although this was found to vary with the query used. This demonstrates the method to be non-random in detecting molecules with similar 3D shape. On the basis of the cut-off criteria, 23 compounds were selected for biological testing. 13 of these were found to selectively inhibit histamine-induced calcium release in a cellular assay. The hits identified came from a wide range of original indications, including antihypertensive, antispasmodic, antipsychotic, and narcotic analgesic effects. While in this case shape-based screening was successful, it was noted by the authors that many repurposing efforts may not consider such druggable targets, and the use of this method may be limited when there are fewer known active molecules available.

Figure 6.19 Structures of the thirteen query molecules used to screen the FDA approved drugs for potential antihistaminic activity.

To see if the use of shape for reprofiling drugs could extend to other methods, the RGMolSA and KQMolSA descriptors outlined in this thesis were deployed on the same data, along with the USRCAT descriptors reported in the literature. This also permits indirect comparison to the ROCS method. As in the original study, 100 conformers for each of the queries and FDA drugs were generated. Here these were produced using the RDKit, as outlined in **Appendix B**.

The percentage of true antihistamines retrieved for each method in the top 1% and 3% of the ranked list are summarised in **Figure 6.20**. Similar retrieval is seen for ROCS and USRCAT for the top 1%, while a greater number of actives is seen in the top 3% for ROCS. RGMolSA assigns high similarity scores (above 0.8) to almost all the FDA approved drugs, and therefore suffers significantly lower retrieval than the more established methods. This may be due to the more local description of shape given by RGMolSA due to the dependence on the base sphere. While KQMolSA does assign a wider range of scores, it still suffers from comparatively poor recall compared to ROCS and USRCAT. Additionally, no pharmacophore features are considered with either RGMolSA or KQMolSA, which may also contribute to recall ability.

6.7 RGMolSA as a Descriptor in the Random Matrix Discriminant Framework

Figure 6.20 Percentage of antihistamines retrieved at the top 1% (12 drugs) and top 3% (40 drugs) of the ranked list. The results for ROCS were taken from the original paper [5]. Note also that the graph for ROCS Top 1% has a different scale to the others.

The top 23 hits for each method are reported in **Table 6.10**. For ROCS and RGMolSA these meet the conditions outlined in the original paper of similarity of 0.8 or above to at least three of the thirteen queries. For USRCAT only two of the hits have similarity greater than 0.8 to one of the queries, three greater than 0.7 and the rest below 0.7. KQMolSA returns nine hits with similarity greater than 0.8 to three queries, ten with similarity greater than 0.8 to two queries and four with similarity greater than 0.8 to one query. Generally very different rankings are seen in each case, with only Chlorpromazine, Ethopropazine, Promazine, Orphenadrine and Chlorprothixene commonly selected by ROCS and USRCAT, and Biperiden common to ROCS, RGMolSA and KQMolSA. Of the five shared hits for USRCAT, four of them have experimentally validated activity, suggesting USRCAT could match the performance of ROCS for drug repurposing, while RGMolSA and KQMolSA would require further development for this purpose. The other point to consider here is that, while molecular shape can identify molecules which may bind, it does not consider the context within which the drug is to be repurposed. For example, Bisacodyl selected by ROCS and KQMolSA is a potent laxative, and therefore would be unsuitable as an antihistamine. Certain cancer drugs also fall into this category, where the higher toxicity acceptable for cancer treatment would not be approved for less severe indications. This could be rectified through the use of further filters to remove inappropriate candidates.

6.7. RGMolSA as a Descriptor in the Random Matrix Discriminant Framework

A novel algorithm for the statistical analysis of small molecule data sets was recently proposed by Lee *et al.*, known as the Random Matrix Discriminant (RMD) [325]. The approach, derived from Random Matrix Theory, works on the basis that specific chemical motifs are recognised by a protein binding site, and that these are likely to be common amongst active molecules, and absent from inactive molecules. However, there are many more motifs than there are molecules

	ROCS	USRCAT	RGMolSA	QMolSA
1	Felbamate	Orphenadrine	Quinethazone	Iopamidol
2	Phenolphthalein	Cyclizine	Biperiden	Iopanoic Acid
3	Phenylbutazone	Promazine	Canadine	Lorazepam
4	Clopidogrel	Trimeprazine	Thyroxine	Mechlorethamine
5	Modafinil	Methdilazine	Carnitine	Kanamycin A
6	Bisacodyl	Ethopropazine	Pranoprofen	Tolterodine
7	Pirenzepine	Chlorphenoxamide	Estradiol Mustard	Flufenamic Acid
8	Chlorpromazine	Methadone	Secobarbital	Topiramate
9	Miconazole	Chlorprothixene	Fluphenazine	Kanamycin C
10	Cyclofenil	Chlorpromazine	Ceftazidime	Tobramycin
11	Lobeline	Methotrimeprazine	Thiopental	Emorfazone
12	Procyclidine	Methadyl Acetate	Gliclazide	Biperiden
13	Pipenzolate	Zotepine	Fluphenazine Decanoate	Moxisylyte
14	Ethopropazine	Bencyclane	Dromostanolone Propionate	Lorcainide
15	Ketanserin	Levopropoxyphene	Cyclobarbitol	Prifinium Bromide
16	Biperiden	Levomethadyl Acetate	Thiopropazate	Simvastatin
17	Adiphenine	Propoxyphene	Lorcainide	Carphenazine
18	Fentanyl	Perphenazine	Ketamine	Carnitine
19	Promazine	Pentapiperide	Milrinone	Alfentanil
20	Orphenadrine	Diltiazem	Salicylamide	Methantheline Bromide
21	Phentolamine	Clothiapine	Repaglinide	Quinethazone
22	Chlorprothixene	Dextromoramide	Physostigmine	Bromocriptine
23	Trihexphenidyl	Quetiapine	Estradiol Enanthate	Bisacodyl

Table 6.10 Top 23 molecules for each method without known antihistaminic activity. For ROCS and RGMolSA these all had scores greater than 0.8 to at least three queries. For USRCAT only the top five had scores greater than 0.7 to one query, with the rest falling below 0.7.

of known activity, leading to a problem known as noise due to undersampling. This is accounted for here by the explicit inclusion of inactive data. The use of RMD identified 4 novel Human M1 Agonists with experimentally confirmed activity by screening the emolecules database.

Here the possibility of replacing common motifs with common shapes is investigated by using the RGMolSA descriptors developed within this thesis as a feature representation. Due to the scaffold hopping capability of shape-based descriptors, inclusion of shape either alone or as a hybrid 2D-3D descriptor could improve the diversity of the proposed hits, which would be useful when addressing unwanted properties. The ability to use 3D descriptors was tested using five of the data sets provided with the original publication, summarised in **Table 6.11**. A small study using the original RMD method in a screen for potential COVID-19 antivirals is also reported. The Python implementation used is available via GitHub [326].

Target	No. Actives	No. Inactives
Serotonin receptor 2B (5-HT2B)	844	361
α -2A adrenergic receptor (ADRA2A)	528	368
Histamine H ₁ receptor (H1)	824	467
μ opioid receptor (MOR1)	2516	787
Human ether-à-go-go-related gene (hERG)	347	2346

Table 6.11 Summary of the data considered with the original RMD method.

6.7.1. Random Matrix Theory

The method proposed is derived from Random Matrix Theory, and uses the 1024 bit Morgan Fingerprint with radius 3 to represent molecules. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is then used to determine which bond paths are important for binding, represented as a set of eigenvectors and their corresponding eigenvalues (V_{\pm}). The Marchenko-Pastur distribution is used to determine which eigenvalues are important for binding. An unknown molecule, represented by its corresponding Morgan fingerprint \mathbf{u} , can be classified as active or inactive depending on which set of eigenvalues it is closest to:

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{u}, V_+) < \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{u}, V_-) + \mathcal{E}, \quad (6.7)$$

where \mathcal{E} is a tolerance parameter that accounts for false positives and false negatives, and $\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{u}, V_{\pm})$ is the distance between the molecule \mathbf{u} and the linear subspace containing known actives and inactives V_{\pm} . This equation is known as the Random Matrix Discriminant (RMD). As the molecules considered experimentally as potential drug candidates often share similar scaffolds, these will have statistically significant eigenvectors regardless of whether the molecule is active or not. The method therefore considers the correlations present in the active set and ignores those of the inactive set. The Tanimoto Coefficient is then used to compare the similarity of the unknown molecules to the active set. For two molecules a and b, the similarity is calculated from the number of features of a and b, and the number of shared features, c:

$$T(a, b) = \frac{c}{a + b - c}. \quad (6.8)$$

Algorithm 1 provides pseudocode for the steps involved in computing the Random Matrix Discriminant.

6.7.2. Including 3D Shape Information in the RMD

The inclusion of 3D shape information was achieved both by using the RGMolSA descriptors (described in **Chapter 4**) in place of the 2D Morgan fingerprints, and by generating a 2D-3D hybrid descriptor. In order to construct the hybrid descriptor, the 3D shape vectors were min-max normalised,

$$x_{scaled} = \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}}, \quad (6.9)$$

to ensure all values were between 0 and 1, to give the same range for all data points, then appended to the end of the Morgan fingerprint.

The results of this are shown in **Figure 6.21**. A significant drop in recall is seen when 3D descriptors are used compared to the 2D descriptors, most likely due to the drop in number of data points, with 9 elements compared to 1024 for the Morgan fingerprints. They do however give better recall than random selection, suggesting initial promise in the use of the descriptors. No significant drop in performance is observed with the hybrid descriptors, with the 2D-3D descriptor either matching, or in some cases giving a small improvement over, 2D descriptors

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode for the RMD Algorithm

```
Get Morgan Fingerprints
Train/Test split 90:10
for Active and Inactive Training Set do
    Calculate z-score
    Find indices where Standard Deviation(SD) = 0
    Remove values at indices where SD = 0
    Generate the covariance matrix
    Identify significant eigenvectors
end for
for Active and Inactive Test Set do
    Remove positions where SD = 0 for Active
    Remove positions where SD = 0 for Inactive
    Mean centre and scale w.r.t the Active
    Mean centre and scale w.r.t the Inactive
    Generate score vs Active and Inactive
end for
Compare Active score vs Inactive + tolerance range
Calculate AUC
Pick intermediate tolerance
for Unknown Molecules do
    Repeat as for Active and Inactive Test Set
    Compare Active score vs Inactive + tolerance range
end for
```

alone dependent on the target. This suggests that 3D shape information could be included in this way to recall true actives while increasing diversity.

6.7 RGMolSA as a Descriptor in the Random Matrix Discriminant Framework

Figure 6.21 AUC plots showing the rate of true positives vs false positives for each of the five target sets considered in the original RMD paper, where 2D, 3D and hybrid descriptors are considered

6.7.3. Applying RMD to Screen for COVID-19 Antivirals

In the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, it was deemed attractive to re-position existing drugs, as this would permit quicker approval compared to the generation of novel antivirals. As a side project to the work presented in this thesis, the original RMD method was tested as a computational route to predict candidates with potential activity against the 2019-nCoV Main Protease for repurposing.

The model was trained using a dataset constructed from the initial fragment screen of XChem's libraries by Diamond Light Source, that provided 79 active and 1222 inactive fragments against M^{pro} [327], 2327 presumed actives identified in a docking study by Life Chemicals [328], and a set of 1520 antibiotic decoys taken from the PubChem database that were presumed inactive. The Drugbank database containing ~1600 approved or investigational drug molecules was used for screening [256].

Use of the above data provided accurate recall, with an AUC score of 0.993. With a tolerance of 0.01, 15 hits were identified. **Table 6.12** provides a summary of their original use, delivery route, structure, and maximum Tanimoto similarity to the active set. It is worth noting that many of the suggestions are on the smaller side, likely due to the use of fragment data within the training set.

Table 6.12 Existing drugs with potential activity against M^{pro} identified from the Drugbank Database using the RMD.

Drug	Original Indication	Delivery Route	Structure	Tanimoto Similarity
Adapalene	Acne	Topical		0.232
Theophylline	Respiratory	Oral		0.266
Celecoxib	NSAID	Oral		0.247
Continued on next page				

Table 6.12 – continued from previous page

Drug	Original Indication	Delivery Route	Structure	Tanimoto Similarity
Fenoprofen	NSAID	Oral		0.261
Temozolomide	Chemotherapy	Oral, IV		0.198
Chlorphenesin	Athletes Foot	Topical		0.295
Azelastine	Antihistamine	Nasal Spray, Eye Drops		0.398
Metyrapone	Diagnosis of Adrenal Insufficiency	Oral		0.224
Halofantrine	Antimalarial	Oral		0.190
Aminophylline	Respiratory	IV		0.261

Continued on next page

Table 6.12 – continued from previous page

Drug	Original Indication	Delivery Route	Structure	Tanimoto Similarity
Pimavanserin	Antipsychotic	Oral		0.294
Bisacodyl	Laxative	Oral		0.208
Bilastine	Antihistamine	Oral		0.313
Edaravone	ALS treatment	IV		0.237
Oxolamine	Cough Suppressant	Oral		0.326

A follow-up docking study (kindly completed by Dr Agnieszka Bronowska) predicted Oxolamine, Halofantrine, Edavarone, Bilastine and Pimavanserin to have activity in the micromolar range. These hits are diverse: Halofantrine has antimalarial properties, Oxolamine is a cough suppressant, Edavarone is a recently approved ALS treatment, Bilastine is an antihistamine and Pimavanserin is an anti-psychotic under investigation for the treatment of Parkinson's Disease. These represent promising possibilities in the context of COVID-19. The suggestion of a cough suppressant is sensible for a respiratory disease, and other antimalarial drugs such as hydroxychloroquine were used from early in the pandemic, if controversially. Perhaps the most interesting result here is Bilastine: while docking studies showed affinity for M^{pro} , Bilastine is

known for selectivity for the human H₁ receptor. At the point this investigation was conducted, the H₁ receptor had recently been proposed as a target in the treatment of COVID-19, with the antihistamine Ebastine already in clinical trial [329]. The use of H₁ agonists could reduce the inflammatory response of the immune system, in turn decreasing the risk of acute respiratory distress syndrome. Edaravone also presents an interesting candidate – its small size will make it a frequent hitter, but the availability in IV formulation would make it particularly suited to use in ICU.

One drawback of the algorithm is that suitability for repurposing in the context of the disease is not considered. For example, Temozolomide is a chemotherapy treatment used in the advanced stages of glioma and glioblastoma. The drug is highly toxic and would therefore be unlikely to gain approval for a respiratory, non-terminal condition. Likewise, Bisacodyl is a potent laxative, so would be an unsuitable candidate in this case.

6.8. Conclusions

In this chapter, the usefulness of RGMolSA and KQMolSA as descriptors of shape has been investigated. Across the studies completed, neither method gave improved performance compared to more established shape-similarity screening software. However, for a first round of development both gave a respectable performance, suggesting future development to potentially be fruitful.

The DUD-E community benchmarking set was used to gain insight into the ability of RGMolSA and KQMolSA to retrieve true active molecules compared to USRCAT and Shape-It, which were run in house, and MolSG, where the results were obtained from the literature. With 102 targets, this data allows performance to be evaluated for a diverse range of proteins with different shaped binding pockets, and thus different shaped ligands. For a single conformer of each molecule, and using each active as a query, the performance was evaluated using the AUC metric for overall performance, and the BEDROC and EF for the top 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5% of ranked molecules to assess early enrichment. On average, both methods developed within this thesis gave comparable overall performance to the existing methods, but fared slightly worse in their ability to place true actives at the top of the ranked list. USRCAT, based on atomic distance with pharmacophoric features included, gave the best performance across all targets in terms of both overall and early enrichment. Comparison to other methods found in literature showed eSim, a recent surface-based method which considers pharmacophoric features using the electrostatic potential, was best overall. Both ROCS and USRCAT were also notable. All three best performers include pharmacophore information, suggesting this may offer improved predictions compared to shape alone. In terms of speed, RGMolSA was not the quickest, but comparable to eSim and ROCS, and therefore can be considered acceptable for real applications. KQMolSA was found to be significantly more computationally expensive.

To probe the importance of conformer sampling, the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 subsets were selected from DUD-E, due to their smaller size on average, and ranked using RGMolSA

and USRCAT. KQMolSA was excluded from this comparison, as the speed of the distance calculations was deemed intractable at this scale. Considering the same performance metrics as above, a small improvement is seen with USRCAT on average, where for RGMolSA a similar performance is given for multiple conformers compared to just one. Across the full set of molecules, changes in performance were found to be target dependent, with a slight uptick in BEDROC scores for CXCR4 with both methods when multiple conformers, while for AKT2 and FABP4 these are largely similar. A different top 5 scoring molecules is also retrieved in each case when multiple conformers are used. Inspection by-eye suggests that, despite retrieval of several inactives for RGMolSA, these have similar shapes.

To probe how the conformers of a molecule which can adopt a large range of shapes are related, a set of conformers were produced for Eicosane, a chain of 20 carbon atoms joined by single bonds. The scores obtained for USRCAT decreased with increasing RMSD, varied independently of RMSD for RGMolSA and showed no variation for KQMolSA. Inspection by-eye highlighted the variation amongst methods for how the conformers are classed.

Further investigation of the relative performance of RGMolSA and KQMolSA compared to other shape descriptors was completed using a subset of the AstraZeneca test originally designed for validation of pharmacophore overlay programs. 10 diverse targets, each with a reference and nine test molecules, were ranked with each method. The ASV scores for each set were kindly provided by Cresset Software to permit comparison to a highly accurate measure of shape. Quantification using Kendall's Tau, Jaccard Index and RBO metrics revealed no correlation between the rankings produced. While this was not unexpected, as different methods often do give different rankings, but closer match to the scores could potentially have been expected.

A further use of shape-based virtual screening has previously been proposed to prioritise candidates for drug repurposing, as this poses an attractive route for identifying new treatments due to the reduced risk of failure. The original study made use of ROCS to screen an FDA-approved list of drugs to identify potential novel antihistaminics. From this, 23 candidates were purchased for testing, with experimentally validated activity given by nine of these. To see if other shape similarity methods could be used in this way, the experiment was replicated using RGMolSA, KQMolSA and USRCAT. Similar performance is seen for USRCAT to ROCS for the top 1% of ranked hits. RGMolSA assigns high similarity across the board, and therefore suffers slightly lower retrieval than the other methods. KQMolSA did give a wider range of scores, but displayed similar performance to RGMolSA. A different top 23 was retrieved for USRCAT, RGMolSA and KQMolSA compared to ROCS, with just five shared hits between ROCS and USRCAT (four of which were experimentally active), where just one shared hit was identified between ROCS and RGMolSA, and two between ROCS and KQMolSA. Experimental validation would be required to check whether any of the molecules suggested had activity against the H₁ receptor. While the use of shape-similarity can identify molecules that will bind, it does have the drawback of not considering whether the candidate is appropriate in the context of the disease to be treated.

Finally, the utility of RGMolSA as a feature representation for machine learning and statistical models was considered using the Random Matrix Discriminant. The algorithm was originally implemented to predict activity by assessing common chemical motifs between molecules using the Morgan fingerprint. RGMolSA was used instead to see if common shape features could also be identified, permitting novel scaffolds to be identified in the suggested hits. The RGMolSA descriptors were used both in place of the Morgan fingerprint, or as a hybrid 2D-3D descriptor. RGMolSA alone yielded significantly lower AUC values than the use of 2D descriptors, while the hybrid descriptor maintained, and in some cases improved on the 2D fingerprints. The hybrid descriptors may therefore offer a route to include 3D information while retaining the performance of the RMD method. A small study was also completed using the original RMD method to retrieve potential candidates for repurposing to treat COVID-19 infection. From the Drugbank database, 15 hits were identified, five of which had predicted activity in the micromolar range.

Overall, the above studies have identified several areas in which RGMolSA and KQMolSA could be improved. Both methods gave poorer performance in terms of early enrichment compared to more established methods. The inclusion of pharmacophore features within the other methods suggests this could also improve the performance of RGMolSA and KQMolSA. The speed of KQMolSA will also need addressed before the method can be used in full scale virtual screening. The major bottleneck lies in the calculation of the distance between matrices, which could be improved in a number of ways that will be discussed further in **Chapter 7**. The lack of increase in performance where multiple conformers are considered, especially for KQMolSA, was a disappointing result. Without significant distinction between conformers, the descriptor is effectively 2D. Further development of the mathematics underpinning both descriptors may be required to improve this.

Chapter 7. Conclusions and Future Work

This thesis has explored the application of Riemannian geometry to the description of 3D molecular shape. From the underpinning *Riemannian metric*, which captures the geometric properties of the surface, two easy to compare descriptors have been derived. RGMolSA applies the spectrum of the Laplacian to the metric to form a 9-element vector of eigenvalues. KQMolSA uses the theory of Kähler quantization to produce a Hermitian matrix descriptor of shape. Both are alignment free, quick to calculate, and either independent of (RGMolSA) or easy to account for the dependence (KQMolSA) on rotation and translation. The methods have been extensively benchmarked against a range of scenarios of relevance to ligand-based virtual screening. Neither RGMolSA nor KQMolSA offered any improvement, but gave a respectable relative performance for a first round of development.

The theory of Riemannian geometry and its application to molecular shape approximation is introduced in **Chapter 3**. Central to the theory is the *Riemannian metric*, a matrix of positive eigenvalues that describes the distribution of area across the surface. Initial representation of the molecule as its corresponding space filling or CPK model, i.e. a series of intersecting spheres, allows explicit calculation of the metric. The application of Riemannian geometry requires the surface to contain no holes, or mathematically have a genus of 0. To achieve this, small rings such as benzene are replaced by a single sphere with a fixed radius of 2.25Å. This requirement introduces the constraint that macrocycles, that contain a genuine hole, cannot be described. Calculation of the matrix also requires choice of a starting atom. Here this is taken to be the geometric centre of the molecule. Improvements to both methods could be made by increasing the robustness of this choice, routes for which will be discussed in **Section 7.1** The dependence of the metric on the initial orientation and parameterisation of the surface makes direct comparison of two metrics challenging.

Riemannian Geometry for Molecular Surface Approximation (RGMolSA), described in **Chapter 4**, represents the first of two routes proposed to convert the Riemannian metric into an easy to compare descriptor. An approximation of the *spectrum* of the Laplacian can be obtained by applying a Rayleigh-Ritz approximation to the explicit form of the metric. This yields a descriptor of the molecular surface geometry of the form

$$v_s = (10^4/A, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_8), \quad (7.1)$$

where the first element was parameterised by considering the PDE5 inhibitors of known similar shape (Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil) to weight the area term such that it does not dominate

over the shape in the final score. Similarity between two descriptors, bound by 0 (different) and 1 (identical), can be compared using the Bray-Curtis distance. The RGMolSA descriptors, while rotation translation invariant, depend on the choice of base sphere. An initial case study using a set of PDE5 inhibitors of known shape suggested the RGMolSA descriptors to have promise as a shape similarity searching method. Similarity between Sildenafil, Vardenafil and Tadalafil was correctly assigned, and was found to handle comparison of conformers well. Use of the method to rank a set of 43 further PDE5 inhibitors was found to give high similarity scores, especially when multiple conformers were used. RGMolSA was also found to assign scores close to one for enantiomers of the same molecule, with the remaining discrepancy likely due to numerical instability within the method.

Chapter 5 outlines a second descriptor, Kähler Quantization for Molecular Surface Approximation (KQMolSA). Here the Riemannian metric is approximated by a Hermitian matrix descriptor of the form

$$\mathbb{M}_{ij} = \iint_{\mathbb{C}} z^i \bar{z}^j e^{-k\varphi} F(z) \sqrt{-1} dz \wedge d\bar{z}. \quad (7.2)$$

Similarity is retrieved by taking the distance between two descriptors after minimization in the space of all descriptors, weighted to include the difference in area,

$$\text{score}(\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2) = 0.3(A_{\min}/A_{\max}) + 0.7 \frac{1}{1 + d(\mathbb{M}_1, \mathbb{M}_2)}. \quad (7.3)$$

Unlike RGMolSA, there is a dependence on rotation and translation, which is readily accounted for in the distance calculation. The speed of the KQMolSA approach is limited by the need for a minimization calculation when comparing descriptors. Replication of the case study presented for RGMolSA found KQMolSA to give a favourable performance compared to other methods, but slightly less favourably than RGMolSA. Similarity between Sildenafil and Vardenafil was correctly identified, but that of Tadalafil was missed, and again conformers of the same molecule were appropriately considered. These were found to be higher for $k = 1$ than $k = 2$ due to the greater sensitivity of the $k = 2$ descriptor to geometric changes. For the same set of other PDE5 inhibitors considered with RGMolSA, use of multiple conformers per molecule was not found to change outcomes when KQMolSA was used, however KQMolSA was found to be more robust to alignment of molecules. Despite yielding lower scores, the same set of top hits was generally identified with KQMolSA. KQMolSA was also found to effectively handle enantiomers of the same molecule, with the small difference attributed to numerical instability.

A full benchmarking study to compare RGMolSA and KQMolSA to existing shape similarity approaches was outlined in **Chapter 6**. While neither method showed significant improvement over more established approaches, a respectable comparative performance was given for a first round of development. The DUD-E community benchmarking set revealed both methods to give comparable performance to USRCAT, Shape-It and MolSG on average across all 102 targets based on the AUC metric, while a slight drop in ability to rank true actives at the top of a ranked list (based on the BEDROC and EF measures) was observed. Comparison to a wider set of results from the literature revealed that inclusion of pharmacophoric features offered improvement in

similarity assignment, and therefore offers an important future route for development of both RGMolSA and KQMolSA. Possibilities for how this could be achieved will be discussed further in **Section 7.1**. RGMolSA was found to be comparable in speed to several existing methods, including ROCS and eSim, while KQMolSA was found to take significantly longer to compute. Consideration of the importance of conformer sampling for RGMolSA compared to USRCAT was completed using the AKT2, CXCR4 and FABP4 subsets of the DUD-E database. For RGMolSA, consideration of multiple conformers was found to make little difference, while for USRCAT a small improvement in both the BEDROC and AUC scores was observed. For RGMolSA the similarity scores were found to vary for a highly flexible molecule able to adopt a range of shapes, while for KQMolSA these were all assigned roughly equivalent similarity. This lack of differentiation will require improvement in future development. Considering the AstraZeneca test with absolute similarity values available, neither RGMolSA nor KQMolSA were found to replicate the ranking produced, verified using metrics for rank correlation. While this was not unexpected, closer matching to the scores could potentially have been expected. Replication of a drug repositioning study for the H₁ Histamine receptor using ROCS found each of RGMolSA, KQMolSA and USRCAT to identify a slightly different set of top scoring hits, with USRCAT selecting four of the molecules previously experimentally validated as active, while RGMolSA and KQMolSA retrieved none. Finally, the usefulness of RGMolSA as a feature representation was probed using the Random Matrix Discriminant. The replacement of the original 2D descriptors with a 3D shape descriptor would in theory permit a more structurally diverse set of predictions to be made. Use of RGMolSA alone gave reduced recall compared to the Morgan fingerprint, but a hybrid of the two gave successful recall while including shape information. A small study using the original RMD implementation identified 15 potential candidates for the treatment of COVID-19, with 5 giving predicted micromolar activity.

7.1. Future Work

While initial tests of the effectiveness of RGMolSA and KQMolSA showed promise, there are several possible routes to improve both methods.

There are still several errors that occur on occasion within each approach to resolve. Within both RGMolSA and KQMolSA, errors occur when replacing the rings in Memantine-type bridged bicyclic molecules (**Chapter 3, Figure 3.9**). Occurrences of such structures in drug-like molecules are relatively rare, with around 20 appearing out of a total of ~1600 molecules in the Drugbank database. Additionally, macrocycles cannot currently be described (**Chapter 3, Figure 3.3**). Significant further development of the mathematics to permit description of surfaces containing holes, or with genus greater than 1, would offer the ideal route to achieve this. Further development of the ring replacement method, for example accounting for different ring sizes, could be investigated as an interim solution. For RGMolSA numerical error occurs for larger molecules containing few rings due to the dependence on the choice of base sphere. The eigenvalues describing the surface become increasingly small the further from the base sphere, and occasionally reach Python's numerical limits. Currently, such cases are handled by

omitting contributions below a defined threshold. Further developments to improve this include optimising the selection of the base sphere, which will be discussed in more detail below, or increasing the number of eigenvalues in the vector descriptor. The latter does depend on the limits of Mathematica, which was used to produce the explicit integral functions. An alternative would be to use numerical methods to approximate the integrals to permit further expansion of the spectrum, or to choose a different set of initial test functions. These improvements would likely also rectify the discrepancy seen in similarity scores when molecules are aligned prior to their comparison.

Further improvement to both methods, but especially RGMolSA, could be achieved by improving the robustness of the choice of base sphere. Currently, this is taken to be the geometric centre of the coordinates, which occasionally ends up being a terminal atom dependent on the conformer adopted, and can be inconsistent between molecules that are similar, thus leading potential hits to be missed. One possibility would be to select several base spheres, similar to the selection of the reference points in the atomic-distance based method USR [133]. Similarity could then be assessed by either taking the pair with maximum similarity between two sets of descriptors, or by constructing an average vector from the set. Alternatively, graph theory could be used, treating selection of the base sphere as a shortest path problem.

A major limitation identified for the KQMolSA descriptors lies in the speed of the distance calculations. These rely first on the minimisation of the distance between the descriptors under consideration, the speed of which depends on the extent of minimisation needed. This is currently achieved using off the shelf algorithms, which cannot guarantee identification of a global minimum. A possible alternative is the use of gradient descent, however the explicit definition of the function is not trivial.

By far, the most significant improvement that could be made to both methods would be in the inclusion of pharmacophoric features to permit consideration of chemical and shape information. In the retrospective benchmarking study presented in **Chapter 6**, the methods including these features outperformed shape alone, proving this addition to be potentially fruitful. This could be achieved in a number of ways. The molecular electrostatic potential can be used to model the electrostatic energy at points across the surface, indicating areas of positive or negative charge that may interact with the protein, as described in eSim [211]. Alternatively, a similar approach to USRCAT [152] could be taken, where the distribution of relevant features such as hydrogen bond donors and acceptors and aromatic rings across the surface could be considered. The pharmacophore features could also be treated separately, similar to the approach taken in SHAFTS [116], and weighted with the shape similarity to give a hybrid score.

Overall, this thesis has described the application of Riemannian geometry to the approximation of molecular shape. It has been demonstrated that both descriptors derived from the theory capture molecular surface shape in a way suitable for virtual screening. The above suggested improvements would increase the overall robustness and utility of both RGMolSA and KQMolSA. Both methods could be made use of for both traditional virtual screening for real drug discovery projects, and as a feature representation for machine learning. Previously, other

shape descriptors have been used with classification algorithms to predict novel hits [52, 53]. The quick to calculate and alignment free nature of both RGMolSA and KQMolSA would make them suitable for this purpose. This work therefore represents a promising first stage in the application of Riemannian geometry to molecular shape approximation.

Appendix A. Filtering for Drug-Like Molecules

For Ligand-Based Virtual Screening, only small “drug-like“ molecules will be of interest. A script containing the following filters was developed using RDKit [70] to prepare data for screening. These options can be used all together, or individually as needed.

As the shape similarity methods presented require surfaces of genus zero, macrocyclic structures are excluded from consideration. Yudin’s definition of a macrocycle as a ring containing more than 12 atoms is used [307]. This is implemented by using the SMARTS pattern for rings > 12 atoms, and the “GetSubstructMatches” function in RDKit (**Algorithm 2**).

Algorithm 2 Method to remove molecules containing a macrocycle from consideration.

```
macrocycle = “[r12-]”  
for each molecule do  
    if molecule does not include macrocycle then  
        return molecule and ID  
    end if  
end for
```

The parent of any salts in the dataset are then obtained using the “SuperParent” function of the “MolStandardize” module in RDKit. Molecules that are either too small (less than 6 heavy atoms) or too big (molecular weight more than 750Da) for consideration in a small molecule drug discovery campaign are filtered as given by **Algorithm 3**. It is also well-defined which

Algorithm 3 Method to remove molecules outwith the size range considered in small molecule drug discovery.

```
for each molecule do  
    if no. heavy atoms >= 6 and mol. weight <= 750 then  
        return molecule and ID  
    end if  
end for
```

atoms can and cannot be present in a drug molecule. Molecules containing unwanted atoms can be removed as defined by **Algorithm 4**, based on a definition provided by [330].

Several sets of rules also exist that consider whether a molecule is likely to have “drug-like” behaviour. There are many examples which do not conform to these rules of thumb, but they are often still useful to consider. Two of the most common, Lipinski’s Rule of 5 and PAINS, are included here as optional extras. Lipinski’s Rule of 5 [255] defines a drug molecule as likely to have oral bio availability if it breaches no more than 1 of the following: no more than 5 hydrogen

Filtering for Drug-Like Molecules

Algorithm 4 Method to remove non-drug-like molecules from a dataset.

```
ok atoms: H, C, N, O, F, P, S, Cl, Br, I, B
for each molecule do
  no. B = 0
  no. C = 0
  include = True
  for atom in molecule do
    if atom not in ok atoms then
      include = False
    end if
    if atom = B then
      no. B + 1
    end if
    if atom = C then
      no. C + 1
    end if
  end for
  if no. B >= 7 and/or no. C == 0 then
    include = False
  end if
  if include = True then
    return molecule and ID
  end if
end for
```

bond donors (HBDs); no more than 10 hydrogen bond acceptors (HBAs); molecular weight less than 500 Da; octanol-water partition coefficient (LogP) no more than 5. **Algorithm 5** defines a method to retain molecules which follow these conditions. Pan Assay Interference Compounds (or PAINS) [294] are molecules that bind to multiple targets, leading to higher risk of toxicity and side effects. These may also often give false positive results in a high throughput screen. These include substructures such as enones, toxoflavin, quinones and catechols. However, many marketed drugs exist containing these moieties and as such they should be considered with caution. [295] **Algorithm 6** provides a procedure to identify molecules containing PAINS using RDKit.

Algorithm 5 Method to check whether a list of molecules obey Lipinski's Rule of 5

```
for each molecule do
  Molecular Weight
  no. HBDs
  no. HBAs
  LogP
  Check each condition
  if >= 3 conditions = True then
    return molecule and ID
  end if
end for
```

Algorithm 6 Method to check whether a list of molecules contain PAINS substructures

```
obtain filter catalogue
for Each Molecule do
  compare molecule to catalogue
  if no match then
    return molecule and ID
  end if
end for
```

Appendix B. Conformer Generation using RDKit

The ETKDG algorithm [283] for conformer generation (implemented in RDKit [70]) was used alongside the rules proposed by Ebejer and co-workers to determine N , the number of conformers to be computed based on the number of rotatable bonds present [315]. A greater number of rotatable bonds indicates higher flexibility, and thus a higher number of conformers should be considered.

Algorithm 7 Algorithm to compute molecular conformers, where n_{rot} is the number of rotatable bonds and N is the number of conformers to produce.

```
Ensure: version = ETKDGv3
useSmallRingTorsions = True
pruneRmsThresh = 0.1
useRandomCoords = True
for each molecule do
    if use bonds = True then
        get  $n_{rot}$ :
        if  $n_{rots} \leq 7$  then
             $N = 50$ 
        else if  $n_{rot} \leq 12$  then
             $N = 200$ 
        else if  $n_{rot} > 12$  then
             $N = 300$ 
        end if
    else if use bonds = False then
         $N = \text{User Specified}$ 
    end if
    get conformer IDs
    MMFF94s optimise
    Save to SDF
end for
```

Appendix C. Comparing Conformers using RGMolSA - Full Results

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.990	0.988	0.988	0.986	0.905	0.991	0.989	0.994	0.991	0.823
1	0.990	self	0.992	0.989	0.990	0.909	0.989	0.986	0.990	0.987	0.820
2	0.988	0.992	self	0.996	0.995	0.915	0.993	0.990	0.994	0.992	0.816
3	0.988	0.989	0.996	self	0.993	0.917	0.992	0.988	0.993	0.992	0.814
4	0.986	0.990	0.995	0.993	self	0.917	0.990	0.991	0.991	0.99	0.814
5	0.905	0.909	0.915	0.917	0.917	self	0.909	0.909	0.910	0.909	0.743
6	0.991	0.989	0.993	0.992	0.990	0.909	self	0.993	0.995	0.997	0.821
7	0.989	0.986	0.990	0.988	0.991	0.909	0.993	self	0.993	0.994	0.821
8	0.994	0.990	0.994	0.993	0.991	0.910	0.995	0.993	self	0.996	0.820
9	0.991	0.987	0.992	0.992	0.990	0.909	0.997	0.994	0.996	self	0.821
10	0.823	0.820	0.816	0.814	0.814	0.743	0.821	0.821	0.820	0.821	self

Table C.1 Similarity scores between random conformers of Sildenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.000	1.991	1.621	1.484	2.311	1.828	2.563	3.230	2.877	2.520	3.070
1	1.991	0.000	2.161	1.267	1.414	1.079	3.472	2.691	3.220	2.460	2.081
2	1.621	2.161	0.000	2.364	2.603	2.453	2.683	3.553	2.930	2.003	3.332
3	1.484	1.267	2.364	0.000	1.727	0.812	3.195	2.918	3.309	2.754	2.529
4	2.311	1.414	2.603	1.727	0.000	1.437	3.357	2.299	3.597	2.849	2.262
5	1.828	1.079	2.453	0.812	1.437	0.000	3.358	2.914	3.403	2.750	2.448
6	2.563	3.472	2.683	3.195	3.357	3.358	0.000	2.745	1.455	2.643	2.725
7	3.230	2.691	3.553	2.918	2.299	2.914	2.745	0.000	2.512	2.776	1.493
8	2.877	3.220	2.930	3.309	3.597	3.403	1.455	2.512	0.000	2.491	2.332
9	2.520	2.460	2.003	2.754	2.849	2.750	2.643	2.776	2.491	0.000	2.520
10	3.070	2.081	3.332	2.529	2.262	2.448	2.725	1.493	2.332	2.520	0.000

Table C.2 RMSD (in Å) scores between random conformers of Sildenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.985	0.984	0.906	0.907	0.985	0.985	0.984	0.984	0.988	0.988
1	0.985	self	0.997	0.920	0.921	0.997	0.999	0.994	0.997	0.997	0.996
2	0.984	0.997	self	0.921	0.922	0.998	0.997	0.995	0.999	0.995	0.994
3	0.906	0.920	0.921	self	0.998	0.919	0.920	0.920	0.921	0.917	0.916
4	0.907	0.921	0.922	0.998	self	0.921	0.922	0.921	0.922	0.918	0.917
5	0.985	0.997	0.998	0.919	0.921	self	0.997	0.994	0.997	0.996	0.996
6	0.985	0.999	0.997	0.920	0.922	0.997	self	0.994	0.997	0.996	0.995
7	0.984	0.994	0.995	0.920	0.921	0.994	0.994	self	0.996	0.995	0.994
8	0.984	0.997	0.999	0.921	0.922	0.997	0.997	0.996	self	0.995	0.994
9	0.988	0.997	0.995	0.917	0.918	0.996	0.996	0.995	0.995	self	0.997
10	0.988	0.996	0.994	0.916	0.917	0.996	0.995	0.994	0.994	0.997	self

Table C.3 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Sildenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.000	1.782	1.918	1.251	1.280	1.896	1.768	1.339	2.009	1.868	1.507
1	1.782	0.000	1.049	2.356	2.221	1.134	1.098	2.541	1.235	1.281	2.626
2	1.918	1.049	0.000	2.486	2.410	1.035	1.404	2.661	1.047	1.543	2.697
3	1.251	2.356	2.486	0.000	0.914	2.394	2.382	0.957	2.498	2.551	1.245
4	1.280	2.221	2.410	0.914	0.000	2.522	2.473	1.168	2.610	2.597	1.341
5	1.896	1.134	1.035	2.394	2.522	0.000	0.953	2.544	0.384	1.237	2.650
6	1.768	1.098	1.404	2.382	2.473	0.953	0.000	2.353	1.001	0.788	2.473
7	1.339	2.541	2.661	0.957	1.168	2.544	2.353	0.000	2.651	2.488	0.750
8	2.009	1.235	1.047	2.498	2.610	0.384	1.001	2.651	0.000	1.327	2.738
9	1.868	1.281	1.543	2.551	2.597	1.237	0.788	2.488	1.327	0.000	2.358
10	1.507	2.626	2.697	1.245	1.341	2.650	2.473	0.750	2.738	2.358	0.000

Table C.4 RMSD (in Å) scores between low energy conformers of Sildenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.924	0.992	0.986	0.989	0.926	0.918	0.986	0.995	0.991	0.993
1	0.924	self	0.921	0.915	0.915	0.996	0.990	0.913	0.923	0.925	0.920
2	0.992	0.921	self	0.993	0.993	0.923	0.915	0.990	0.994	0.993	0.996
3	0.986	0.915	0.993	self	0.997	0.918	0.908	0.996	0.990	0.988	0.993
4	0.989	0.915	0.993	0.997	self	0.918	0.909	0.996	0.992	0.989	0.995
5	0.926	0.996	0.923	0.918	0.918	self	0.988	0.916	0.925	0.927	0.922
6	0.918	0.990	0.915	0.908	0.909	0.988	self	0.906	0.917	0.920	0.913
7	0.986	0.913	0.990	0.996	0.996	0.916	0.906	self	0.989	0.986	0.992
8	0.995	0.923	0.994	0.990	0.992	0.925	0.917	0.989	self	0.993	0.996
9	0.991	0.925	0.993	0.988	0.989	0.927	0.920	0.986	0.993	self	0.993
10	0.993	0.920	0.996	0.993	0.995	0.922	0.913	0.992	0.996	0.993	self

Table C.5 Similarity scores between random conformers of Vardenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.000	2.205	1.949	1.990	2.350	2.033	2.656	2.124	2.594	2.630	2.800
1	2.205	0.000	1.075	1.223	2.685	1.229	2.967	2.876	3.050	1.961	3.139
2	1.949	1.075	0.000	0.664	2.830	1.031	2.930	3.102	2.735	2.154	3.010
3	1.990	1.223	0.664	0.000	3.026	1.045	2.979	3.224	2.533	2.323	2.784
4	2.350	2.685	2.830	3.026	0.000	2.777	2.295	1.047	3.736	2.771	3.912
5	2.033	1.229	1.031	1.045	2.777	0.000	2.964	3.071	2.763	2.368	2.954
6	2.656	2.967	2.930	2.979	2.295	2.964	0.000	2.540	2.710	3.238	3.025
7	2.124	2.876	3.102	3.224	1.047	3.071	2.540	0.000	3.740	2.841	3.704
8	2.594	3.050	2.735	2.533	3.736	2.763	2.710	3.740	0.000	2.925	1.081
9	2.630	1.961	2.154	2.323	2.771	2.368	3.238	2.841	2.925	0.000	2.706
10	2.800	3.139	3.010	2.784	3.912	2.954	3.025	3.704	1.081	2.706	0.000

Table C.6 RMSD (in Å) scores between random conformers of Vardenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.928	0.987	0.987	0.988	0.986	0.987	0.925	0.925	0.927	0.986
1	0.928	self	0.919	0.919	0.920	0.918	0.919	0.991	0.995	0.997	0.918
2	0.987	0.919	self	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.998	0.914	0.915	0.918	0.998
3	0.987	0.919	0.997	self	0.999	0.997	0.999	0.914	0.915	0.918	0.998
4	0.988	0.920	0.997	0.999	self	0.996	0.999	0.915	0.916	0.919	0.998
5	0.986	0.918	0.997	0.997	0.996	self	0.997	0.914	0.915	0.917	0.998
6	0.987	0.919	0.998	0.999	0.999	0.997	self	0.915	0.916	0.918	0.998
7	0.925	0.991	0.914	0.914	0.915	0.914	0.915	self	0.994	0.993	0.914
8	0.925	0.995	0.915	0.915	0.916	0.915	0.916	0.994	self	0.997	0.915
9	0.927	0.997	0.918	0.918	0.919	0.917	0.918	0.993	0.997	self	0.917
10	0.986	0.918	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.914	0.915	0.917	self

Table C.7 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Vardenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.000	1.916	1.928	2.343	2.348	2.099	2.260	2.570	2.060	2.069	2.332
1	1.916	0.000	1.172	2.604	2.656	2.705	2.589	2.964	1.201	0.994	2.673
2	1.928	1.172	0.000	2.591	2.454	2.893	2.513	2.879	1.356	0.967	2.782
3	2.343	2.604	2.591	0.000	1.144	1.034	0.821	1.244	2.964	2.602	1.074
4	2.348	2.656	2.454	1.144	0.000	1.510	0.875	1.111	3.019	2.414	1.393
5	2.099	2.705	2.893	1.034	1.510	0.000	1.183	1.515	3.080	2.766	0.701
6	2.260	2.589	2.513	0.821	0.875	1.183	0.000	1.404	2.969	2.477	1.158
7	2.570	2.964	2.879	1.244	1.111	1.515	1.404	0.000	2.995	2.815	1.422
8	2.060	1.201	1.356	2.964	3.019	3.080	2.969	2.995	0.000	1.496	3.118
9	2.069	0.994	0.967	2.602	2.414	2.766	2.477	2.815	1.496	0.000	2.610
10	2.332	2.673	2.782	1.074	1.393	0.701	1.158	1.422	3.118	2.610	0.000

Table C.8 RMSD (in Å) scores between low energy conformers of Vardenafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.978	0.978	0.979	0.965	0.979	0.981	0.983	0.981	0.983	0.971
1	0.978	self	1	0.998	0.985	0.995	0.982	0.980	0.981	0.980	0.972
2	0.978	1	self	0.998	0.985	0.995	0.981	0.980	0.981	0.980	0.972
3	0.979	0.998	0.998	self	0.984	0.994	0.982	0.980	0.981	0.980	0.972
4	0.965	0.985	0.985	0.984	self	0.984	0.979	0.978	0.979	0.978	0.978
5	0.979	0.995	0.995	0.994	0.984	self	0.984	0.982	0.983	0.982	0.973
6	0.981	0.982	0.981	0.982	0.979	0.984	self	0.998	1	0.998	0.988
7	0.983	0.980	0.980	0.980	0.978	0.982	0.998	self	0.998	1	0.987
8	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.979	0.983	1	0.998	self	0.998	0.988
9	0.983	0.980	0.980	0.980	0.978	0.982	0.998	1	0.998	self	0.987
10	0.971	0.972	0.972	0.972	0.978	0.973	0.988	0.987	0.988	0.987	self

Table C.9 Similarity scores between random conformers of Tadalafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.000	1.263	1.262	1.061	1.701	1.082	1.427	1.302	0.871	1.302	1.413
1	1.263	0.000	0.000	1.960	2.390	0.415	1.968	1.704	1.448	1.704	1.605
2	1.262	0.000	0.000	1.960	2.390	0.415	1.968	1.704	1.448	1.704	1.605
3	1.061	1.960	1.960	0.000	1.292	1.854	1.347	1.731	1.148	1.731	1.781
4	1.701	2.390	2.390	1.292	0.000	2.283	1.247	1.512	1.587	1.512	1.908
5	1.082	0.415	0.415	1.854	2.283	0.000	1.870	1.584	1.278	1.584	1.575
6	1.427	1.968	1.968	1.347	1.247	1.870	0.000	1.419	1.255	1.419	1.399
7	1.302	1.704	1.704	1.731	1.512	1.584	1.419	0.000	1.641	0.000	1.010
8	0.871	1.448	1.448	1.148	1.587	1.278	1.255	1.641	0.000	1.641	1.838
9	1.302	1.704	1.704	1.731	1.512	1.584	1.419	0.000	1.641	0.000	1.010
10	1.413	1.605	1.605	1.781	1.908	1.575	1.399	1.010	1.838	1.010	0.000

Table C.10 RMSD (in Å) scores between random conformers of Tadalafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.978	0.979
1	0.978	self	1	1	1	0.999	1	1	1	0.999	0.999
2	0.978	1	self	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.998
3	0.978	1	1	self	1	0.999	1	1	1	0.999	0.999
4	0.978	1	1	1	self	1	1	1	1	1	0.998
5	0.978	0.999	1	0.999	1	self	1	1	0.999	1	0.998
6	0.978	1	1	1	1	1	self	1	1	1	0.998
7	0.978	1	1	1	1	1	1	self	1	1	0.998
8	0.978	1	1	1	1	0.999	1	1	self	0.999	0.998
9	0.978	0.999	1	0.999	1	1	1	1	0.999	self	0.998
10	0.979	0.999	0.998	0.999	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	self

Table C.11 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Tadalafil.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	0.000	1.706	1.263	1.706	1.262	1.262	1.263	1.706	1.706	1.262	1.042
1	1.706	0.000	2.386	0.000	2.386	2.386	2.386	0.000	0.001	2.386	1.250
2	1.263	2.386	0.000	2.386	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.386	2.386	0.001	1.952
3	1.706	0.000	2.386	0.000	2.386	2.386	2.386	0.000	0.001	2.386	1.250
4	1.262	2.386	0.000	2.386	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.386	2.386	0.001	1.952
5	1.262	2.386	0.000	2.386	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.386	2.386	0.001	1.952
6	1.263	2.386	0.000	2.386	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.386	2.386	0.001	1.952
7	1.706	0.000	2.386	0.000	2.386	2.386	2.386	0.000	0.001	2.386	1.250
8	1.706	0.001	2.386	0.001	2.386	2.386	2.386	0.001	0.000	2.386	1.250
9	1.262	2.386	0.001	2.386	0.001	0.001	0.001	2.386	2.386	0.000	1.952
10	1.042	1.250	1.952	1.250	1.952	1.952	1.952	1.250	1.250	1.952	0.000

Table C.12 RMSD (in Å) score between low energy conformers of Tadalafil.

Appendix D. Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using RGMolSA - Full Results

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using RGMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.450	0.509	0.339	0.433	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.964	0.874	0.843	0.894	0	308.73	10.30
11993171	0.073	0.085	0.052	0.070	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.034	0.039	0.024	0.032	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.958	0.901	0.806	0.888	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.930	0.842	0.878	0.883	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.964	0.899	0.817	0.893	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.487	0.550	0.382	0.473	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.924	0.836	0.884	0.881	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.935	0.846	0.873	0.885	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.932	0.893	0.794	0.873	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.943	0.914	0.789	0.882	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.926	0.838	0.881	0.882	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.071	0.083	0.051	0.068	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.613	0.695	0.478	0.595	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.798	0.803	0.722	0.774	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.923	0.835	0.885	0.881	0	283.22	9.62
45486519	0.304	0.352	0.240	0.299	8	271.41	9.60
11992741	0.657	0.736	0.530	0.641	0	292.16	9.60
11992528	0.916	0.829	0.892	0.879	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.078	0.091	0.056	0.075	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.950	0.910	0.797	0.886	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.182	0.213	0.135	0.177	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.481	0.543	0.376	0.467	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.153	0.178	0.112	0.148	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.948	0.910	0.792	0.883	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.930	0.842	0.878	0.883	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.925	0.838	0.883	0.882	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.926	0.838	0.882	0.882	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.762	0.678	0.841	0.760	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.499	0.563	0.395	0.486	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.955	0.879	0.845	0.893	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.781	0.730	0.838	0.783	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.923	0.835	0.885	0.881	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.914	0.827	0.895	0.879	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.384	0.437	0.292	0.371	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.964	0.894	0.820	0.893	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.962	0.903	0.810	0.892	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.892	0.837	0.827	0.852	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.500	0.564	0.395	0.486	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.916	0.828	0.892	0.879	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.937	0.848	0.871	0.885	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.943	0.865	0.858	0.889	1	271.48	7.79

Table D.1 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case below where alignment is used.

ID	S	V	T	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.504	0.521	0.523	0.516	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.887	0.855	0.848	0.863	0	308.73	10.30
11993171	0.084	0.087	0.089	0.087	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.039	0.041	0.041	0.040	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.907	0.886	0.861	0.885	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.855	0.823	0.833	0.837	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.906	0.879	0.859	0.881	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.544	0.562	0.575	0.560	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.849	0.817	0.831	0.832	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.859	0.827	0.836	0.841	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.915	0.889	0.877	0.894	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.919	0.899	0.874	0.897	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.851	0.818	0.831	0.833	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.082	0.086	0.087	0.085	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.685	0.710	0.706	0.700	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.815	0.796	0.835	0.815	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.848	0.816	0.830	0.831	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.730	0.751	0.762	0.748	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.348	0.361	0.374	0.361	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.842	0.809	0.826	0.826	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.090	0.094	0.095	0.093	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.917	0.895	0.870	0.894	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.210	0.219	0.223	0.217	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.537	0.555	0.567	0.553	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.176	0.183	0.185	0.181	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.918	0.895	0.871	0.895	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.855	0.822	0.832	0.836	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.851	0.818	0.832	0.834	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.851	0.819	0.832	0.834	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.691	0.659	0.666	0.672	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.557	0.576	0.591	0.575	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.891	0.860	0.868	0.873	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.759	0.723	0.734	0.739	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.848	0.815	0.828	0.830	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.840	0.808	0.827	0.825	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.432	0.448	0.454	0.445	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.901	0.875	0.854	0.877	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.911	0.886	0.864	0.887	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.865	0.829	0.865	0.853	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.558	0.576	0.591	0.575	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.841	0.809	0.827	0.826	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.861	0.829	0.836	0.842	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.877	0.846	0.862	0.862	1	271.48	7.79

Table D.2 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered, with the query conformers obtained from the bound crystal structure. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case below where alignment is used.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using RGMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	ΔS	V	ΔV	T	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.006	0.444	0.522	-0.013	0.339	-0.011	0.433	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.962	0.002	0.882	-0.008	0.843	0.001	0.894	0	308.73	10.30
11993171	0.077	-0.004	0.520	-0.435	0.052	-0.296	0.070	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.469	-0.435	0.516	-0.477	0.024	-0.118	0.032	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.953	0.005	0.906	-0.005	0.806	-0.004	0.888	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.929	0.001	0.842	0.000	0.878	0.000	0.883	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.963	0.001	0.900	-0.001	0.817	0.002	0.893	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.490	-0.003	0.553	-0.003	0.382	-0.010	0.473	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.922	0.002	0.834	0.002	0.884	0.338	0.881	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.934	0.001	0.847	-0.001	0.873	0.337	0.885	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.884	0.048	0.910	-0.017	0.794	0.007	0.873	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.943	0.000	0.915	-0.001	0.789	0.330	0.882	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.922	0.004	0.842	-0.004	0.881	0.365	0.882	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.455	-0.384	0.003	0.080	0.051	-0.296	0.068	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.963	-0.350	0.903	-0.208	0.478	0.007	0.595	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.723	0.075	0.829	-0.026	0.722	-0.206	0.774	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.919	0.004	0.831	0.004	0.885	0.345	0.881	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.937	-0.280	0.850	-0.114	0.530	-0.003	0.641	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.019	0.285	0.697	-0.345	0.240	-0.163	0.299	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.922	-0.006	0.830	-0.001	0.892	0.348	0.879	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.468	-0.390	0.530	-0.439	0.056	-0.298	0.075	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.950	0.000	0.908	0.002	0.797	0.337	0.886	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.466	-0.284	0.519	-0.306	0.135	-0.213	0.177	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.496	-0.015	0.544	-0.001	0.376	-0.013	0.467	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.477	-0.324	0.179	-0.001	0.112	-0.248	0.148	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.944	0.004	0.911	-0.001	0.792	0.000	0.883	0	344.25	9.420
11993435	0.930	0.000	0.843	-0.001	0.878	0.339	0.883	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.925	0.000	0.838	0.000	0.883	0.339	0.882	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.925	0.001	0.838	0.000	0.882	0.339	0.882	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.891	-0.129	0.706	-0.028	0.841	0.414	0.760	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.096	0.403	0.554	0.009	0.395	0.008	0.486	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.952	0.003	0.883	-0.004	0.845	0.000	0.893	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.627	0.154	0.151	0.579	0.838	0.013	0.783	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.925	-0.002	0.838	-0.003	0.885	0.344	0.881	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.914	0.000	0.828	-0.001	0.895	0.000	0.879	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.378	0.006	0.428	0.009	0.292	0.001	0.371	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.922	0.042	0.898	-0.004	0.820	0.374	0.893	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.963	-0.001	0.904	-0.001	0.810	-0.001	0.892	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.849	0.043	0.840	-0.003	0.827	0.192	0.852	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.014	0.486	0.555	0.009	0.395	0.004	0.486	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.915	0.001	0.829	-0.001	0.892	0.338	0.879	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.937	0.000	0.848	0.000	0.871	0.344	0.885	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.938	0.005	0.864	0.001	0.858	0.365	0.889	1	271.48	7.79

Table D.3 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered. Here the PDE5 inhibitors are aligned to each query in turn prior to similarity calculation. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between the scores obtained with and without alignment to each query. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case above where alignment is not used.

ID	S	ΔS	V	ΔV	T	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.516	-0.012	0.541	-0.020	0.523	0.305	0.516	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.320	0.567	0.854	0.001	0.848	0.002	0.863	0	308.73	10.30
11993171	0.526	-0.442	0.542	-0.455	0.089	-0.447	0.087	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.237	-0.198	0.238	-0.197	0.041	-0.494	0.040	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.918	-0.011	0.893	-0.007	0.861	0.199	0.885	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.325	0.530	0.820	0.003	0.833	0.474	0.837	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.910	-0.004	0.875	0.004	0.859	0.000	0.881	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.548	-0.004	0.563	-0.001	0.575	-0.001	0.560	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.848	0.001	0.815	0.002	0.831	0.003	0.832	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.331	0.528	0.825	0.002	0.836	0.003	0.841	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.899	0.016	0.767	0.122	0.877	-0.034	0.894	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.920	-0.001	0.898	0.001	0.874	0.003	0.897	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.846	0.005	0.817	0.001	0.831	0.003	0.833	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.514	-0.432	0.532	-0.446	0.087	0.075	0.085	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.910	-0.225	0.884	-0.174	0.706	-0.153	0.700	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.797	0.018	0.823	-0.027	0.835	0.107	0.815	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.847	0.001	0.819	-0.003	0.830	0.469	0.831	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.334	0.396	0.349	0.402	0.762	-0.070	0.748	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.399	-0.051	0.841	-0.480	0.374	-0.233	0.361	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.837	0.005	0.804	0.005	0.826	0.063	0.826	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.519	-0.429	0.112	-0.018	0.095	-0.059	0.093	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.918	-0.001	0.894	0.001	0.870	0.002	0.894	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.528	-0.318	0.537	-0.318	0.223	-0.318	0.217	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.534	0.003	0.555	0.000	0.567	0.495	0.553	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.526	-0.350	0.546	-0.363	0.185	-0.366	0.181	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.915	0.003	0.133	0.762	0.871	-0.004	0.895	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.856	-0.001	0.821	0.001	0.832	0.521	0.836	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.334	0.517	0.355	0.463	0.832	0.002	0.834	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.851	0.000	0.820	-0.001	0.832	0.000	0.834	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.715	-0.024	0.830	-0.171	0.666	0.179	0.672	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.552	0.005	0.573	0.003	0.591	0.004	0.575	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.891	0.000	0.658	0.202	0.868	0.193	0.873	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.772	-0.013	0.785	-0.062	0.734	0.688	0.739	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.851	-0.003	0.818	-0.003	0.828	-0.003	0.830	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.838	0.002	0.807	0.001	0.827	0.042	0.825	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.105	0.327	0.444	0.004	0.454	0.001	0.445	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.910	-0.009	0.870	0.005	0.854	0.341	0.877	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.909	0.002	0.699	0.187	0.864	0.001	0.887	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.888	-0.023	0.312	0.517	0.865	0.027	0.853	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.553	0.005	0.566	0.010	0.591	0.470	0.575	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.335	0.506	0.807	0.002	0.827	0.002	0.826	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.862	-0.001	0.831	-0.002	0.836	0.002	0.842	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.833	0.044	0.802	0.044	0.862	0.041	0.862	1	271.48	7.79

Table D.4 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered. Here the PDE5 inhibitors are aligned to each query in turn prior to similarity calculation. ΔS , ΔV and ΔT are the difference between the scores obtained with and without alignment to each query. The query conformers are taken from the bound crystal structure in this instance. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case above where alignment is not used.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using RGMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Average	Max S	Max V	Max T	No. Confs	pIC50
11993170	0.551	0.562	0.450	0.521	0.970	0.939	0.841	278	10.40
11992634	0.550	0.563	0.448	0.520	0.969	0.942	0.872	296	10.30
11993171	0.600	0.615	0.489	0.568	0.969	0.937	0.898	300	10.30
45486504	0.553	0.570	0.446	0.523	0.970	0.939	0.837	275	10.22
11993561	0.773	0.775	0.650	0.733	0.963	0.964	0.884	298	10.16
11992831	0.781	0.738	0.733	0.750	0.964	0.897	0.934	267	10.16
11993465	0.757	0.754	0.632	0.714	0.965	0.956	0.890	300	10.10
11992739	0.742	0.713	0.685	0.713	0.960	0.887	0.935	275	10.05
11992635	0.752	0.723	0.694	0.723	0.958	0.888	0.916	264	10.00
11992529	0.786	0.749	0.720	0.752	0.967	0.903	0.924	293	9.96
11993562	0.762	0.761	0.639	0.721	0.960	0.963	0.908	300	9.89
11993463	0.775	0.783	0.645	0.734	0.950	0.966	0.881	300	9.89
11992740	0.739	0.713	0.684	0.712	0.957	0.887	0.923	285	9.85
11993342	0.558	0.566	0.466	0.530	0.970	0.940	0.917	300	9.85
11993365	0.743	0.742	0.621	0.702	0.963	0.959	0.910	298	9.82
45486496	0.754	0.720	0.696	0.724	0.962	0.904	0.920	294	9.77
11992742	0.727	0.702	0.677	0.702	0.960	0.887	0.900	280	9.62
11992741	0.777	0.742	0.716	0.745	0.949	0.876	0.931	293	9.60
45486519	0.669	0.662	0.601	0.644	0.951	0.872	0.917	279	9.60
11992528	0.729	0.702	0.673	0.701	0.960	0.887	0.896	292	9.59
45486497	0.569	0.584	0.468	0.540	0.970	0.939	0.891	291	9.55
45486572	0.762	0.764	0.642	0.723	0.960	0.963	0.873	299	9.50
45486514	0.529	0.545	0.434	0.503	0.968	0.940	0.927	299	9.50
45486550	0.738	0.707	0.687	0.711	0.962	0.887	0.933	291	9.47
45486581	0.555	0.571	0.455	0.527	0.970	0.939	0.876	279	9.44
45486498	0.764	0.773	0.638	0.725	0.953	0.965	0.897	300	9.42
11993435	0.770	0.734	0.713	0.739	0.964	0.898	0.915	278	9.40
45486564	0.744	0.718	0.688	0.717	0.961	0.889	0.919	290	9.27
45486501	0.724	0.701	0.673	0.699	0.959	0.888	0.940	287	9.26
11992443	0.794	0.757	0.715	0.755	0.954	0.897	0.913	270	9.17
45486527	0.722	0.693	0.675	0.697	0.957	0.881	0.920	271	9.17
45486505	0.750	0.724	0.695	0.723	0.965	0.893	0.939	294	9.15
11992631	0.774	0.736	0.711	0.740	0.945	0.885	0.931	292	9.11
45486574	0.719	0.698	0.666	0.694	0.961	0.892	0.933	285	9.06
11992531	0.739	0.708	0.689	0.712	0.956	0.881	0.934	273	8.98
11992827	0.780	0.743	0.694	0.739	0.964	0.915	0.934	299	8.96
11993437	0.742	0.745	0.621	0.703	0.965	0.958	0.904	300	8.93
11993560	0.767	0.765	0.643	0.725	0.961	0.958	0.917	299	8.78
11993243	0.805	0.765	0.731	0.767	0.958	0.890	0.933	281	8.59
45486513	0.737	0.711	0.688	0.712	0.961	0.886	0.942	277	8.59
45486549	0.708	0.684	0.659	0.684	0.957	0.884	0.946	276	8.53
45486571	0.765	0.731	0.703	0.733	0.945	0.870	0.918	294	8.40
45486511	0.633	0.629	0.577	0.613	0.957	0.875	0.934	290	7.79

Table D.5 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T). The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

ID	S	V	T	Average	Max S	Max V	Max T	No. Confs	pIC50
11993170	0.565	0.561	0.557	0.561	0.951	0.920	0.899	278	10.40
11992634	0.564	0.562	0.561	0.562	0.954	0.925	0.926	296	10.30
11993171	0.616	0.613	0.609	0.613	0.948	0.918	0.899	300	10.30
45486504	0.570	0.568	0.564	0.568	0.951	0.919	0.899	275	10.22
11993561	0.776	0.770	0.754	0.766	0.964	0.951	0.908	298	10.16
11992831	0.749	0.729	0.743	0.740	0.910	0.878	0.915	267	10.16
11993465	0.756	0.749	0.734	0.746	0.962	0.940	0.905	300	10.10
11992739	0.720	0.705	0.721	0.715	0.899	0.868	0.896	275	10.05
11992635	0.731	0.716	0.732	0.726	0.900	0.869	0.911	264	10.00
11992529	0.756	0.738	0.748	0.747	0.915	0.884	0.899	293	9.96
11993562	0.763	0.757	0.740	0.753	0.960	0.949	0.905	300	9.89
11993463	0.788	0.781	0.764	0.778	0.963	0.959	0.913	300	9.89
11992740	0.715	0.702	0.717	0.711	0.899	0.868	0.890	285	9.85
11993342	0.575	0.569	0.567	0.570	0.955	0.931	0.910	300	9.85
11993365	0.743	0.737	0.720	0.733	0.961	0.943	0.906	298	9.82
45486496	0.725	0.708	0.720	0.718	0.916	0.884	0.899	294	9.77
11992742	0.706	0.693	0.709	0.703	0.900	0.869	0.891	280	9.62
11992741	0.750	0.732	0.743	0.742	0.900	0.867	0.892	293	9.60
45486519	0.661	0.654	0.672	0.662	0.884	0.853	0.892	279	9.60
11992528	0.709	0.694	0.710	0.704	0.899	0.868	0.891	292	9.59
45486497	0.584	0.580	0.577	0.580	0.957	0.924	0.912	291	9.55
45486572	0.764	0.758	0.741	0.754	0.964	0.951	0.905	299	9.50
45486514	0.552	0.552	0.552	0.552	0.956	0.924	0.923	299	9.50
45486550	0.718	0.702	0.719	0.713	0.899	0.868	0.874	291	9.47
45486581	0.576	0.573	0.569	0.572	0.958	0.922	0.907	279	9.44
45486498	0.772	0.766	0.749	0.762	0.963	0.959	0.913	300	9.42
11993435	0.746	0.727	0.741	0.738	0.910	0.878	0.897	278	9.37
45486564	0.731	0.716	0.734	0.727	0.901	0.872	0.893	290	9.27
45486501	0.720	0.705	0.724	0.716	0.900	0.869	0.904	287	9.26
11992443	0.762	0.744	0.751	0.752	0.896	0.887	0.942	270	9.17
45486527	0.699	0.684	0.703	0.695	0.893	0.862	0.872	271	9.17
45486505	0.728	0.712	0.729	0.723	0.906	0.874	0.903	294	9.15
11992631	0.747	0.729	0.738	0.738	0.898	0.873	0.888	292	9.11
45486574	0.700	0.687	0.704	0.697	0.904	0.873	0.900	285	9.06
11992531	0.709	0.693	0.712	0.705	0.894	0.863	0.876	273	8.98
11992827	0.750	0.731	0.736	0.739	0.927	0.897	0.915	299	8.96
11993437	0.741	0.736	0.721	0.733	0.965	0.943	0.918	300	8.93
11993560	0.765	0.758	0.741	0.755	0.961	0.942	0.905	299	8.78
11993243	0.775	0.754	0.761	0.763	0.908	0.871	0.898	281	8.59
45486513	0.718	0.703	0.722	0.715	0.904	0.873	0.880	277	8.59
45486549	0.689	0.675	0.694	0.686	0.896	0.865	0.886	276	8.53
45486571	0.741	0.723	0.734	0.733	0.911	0.877	0.912	294	8.40
45486511	0.638	0.631	0.652	0.641	0.886	0.855	0.903	290	7.79

Table D.6 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T). The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries. The query conformers are taken from the bound crystal structure in this instance.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using RGMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Average	Max S	Max V	Max T	pIC50
11993170	0.545	0.545	0.503	0.531	0.970	0.970	0.949	10.40
11992634	0.551	0.549	0.504	0.535	0.972	0.969	0.952	10.30
11993171	0.592	0.592	0.548	0.578	0.970	0.970	0.951	10.30
45486504	0.555	0.554	0.505	0.538	0.970	0.970	0.950	10.22
11993561	0.721	0.728	0.701	0.717	0.968	0.969	0.942	10.16
11992831	0.706	0.693	0.738	0.713	0.962	0.954	0.958	10.16
11993465	0.709	0.712	0.682	0.701	0.967	0.970	0.943	10.10
11992739	0.684	0.674	0.705	0.688	0.960	0.957	0.954	10.05
11992635	0.693	0.683	0.714	0.697	0.959	0.958	0.948	10.00
11992529	0.717	0.705	0.736	0.719	0.965	0.972	0.953	9.96
11993562	0.711	0.716	0.688	0.705	0.968	0.968	0.937	9.89
11993463	0.723	0.733	0.700	0.719	0.966	0.977	0.942	9.89
11992740	0.684	0.674	0.704	0.687	0.961	0.966	0.957	9.85
11993342	0.550	0.548	0.514	0.537	0.970	0.969	0.952	9.85
11993365	0.696	0.700	0.670	0.689	0.970	0.968	0.943	9.82
45486496	0.691	0.680	0.711	0.694	0.964	0.962	0.953	9.77
11992742	0.675	0.665	0.695	0.678	0.961	0.953	0.959	9.62
11992741	0.711	0.699	0.731	0.714	0.958	0.973	0.956	9.60
45486519	0.639	0.633	0.639	0.637	0.952	0.954	0.968	9.60
11992528	0.675	0.665	0.693	0.677	0.961	0.963	0.963	9.59
45486497	0.567	0.566	0.523	0.552	0.971	0.970	0.950	9.55
45486572	0.712	0.717	0.691	0.707	0.968	0.967	0.937	9.50
45486514	0.535	0.533	0.490	0.519	0.970	0.971	0.952	9.50
45486550	0.680	0.669	0.704	0.684	0.962	0.951	0.964	9.47
45486581	0.554	0.554	0.510	0.539	0.970	0.969	0.947	9.44
45486498	0.716	0.725	0.693	0.711	0.966	0.972	0.941	9.42
11993435	0.703	0.692	0.728	0.708	0.964	0.963	0.967	9.37
45486564	0.688	0.678	0.709	0.692	0.961	0.948	0.968	9.27
45486501	0.673	0.664	0.694	0.677	0.961	0.954	0.968	9.26
11992443	0.725	0.713	0.737	0.725	0.957	0.972	0.956	9.17
45486527	0.666	0.656	0.691	0.671	0.958	0.961	0.968	9.17
45486505	0.692	0.683	0.716	0.697	0.962	0.955	0.967	9.15
11992631	0.706	0.694	0.725	0.708	0.958	0.972	0.957	9.11
45486574	0.671	0.662	0.689	0.674	0.962	0.958	0.960	9.06
11992531	0.680	0.669	0.705	0.685	0.957	0.963	0.962	8.98
11992827	0.712	0.701	0.718	0.710	0.968	0.973	0.951	8.96
11993437	0.700	0.704	0.673	0.692	0.970	0.970	0.942	8.93
11993560	0.716	0.720	0.691	0.709	0.968	0.972	0.941	8.78
11993243	0.730	0.718	0.748	0.732	0.960	0.968	0.964	8.59
45486513	0.681	0.672	0.706	0.686	0.960	0.953	0.969	8.59
45486549	0.658	0.649	0.679	0.662	0.964	0.952	0.968	8.53
45486571	0.701	0.690	0.720	0.704	0.954	0.969	0.958	8.40
45486511	0.610	0.603	0.612	0.608	0.958	0.950	0.967	7.79

Table D.7 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of both the 43 PDE5 inhibitors and Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T). The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

Appendix E. KQMolSA Development - Full Results

Figure E.1 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target P00489 when d_r and d_θ are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.2 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target POA017 when d_r and d_θ are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.3 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target Q9BJF5 when d_r and d_{θ} are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.4 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target O15530 when d_r and d_{θ} are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.5 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target P07900 when d_r and d_θ are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.6 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target P24182 when d_r and d_{θ} are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.7 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target P25440 when d_r and d_θ are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.8 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target Q92731 when d_r and d_θ are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.9 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target P68400 when d_r and d_θ are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.10 Heat maps for the correlation matrix showing variation in similarity scores obtained for target Q08499 when d_r and d_{θ} are varied between 10 and 200 (using $k = 1$ descriptors).

Figure E.11 Heat maps of the similarity scores obtained across the 9 test molecules compared to the reference for each target when x is varied between 0 and 0.5, and y is varied between 1 and 0.5 (using $k = 1$). Green indicates higher similarity scores.

Appendix F. Comparing Conformers using KQMolSA - Full Results

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.861	0.744	0.753	0.869	0.709	0.908	0.967	0.801	0.787	0.754
1	0.860	self	0.826	0.839	0.969	0.780	0.925	0.870	0.907	0.884	0.842
2	0.744	0.827	self	0.970	0.815	0.918	0.792	0.756	0.895	0.906	0.966
3	0.753	0.840	0.957	self	0.830	0.902	0.804	0.765	0.905	0.928	0.977
4	0.872	0.958	0.816	0.830	self	0.772	0.954	0.889	0.890	0.873	0.832
5	0.709	0.780	0.918	0.902	0.772	self	0.751	0.719	0.835	0.852	0.898
6	0.907	0.927	0.792	0.805	0.954	0.751	self	0.924	0.862	0.845	0.806
7	0.968	0.870	0.756	0.765	0.889	0.719	0.926	self	0.814	0.799	0.767
8	0.800	0.905	0.890	0.908	0.894	0.835	0.861	0.815	self	0.965	0.914
9	0.786	0.886	0.908	0.933	0.876	0.852	0.845	0.800	0.956	self	0.929
10	0.755	0.843	0.950	0.989	0.833	0.898	0.806	0.767	0.915	0.926	self

Table F.1 Similarity scores between random conformers of Sildenafil for $k = 1$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.858	0.736	0.759	0.701	0.660	0.766	0.826	0.763	0.756	0.705
1	0.842	self	0.798	0.839	0.890	0.716	0.732	0.849	0.731	0.806	0.777
2	0.664	0.769	self	0.890	0.738	0.869	0.754	0.726	0.805	0.839	0.704
3	0.747	0.817	0.925	self	0.786	0.880	0.722	0.723	0.755	0.857	0.803
4	0.810	0.906	0.743	0.803	self	0.734	0.785	0.881	0.705	0.802	0.778
5	0.715	0.717	0.843	0.785	0.589	self	0.685	0.708	0.699	0.715	0.763
6	0.690	0.691	0.706	0.687	0.698	0.672	self	0.757	0.836	0.745	0.697
7	0.890	0.807	0.695	0.770	0.851	0.672	0.758	self	0.728	0.783	0.752
8	0.672	0.749	0.759	0.726	0.735	0.700	0.836	0.754	self	0.815	0.751
9	0.759	0.794	0.878	0.833	0.770	0.743	0.764	0.750	0.798	self	0.852
10	0.720	0.778	0.795	0.865	0.769	0.778	0.700	0.750	0.742	0.844	self

Table F.2 Similarity scores between random conformers of Sildenafil for $k = 2$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.714	0.708	0.704	0.718	0.716	0.712	0.711	0.709	0.858	0.856
1	0.714	self	0.963	0.968	0.988	0.960	0.969	0.961	0.985	0.790	0.791
2	0.708	0.942	self	0.979	0.974	0.935	0.968	0.976	0.970	0.780	0.782
3	0.704	0.965	0.986	self	0.964	0.965	0.970	0.978	0.984	0.776	0.778
4	0.718	0.987	0.974	0.964	self	0.988	0.981	0.980	0.978	0.794	0.796
5	0.716	0.970	0.948	0.964	0.994	self	0.951	0.950	0.955	0.792	0.793
6	0.711	0.975	0.963	0.974	0.983	0.948	self	0.946	0.984	0.785	0.787
7	0.711	0.947	0.911	0.977	0.980	0.940	0.980	self	0.934	0.782	0.785
8	0.709	0.949	0.952	0.977	0.976	0.954	0.967	0.946	self	0.782	0.785
9	0.858	0.789	0.781	0.776	0.794	0.793	0.785	0.784	0.783	self	0.964
10	0.856	0.790	0.782	0.777	0.796	0.794	0.788	0.787	0.784	0.982	self

Table F.3 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Sildenafil for $k = 1$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.700	0.687	0.574	0.710	0.707	0.712	0.712	0.700	0.864	0.870
1	0.718	self	0.958	0.913	0.941	0.954	0.973	0.783	0.941	0.771	0.759
2	0.709	0.879	self	0.798	0.562	0.939	0.951	0.776	0.955	0.763	0.762
3	0.706	0.554	0.879	self	0.965	0.783	0.556	0.747	0.919	0.577	0.718
4	0.692	0.723	0.729	0.965	self	0.730	0.743	0.826	0.713	0.681	0.684
5	0.720	0.955	0.961	0.927	0.822	self	0.935	0.748	0.953	0.779	0.757
6	0.715	0.984	0.958	0.965	0.825	0.937	self	0.837	0.937	0.767	0.767
7	0.674	0.748	0.674	0.967	0.813	0.681	0.685	self	0.704	0.670	0.732
8	0.697	0.957	0.982	0.843	0.859	0.968	0.965	0.738	self	0.771	0.755
9	0.850	0.776	0.761	0.742	0.767	0.772	0.773	0.701	0.764	self	0.891
10	0.825	0.766	0.763	0.738	0.779	0.762	0.768	0.739	0.755	0.983	self

Table F.4 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Sildenafil for $k = 2$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.753	0.930	0.775	0.772	0.775	0.780	0.715	0.793	0.977	0.764
1	0.753	self	0.789	0.946	0.952	0.927	0.905	0.912	0.921	0.764	0.972
2	0.930	0.789	self	0.816	0.812	0.815	0.820	0.746	0.837	0.949	0.802
3	0.775	0.947	0.816	self	0.993	0.982	0.983	0.879	0.966	0.787	0.971
4	0.772	0.952	0.812	0.993	self	0.993	0.981	0.884	0.960	0.784	0.977
5	0.775	0.933	0.815	0.992	0.981	self	0.915	0.878	0.963	0.787	0.970
6	0.780	0.918	0.820	0.984	0.981	0.941	self	0.873	0.968	0.792	0.966
7	0.715	0.916	0.746	0.879	0.884	0.880	0.874	self	0.855	0.724	0.898
8	0.793	0.922	0.837	0.966	0.960	0.962	0.968	0.855	self	0.806	0.943
9	0.978	0.764	0.949	0.787	0.784	0.787	0.792	0.724	0.806	self	0.775
10	0.764	0.970	0.802	0.971	0.977	0.969	0.964	0.898	0.942	0.775	self

Table F.5 Similarity scores between random conformers of Vardenafil for $k = 1$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.578	0.631	0.601	0.600	0.575	0.592	0.582	0.598	0.632	0.591
1	0.733	self	0.775	0.898	0.564	0.883	0.793	0.875	0.788	0.761	0.557
2	0.607	0.755	self	0.822	0.819	0.731	0.705	0.750	0.818	0.936	0.788
3	0.601	0.730	0.822	self	0.988	0.754	0.763	0.877	0.943	0.799	0.923
4	0.584	0.823	0.819	0.988	self	0.918	0.851	0.881	0.940	0.795	0.926
5	0.585	0.917	0.592	0.572	0.908	self	0.807	0.874	0.897	0.576	0.563
6	0.595	0.789	0.572	0.562	0.865	0.814	self	0.821	0.562	0.755	0.571
7	0.572	0.832	0.750	0.877	0.881	0.835	0.819	self	0.866	0.732	0.906
8	0.585	0.855	0.818	0.943	0.940	0.846	0.790	0.866	self	0.800	0.939
9	0.632	0.704	0.936	0.799	0.795	0.733	0.712	0.732	0.800	self	0.770
10	0.591	0.816	0.788	0.923	0.926	0.917	0.806	0.906	0.940	0.770	self

Table F.6 Similarity scores between random conformers of Vardenafil for $k = 2$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.704	0.707	0.711	0.713	0.708	0.710	0.880	0.882	0.710	0.707
1	0.704	self	0.984	0.976	0.966	0.964	0.982	0.760	0.757	0.918	0.985
2	0.707	0.976	self	0.987	0.982	0.994	0.991	0.765	0.764	0.974	0.995
3	0.711	0.976	0.987	self	0.993	0.990	0.995	0.770	0.770	0.985	0.989
4	0.713	0.969	0.982	0.993	self	0.985	0.990	0.773	0.772	0.987	0.983
5	0.708	0.987	0.995	0.990	0.985	self	0.994	0.766	0.766	0.991	0.996
6	0.710	0.977	0.990	0.996	0.990	0.993	self	0.769	0.768	0.986	0.992
7	0.881	0.761	0.765	0.770	0.773	0.766	0.769	self	0.952	0.768	0.766
8	0.882	0.758	0.764	0.769	0.772	0.765	0.768	0.971	self	0.764	0.765
9	0.710	0.899	0.979	0.981	0.976	0.986	0.976	0.768	0.768	self	0.985
10	0.707	0.983	0.996	0.989	0.983	0.997	0.992	0.766	0.765	0.986	self

Table F.7 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Vardenafil for $k = 1$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.560	0.576	0.577	0.577	0.577	0.576	0.617	0.596	0.561	0.576
1	0.558	self	0.874	0.555	0.808	0.895	0.556	0.728	0.745	0.930	0.900
2	0.576	0.853	self	0.983	0.979	0.984	0.983	0.743	0.748	0.986	0.986
3	0.577	0.971	0.983	self	0.992	0.993	0.995	0.756	0.752	0.824	0.985
4	0.577	0.921	0.979	0.992	self	0.987	0.991	0.759	0.757	0.960	0.980
5	0.577	0.959	0.984	0.993	0.987	self	0.995	0.724	0.751	0.858	0.989
6	0.576	0.945	0.983	0.995	0.991	0.995	self	0.737	0.755	0.929	0.988
7	0.605	0.697	0.749	0.752	0.715	0.565	0.753	self	0.874	0.724	0.728
8	0.598	0.747	0.579	0.696	0.727	0.749	0.718	0.827	self	0.750	0.579
9	0.557	0.963	0.866	0.774	0.840	0.552	0.933	0.742	0.748	self	0.547
10	0.576	0.971	0.987	0.985	0.980	0.989	0.988	0.747	0.749	0.804	self

Table F.8 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Vardenafil for $k = 2$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.823	0.822	0.868	0.854	0.819	0.764	0.760	0.752	0.761	0.669
1	0.823	self	0.999	0.933	0.945	0.991	0.677	0.675	0.670	0.675	0.612
2	0.822	0.999	self	0.933	0.944	0.991	0.677	0.675	0.669	0.675	0.612
3	0.868	0.933	0.933	self	0.981	0.926	0.700	0.698	0.692	0.698	0.627
4	0.854	0.945	0.944	0.981	self	0.937	0.692	0.690	0.684	0.690	0.621
5	0.819	0.991	0.991	0.926	0.937	self	0.675	0.673	0.668	0.673	0.611
6	0.764	0.677	0.677	0.700	0.692	0.675	self	0.992	0.974	0.993	0.805
7	0.760	0.675	0.675	0.698	0.690	0.673	0.992	self	0.982	0.999	0.809
8	0.752	0.670	0.669	0.692	0.684	0.668	0.974	0.982	self	0.981	0.819
9	0.761	0.675	0.675	0.698	0.690	0.673	0.993	0.999	0.981	self	0.808
10	0.669	0.612	0.612	0.627	0.621	0.611	0.805	0.809	0.819	0.808	self

Table F.9 Similarity scores between random conformers of Tadalafil for $k = 1$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.818	0.818	0.791	0.834	0.816	0.759	0.679	0.677	0.679	0.675
1	0.752	self	0.999	0.906	0.915	0.969	0.650	0.650	0.648	0.650	0.600
2	0.751	0.999	self	0.905	0.915	0.968	0.649	0.650	0.648	0.650	0.599
3	0.791	0.906	0.905	self	0.972	0.909	0.676	0.676	0.674	0.676	0.618
4	0.780	0.915	0.915	0.972	self	0.916	0.667	0.668	0.665	0.668	0.612
5	0.757	0.969	0.968	0.909	0.916	self	0.652	0.652	0.650	0.652	0.601
6	0.759	0.650	0.649	0.676	0.667	0.652	self	0.980	0.976	0.980	0.814
7	0.759	0.650	0.650	0.676	0.668	0.652	0.980	self	0.977	0.999	0.815
8	0.755	0.648	0.648	0.674	0.665	0.650	0.976	0.977	self	0.976	0.822
9	0.759	0.650	0.650	0.676	0.668	0.652	0.980	0.999	0.976	self	0.815
10	0.675	0.600	0.599	0.618	0.612	0.601	0.814	0.815	0.822	0.815	self

Table F.10 Similarity scores between random conformers of Tadalafil for $k = 2$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.834	0.823	0.834	0.823	0.822	0.823	0.834	0.834	0.822	0.864
1	0.834	self	0.981	0.999	0.981	0.980	0.982	1	0.999	0.980	0.954
2	0.823	0.981	self	0.981	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.981	0.980	0.999	0.937
3	0.834	0.999	0.981	self	0.981	0.980	0.982	0.999	1	0.980	0.954
4	0.823	0.981	1	0.981	self	0.999	0.999	0.981	0.981	0.999	0.938
5	0.822	0.980	0.999	0.980	0.999	self	0.998	0.980	0.980	0.999	0.937
6	0.823	0.982	0.999	0.982	0.999	0.998	self	0.982	0.981	0.998	0.938
7	0.834	1	0.981	0.999	0.981	0.980	0.982	self	0.999	0.980	0.954
8	0.834	0.999	0.980	1	0.981	0.980	0.981	0.999	self	0.980	0.954
9	0.822	0.980	0.999	0.980	0.999	0.999	0.998	0.980	0.980	self	0.936
10	0.864	0.954	0.937	0.954	0.938	0.937	0.938	0.954	0.954	0.936	self

Table F.11 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Tadalafil for $k = 1$.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
0	self	0.763	0.818	0.763	0.818	0.818	0.818	0.761	0.763	0.817	0.792
1	0.763	self	0.943	0.999	0.944	0.943	0.944	0.989	0.998	0.943	0.938
2	0.752	0.943	self	0.943	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.941	0.943	0.998	0.906
3	0.763	0.999	0.943	self	0.944	0.943	0.944	0.988	0.997	0.943	0.939
4	0.752	0.944	0.999	0.944	self	0.998	0.999	0.941	0.943	0.997	0.907
5	0.751	0.943	0.999	0.943	0.998	self	0.998	0.941	0.943	0.999	0.906
6	0.752	0.944	0.999	0.944	0.999	0.998	self	0.941	0.944	0.997	0.907
7	0.761	0.989	0.941	0.988	0.941	0.941	0.941	self	0.991	0.941	0.937
8	0.763	0.998	0.943	0.997	0.943	0.943	0.944	0.991	self	0.943	0.938
9	0.751	0.943	0.998	0.943	0.997	0.999	0.997	0.941	0.943	self	0.905
10	0.792	0.938	0.906	0.939	0.907	0.906	0.907	0.937	0.938	0.905	self

Table F.12 Similarity scores between low energy conformers of Tadalafil for $k = 2$.

Appendix G. Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.522	0.502	0.760	0.595	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.491	0.473	0.881	0.615	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.502	0.484	0.887	0.624	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.520	0.500	0.776	0.599	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.593	0.586	0.541	0.573	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.457	0.441	0.800	0.566	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.569	0.566	0.588	0.574	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.454	0.438	0.817	0.570	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.461	0.445	0.878	0.595	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.459	0.443	0.798	0.567	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.609	0.601	0.530	0.580	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.673	0.655	0.481	0.603	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.475	0.457	0.927	0.620	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.509	0.490	0.839	0.613	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.569	0.566	0.585	0.573	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.468	0.451	0.863	0.594	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.470	0.453	0.948	0.624	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.467	0.451	0.841	0.586	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.489	0.470	0.767	0.575	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.459	0.443	0.886	0.596	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.522	0.502	0.768	0.597	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.643	0.630	0.502	0.592	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.486	0.468	0.839	0.598	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.456	0.440	0.828	0.575	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.522	0.502	0.752	0.592	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.642	0.629	0.496	0.589	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.463	0.447	0.843	0.584	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.466	0.449	0.921	0.612	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.477	0.459	0.904	0.613	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.479	0.461	0.903	0.614	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.468	0.451	0.934	0.618	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.464	0.447	0.934	0.615	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.470	0.453	0.866	0.596	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.477	0.460	0.908	0.615	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.475	0.458	0.875	0.603	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.495	0.477	0.848	0.607	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.577	0.573	0.575	0.575	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.584	0.579	0.562	0.575	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.481	0.463	0.910	0.618	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.472	0.454	0.911	0.612	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.472	0.455	0.906	0.611	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.473	0.456	0.908	0.612	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.491	0.472	0.760	0.574	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.1 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where a single random conformer of each is considered for $k = 1$. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case using alignment below.

ID	S	V	T	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.493	0.488	0.489	0.490	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.473	0.487	0.514	0.491	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.476	0.487	0.496	0.486	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.469	0.487	0.483	0.480	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.493	0.505	0.404	0.467	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.440	0.445	0.505	0.463	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.492	0.509	0.420	0.474	0	326.61	10.01
11992739	0.423	0.413	0.525	0.454	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.446	0.445	0.518	0.470	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.467	0.453	0.508	0.476	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.473	0.530	0.402	0.468	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.487	0.495	0.390	0.457	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.435	0.463	0.500	0.466	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.492	0.487	0.487	0.489	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.487	0.533	0.445	0.488	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.448	0.460	0.506	0.471	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.446	0.461	0.504	0.470	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.472	0.454	0.503	0.476	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.459	0.455	0.558	0.491	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.456	0.445	0.520	0.474	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.494	0.489	0.479	0.487	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.467	0.534	0.419	0.473	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.493	0.481	0.514	0.496	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.424	0.421	0.516	0.454	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.517	0.495	0.493	0.502	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.462	0.531	0.394	0.462	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.465	0.451	0.496	0.471	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.453	0.445	0.513	0.470	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.452	0.460	0.504	0.472	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.457	0.471	0.463	0.464	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.433	0.464	0.505	0.467	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.458	0.450	0.529	0.479	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.476	0.461	0.476	0.471	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.439	0.460	0.510	0.470	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.457	0.470	0.546	0.491	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.459	0.468	0.487	0.471	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.471	0.531	0.412	0.471	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.498	0.508	0.433	0.480	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.489	0.470	0.501	0.487	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.457	0.456	0.505	0.473	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.470	0.466	0.506	0.481	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.479	0.467	0.472	0.473	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.459	0.490	0.500	0.483	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.2 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where a single random conformer of each is considered for $k = 2$. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case using alignment below.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.511	0.444	0.877	0.611	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.482	0.426	0.771	0.560	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.493	0.433	0.857	0.594	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.509	0.443	0.899	0.617	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.581	0.503	0.582	0.555	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.449	0.399	0.720	0.523	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.560	0.484	0.641	0.562	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.446	0.395	0.734	0.525	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.453	0.399	0.777	0.543	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.451	0.400	0.719	0.523	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.595	0.511	0.568	0.558	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.651	0.530	0.509	0.563	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.466	0.407	0.866	0.580	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.499	0.437	0.906	0.614	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.560	0.486	0.637	0.561	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.459	0.406	0.764	0.543	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.461	0.404	0.839	0.568	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.459	0.406	0.748	0.538	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.478	0.410	0.869	0.586	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.450	0.397	0.783	0.543	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.511	0.445	0.888	0.615	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.625	0.523	0.534	0.561	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.477	0.423	0.742	0.547	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.448	0.397	0.741	0.529	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.511	0.443	0.863	0.606	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.624	0.519	0.528	0.557	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.455	0.402	0.751	0.536	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.457	0.402	0.807	0.555	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.467	0.408	0.890	0.588	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.470	0.414	0.791	0.558	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.459	0.401	0.873	0.578	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.455	0.400	0.818	0.558	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.461	0.407	0.765	0.544	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.468	0.409	0.884	0.587	0	284.664	9.06
11992531	0.466	0.405	0.933	0.601	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.485	0.424	0.922	0.610	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.567	0.489	0.624	0.560	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.573	0.495	0.608	0.559	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.472	0.416	0.796	0.561	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.462	0.404	0.894	0.587	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.463	0.404	0.898	0.588	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.464	0.409	0.796	0.556	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.480	0.411	0.859	0.583	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.3 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered, with the query conformers taken from the bound crystal structure for $k = 1$. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case using alignment below.

ID	S	V	T	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.512	0.454	0.490	0.485	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.502	0.448	0.513	0.488	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.508	0.455	0.497	0.487	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.508	0.449	0.483	0.480	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.504	0.486	0.432	0.474	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.459	0.413	0.502	0.458	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.530	0.505	0.424	0.486	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.419	0.406	0.513	0.446	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.457	0.410	0.514	0.460	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.463	0.420	0.505	0.463	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.504	0.526	0.436	0.489	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.488	0.479	0.411	0.459	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.476	0.429	0.498	0.468	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.496	0.455	0.489	0.480	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.515	0.508	0.451	0.491	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.475	0.426	0.476	0.459	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.475	0.422	0.500	0.466	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.467	0.419	0.498	0.461	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.442	0.411	0.563	0.472	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.457	0.409	0.510	0.459	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.504	0.450	0.480	0.478	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.506	0.534	0.424	0.488	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.495	0.442	0.508	0.482	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.410	0.408	0.511	0.443	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.510	0.455	0.497	0.487	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.500	0.485	0.420	0.468	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.463	0.417	0.491	0.457	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.459	0.410	0.510	0.460	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.472	0.420	0.533	0.475	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.488	0.435	0.507	0.477	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.448	0.413	0.553	0.471	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.463	0.406	0.519	0.463	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.473	0.427	0.505	0.468	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.437	0.428	0.513	0.459	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.445	0.420	0.546	0.470	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.487	0.440	0.490	0.472	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.510	0.480	0.444	0.478	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.508	0.482	0.439	0.476	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.490	0.439	0.500	0.476	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.450	0.397	0.539	0.462	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.478	0.422	0.503	0.468	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.478	0.431	0.511	0.473	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.499	0.435	0.562	0.499	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.4 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered, with the query conformers taken from the bound crystal structure for $k = 2$. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case using alignment below.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	ΔS	V	ΔV	T	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.522	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.760	0.000	0.595	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.491	0.000	0.473	0.000	0.881	0.000	0.615	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.502	0.000	0.484	0.000	0.887	0.000	0.624	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.520	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.776	0.000	0.599	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.593	0.000	0.586	0.000	0.541	0.000	0.573	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.457	0.000	0.441	0.000	0.800	0.000	0.566	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.569	0.000	0.566	0.000	0.588	0.000	0.574	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.454	0.000	0.438	0.000	0.817	0.000	0.570	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.461	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.878	0.000	0.595	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.459	0.000	0.443	0.000	0.798	0.000	0.567	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.609	0.000	0.601	0.000	0.530	0.000	0.580	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.673	0.000	0.655	0.000	0.481	0.000	0.603	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.475	0.000	0.457	0.000	0.927	0.000	0.620	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.509	0.000	0.490	0.000	0.839	0.000	0.613	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.569	0.000	0.566	0.000	0.585	0.000	0.573	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.468	0.000	0.451	0.000	0.863	0.000	0.594	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.470	0.000	0.453	0.000	0.948	0.000	0.624	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.467	0.000	0.451	0.000	0.841	0.000	0.586	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.489	0.000	0.470	0.000	0.767	0.000	0.575	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.459	0.000	0.443	0.000	0.886	0.000	0.596	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.522	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.768	0.000	0.597	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.643	0.000	0.630	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.592	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.486	0.000	0.468	0.000	0.839	0.000	0.598	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.456	0.000	0.440	0.000	0.828	0.000	0.575	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.522	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.752	0.000	0.592	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.642	0.000	0.629	0.000	0.496	0.000	0.589	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.463	0.000	0.447	0.000	0.843	0.000	0.584	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.466	0.000	0.449	0.000	0.921	0.000	0.612	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.477	0.000	0.459	0.000	0.904	0.000	0.613	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.479	0.000	0.461	0.000	0.903	0.000	0.614	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.468	0.000	0.451	0.000	0.934	0.000	0.618	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.464	0.000	0.447	0.000	0.934	0.000	0.615	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.470	0.000	0.453	0.000	0.866	0.000	0.596	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.477	0.000	0.460	0.000	0.908	0.000	0.615	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.475	0.000	0.458	0.000	0.875	0.000	0.603	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.495	0.000	0.477	0.000	0.848	0.000	0.607	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.577	0.000	0.573	0.000	0.575	0.000	0.575	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.584	0.000	0.579	0.000	0.562	0.000	0.575	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.481	0.000	0.463	0.000	0.910	0.000	0.618	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.472	0.000	0.454	0.000	0.911	0.000	0.612	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.472	0.000	0.455	0.000	0.906	0.000	0.611	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.473	0.000	0.456	0.000	0.908	0.000	0.612	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.491	0.000	0.472	0.000	0.760	0.000	0.574	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.5 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered for $k = 1$. Here the PDE5 inhibitors are aligned to each query in turn prior to similarity calculation. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case with no alignment.

ID	S	ΔS	V	ΔV	T	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.493	0.000	0.488	0.000	0.489	0.000	0.490	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.473	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.514	0.000	0.491	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.476	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.496	0.000	0.486	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.469	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.483	0.000	0.480	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.493	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.404	0.000	0.467	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.440	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.463	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.492	0.000	0.509	0.000	0.420	0.000	0.474	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.423	0.000	0.413	0.000	0.525	0.000	0.454	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.446	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.518	0.000	0.470	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.467	0.000	0.453	0.000	0.508	0.000	0.476	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.473	0.000	0.530	0.000	0.402	0.000	0.468	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.487	0.000	0.495	0.000	0.390	0.000	0.457	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.435	0.000	0.463	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.466	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.492	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.489	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.487	0.000	0.533	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.488	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.448	0.000	0.460	0.000	0.506	0.000	0.471	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.446	0.000	0.461	0.000	0.504	0.000	0.470	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.472	0.000	0.454	0.000	0.503	0.000	0.476	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.459	0.000	0.455	0.000	0.558	0.000	0.491	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.456	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.520	0.000	0.474	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.494	0.000	0.489	0.000	0.479	0.000	0.487	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.467	0.000	0.534	0.000	0.419	0.000	0.473	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.493	0.000	0.481	0.000	0.514	0.000	0.496	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.424	0.000	0.421	0.000	0.516	0.000	0.454	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.517	0.000	0.495	0.000	0.493	0.000	0.502	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.462	0.000	0.531	0.000	0.394	0.000	0.462	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.465	0.000	0.451	0.000	0.496	0.000	0.471	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.453	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.513	0.000	0.470	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.452	0.000	0.460	0.000	0.504	0.000	0.472	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.457	0.000	0.471	0.000	0.463	0.000	0.464	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.433	0.000	0.464	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.467	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.458	0.000	0.450	0.000	0.529	0.000	0.479	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.476	0.000	0.461	0.000	0.476	0.000	0.471	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.439	0.000	0.460	0.000	0.510	0.000	0.470	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.457	0.000	0.470	0.000	0.546	0.000	0.491	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.459	0.000	0.468	0.000	0.487	0.000	0.471	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.471	0.000	0.531	0.000	0.412	0.000	0.471	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.498	0.000	0.508	0.000	0.433	0.000	0.480	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.489	0.000	0.470	0.000	0.501	0.000	0.487	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.457	0.000	0.456	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.473	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.470	0.000	0.466	0.000	0.506	0.000	0.481	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.479	0.000	0.467	0.000	0.472	0.000	0.473	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.459	0.000	0.490	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.483	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.6 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered for $k = 2$. Here the PDE5 inhibitors are aligned to each query in turn prior to similarity calculation. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case with no alignment.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using QQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	ΔS	V	ΔV	T	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.511	0.000	0.444	0.000	0.877	0.000	0.611	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.482	0.000	0.426	0.000	0.771	0.000	0.560	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.493	0.000	0.433	0.000	0.857	0.000	0.594	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.509	0.000	0.443	0.000	0.899	0.000	0.617	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.581	0.000	0.503	0.000	0.582	0.000	0.555	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.449	0.000	0.399	0.000	0.720	0.000	0.523	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.560	0.000	0.484	0.000	0.641	0.000	0.562	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.446	0.000	0.395	0.000	0.734	0.000	0.525	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.453	0.000	0.399	0.000	0.777	0.000	0.543	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.451	0.000	0.400	0.000	0.719	0.000	0.523	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.595	0.000	0.511	0.000	0.568	0.000	0.558	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.651	0.000	0.530	0.000	0.509	0.000	0.563	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.466	0.000	0.407	0.000	0.866	0.000	0.580	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.499	0.000	0.437	0.000	0.906	0.000	0.614	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.560	0.000	0.486	0.000	0.637	0.000	0.561	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.459	0.000	0.406	0.000	0.764	0.000	0.543	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.461	0.000	0.404	0.000	0.839	0.000	0.568	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.459	0.000	0.406	0.000	0.748	0.000	0.538	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.478	0.000	0.410	0.000	0.869	0.000	0.586	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.450	0.000	0.397	0.000	0.783	0.000	0.543	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.511	0.000	0.445	0.000	0.888	0.000	0.615	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.625	0.000	0.523	0.000	0.534	0.000	0.561	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.477	0.000	0.423	0.000	0.742	0.000	0.547	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.448	0.000	0.397	0.000	0.741	0.000	0.529	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.511	0.000	0.443	0.000	0.863	0.000	0.606	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.624	0.000	0.519	0.000	0.528	0.000	0.557	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.455	0.000	0.402	0.000	0.751	0.000	0.536	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.457	0.000	0.402	0.000	0.807	0.000	0.555	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.467	0.000	0.408	0.000	0.890	0.000	0.588	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.470	0.000	0.414	0.000	0.791	0.000	0.558	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.459	0.000	0.401	0.000	0.873	0.000	0.578	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.455	0.000	0.400	0.000	0.818	0.000	0.558	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.461	0.000	0.407	0.000	0.765	0.000	0.544	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.468	0.000	0.409	0.000	0.884	0.000	0.587	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.466	0.000	0.405	0.000	0.933	0.000	0.601	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.485	0.000	0.424	0.000	0.922	0.000	0.610	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.567	0.000	0.489	0.000	0.624	0.000	0.560	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.573	0.000	0.495	0.000	0.608	0.000	0.559	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.472	0.000	0.416	0.000	0.796	0.000	0.561	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.462	0.000	0.404	0.000	0.894	0.000	0.587	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.463	0.000	0.404	0.000	0.898	0.000	0.588	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.464	0.000	0.409	0.000	0.796	0.000	0.556	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.480	0.000	0.411	0.000	0.859	0.000	0.583	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.7 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered for $k = 1$. Here the PDE5 inhibitors are aligned to each query (taken from the crystal structures) in turn prior to similarity calculation. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case with no alignment.

ID	S	ΔS	V	ΔV	T	ΔT	Average	Base Sphere	Surface Area	pIC50
11993170	0.512	0.000	0.454	0.000	0.490	0.000	0.485	9	313.48	10.40
11992634	0.502	0.000	0.448	0.000	0.513	0.000	0.488	0	310.89	10.30
11993171	0.508	0.000	0.455	0.000	0.497	0.000	0.487	9	311.38	10.30
45486504	0.508	0.000	0.449	0.000	0.483	0.000	0.480	9	313.93	10.22
11993561	0.504	0.000	0.486	0.000	0.432	0.000	0.474	0	336.86	10.16
11992831	0.459	0.000	0.413	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.458	0	287.30	10.16
11993465	0.530	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.424	0.000	0.486	0	326.61	10.10
11992739	0.419	0.000	0.406	0.000	0.513	0.000	0.446	8	282.21	10.05
11992635	0.457	0.000	0.410	0.000	0.514	0.000	0.460	0	282.68	10.00
11992529	0.463	0.000	0.420	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.463	0	289.30	9.96
11993562	0.504	0.000	0.526	0.000	0.436	0.000	0.489	0	334.25	9.89
11993463	0.488	0.000	0.479	0.000	0.411	0.000	0.459	0	344.79	9.89
11992740	0.476	0.000	0.429	0.000	0.498	0.000	0.468	0	284.42	9.85
11993342	0.496	0.000	0.455	0.000	0.489	0.000	0.480	9	312.74	9.85
11993365	0.515	0.000	0.508	0.000	0.451	0.000	0.491	0	327.91	9.82
45486496	0.475	0.000	0.426	0.000	0.476	0.000	0.459	0	290.51	9.77
11992742	0.475	0.000	0.422	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.466	0	283.22	9.62
11992741	0.467	0.000	0.419	0.000	0.498	0.000	0.461	0	292.16	9.60
45486519	0.442	0.000	0.411	0.000	0.563	0.000	0.472	8	271.41	9.60
11992528	0.457	0.000	0.409	0.000	0.510	0.000	0.459	0	279.92	9.59
45486497	0.504	0.000	0.450	0.000	0.480	0.000	0.478	9	314.67	9.55
45486572	0.506	0.000	0.534	0.000	0.424	0.000	0.488	0	338.16	9.50
45486514	0.495	0.000	0.442	0.000	0.508	0.000	0.482	9	309.94	9.50
45486550	0.410	0.000	0.408	0.000	0.511	0.000	0.443	8	283.43	9.47
45486581	0.510	0.000	0.455	0.000	0.497	0.000	0.487	9	310.47	9.44
45486498	0.500	0.000	0.485	0.000	0.420	0.000	0.468	0	344.25	9.42
11993435	0.463	0.000	0.417	0.000	0.491	0.000	0.457	0	287.98	9.37
45486564	0.459	0.000	0.410	0.000	0.510	0.000	0.460	0	283.43	9.27
45486501	0.472	0.000	0.420	0.000	0.533	0.000	0.475	0	283.35	9.26
11992443	0.488	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.507	0.000	0.477	0	296.81	9.17
45486527	0.448	0.000	0.413	0.000	0.553	0.000	0.471	8	277.71	9.17
45486505	0.463	0.000	0.406	0.000	0.519	0.000	0.463	1	280.10	9.15
11992631	0.473	0.000	0.427	0.000	0.505	0.000	0.468	0	292.05	9.11
45486574	0.437	0.000	0.428	0.000	0.513	0.000	0.459	0	284.66	9.06
11992531	0.445	0.000	0.420	0.000	0.546	0.000	0.470	0	277.63	8.98
11992827	0.487	0.000	0.440	0.000	0.490	0.000	0.472	9	297.61	8.96
11993437	0.510	0.000	0.480	0.000	0.444	0.000	0.478	0	327.73	8.93
11993560	0.508	0.000	0.482	0.000	0.439	0.000	0.476	0	329.77	8.78
11993243	0.490	0.000	0.439	0.000	0.500	0.000	0.476	0	298.23	8.59
45486513	0.450	0.000	0.397	0.000	0.539	0.000	0.462	8	278.47	8.59
45486549	0.478	0.000	0.422	0.000	0.503	0.000	0.468	0	278.40	8.53
45486571	0.478	0.000	0.431	0.000	0.511	0.000	0.473	0	291.14	8.40
45486511	0.499	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.562	0.000	0.499	1	271.48	7.79

Table G.8 Similarity scores for the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T), and the average across all three queries, where 1 conformer of each is considered for $k = 2$. Here the PDE5 inhibitors are aligned to each query (taken from the crystal structures) in turn prior to similarity calculation. The base sphere and surface area are included for comparison to the case with no alignment.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Max S	Max V	Max T	Average	No. Confs	pIC50
11993170	0.479	0.461	0.872	0.604	0.497	0.478	0.925	278	10.40
11992634	0.460	0.444	0.791	0.565	0.488	0.474	0.881	296	10.30
11993171	0.469	0.452	0.870	0.597	0.497	0.482	0.936	300	10.30
45486504	0.475	0.457	0.862	0.598	0.511	0.492	0.932	275	10.22
11993561	0.600	0.571	0.566	0.579	0.629	0.602	0.605	298	10.16
11992831	0.464	0.448	0.804	0.572	0.469	0.452	0.842	267	10.16
11993465	0.536	0.514	0.661	0.570	0.555	0.535	0.692	300	10.10
11992739	0.481	0.463	0.935	0.626	0.487	0.469	0.940	275	10.05
11992635	0.481	0.463	0.935	0.626	0.485	0.467	0.940	264	10.00
11992529	0.461	0.445	0.781	0.563	0.476	0.459	0.918	293	9.96
11993562	0.584	0.558	0.582	0.575	0.616	0.591	0.626	300	9.89
11993463	0.685	0.646	0.517	0.616	0.740	0.693	0.551	300	9.89
11992740	0.489	0.471	0.873	0.611	0.493	0.474	0.919	285	9.85
11993342	0.473	0.455	0.839	0.589	0.508	0.492	0.936	300	9.85
11993365	0.555	0.531	0.623	0.570	0.580	0.559	0.658	298	9.82
45486496	0.462	0.446	0.791	0.567	0.472	0.455	0.910	294	9.77
11992742	0.489	0.470	0.873	0.611	0.494	0.475	0.915	280	9.62
11992741	0.466	0.450	0.823	0.580	0.474	0.457	0.897	293	9.60
45486519	0.520	0.499	0.699	0.573	0.527	0.506	0.737	279	9.60
11992528	0.477	0.460	0.925	0.621	0.481	0.463	0.938	292	9.59
45486497	0.476	0.458	0.866	0.600	0.489	0.472	0.932	291	9.55
45486572	0.601	0.573	0.566	0.580	0.636	0.608	0.602	299	9.50
45486514	0.458	0.440	0.777	0.558	0.490	0.476	0.887	299	9.50
45486550	0.483	0.465	0.920	0.622	0.486	0.468	0.940	291	9.47
45486581	0.474	0.456	0.843	0.591	0.510	0.490	0.921	279	9.44
45486498	0.689	0.649	0.516	0.618	0.724	0.685	0.542	300	9.42
11993435	0.466	0.449	0.818	0.578	0.469	0.453	0.849	278	9.37
45486564	0.483	0.465	0.922	0.623	0.489	0.470	0.938	290	9.27
45486501	0.491	0.473	0.855	0.606	0.495	0.476	0.930	287	9.26
11992443	0.464	0.447	0.800	0.570	0.483	0.466	0.937	270	9.17
45486527	0.493	0.474	0.839	0.602	0.497	0.478	0.867	271	9.17
45486505	0.480	0.462	0.935	0.626	0.486	0.468	0.938	294	9.15
11992631	0.461	0.445	0.779	0.562	0.474	0.457	0.895	292	9.11
45486574	0.491	0.473	0.854	0.606	0.495	0.477	0.890	285	9.06
11992531	0.496	0.477	0.817	0.597	0.500	0.481	0.860	273	8.98
11992827	0.478	0.461	0.924	0.621	0.499	0.484	0.936	299	8.96
11993437	0.554	0.530	0.623	0.569	0.578	0.557	0.652	300	8.93
11993560	0.555	0.532	0.624	0.570	0.588	0.566	0.656	299	8.78
11993243	0.465	0.448	0.810	0.574	0.481	0.464	0.932	281	8.59
45486513	0.496	0.477	0.822	0.598	0.500	0.481	0.935	277	8.59
45486549	0.499	0.480	0.800	0.593	0.502	0.483	0.826	276	8.53
45486571	0.462	0.446	0.789	0.566	0.475	0.458	0.902	294	8.40
45486511	0.524	0.503	0.691	0.573	0.530	0.508	0.735	290	7.79

Table G.9 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T) for $k = 1$. The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

ID	S	V	T	Max S	Max V	Max T	Average	No. Confs	pIC50
11993170	0.461	0.461	0.484	0.469	0.492	0.509	0.494	278	10.40
11992634	0.452	0.451	0.504	0.469	0.500	0.481	0.517	296	10.30
11993171	0.458	0.458	0.495	0.471	0.499	0.487	0.526	300	10.30
45486504	0.459	0.460	0.483	0.468	0.502	0.483	0.499	275	10.22
11993561	0.481	0.473	0.436	0.463	0.515	0.508	0.455	298	10.16
11992831	0.447	0.445	0.494	0.462	0.464	0.454	0.500	267	10.16
11993465	0.474	0.471	0.455	0.467	0.507	0.504	0.470	300	10.10
11992739	0.467	0.472	0.503	0.481	0.491	0.475	0.521	275	10.05
11992635	0.469	0.472	0.500	0.480	0.493	0.475	0.521	264	10.00
11992529	0.447	0.450	0.480	0.459	0.481	0.465	0.500	293	9.96
11993562	0.481	0.473	0.440	0.465	0.521	0.509	0.460	300	9.89
11993463	0.486	0.473	0.426	0.462	0.516	0.534	0.443	300	9.89
11992740	0.481	0.484	0.505	0.490	0.505	0.489	0.534	285	9.85
11993342	0.460	0.459	0.486	0.468	0.497	0.486	0.508	300	9.85
11993365	0.476	0.470	0.446	0.464	0.513	0.503	0.470	298	9.82
45486496	0.447	0.450	0.478	0.458	0.468	0.462	0.508	294	9.77
11992742	0.480	0.484	0.505	0.489	0.505	0.488	0.531	280	9.62
11992741	0.453	0.452	0.503	0.469	0.475	0.459	0.515	293	9.60
45486519	0.504	0.511	0.525	0.513	0.534	0.585	0.536	279	9.60
11992528	0.461	0.465	0.497	0.475	0.484	0.469	0.938	292	9.59
45486497	0.459	0.460	0.482	0.467	0.508	0.499	0.502	291	9.55
45486572	0.480	0.474	0.436	0.463	0.511	0.510	0.455	299	9.50
45486514	0.452	0.451	0.501	0.468	0.500	0.479	0.515	299	9.50
45486550	0.469	0.473	0.500	0.481	0.494	0.477	0.519	291	9.47
45486581	0.459	0.459	0.482	0.467	0.499	0.479	0.496	279	9.44
45486498	0.484	0.472	0.425	0.461	0.523	0.521	0.438	300	9.42
11993435	0.448	0.446	0.492	0.462	0.465	0.451	0.498	278	9.37
45486564	0.468	0.473	0.498	0.480	0.493	0.478	0.518	290	9.27
45486501	0.479	0.485	0.502	0.489	0.506	0.491	0.533	287	9.26
11992443	0.454	0.453	0.485	0.464	0.492	0.470	0.505	270	9.17
45486527	0.483	0.486	0.504	0.491	0.506	0.491	0.530	271	9.17
45486505	0.463	0.466	0.496	0.475	0.485	0.473	0.514	294	9.15
11992631	0.446	0.449	0.483	0.459	0.479	0.466	0.509	292	9.11
45486574	0.481	0.485	0.502	0.489	0.506	0.491	0.528	285	9.06
11992531	0.485	0.489	0.505	0.493	0.511	0.494	0.533	273	8.98
11992827	0.459	0.458	0.470	0.462	0.492	0.485	0.482	299	8.96
11993437	0.476	0.471	0.446	0.464	0.518	0.504	0.464	300	8.93
11993560	0.476	0.470	0.447	0.464	0.521	0.505	0.465	299	8.78
11993243	0.454	0.453	0.482	0.463	0.472	0.464	0.505	281	8.59
45486513	0.483	0.487	0.500	0.490	0.510	0.493	0.527	277	8.59
45486549	0.485	0.490	0.502	0.492	0.511	0.494	0.528	276	8.53
45486571	0.446	0.449	0.482	0.459	0.468	0.465	0.505	294	8.40
45486511	0.503	0.512	0.524	0.513	0.535	0.521	0.532	290	7.79

Table G.10 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T) for $k = 2$. The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Max S	Max V	Max T	Average	No. Confs	pIC50
11993170	0.469	0.412	0.850	0.577	0.487	0.423	0.942	278	10.40
11992634	0.452	0.401	0.710	0.521	0.483	0.428	0.776	296	10.30
11993171	0.460	0.406	0.766	0.544	0.491	0.434	0.815	300	10.30
45486504	0.466	0.409	0.833	0.569	0.500	0.431	0.917	275	10.22
11993561	0.580	0.471	0.605	0.552	0.613	0.498	0.654	298	10.16
11992831	0.456	0.404	0.722	0.527	0.460	0.407	0.748	267	10.16
11993465	0.523	0.443	0.729	0.565	0.545	0.464	0.771	300	10.10
11992739	0.471	0.414	0.836	0.574	0.478	0.418	0.891	275	10.05
11992635	0.472	0.414	0.836	0.574	0.475	0.416	0.870	264	10.00
11992529	0.453	0.403	0.705	0.521	0.468	0.412	0.804	293	9.96
11993562	0.567	0.466	0.625	0.553	0.601	0.492	0.682	300	9.89
11993463	0.656	0.505	0.545	0.569	0.705	0.532	0.586	300	9.89
11992740	0.479	0.418	0.903	0.600	0.483	0.421	0.938	285	9.85
11993342	0.463	0.408	0.811	0.561	0.501	0.439	0.948	300	9.85
11993365	0.540	0.452	0.678	0.557	0.569	0.476	0.724	298	9.82
45486496	0.454	0.403	0.712	0.523	0.463	0.408	0.798	294	9.77
11992742	0.479	0.418	0.903	0.600	0.484	0.421	0.942	280	9.62
11992741	0.458	0.406	0.735	0.533	0.465	0.410	0.787	293	9.60
45486519	0.507	0.434	0.782	0.575	0.515	0.438	0.835	279	9.60
11992528	0.468	0.412	0.810	0.563	0.471	0.414	0.835	292	9.59
45486497	0.466	0.409	0.843	0.573	0.480	0.419	0.916	291	9.55
45486572	0.582	0.473	0.606	0.553	0.619	0.500	0.651	299	9.50
45486514	0.449	0.399	0.702	0.517	0.485	0.430	0.780	299	9.50
45486550	0.473	0.415	0.853	0.581	0.477	0.417	0.884	291	9.47
45486581	0.465	0.408	0.836	0.570	0.499	0.430	0.943	279	9.44
45486498	0.660	0.506	0.544	0.570	0.697	0.533	0.575	300	9.42
11993435	0.458	0.405	0.732	0.532	0.461	0.408	0.755	278	9.37
45486564	0.474	0.415	0.854	0.581	0.479	0.418	0.903	290	9.27
45486501	0.481	0.420	0.923	0.608	0.485	0.422	0.950	287	9.26
11992443	0.455	0.404	0.719	0.526	0.474	0.416	0.857	270	9.17
45486527	0.483	0.421	0.938	0.614	0.487	0.423	0.951	271	9.17
45486505	0.470	0.413	0.827	0.570	0.477	0.417	0.879	294	9.15
11992631	0.453	0.403	0.704	0.520	0.465	0.410	0.786	292	9.11
45486574	0.481	0.420	0.924	0.608	0.485	0.422	0.951	285	9.06
11992531	0.486	0.422	0.944	0.617	0.490	0.425	0.952	273	8.98
11992827	0.469	0.412	0.815	0.565	0.493	0.435	0.857	299	8.96
11993437	0.540	0.452	0.678	0.556	0.567	0.475	0.717	300	8.93
11993560	0.541	0.452	0.679	0.558	0.576	0.480	0.723	299	8.78
11993243	0.457	0.405	0.726	0.529	0.472	0.414	0.841	281	8.59
45486513	0.485	0.422	0.946	0.618	0.489	0.424	0.952	277	8.59
45486549	0.488	0.424	0.927	0.613	0.491	0.426	0.951	276	8.53
45486571	0.454	0.403	0.711	0.523	0.466	0.411	0.791	294	8.40
45486511	0.511	0.437	0.770	0.573	0.517	0.440	0.833	290	7.79

Table G.11 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T) (taken from the bound crystal structure) for $k = 1$. The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

ID	S	V	T	Max S	Max V	Max T	Average	No. Confs	pIC50
11993170	0.471	0.429	0.489	0.463	0.494	0.441	0.496	278	10.40
11992634	0.459	0.417	0.501	0.459	0.481	0.444	0.517	296	10.30
11993171	0.469	0.425	0.497	0.464	0.498	0.455	0.508	300	10.30
45486504	0.470	0.428	0.489	0.462	0.509	0.455	0.502	275	10.22
11993561	0.481	0.454	0.445	0.460	0.522	0.583	0.464	298	10.16
11992831	0.456	0.415	0.492	0.454	0.461	0.420	0.499	267	10.16
11993465	0.484	0.446	0.465	0.465	0.521	0.481	0.476	300	10.10
11992739	0.480	0.432	0.506	0.473	0.490	0.438	0.524	275	10.05
11992635	0.481	0.432	0.508	0.474	0.490	0.439	0.525	264	10.00
11992529	0.462	0.420	0.479	0.454	0.477	0.432	0.499	293	9.96
11993562	0.483	0.451	0.449	0.461	0.524	0.496	0.467	300	9.89
11993463	0.479	0.461	0.434	0.458	0.525	0.514	0.452	300	9.89
11992740	0.494	0.440	0.523	0.486	0.503	0.447	0.537	285	9.85
11993342	0.471	0.428	0.489	0.463	0.504	0.460	0.507	300	9.85
11993365	0.480	0.446	0.455	0.460	0.520	0.487	0.472	298	9.82
45486496	0.462	0.419	0.479	0.453	0.474	0.424	0.510	294	9.77
11992742	0.494	0.440	0.522	0.485	0.503	0.445	0.536	280	9.62
11992741	0.464	0.419	0.503	0.462	0.471	0.425	0.515	293	9.60
45486519	0.521	0.459	0.537	0.506	0.538	0.467	0.546	279	9.60
11992528	0.474	0.427	0.501	0.467	0.483	0.433	0.519	292	9.59
45486497	0.470	0.429	0.489	0.462	0.487	0.441	0.500	291	9.55
45486572	0.484	0.455	0.446	0.461	0.524	0.500	0.463	299	9.50
45486514	0.458	0.417	0.499	0.458	0.610	0.445	0.513	299	9.50
45486550	0.482	0.433	0.506	0.473	0.491	0.439	0.525	291	9.47
45486581	0.472	0.429	0.489	0.463	0.495	0.443	0.501	279	9.44
45486498	0.479	0.461	0.433	0.458	0.534	0.513	0.449	300	9.42
11993435	0.457	0.415	0.491	0.454	0.463	0.420	0.498	278	9.37
45486564	0.482	0.433	0.507	0.474	0.491	0.441	0.525	290	9.27
45486501	0.493	0.441	0.521	0.485	0.505	0.448	0.536	287	9.26
11992443	0.467	0.423	0.490	0.460	0.492	0.440	0.507	270	9.17
45486527	0.497	0.442	0.524	0.488	0.506	0.448	0.535	271	9.17
45486505	0.474	0.428	0.498	0.467	0.484	0.436	0.516	294	9.15
11992631	0.461	0.419	0.481	0.454	0.482	0.431	0.509	292	9.11
45486574	0.494	0.441	0.521	0.485	0.504	0.449	0.533	285	9.06
11992531	0.499	0.444	0.528	0.490	0.510	0.450	0.538	273	8.98
11992827	0.474	0.432	0.478	0.461	0.503	0.458	0.484	299	8.96
11993437	0.482	0.447	0.457	0.462	0.521	0.487	0.471	300	8.93
11993560	0.481	0.446	0.457	0.461	0.522	0.490	0.472	299	8.78
11993243	0.467	0.423	0.489	0.460	0.473	0.427	0.505	281	8.59
45486513	0.498	0.443	0.523	0.488	0.507	0.450	0.534	277	8.59
45486549	0.501	0.446	0.524	0.490	0.510	0.451	0.534	276	8.53
45486571	0.462	0.419	0.480	0.454	0.477	0.427	0.504	294	8.40
45486511	0.522	0.460	0.533	0.505	0.538	0.469	0.549	290	7.79

Table G.12 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of the 43 PDE5 inhibitors to a single conformer of Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T) (taken from the bound crystal structure) for $k = 2$. The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

Small PDE5 Inhibitor Screen using KQMolSA - Full Results

ID	S	V	T	Max S	Max V	Max T	Average	pIC50
11993170	0.437	0.422	0.787	0.549	0.501	0.471	0.950	10.40
11992634	0.427	0.412	0.700	0.513	0.487	0.468	0.941	10.30
11993171	0.434	0.418	0.758	0.536	0.503	0.478	0.948	10.30
45486504	0.432	0.417	0.769	0.539	0.516	0.485	0.951	10.22
11993561	0.543	0.505	0.637	0.562	0.644	0.591	0.969	10.16
11992831	0.442	0.422	0.727	0.531	0.471	0.447	0.941	10.16
11993465	0.494	0.467	0.711	0.557	0.564	0.528	0.964	10.10
11992739	0.456	0.434	0.823	0.571	0.491	0.464	0.951	10.05
11992635	0.456	0.434	0.823	0.571	0.488	0.462	0.951	10.00
11992529	0.440	0.420	0.710	0.523	0.479	0.455	0.945	9.96
11993562	0.532	0.497	0.654	0.561	0.630	0.580	0.968	9.89
11993463	0.602	0.551	0.566	0.573	0.765	0.673	0.967	9.89
11992740	0.462	0.439	0.828	0.576	0.496	0.469	0.952	9.85
11993342	0.433	0.417	0.750	0.533	0.515	0.487	0.952	9.85
11993365	0.508	0.478	0.689	0.558	0.592	0.550	0.966	9.82
45486496	0.441	0.421	0.717	0.526	0.475	0.450	0.947	9.77
11992742	0.462	0.439	0.828	0.577	0.497	0.470	0.954	9.62
11992741	0.445	0.424	0.742	0.537	0.477	0.453	0.947	9.60
45486519	0.483	0.457	0.732	0.557	0.532	0.499	0.946	9.60
11992528	0.453	0.431	0.811	0.565	0.483	0.458	0.950	9.59
45486497	0.434	0.418	0.770	0.541	0.493	0.466	0.950	9.55
45486572	0.546	0.507	0.637	0.563	0.651	0.596	0.968	9.50
45486514	0.423	0.407	0.680	0.503	0.489	0.471	0.942	9.50
45486550	0.457	0.435	0.826	0.573	0.490	0.463	0.951	9.47
45486581	0.431	0.416	0.759	0.535	0.515	0.484	0.950	9.44
45486498	0.604	0.552	0.564	0.573	0.748	0.667	0.967	9.42
11993435	0.444	0.424	0.738	0.535	0.472	0.448	0.940	9.37
45486564	0.458	0.435	0.827	0.573	0.492	0.465	0.952	9.27
45486501	0.464	0.440	0.824	0.576	0.499	0.471	0.952	9.26
11992443	0.442	0.422	0.723	0.529	0.486	0.461	0.948	9.17
45486527	0.465	0.442	0.818	0.575	0.501	0.473	0.951	9.17
45486505	0.455	0.433	0.818	0.568	0.489	0.463	0.953	9.15
11992631	0.440	0.420	0.708	0.522	0.476	0.452	0.946	9.11
45486574	0.464	0.441	0.823	0.576	0.499	0.471	0.951	9.06
11992531	0.468	0.444	0.809	0.573	0.504	0.475	0.952	8.98
11992827	0.453	0.431	0.809	0.564	0.505	0.479	0.951	8.96
11993437	0.507	0.478	0.688	0.557	0.590	0.548	0.966	8.93
11993560	0.507	0.478	0.690	0.558	0.600	0.557	0.966	8.78
11993243	0.443	0.423	0.732	0.533	0.484	0.459	0.948	8.59
45486513	0.468	0.444	0.812	0.574	0.504	0.475	0.952	8.59
45486549	0.469	0.445	0.801	0.572	0.506	0.477	0.953	8.53
45486571	0.441	0.421	0.715	0.526	0.477	0.453	0.944	8.40
45486511	0.487	0.460	0.730	0.559	0.536	0.501	0.944	7.79

Table G.13 Average and maximum similarity scores for multiple conformers of both the 43 PDE5 inhibitors and Sildenafil (S), Vardenafil (V) and Tadalafil (T) for $k = 1$. The average reported is the average of the averages for the three queries.

Appendix H. RGMolSA Exclusions - Full Results

Table H.1 Count of molecules filtered from the DUD-E dataset containing macrocycles, or which returned an error when calculating the descriptor.

Target	Macrocycles (A)	Error (A)	Macrocycles (D)	Error (D)
aa2ar	0	1	43	18
abl1	0	0	7	4
ace	5	0	3	4
aces	0	0	14	10
ada	0	0	1	0
ada17	33	0	16	14
adrb1	0	0	5	1
adrb2	0	0	6	1
akt1	0	0	9	5
akt2	0	0	2	1
aldr	0	0	5	2
ampc	0	0	1	1
andr	0	1	15	15
aofb	1	0	1	6
bace1	29	0	7	3
braf	0	0	6	4
cah2	2	0	21	13
casp3	0	2	3	4
cdk2	2	0	9	11
comt	0	0	0	1
cp2c9	0	1	6	2
cp3a4	2	1	9	4
csf1r	0	1	12	5
cxcr4	4	0	6	3
def	7	0	1	0
dhi1	0	0	15	6
dpp4	1	0	28	17
drd3	2	0	18	8
dyr	1	0	18	8
egfr	0	2	19	12
esr1	1	2	27	8

Continued on next page

Table H.1 – continued from previous page

Target	Macrocycles (A)	Error (A)	Macrocycles (D)	Error (D)
esr2	5	2	28	13
fa10	0	0	16	5
fa7	0	0	12	2
fabp4	0	0	3	0
fak1	0	0	0	3
fgfr1	0	0	14	5
fbk1a	0	0	3	1
fnta	31	0	22	12
fpps	0	0	0	6
gcr	0	1	12	4
glcm	0	0	1	1
gria2	0	0	5	5
grik1	0	0	0	8
hdac2	15	0	0	0
hdac8	16	0	0	5
hivint	0	0	5	2
hivpr	30	0	37	3
hivrt	0	0	18	13
hmdh	0	0	3	4
hs90a	15	0	8	2
hvk4	0	0	0	0
igf1r	0	4	7	4
inha	0	0	2	0
ital	0	0	8	3
jak2	0	0	7	1
kif11	0	0	9	9
kit	1	0	11	1
kith	0	0	1	0
kpcb	18	0	4	1
lck	3	0	26	10
lkha4	0	0	1	3
mapk2	1	0	1	1
mcr	0	0	6	6
met	0	0	5	8
mk01	0	0	7	3
mk10	0	0	1	6
mk14	0	0	19	14
mmp13	2	0	28	17
mp2k1	0	0	4	5
nos1	0	0	14	8

Continued on next page

Table H.1 – continued from previous page

Target	Macrocycles (A)	Error (A)	Macrocycles (D)	Error (D)
nram	0	0	0	0
pa2ga	0	0	0	0
parp1	0	0	12	26
pde5a	0	1	10	4
pgh1	0	0	24	10
pgh2	1	0	24	21
plk1	1	0	1	5
pnph	0	0	1	3
ppara	0	0	29	1
ppard	0	0	21	0
pparg	0	0	36	4
prgr	0	1	26	13
ptn1	0	0	13	3
pur2	0	0	0	0
pygm	0	0	2	2
pyrd	0	0	3	2
reni	1	0	0	0
rock1	0	0	7	1
rxra	0	0	26	4
sahh	0	0	3	2
src	11	0	14	7
tgfr1	0	0	5	2
thb	0	0	23	0
thrb	17	0	18	7
try1	12	1	56	10
tryb1	0	0	12	4
tysy	0	0	2	4
urok	0	0	14	6
vgfr2	0	0	27	10
wee1	0	0	15	0
xiap	0	0	1	1

Appendix I. KQMolSA Exclusions - Full Results

Table I.1 Count of molecules filtered from the DUD-E dataset containing macrocycles, or which returned an error when calculating the descriptor or the score between descriptors.

Target	Macrocycles (A)	Error (A)	Macrocycles (D)	Error (D)	Score Error
aa2ar	0	0	43	4	16
adrb1	0	0	5	0	0
adrb2	0	0	6	0	0
cxcr4	4	0	6	2	0
drd3	2	0	19	4	2
akt1	0	0	9	1	1
ampc	0	0	1	0	0
cp3a4	2	0	9	2	0
gcr	0	0	12	2	1
hivpr	30	0	37	0	1
hivrt	0	0	18	8	0
kif11	0	0	9	4	0
andr	0	0	15	0	1
esr1	1	1	27	6	0
esr2	5	1	28	11	0
mcr	0	0	6	0	0
ppara	0	0	29	1	1
ppard	0	0	21	0	0
pparg	0	0	36	1	0
prgr	0	0	26	6	0
rxra	0	0	26	1	0
thb	0	0	23	0	0
ace	5	0	3	2	0
ada17	33	0	16	1	0
bace1	29	0	7	3	1
casp3	0	0	3	0	1
dpp4	1	0	28	6	0
fa10	0	0	16	1	1
fa7	0	0	12	0	0
lkha4	0	0	1	2	0
mmp13	2	0	28	0	2

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Table I.1 – continued from previous page

Target	Macrocycles (A)	Error (A)	Macrocycles (D)	Error (D)	Score Error
reni	1	0	0	1	0
thrb	17	0	18	1	1
try1	12	0	56	3	1
tryb1	0	0	12	3	1
urok	0	0	14	1	0
abl1	0	0	7	1	0
akt2	0	0	2	0	0
braf	0	0	6	3	0
cdk2	2	0	9	3	0
csf1r	0	0	12	0	0
egfr	0	0	19	2	0
fak1	0	0	0	0	0
fgfr1	0	0	4	2	0
igf1r	0	0	7	3	0
jak2	0	0	7	1	0
kit	1	0	11	1	0
kpcb	18	0	4	1	0
lck	3	0	26	7	0
mapk2	1	0	1	1	0
met	0	0	5	2	0
mk01	0	0	7	1	0
mk10	0	0	1	1	0
mk14	0	0	19	2	1
mp2k1	0	0	4	3	0
plk1	1	0	1	2	0
rock1	0	0	7	0	0
src	11	0	14	2	0
tgfr1	0	0	5	0	0
vgfr2	0	0	27	2	0
wee1	0	0	15	0	0
aces	0	0	14	6	6
ada	0	0	1	0	0
aldr	0	0	5	1	0
comt	0	0	0	0	0
dyr	1	0	18	2	0
hmdh	0	0	3	1	0
hs90a	15	0	9	1	0
inha	0	0	2	0	0
kith	0	0	2	0	0
nram	0	0	0	0	0

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Table I.1 – continued from previous page

Target	Macrocycles (A)	Error (A)	Macrocycles (D)	Error (D)	Score Error
parp1	0	0	12	12	1
pde5a	0	0	10	0	0
pgh1	0	0	24	8	0
pgh2	1	0	24	10	1
pnph	0	0	1	0	0
pur2	0	0	0	0	0
pygm	0	0	2	0	0
sahh	0	0	3	1	0
aofb	1	0	1	5	0
cah2	2	0	21	2	0
cp2c9	0	0	6	1	0
def	7	0	1	0	0
dhi1	0	0	15	1	0
fabp4	0	0	3	0	0
fkbl1a	0	0	3	0	0
fnta	31	0	22	4	0
fpps	0	0	0	3	0
glcm	0	0	1	1	0
gria2	0	0	5	1	0
grik1	0	0	0	4	0
hdac2	15	0	0	0	0
hdac8	16	0	0	2	0
hivint	0	0	5	1	0
hxx4	0	0	0	0	0
ital	0	0	8	1	0
nos1	0	0	14	6	0
pa2ga	0	0	0	0	0
ptn1	0	0	13	1	0
pyrd	0	0	3	0	0
tysy	0	0	2	2	0
xiap	0	0	1	0	0

Appendix J. Full Retrospective Benchmarking using the Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced.

Table J.1 Average Enrichment Factors for the top 5% of ranked hits for each method used to screen the DUD-E benchmarking set.

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMoISA	MolSG	KQMoISA
AA2AR	0.119	0.105	0.094	0.108	0.082
ABL1	0.182	0.146	0.082	0.165	0.077
ACE	0.161	0.073	0.098	0.160	0.075
ACES	0.183	0.215	0.126	0.278	0.101
ADA	0.271	0.175	0.117	0.191	0.095
ADA17	0.124	0.093	0.083	0.088	0.073
ADRB1	0.152	0.109	0.094	0.194	0.074
ADRB2	0.132	0.099	0.087	0.164	0.075
AKT2	0.254	0.200	0.153	0.154	0.102
ALDR	0.237	0.173	0.195	0.188	0.116
AMPC	0.113	0.161	0.084	0.138	0.090
ANDR	0.163	0.135	0.080	0.122	0.103
AOFB	0.133	0.130	0.086	0.108	0.114
ATK1	0.096	0.160	0.067	0.104	0.078
BACE1	0.109	0.103	0.091	0.107	0.102
BRAF	0.169	0.128	0.133	0.115	0.080
CAH2	0.107	0.112	0.074	0.110	0.059
CASP3	0.120	0.105	0.091	0.125	0.076
CDK2	0.117	0.111	0.068	0.101	0.064
COMT	0.230	0.188	0.098	0.169	0.097
CP2C9	0.079	0.068	0.065	0.079	0.060
CP3A4	0.076	0.062	0.064	0.081	0.069
CSF1R	0.150	0.145	0.084	0.106	0.074
CXCR4	0.181	0.212	0.176	0.188	0.171
DEF	0.205	0.162	0.143	0.202	0.118
DHI1	0.080	0.106	0.084	0.089	0.057
DPP4	0.143	0.101	0.075	0.112	0.063
DRD3	0.194	0.162	0.107	0.182	0.096
DYR	0.199	0.106	0.095	0.092	0.071
EGFR	0.106	0.137	0.083	0.109	0.071

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Table J.1 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	MolSG	KQMolSA
ESR1	0.312	0.154	0.175	0.109	0.107
ESR2	0.318	0.163	0.181	0.147	0.122
FA10	0.152	0.153	0.101	0.153	0.091
FA7	0.239	0.125	0.091	0.153	0.072
FABP4	0.245	0.323	0.190	0.377	0.108
FAK1	0.231	0.276	0.103	0.162	0.136
FGFR1	0.256	0.214	0.083	0.000	0.093
FKB1A	0.179	0.221	0.118	0.188	0.071
FNTA	0.105	0.079	0.081	0.119	0.083
FPPS	0.342	0.525	0.165	0.198	0.157
GCR	0.131	0.105	0.098	0.135	0.107
GLCM	0.153	0.118	0.077	0.118	0.063
GRIA2	0.129	0.133	0.093	0.084	0.098
GRIK1	0.156	0.148	0.090	0.106	0.091
HDAC2	0.280	0.121	0.110	0.152	0.066
HDAC8	0.356	0.109	0.126	0.134	0.062
HIVINT	0.184	0.144	0.078	0.097	0.072
HIVPR	0.120	0.089	0.079	0.143	0.093
HIVRT	0.105	0.119	0.070	0.087	0.091
HMDH	0.347	0.312	0.138	0.221	0.136
HS90A	0.211	0.245	0.141	0.154	0.138
HXK4	0.372	0.265	0.105	0.295	0.125
IGF1R	0.216	0.158	0.111	0.152	0.104
INHA	0.346	0.223	0.135	0.175	0.115
ITAL	0.147	0.184	0.147	0.176	0.099
JAK2	0.124	0.153	0.084	0.085	0.070
KIF11	0.167	0.225	0.141	0.184	0.170
KIT	0.174	0.160	0.132	0.175	0.066
KITH	0.246	0.269	0.115	0.193	0.166
KPCB	0.208	0.163	0.090	0.123	0.079
LCK	0.160	0.129	0.080	0.090	0.073
LKHA4	0.156	0.203	0.098	0.215	0.114
MAPK2	0.243	0.245	0.104	0.119	0.084
MCR	0.186	0.178	0.087	0.206	0.194
MET	0.209	0.160	0.118	0.203	0.117
MK01	0.192	0.183	0.166	0.181	0.145
MK10	0.109	0.114	0.125	0.123	0.077
MK14	0.128	0.099	0.091	0.086	0.071
MMP13	0.125	0.100	0.072	0.101	0.067
MP2K1	0.170	0.152	0.117	0.174	0.108

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Table J.1 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMoISA	MolSG	KQMoISA
NOS1	0.118	0.100	0.080	0.114	0.088
NRAM	0.457	0.284	0.122	0.428	0.265
PA2GA	0.257	0.234	0.107	0.134	0.147
PARP1	0.120	0.150	0.086	0.134	0.067
PDE5A	0.109	0.160	0.109	0.138	0.168
PGH1	0.118	0.161	0.104	0.126	0.100
PGH2	0.141	0.196	0.118	0.118	0.116
PLK1	0.166	0.171	0.135	0.136	0.109
PNPH	0.200	0.173	0.242	0.133	0.147
PPARA	0.256	0.164	0.113	0.239	0.103
PPARD	0.399	0.178	0.153	0.119	0.077
PPARG	0.170	0.119	0.098	0.189	0.084
PRGR	0.226	0.161	0.090	0.133	0.130
PTN1	0.108	0.091	0.089	0.105	0.065
PUR2	0.908	0.318	0.577	0.331	0.315
PYGM	0.212	0.186	0.144	0.160	0.106
PYRD	0.246	0.301	0.138	0.199	0.085
RENI	0.188	0.130	0.090	0.142	0.100
ROCK1	0.146	0.145	0.081	0.125	0.092
RXRA	0.425	0.202	0.076	0.141	0.112
SAHH	0.478	0.481	0.315	0.290	0.291
SRC	0.194	0.131	0.096	0.092	0.087
TGFR1	0.168	0.204	0.145	0.123	0.130
THB	0.343	0.249	0.167	0.212	0.101
THRB	0.152	0.090	0.117	0.095	0.079
TRY1	0.164	0.072	0.085	0.104	0.070
TRYB1	0.184	0.148	0.184	0.174	0.093
TYSY	0.251	0.143	0.218	0.151	0.106
UROK	0.171	0.120	0.112	0.111	0.071
VGFR2	0.169	0.159	0.093	0.164	0.084
WEE1	0.307	0.262	0.149	0.173	0.103
XIAP	0.303	0.264	0.169	0.197	0.103

Table J.2 Average AUC for each method used to screen the DUD-E benchmarking set.

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMoISA	MolSG	KQMoISA
AA2AR	0.533	0.537	0.536	0.586	0.581
ABL1	0.562	0.608	0.530	0.626	0.479
ACE	0.582	0.488	0.614	0.636	0.495
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Table J.2 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	MolSG	KQMolSA
ACES	0.511	0.620	0.520	0.752	0.422
ADA	0.680	0.492	0.470	0.597	0.523
ADA17	0.512	0.534	0.508	0.553	0.502
ADRB1	0.535	0.532	0.480	0.692	0.449
ADRB2	0.517	0.507	0.495	0.666	0.436
AKT2	0.627	0.589	0.463	0.627	0.524
ALDR	0.575	0.526	0.600	0.570	0.548
AMPC	0.581	0.534	0.497	0.562	0.540
ANDR	0.661	0.580	0.525	0.586	0.557
AOFB	0.548	0.601	0.552	0.576	0.615
ATK1	0.512	0.611	0.497	0.524	0.508
BACE1	0.562	0.509	0.532	0.590	0.597
BRAF	0.591	0.518	0.519	0.551	0.447
CAH2	0.508	0.560	0.478	0.574	0.439
CASP3	0.483	0.475	0.497	0.541	0.412
CDK2	0.571	0.549	0.506	0.576	0.507
COMT	0.624	0.630	0.532	0.544	0.497
CP2C9	0.507	0.489	0.507	0.508	0.478
CP3A4	0.496	0.478	0.492	0.520	0.509
CSF1R	0.564	0.607	0.518	0.530	0.519
CXCR4	0.642	0.563	0.660	0.668	0.688
DEF	0.642	0.621	0.603	0.713	0.605
DHI1	0.457	0.582	0.517	0.578	0.437
DPP4	0.558	0.570	0.512	0.613	0.530
DRD3	0.511	0.579	0.533	0.645	0.450
DYR	0.595	0.534	0.541	0.560	0.497
EGFR	0.506	0.564	0.517	0.585	0.482
ESR1	0.655	0.544	0.644	0.495	0.528
ESR2	0.665	0.554	0.667	0.538	0.535
FA10	0.623	0.583	0.552	0.659	0.545
FA7	0.663	0.542	0.485	0.609	0.534
FABP4	0.627	0.704	0.575	0.764	0.577
FAK1	0.641	0.635	0.499	0.616	0.682
FGFR1	0.618	0.658	0.496	0.000	0.551
FKB1A	0.572	0.624	0.564	0.616	0.408
FNTA	0.579	0.491	0.529	0.631	0.613
FPPS	0.738	0.791	0.619	0.609	0.632
GCR	0.577	0.563	0.573	0.647	0.619
GLCM	0.483	0.537	0.467	0.543	0.475
GRIA2	0.514	0.518	0.507	0.480	0.511

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Table J.2 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RG MolSA	MolSG	KQMolSA
GRIK1	0.584	0.538	0.520	0.542	0.539
HDAC2	0.637	0.525	0.543	0.629	0.438
HDAC8	0.690	0.474	0.544	0.578	0.445
HIVINT	0.566	0.532	0.501	0.545	0.526
HIVPR	0.591	0.489	0.516	0.669	0.577
HIVRT	0.550	0.480	0.479	0.511	0.509
HMDH	0.592	0.684	0.635	0.698	0.709
HS90A	0.656	0.681	0.494	0.635	0.710
HXK4	0.808	0.681	0.514	0.727	0.645
IGF1R	0.628	0.593	0.534	0.592	0.594
INHA	0.630	0.637	0.571	0.627	0.559
ITAL	0.547	0.580	0.545	0.599	0.484
JAK2	0.547	0.573	0.521	0.502	0.489
KIF11	0.672	0.655	0.513	0.652	0.706
KIT	0.601	0.611	0.540	0.680	0.455
KITH	0.622	0.586	0.492	0.704	0.580
KPCB	0.606	0.510	0.493	0.469	0.502
LCK	0.550	0.590	0.508	0.541	0.514
LKHA4	0.519	0.641	0.467	0.757	0.492
MAPK2	0.615	0.674	0.536	0.506	0.513
MCR	0.624	0.665	0.524	0.731	0.674
MET	0.540	0.582	0.524	0.575	0.472
MK01	0.576	0.571	0.474	0.610	0.599
MK10	0.529	0.543	0.549	0.509	0.514
MK14	0.559	0.536	0.489	0.536	0.520
MMP13	0.539	0.526	0.502	0.530	0.457
MP2K1	0.567	0.563	0.514	0.574	0.517
NOS1	0.461	0.458	0.469	0.494	0.433
NRAM	0.758	0.732	0.511	0.848	0.716
PA2GA	0.543	0.539	0.483	0.491	0.660
PARP1	0.544	0.585	0.534	0.610	0.469
PDE5A	0.568	0.623	0.560	0.585	0.700
PGH1	0.584	0.615	0.564	0.559	0.626
PGH2	0.610	0.631	0.570	0.540	0.642
PLK1	0.569	0.590	0.517	0.585	0.605
PNPH	0.632	0.512	0.564	0.578	0.620
PPARA	0.678	0.608	0.516	0.742	0.422
PPARD	0.759	0.589	0.586	0.603	0.423
PPARG	0.590	0.548	0.499	0.697	0.421
PRGR	0.655	0.606	0.557	0.611	0.672

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Table J.2 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RG MolSA	MolSG	KQMolSA
PTN1	0.516	0.511	0.494	0.585	0.428
PUR2	0.972	0.764	0.883	0.844	0.707
PYGM	0.562	0.540	0.553	0.540	0.580
PYRD	0.665	0.756	0.593	0.709	0.543
RENI	0.532	0.514	0.572	0.630	0.556
ROCK1	0.622	0.564	0.489	0.568	0.577
RXRA	0.720	0.611	0.523	0.601	0.618
SAHH	0.808	0.761	0.580	0.756	0.754
SRC	0.551	0.601	0.564	0.554	0.554
TGFR1	0.569	0.518	0.618	0.481	0.609
THB	0.649	0.708	0.633	0.628	0.590
THRB	0.587	0.510	0.588	0.585	0.535
TRY1	0.599	0.490	0.541	0.598	0.536
TRYB1	0.516	0.540	0.552	0.732	0.492
TYSY	0.650	0.511	0.669	0.605	0.458
UROK	0.561	0.544	0.526	0.559	0.545
VGFR2	0.589	0.631	0.535	0.675	0.505
WEE1	0.627	0.619	0.576	0.548	0.613
XIAP	0.696	0.635	0.645	0.739	0.588

Table J.3 Average Enrichment Factors for the top 0.5% of ranked hits for each method used to screen the DUD-E benchmarking set.

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RG MolSA	KQMolSA
AA2AR	6.890	6.218	2.910	1.818
ABL1	10.494	7.858	3.573	2.188
ACE	9.407	3.335	3.126	1.816
ACES	10.911	11.047	7.133	6.327
ADA	22.805	19.706	6.244	3.977
ADA17	8.895	5.753	3.228	1.933
ADRB1	8.835	5.021	4.032	2.215
ADRB2	7.487	4.733	4.069	3.210
AKT2	15.255	16.882	12.447	4.301
ALDR	18.993	19.366	21.580	4.905
AMPC	5.568	12.158	3.261	2.755
ANDR	6.806	13.017	3.401	2.296
AOFB	7.291	5.930	3.322	2.129
ATK1	4.783	7.134	1.919	1.664
BACE1	6.475	8.873	4.534	3.220

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Table J.3 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
BRAF	10.493	9.183	7.063	3.894
CAH2	5.240	5.039	2.541	1.401
CASP3	8.236	9.015	5.600	2.959
CDK2	4.570	4.729	2.097	1.472
COMT	21.574	17.899	5.570	4.504
CP2C9	3.471	3.220	2.011	1.574
CP3A4	3.228	2.436	1.789	1.669
CSF1R	10.031	9.951	4.256	2.216
CXCR4	18.280	20.734	8.779	6.963
DEF	16.842	12.011	7.399	5.074
DHI1	4.461	4.368	3.760	1.702
DPP4	8.436	4.808	2.590	1.381
DRD3	13.149	8.649	3.889	4.178
DYR	16.544	5.786	3.693	2.473
EGFR	5.748	6.918	3.429	1.722
ESR1	27.732	9.662	6.205	3.019
ESR2	29.759	10.518	6.308	3.543
FA10	6.566	7.804	3.445	2.167
FA7	17.182	8.637	4.632	2.386
FABP4	22.993	37.214	26.843	3.966
FAK1	18.733	25.574	5.619	4.167
FGFR1	20.211	12.491	4.608	2.673
FKB1A	13.295	16.086	5.966	2.193
FNTA	4.958	4.555	3.657	2.127
FPPS	34.149	59.429	11.883	5.653
GCR	7.413	5.786	4.758	2.518
GLCM	15.613	8.614	2.220	2.152
GRIA2	9.272	8.982	4.998	3.067
GRIK1	10.665	11.614	5.220	2.670
HDAC2	18.687	5.590	5.555	2.193
HDAC8	27.031	5.748	5.583	2.003
HIVINT	16.968	11.899	2.782	2.201
HIVPR	5.984	5.613	4.156	2.808
HIVRT	5.358	7.899	2.998	2.974
HMDH	29.882	25.340	5.222	2.928
HS90A	15.238	26.274	10.797	3.961
HXK4	25.373	21.609	7.981	5.075
IGF1R	14.180	10.719	5.949	3.205
INHA	31.771	19.452	9.286	3.671
ITAL	12.150	16.318	12.445	3.241

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Table J.3 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
JAK2	6.351	9.295	3.664	2.290
KIF11	10.693	14.794	9.044	5.463
KIT	9.923	8.323	5.875	1.633
KITH	24.824	26.462	8.130	6.371
KPCB	17.965	14.409	6.371	3.070
LCK	9.296	5.302	3.208	1.723
LKHA4	10.993	11.371	4.603	3.524
MAPK2	19.116	16.313	5.400	3.213
MCR	15.382	11.320	3.714	4.877
MET	14.136	10.525	8.442	4.833
MK01	17.236	17.736	11.330	5.964
MK10	6.128	7.434	6.360	2.171
MK14	5.925	5.013	3.779	1.702
MMP13	6.545	5.081	3.306	1.941
MP2K1	16.213	11.726	9.371	4.673
NOS1	9.014	7.810	4.024	3.345
NRAM	31.253	19.290	9.707	11.363
PA2GA	23.602	21.580	5.845	3.824
PARP1	6.550	8.033	3.386	1.943
PDE5A	6.154	8.747	4.658	4.161
PGH1	5.869	8.727	4.961	2.365
PGH2	6.845	12.003	5.159	2.976
PLK1	10.938	16.781	9.524	3.330
PNPH	20.286	17.415	17.983	5.574
PPARA	12.494	7.306	4.993	3.799
PPARD	23.850	11.404	6.273	2.665
PPARG	8.300	5.357	4.425	3.333
PRGR	16.948	7.643	3.671	3.473
PTN1	5.988	4.942	6.283	2.241
PUR2	53.021	27.030	23.911	19.273
PYGM	21.797	21.274	13.254	4.769
PYRD	21.705	23.918	9.381	4.001
RENI	17.991	11.531	4.403	3.769
ROCK1	9.893	10.458	3.428	3.227
RXRA	29.386	13.540	3.580	3.203
SAHH	40.111	41.710	23.843	15.916
SRC	14.860	6.193	3.816	1.933
TGFR1	11.407	17.216	7.379	4.209
THB	32.346	21.482	10.530	2.467
THRB	8.486	5.469	4.689	2.194

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Table J.3 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
TRY1	9.604	3.043	2.672	1.619
TRYB1	16.269	12.238	11.764	3.235
TYSY	17.197	10.451	13.032	4.982
UROK	12.339	5.482	4.424	1.884
VGFR2	8.859	6.587	3.465	2.106
WEE1	30.993	29.779	12.878	2.818
XIAP	26.916	25.072	8.903	3.158

Table J.4 Average Enrichment Factors for the top 1% of ranked hits for each method used to screen the DUD-E benchmarking set.

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
AA2AR	4.672	4.181	2.316	1.763
ABL1	7.741	5.527	2.422	1.886
ACE	6.692	2.339	2.471	1.662
ACES	7.824	8.062	5.096	4.571
ADA	14.514	11.322	4.463	2.925
ADA17	5.843	3.725	2.593	1.660
ADRB1	6.266	3.588	3.064	1.877
ADRB2	5.206	3.326	3.059	2.492
AKT2	10.980	10.430	8.108	3.106
ALDR	12.976	11.136	13.334	3.410
AMPC	3.964	7.877	2.469	2.303
ANDR	5.677	7.569	2.726	2.244
AOFB	4.950	4.255	2.410	2.074
ATK1	3.363	5.520	1.531	1.503
BACE1	4.247	5.231	3.146	2.544
BRAF	7.171	5.839	5.254	2.962
CAH2	3.775	3.694	2.018	1.270
CASP3	5.137	5.376	3.663	2.406
CDK2	3.560	3.529	1.654	1.354
COMT	13.373	10.638	3.525	2.857
CP2C9	2.544	2.147	1.480	1.267
CP3A4	2.415	1.721	1.397	1.537
CSF1R	6.788	6.443	2.932	2.029
CXCR4	11.105	12.493	6.539	5.216
DEF	11.060	7.616	5.041	3.990
DHI1	3.065	3.154	2.770	1.341
DPP4	6.118	3.335	2.012	1.324

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Table J.4 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RG MolSA	KQMolSA
DRD3	9.449	6.234	3.131	3.393
DYR	10.679	3.994	2.764	1.961
EGFR	4.033	4.973	2.536	1.558
ESR1	19.094	6.660	5.336	2.734
ESR2	19.964	7.225	5.426	3.119
FA10	4.749	5.529	2.690	1.907
FA7	11.313	5.414	3.055	1.809
FABP4	14.451	21.469	14.436	3.459
FAK1	11.669	16.492	3.941	3.603
FGFR1	13.750	8.552	2.929	2.031
FKB1A	9.237	10.382	4.353	1.927
FNTA	3.615	3.076	2.644	1.895
FPPS	21.316	37.822	8.571	4.517
GCR	5.133	3.810	3.414	2.291
GLCM	9.283	5.660	2.001	1.725
GRIA2	5.796	5.872	3.372	2.367
GRIK1	6.925	7.062	3.473	2.326
HDAC2	13.436	4.033	4.140	1.912
HDAC8	18.964	4.055	3.886	1.638
HIVINT	10.557	7.542	2.021	1.841
HIVPR	4.391	3.650	2.750	2.309
HIVRT	3.647	5.157	2.182	2.361
HMDH	21.125	17.054	4.071	2.594
HS90A	10.210	15.212	6.426	3.494
HXK4	17.666	13.532	5.480	3.526
IGF1R	9.873	7.083	4.022	2.518
INHA	21.235	12.157	6.640	2.969
ITAL	7.686	9.925	7.258	2.540
JAK2	4.526	6.020	2.440	1.753
KIF11	6.689	9.634	5.861	4.458
KIT	6.905	5.833	4.586	1.493
KITH	14.506	16.994	5.096	5.157
KPCB	11.381	8.766	4.300	2.201
LCK	6.713	4.007	2.281	1.521
LKHA4	7.555	7.958	3.314	3.117
MAPK2	12.891	10.799	3.674	2.443
MCR	9.453	7.361	2.942	4.427
MET	9.421	6.952	5.469	3.928
MK01	11.021	10.319	7.077	4.481
MK10	4.067	4.849	4.300	1.839

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Table J.4 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
MK14	4.461	3.489	2.887	1.529
MMP13	4.722	3.553	2.377	1.668
MP2K1	9.878	7.374	6.174	3.400
NOS1	5.752	4.969	2.723	2.754
NRAM	24.443	13.204	6.108	8.536
PA2GA	15.593	14.063	4.039	3.121
PARP1	4.595	5.643	2.464	1.649
PDE5A	4.136	6.078	3.607	3.861
PGH1	4.155	6.191	3.376	2.052
PGH2	4.929	8.394	3.687	2.657
PLK1	7.695	9.729	5.891	2.659
PNPH	11.978	10.409	12.765	4.320
PPARA	9.631	5.452	3.847	3.269
PPARD	18.750	7.573	4.829	2.261
PPARG	6.160	3.869	3.413	2.705
PRGR	11.779	5.615	2.656	2.985
PTN1	4.081	3.303	3.918	1.838
PUR2	52.981	16.714	20.752	14.915
PYGM	12.738	12.252	8.411	3.747
PYRD	14.497	15.718	6.081	2.846
RENI	11.312	7.081	3.349	2.876
ROCK1	6.622	6.652	2.319	2.541
RXRA	22.835	9.232	2.467	2.713
SAHH	27.224	29.022	17.408	11.501
SRC	10.238	4.401	2.734	1.748
TGFR1	7.441	11.114	5.087	3.360
THB	21.086	13.386	6.819	2.110
THRB	5.960	3.539	3.527	1.783
TRY1	6.666	2.170	2.190	1.471
TRYB1	9.984	7.313	8.186	2.566
TYSY	11.800	6.886	9.128	3.639
UROK	8.228	4.051	3.356	1.616
VGFR2	6.445	5.020	2.617	1.875
WEE1	19.074	17.341	7.838	2.046
XIAP	19.159	15.671	5.994	2.538

Full Retrospective Benchmarking using the Directory of Useful Decoys - Enhanced.**Table J.5** Average Enrichment Factors for the top 2% of ranked hits for each method used to screen the DUD-E benchmarking set.

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMoISA	KQMoISA
AA2AR	3.301	2.935	1.969	1.591
ABL1	5.527	3.893	1.742	1.641
ACE	4.791	1.760	2.113	1.459
ACES	5.550	6.017	3.704	3.142
ADA	9.259	6.389	3.354	2.281
ADA17	3.905	2.534	2.086	1.523
ADRB1	4.492	2.661	2.422	1.659
ADRB2	3.737	2.462	2.284	1.903
AKT2	7.894	6.583	5.260	2.374
ALDR	8.431	6.446	7.483	2.732
AMPC	2.893	5.107	1.960	1.866
ANDR	4.203	4.247	2.023	2.244
AOFB	3.571	3.120	1.806	1.974
ATK1	2.439	4.223	1.295	1.343
BACE1	2.935	3.205	2.252	2.152
BRAF	5.014	3.738	3.923	2.140
CAH2	2.811	2.819	1.612	1.168
CASP3	3.446	3.248	2.514	1.943
CDK2	2.836	2.704	1.425	1.248
COMT	8.571	6.292	2.796	2.644
CP2C9	1.927	1.547	1.264	1.247
CP3A4	1.869	1.366	1.158	1.404
CSF1R	4.637	4.374	2.142	1.648
CXCR4	6.721	7.649	4.857	4.067
DEF	6.995	4.962	3.733	2.716
DHI1	2.123	2.425	2.135	1.118
DPP4	4.377	2.475	1.661	1.238
DRD3	6.575	4.572	2.659	2.677
DYR	6.927	2.851	2.167	1.570
EGFR	2.937	3.706	1.997	1.408
ESR1	11.541	4.620	4.436	2.371
ESR2	11.921	4.968	4.583	2.785
FA10	3.571	3.943	2.121	1.675
FA7	7.561	3.482	2.187	1.439
FABP4	8.934	11.774	7.426	2.975
FAK1	7.302	9.998	2.796	3.035
FGFR1	8.916	6.182	2.005	1.703
FKB1A	6.004	6.862	3.097	1.622

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Table J.5 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
FNTA	2.712	2.153	2.067	1.720
FPPS	13.212	22.480	5.714	3.741
GCR	3.671	2.677	2.458	2.023
GLCM	5.729	3.624	1.642	1.310
GRIA2	3.738	3.975	2.457	2.085
GRIK1	4.651	4.676	2.392	1.978
HDAC2	9.363	3.088	3.066	1.601
HDAC8	12.499	2.982	3.067	1.377
HIVINT	6.397	4.722	1.870	1.628
HIVPR	3.259	2.484	1.960	1.975
HIVRT	2.651	3.489	1.608	1.963
HMDH	13.219	10.822	3.320	2.527
HS90A	6.843	8.699	4.425	2.887
HXK4	12.073	8.618	3.264	2.728
IGF1R	6.810	4.735	2.990	2.095
INHA	13.520	7.560	3.694	2.371
ITAL	4.757	6.064	4.340	2.146
JAK2	3.260	4.306	1.929	1.506
KIF11	4.690	6.618	4.068	3.977
KIT	5.020	4.320	3.765	1.404
KITH	8.379	9.798	3.208	4.180
KPCB	7.103	5.485	2.759	1.660
LCK	4.771	3.179	1.792	1.388
LKHA4	5.126	5.714	2.587	2.559
MAPK2	8.362	7.249	2.735	1.887
MCR	6.016	4.971	2.283	4.196
MET	6.557	4.788	3.601	3.298
MK01	6.878	6.111	5.236	3.578
MK10	2.813	3.337	3.102	1.634
MK14	3.397	2.549	2.223	1.400
MMP13	3.488	2.585	1.750	1.459
MP2K1	5.824	4.747	4.046	2.697
NOS1	3.883	3.186	1.914	2.332
NRAM	17.704	9.015	3.827	6.450
PA2GA	9.770	8.509	2.893	2.811
PARP1	3.274	4.106	1.919	1.398
PDE5A	2.916	4.429	2.788	3.532
PGH1	3.073	4.464	2.532	1.878
PGH2	3.702	5.840	2.867	2.341
PLK1	5.267	5.784	3.789	2.318

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Table J.5 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RG MolSA	KQMolSA
PNPH	7.081	6.216	8.569	3.394
PPARA	7.341	4.183	3.038	2.723
PPARD	13.409	5.130	3.803	1.793
PPARG	4.607	2.877	2.622	2.175
PRGR	7.498	4.150	2.084	2.530
PTN1	2.878	2.346	2.570	1.580
PUR2	42.158	10.483	17.405	10.687
PYGM	7.430	6.956	5.087	2.735
PYRD	9.014	9.832	3.845	2.086
RENI	6.835	4.389	2.342	2.280
ROCK1	4.305	4.331	1.764	2.092
RXRA	15.627	6.261	1.787	2.339
SAHH	17.577	18.147	11.369	8.829
SRC	6.759	3.293	2.111	1.638
TGFR1	4.901	7.132	3.680	2.803
THB	13.508	8.330	4.882	1.962
THRB	4.286	2.392	2.864	1.581
TRY1	4.729	1.670	1.861	1.329
TRYB1	6.105	4.588	5.587	2.130
TYSY	8.099	4.555	7.011	2.800
UROK	5.455	3.104	2.629	1.405
VGFR2	4.744	3.935	2.171	1.650
WEE1	11.472	9.870	4.720	2.043
XIAP	11.371	9.474	4.317	2.028

Table J.6 Average Enrichment Factors for the top 5% of ranked hits for each method used to screen the DUD-E benchmarking set.

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RG MolSA	KQMolSA
AA2AR	2.224	1.932	1.702	1.441
ABL1	3.515	2.685	1.349	1.337
ACE	3.041	1.300	1.735	1.335
ACES	3.523	4.154	2.378	1.927
ADA	5.158	3.140	2.366	1.681
ADA17	2.352	1.675	1.560	1.351
ADRB1	2.909	1.989	1.812	1.424
ADRB2	2.463	1.804	1.674	1.414
AKT2	4.919	3.683	2.949	1.864
ALDR	4.574	3.127	3.441	2.136

Continued on next page

Table J.6 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
AMPC	2.051	2.998	1.489	1.597
ANDR	3.173	2.384	1.461	1.896
AOFB	2.465	2.283	1.489	1.940
ATK1	1.727	3.025	1.124	1.379
BACE1	1.974	1.843	1.661	1.910
BRAF	3.252	2.368	2.514	1.422
CAH2	2.006	2.069	1.359	1.054
CASP3	2.166	1.825	1.536	1.392
CDK2	2.165	2.018	1.206	1.097
COMT	4.608	3.526	1.775	2.030
CP2C9	1.462	1.162	1.153	1.058
CP3A4	1.393	1.089	1.135	1.234
CSF1R	2.850	2.711	1.545	1.340
CXCR4	3.383	4.212	3.723	3.437
DEF	3.743	2.916	2.738	2.083
DHI1	1.418	1.904	1.521	0.973
DPP4	2.825	1.860	1.399	1.127
DRD3	3.923	3.133	2.127	1.869
DYR	3.880	1.997	1.738	1.286
EGFR	1.981	2.594	1.495	1.277
ESR1	5.827	2.891	3.290	1.884
ESR2	5.935	3.079	3.446	2.198
FA10	2.561	2.604	1.652	1.484
FA7	4.445	2.258	1.654	1.249
FABP4	4.802	6.030	3.302	1.928
FAK1	4.198	5.109	1.773	2.325
FGFR1	8.916	4.091	1.452	1.485
FKB1A	3.300	4.132	2.106	1.298
FNTA	1.999	1.493	1.538	1.515
FPPS	6.894	10.804	3.275	3.159
GCR	2.435	1.855	1.704	1.820
GLCM	2.845	2.204	1.429	1.178
GRIA2	2.392	2.533	1.735	1.820
GRIK1	2.883	2.795	1.580	1.641
HDAC2	5.470	2.236	2.030	1.239
HDAC8	7.062	2.040	2.456	1.150
HIVINT	3.472	2.660	1.383	1.236
HIVPR	2.260	1.629	1.391	1.663
HIVRT	1.857	2.197	1.244	1.631
HMDH	6.625	5.830	2.499	2.347

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Table J.6 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMoISA	KQMoISA
HS90A	3.982	4.241	2.768	2.449
HXK4	6.947	4.853	1.768	2.194
IGF1R	4.153	2.941	2.062	1.808
INHA	6.616	4.033	2.359	2.027
ITAL	2.711	3.370	2.564	1.851
JAK2	2.342	2.901	1.362	1.229
KIF11	3.023	4.261	2.503	3.187
KIT	3.325	3.054	2.683	1.224
KITH	4.496	4.895	1.957	2.961
KPCB	3.863	3.026	1.652	1.378
LCK	3.109	2.429	1.421	1.281
LKHA4	2.958	3.822	1.813	2.150
MAPK2	4.654	4.689	1.826	1.519
MCR	3.454	3.234	1.533	3.752
MET	4.119	3.046	2.307	2.312
MK01	3.572	3.323	3.386	2.615
MK10	1.992	2.121	2.399	1.372
MK14	2.416	1.808	1.701	1.246
MMP13	2.392	1.840	1.274	1.216
MP2K1	3.152	2.810	2.202	2.052
NOS1	2.252	1.904	1.484	1.753
NRAM	9.436	5.528	2.275	5.067
PA2GA	4.789	4.240	2.030	2.620
PARP1	2.208	2.779	1.520	1.174
PDE5A	1.999	3.046	2.053	3.096
PGH1	2.134	2.989	1.805	1.711
PGH2	2.599	3.663	2.082	2.012
PLK1	3.159	3.126	2.468	1.933
PNPH	3.706	3.227	4.962	2.664
PPARA	4.962	3.049	2.144	1.985
PPARD	7.792	3.260	2.847	1.418
PPARG	3.188	2.139	1.815	1.568
PRGR	4.158	2.984	1.563	2.168
PTN1	1.928	1.593	1.583	1.173
PUR2	18.027	5.882	12.632	6.190
PYGM	3.749	3.254	2.633	1.904
PYRD	4.562	5.563	2.493	1.530
RENI	3.645	2.412	1.635	1.846
ROCK1	2.695	2.736	1.498	1.694
RXRA	8.344	3.752	1.249	1.968

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Table J.6 – continued from previous page

Target	USRCAT	Shape-It	RGMolSA	KQMolSA
SAHH	9.114	9.323	6.060	5.725
SRC	3.771	2.401	1.714	1.545
TGFR1	3.113	3.984	2.650	2.290
THB	6.792	4.686	3.232	1.879
THRB	2.871	1.593	2.224	1.400
TRY1	3.049	1.272	1.564	1.219
TRYB1	3.267	2.635	3.666	1.662
TYSY	4.913	2.667	4.516	1.964
UROK	3.206	2.262	2.092	1.248
VGFR2	3.221	2.989	1.731	1.492
WEE1	5.727	4.812	2.595	1.829
XIAP	5.490	4.832	2.970	1.748

Appendix K. Full Results from Comparison using the AstraZeneca Test.

Figure K.1 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P00489.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
5	0.703	0.735	0.603	0.639	0.178	0.907
3	0.682	0.363	0.526	0.529	0.464	0.992
1	0.671	0.730	0.684	0.709	0.187	0.948
6	0.664	0.737	0.565	0.605	0.168	0.859
7	0.655	0.731	0.613	0.635	0.194	0.904
4	0.643	0.341	0.465	0.476	0.226	0.934
0	0.596	0.733	0.570	0.608	0.151	0.837
2	0.591	0.738	0.537	0.575	0.138	0.824
8	0.476	0.765	0.378	0.414	0.098	0.634
Average	0.631	0.653	0.549	0.577	0.200	0.871

Table K.1 Similarity Scores for P00489 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	5	3	1	6	7	4	0	2	8
RGMolSA	8	2	6	5	0	7	1	3	4
KQMolSA (k = 1)	1	7	5	0	6	2	3	4	8
KQMolSA (k = 2)	1	5	7	0	6	2	3	4	8
USRCAT	3	4	7	1	5	6	0	2	8
Surface Area	3	1	4	5	7	6	0	2	8

Table K.2 Ranking by each method for P00489.

Figure K.2 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P0A017.

	ASV	RG MolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
0	0.805	0.993	0.965	0.955	0.779	0.998
1	0.655	0.929	0.783	0.626	0.308	0.924
7	0.600	0.915	0.823	0.590	0.359	0.854
8	0.595	0.916	0.800	0.590	0.349	0.851
6	0.561	0.902	0.888	0.636	0.176	0.787
4	0.519	0.884	0.848	0.538	0.328	0.720
2	0.487	0.461	0.432	0.453	0.315	0.832
3	0.483	0.343	0.376	0.401	0.143	0.783
5	0.465	0.908	0.834	0.601	0.176	0.822
Average	0.574	0.806	0.750	0.599	0.326	0.841

Table K.3 Similarity Scores for P0A017 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	0	1	7	8	6	4	2	3	5
RG MolSA	0	1	8	7	5	6	4	2	3
KQMolSA (k = 1)	0	6	4	5	7	8	1	2	3
KQMolSA (k = 2)	0	6	1	5	7	8	4	2	3
USRCAT	0	7	8	4	2	1	6	5	3
Surface Area	0	1	7	8	2	5	6	3	4

Table K.4 Ranking by each method for P0A017.

Figure K.3 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of Q9BJF5.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
2	0.765	0.920	0.672	0.569	0.179	0.850
6	0.696	0.584	0.681	0.638	0.279	0.979
4	0.671	0.569	0.768	0.800	0.217	0.940
0	0.670	0.979	0.611	0.651	0.561	0.990
3	0.580	0.946	0.913	0.753	0.217	0.896
5	0.572	0.511	0.944	0.581	0.169	0.835
7	0.553	0.927	0.662	0.581	0.223	0.948
1	0.551	0.811	0.416	0.439	0.203	0.676
8	0.498	0.658	0.744	0.715	0.173	0.732
Average	0.617	0.767	0.712	0.636	0.247	0.872

Table K.5 Similarity Scores for Q9BJF5 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules									
ASV	2	6	4	0	3	5	7	1	8	
RGMolSA	0	3	7	2	1	8	6	4	5	
KQMolSA (k = 1)	5	3	4	8	6	2	7	0	1	
KQMolSA (k = 2)	4	3	8	0	6	5	7	2	1	
USRCAT	0	6	7	3	4	1	2	8	5	
Surface Area	0	6	7	4	3	2	5	8	1	

Table K.6 Ranking by each method for Q9BJF5.

Full Results from Comparison using the AstraZeneca Test.

Figure K.4 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of O15530.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
0	0.783	0.957	0.750	0.799	0.607	0.923
1	0.771	0.926	0.582	0.574	0.357	0.860
8	0.683	0.988	0.881	0.886	0.558	0.993
5	0.585	0.918	0.823	0.719	0.237	0.856
6	0.459	0.925	0.644	0.540	0.154	0.781
3	0.451	0.834	0.603	0.551	0.214	0.638
2	0.438	0.772	0.505	0.471	0.213	0.564
7	0.381	0.734	0.482	0.426	0.217	0.512
4	0.317	0.820	0.395	0.418	0.089	0.906
Average	0.541	0.875	0.629	0.598	0.294	0.781

Table K.7 Similarity Scores for O15530 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	0	1	8	5	6	3	2	7	4
RGMolSA	8	0	1	6	5	3	4	2	7
KQMolSA (k = 1)	8	5	0	6	3	1	2	7	4
KQMolSA (k = 2)	8	0	5	1	3	6	2	7	4
USRCAT	0	8	1	5	7	3	2	6	4
Surface Area	8	0	4	1	5	6	3	2	7

Table K.8 Ranking by each method for O15530.

Figure K.5 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P07900.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
1	0.731	0.955	0.807	0.810	0.472	0.965
0	0.718	0.988	0.646	0.613	0.234	0.995
2	0.695	0.883	0.880	0.726	0.215	0.779
3	0.680	0.960	0.737	0.731	0.216	0.935
5	0.633	0.834	0.662	0.516	0.254	0.787
6	0.629	0.861	0.734	0.526	0.266	0.831
4	0.520	0.525	0.433	0.465	0.191	0.904
8	0.508	0.914	0.544	0.572	0.216	0.811
7	0.438	0.902	0.424	0.424	0.212	0.833
Average	0.617	0.869	0.652	0.598	0.253	0.871

Table K.9 Similarity Scores for P07900 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	1	0	2	3	5	6	4	8	7
RGMolSA	0	3	1	8	7	2	6	5	4
KQMolSA (k = 1)	2	1	3	6	5	0	8	4	7
KQMolSA (k = 2)	1	3	2	0	8	6	5	4	7
USRCAT	1	6	5	0	8	3	2	7	4
Surface Area	0	1	3	4	7	6	8	5	2

Table K.10 Ranking by each method for P07900.

Full Results from Comparison using the AstraZeneca Test.

Figure K.6 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P24182.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
0	0.469	0.882	0.513	0.474	0.170	0.801
4	0.467	0.592	0.497	0.464	0.162	0.847
2	0.439	0.865	0.872	0.457	0.202	0.754
6	0.438	0.708	0.734	0.464	0.181	0.665
8	0.421	0.610	0.841	0.378	0.149	0.540
1	0.414	0.852	0.833	0.478	0.190	0.736
3	0.396	0.760	0.595	0.432	0.152	0.579
7	0.394	0.573	0.338	0.360	0.182	0.628
5	0.364	0.647	0.405	0.344	0.129	0.469
Average	0.422	0.721	0.625	0.428	0.169	0.669

Table K.11 Similarity Scores for P24182 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	0	4	2	6	8	1	3	7	5
RGMolSA	0	2	1	3	6	5	8	4	7
KQMolSA (k = 1)	2	8	1	6	3	0	4	5	7
KQMolSA (k = 2)	1	0	6	4	2	3	8	7	5
USRCAT	2	1	7	6	0	4	3	8	5
Surface Area	4	0	2	1	6	7	3	8	5

Table K.12 Ranking by each method for P24182.

Figure K.7 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P25440.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
0	0.680	0.564	0.484	0.471	0.170	0.938
7	0.415	0.288	0.313	0.292	0.111	0.492
3	0.409	0.466	0.278	0.271	0.100	0.437
1	0.407	0.566	0.539	0.427	0.153	0.781
4	0.407	0.502	0.345	0.323	0.127	0.584
6	0.402	0.395	0.843	0.449	0.142	0.814
8	0.398	0.279	0.307	0.284	0.100	0.458
2	0.331	0.239	0.264	0.255	0.109	0.384
5	0.304	0.695	0.314	0.289	0.111	0.351
Average	0.417	0.444	0.410	0.340	0.125	0.582

Table K.13 Similarity Scores for P25440 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	0	7	3	1	4	6	8	2	5
RGMolSA	5	1	0	4	3	6	7	8	2
KQMolSA (k = 1)	6	1	0	4	5	7	8	3	2
KQMolSA (k = 2)	0	6	1	4	7	5	8	3	2
USRCAT	0	1	6	4	7	5	2	3	8
Surface Area	0	6	1	4	7	8	3	2	5

Table K.14 Ranking by each method for P25440.

Figure K.8 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of Q92731.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
8	0.770	0.628	0.696	0.728	0.303	0.995
5	0.763	0.893	0.730	0.757	0.344	0.990
3	0.753	0.867	0.731	0.750	0.330	0.983
7	0.746	0.806	0.911	0.820	0.250	0.963
1	0.713	0.666	0.789	0.788	0.295	0.957
0	0.699	0.633	0.690	0.695	0.343	0.944
6	0.696	0.909	0.747	0.734	0.311	0.940
4	0.686	0.902	0.758	0.769	0.291	0.921
2	0.666	0.669	0.897	0.811	0.313	0.878
Average	0.721	0.775	0.772	0.761	0.309	0.952

Table K.15 Similarity Scores for Q92731 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	8	5	3	7	1	0	6	4	2
RGMolSA	6	4	5	3	7	2	1	0	8
KQMolSA (k = 1)	7	2	1	4	6	3	5	8	0
KQMolSA (k = 2)	7	2	1	4	5	3	6	8	0
USRCAT	5	0	3	2	6	8	1	4	7
Surface Area	8	4	6	5	7	1	2	0	3

Table K.16 Ranking by each method for Q92731.

Figure K.9 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of P68400.

	ASV	RGMoISA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
1	0.721	0.656	0.898	0.707	0.170	0.812
8	0.670	0.761	0.578	0.614	0.217	0.857
7	0.662	0.919	0.583	0.628	0.211	0.865
6	0.653	0.709	0.605	0.614	0.213	0.806
4	0.647	0.881	0.846	0.724	0.193	0.784
0	0.637	0.879	0.534	0.562	0.220	0.960
3	0.578	0.433	0.696	0.704	0.155	0.772
5	0.561	0.351	0.645	0.644	0.221	0.809
2	0.438	0.388	0.290	LinAlgError	0.188	0.551
Average	0.619	0.664	0.631	0.650	0.199	0.802

Table K.17 Similarity Scores for P68400 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	1	8	7	6	4	0	3	5	2
RGMoISA	7	4	0	8	6	1	3	2	5
KQMolSA (k = 1)	1	4	3	5	6	7	8	0	2
KQMolSA (k = 2)	4	1	3	5	7	8	6	0	2 (error)
USRCAT	5	0	8	6	7	4	2	1	3
Surface Area	0	7	8	1	5	6	4	3	2

Table K.18 Ranking by each method for P68400.

Figure K.10 Space Filling Models for the reference and test structures of Q08499.

	ASV	RGMolSA	KQMolSA (k = 1)	KQMolSA (k = 2)	USRCAT	Surface Area
0	0.693	0.425	0.615	0.666	0.196	0.950
8	0.596	0.918	0.618	0.639	0.291	0.925
1	0.573	0.313	0.666	0.561	0.189	0.875
2	0.563	0.155	0.554	0.528	0.180	0.741
4	0.517	0.822	0.504	0.518	0.241	0.732
6	0.511	0.127	0.531	0.542	0.187	0.764
5	0.498	0.527	0.594	0.609	0.295	0.803
7	0.495	0.290	0.594	0.601	0.307	0.825
3	0.409	0.829	0.382	0.398	0.154	0.499
Average	0.539	0.490	0.562	0.562	0.227	0.790

Table K.19 Similarity Scores for Q08499 sorted by highest ASV score.

	Rank Order of Molecules								
ASV	0	8	1	2	4	6	5	7	3
RGMolSA	8	3	4	5	0	1	7	2	6
KQMolSA (k = 1)	1	8	0	5	7	2	6	4	3
KQMolSA (k = 2)	0	8	5	7	1	6	2	4	3
USRCAT	7	5	8	4	0	1	6	2	3
Surface Area	0	8	1	7	5	6	2	4	3

Table K.20 Ranking by each method for Q08499.

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